

**ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP IN TEAMS:
EVIDENCE FROM UNIVERSITY-BASED BUSINESS
INCUBATORS (UBIs) OF PAKISTAN**

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Dedication

Dedicated to my beloved wife, Summiya Fida Ahmed, who has been a constant source of support, encouragement, and love throughout my academic journey. This thesis would not have been possible without your unwavering trust in me.

To my beloved daughters, Emin Fida and Sassa Fida, who fill me each day with joy and inspiration. Your boundless enthusiasm and curiosity remind me of the significance of lifelong education and exploration. I hope that one day you will read these pages and find within them inspiration to pursue your own dreams and passions.

This thesis is dedicated to my family, whose love and sacrifice have enabled me to pursue my academic ambitions and reach new heights. I will always be grateful for your presence in my life.

Student Declaration

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

Signed: _____

Date: _____

Abstract

As the workplace becomes increasingly complex and dynamic, organisations are seeking new leadership styles to overcome challenges and capitalise on business opportunities in a competitive environment. Entrepreneurial leadership, emerging at the intersection of leadership and entrepreneurship, is a growing area of interest for researchers and practitioners. Notwithstanding the considerable attention that entrepreneurial leadership has garnered, research in this area is still in its formative stage, and the concept remains elusive on several fronts, highlighting the need for further research and empirical evidence. More specifically, the knowledge base regarding both the theoretical and empirical aspects of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development is currently limited. To fill this research gap, this study aimed to investigate entrepreneurial leadership in the context of university-based business incubators by exploring the challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders and identifying the competencies they need to succeed in their entrepreneurial pursuits. The study also proposed an empirical model for the development of entrepreneurial leadership in a team context. The study is grounded in an interpretivist-constructionist philosophy and adopts a qualitative research method involving semi-structured interviews for data collection and thematic analysis for data analysis.

The study identified three categories of challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders—personal, business function, and contextual—and highlighted crucial competencies required for the success of entrepreneurial leaders, including self-competencies, organising, interpersonal, entrepreneurial, and conceptual competencies. The findings revealed that entrepreneurial leaders can hone their competencies through a variety of classroom-based, project-based, social, and self-regulated learning approaches. The study's empirical model provides a useful resource for practitioners and policymakers to understand the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in teams and expand entrepreneurial leadership in their regions. The

model suggests that the development of entrepreneurial leadership is a dynamic social phenomenon, underscoring the importance of comprehending contextual factors when designing and launching entrepreneurial leadership development programmes in university-based business incubators (UBIs). The results of this research enrich the field of entrepreneurial leadership by broadening our comprehension of entrepreneurial leadership from an individualistic to an inclusive and relational form of leadership that occurs in a dynamic team environment.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Research background

Leadership research have witnessed a significant surge in recent times marked by the emergence of new theoretical models and paradigm shifts (King, 1990; Yammarino, 2000). These developments in leadership research are driven by the escalating complexities and uncertainties in the workplace, which present formidable challenges to organisations (Gupta et al., 2004). Despite the growing body of literature, the field of leadership remains complex and elusive, primarily due to the absence of consensus on definitional and theoretical frameworks (Northouse, 2019). Similarly, entrepreneurship, though relatively nascent, has undergone a comparable evolution in terms of its definition and conceptualisation (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004). Both fields have encountered similar theoretical challenges, including deficiencies in scale development, inappropriate utilisation of analytical tools, and confusion regarding levels of analysis (Antonakis et al., 2004; Vecchio, 2003).

Both entrepreneurship and leadership faced conceptual challenges and exhibit commonalities, leading to increased scholarly interest in comparing their overlaps (Clark, 2020). Scholars have identified intersections between the two fields, such as vision, influence, creativity, and planning (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004). Vecchio (2003) even suggests that entrepreneurship can be viewed as a form of leadership, particularly within the context of new ventures. McGrath and MacMillan (2000) advocate for integrating an “entrepreneurial mindset” into strategic management, emphasising its importance in navigating competitive business landscapes. Moreover, research highlights the significance of entrepreneurial behaviours among leaders for sustaining venture performance (Zahra and Covin, 1995). Similarly, fostering an entrepreneurial mindset within organisations is essential for corporate transformation, seizing emerging entrepreneurial opportunities, and creating value for the firms (Gupta et al., 2004).

The ongoing discourse surrounding the similarities between entrepreneurship and leadership has given rise to the concept of “entrepreneurial leadership” (EL) (Roomi & Harrison, 2011). Although EL has gained traction as an emerging concept, the investigation into entrepreneurial leadership is still in its early stages. Much like its theoretical predecessors, entrepreneurship and leadership, the concept of entrepreneurial leadership is perceived as intricate and elusive due to a lack of theoretical advancement, definitional clarity, and suitable measurement tools (Gupta et al., 2004; Harrison et al., 2018).

Nevertheless, entrepreneurial leadership has garnered significant scholarly attention across various contexts (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Fernald et al., 2005; Harrison et al., 2018; Kuratko, 2007). Roomi and Harrison (2011) delineate four perspectives of entrepreneurial leadership, including the intersection of leadership and entrepreneurship, the psychological perspective, the contextual approach, and the holistic approach. Similarly, Harrison et al. (2018) categorise existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership into three perspectives: the psychological or trait-based perspective, the behavioural perspective, and the skills perspective.

Despite their valuable contributions, research on entrepreneurial leadership is still evolving, with various aspects of the concept and theoretical perspective requiring further exploration. These include entrepreneurial leadership development, competency perspectives, and team dynamics (Ahmed and Ramzan, 2013; Clark, 2020). Additional research and theoretical frameworks are indispensable to establish a solid foundation for entrepreneurial leadership research.

The growing scholarship of entrepreneurial leadership has led to the emergence of multiple definitions of the notion (Cohen, 2004; Gupta et al., 2004; Greenberg et al., 2013; Harrison et al., 2018; Renko et al., 2015; Surie and Ashley, 2008). For instance, Cohen (2004) defines EL as a leadership approach that creates an environment of entrepreneurial behaviour in an

organisation, which is critical to organisational progress. On the other hand, Gupta et al. (2004, p. 242) defined entrepreneurial leadership as “leadership that creates visionary scenarios that are used to assemble and mobilise a ‘supporting cast’ of participants who become committed by the vision to the discovery and exploitation of strategic value creation.” Greenberg et al. (2013) view entrepreneurial leadership as a leadership style that helps solve complex business, social, and environmental problems.

However, one of the important aspects missing in existing conceptualisation of entrepreneurial leadership is its focus on team. According to Gupta et al. (2004), a team oriented entrepreneurial leadership elicit high level of participation and creativity and involvement of teams in strategic value creation. Likewise, Chen (2007) proposed that team led by entrepreneurial leaders produce more creative outcomes. However, despite team’s significance in achieving entrepreneurial outcomes, entrepreneurial leadership from a team context received scarce theoretical and empirical attention (Cai et al., 2019; Chen, 2007; Harrison, 2016). Therefore, this thesis aims to fill this research gap by exploring entrepreneurial leadership from a team dynamic within the context of university business incubators (UBIs) of Pakistan. Specifically, this research focuses on the dynamics of entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and their development in teams.

The significance of this research stems from the crucial role of university business incubators in developing entrepreneurial leadership in Pakistan. University-based incubators are centralised entrepreneurial platforms to nurture entrepreneurial minds toward entrepreneurship by fostering technology transfer to industries, fostering innovation, uplifting entrepreneurial skills, thereby contributing regional and national economic development (Jamil et al., 2016; Mahmoodi al., 2015; Mumtaz et al., 2017).

Despite their significant role in fostering entrepreneurship and economic growth, business incubators, particularly university business incubators in Pakistan, have received relatively little scholarly attention compared to other developing nations (Jamil et al., 2016). Existing literature primarily focuses on UBIs in Pakistan, offering insights into policy issues, the nature and types of UBIs, challenges, and processes (Jamil et al., 2016; Mahmoodi et al., 2015; Mumtaz et al., 2017). However, there is a noticeable absence of empirical studies addressing the challenges, competencies, and the development of entrepreneurial leadership through university-based incubators in Pakistan.

The evidence suggests that majority of graduates in Pakistan lack required entrepreneurial skills to meet the foreign and local job market needs (Mahmood et al., 2015). Likewise, majority of start-ups fail in their early phase due to challenges in entrepreneurial teams, lack of entrepreneurial skillsets, and knowledge in teams (Eisenhardt, 2013; Kaplan and Strömberg, 2004). Working as a team is viewed as a complex phenomenon and requires specific leadership competencies to overcome the challenges faced in entrepreneurial endeavours (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; de Mol et al., 2015; Gundry et al., 2016). Starting a business as a team is more challenging than starting alone, as it requires the development of collective abilities, shared direction, coordinated efforts, and mutual competencies (Santos et al., 2019).

Entrepreneurial leadership, as an emerging concept, has contributed a significant amount of research to our understanding. Surprisingly, aspects of entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and development from a team perspective have remained understudied. No prior research has delved into how entrepreneurial leadership is practiced within teams and the specific competencies needed to navigate challenges and seize business opportunities. To fill this gap, this study seeks to investigate the challenges and competencies faced by emerging entrepreneurial leaders in Pakistani UBIs from a team perspective. Examining entrepreneurial

leadership competencies within a team context offers significant theoretical and empirical contributions to the literature, as underscored by previous scholars (Chen, 2007; Carland & Carland Jr., 2012; Devarajan et al., 2003; Harrison, 2016).

Pakistan's dynamic environment as a developing economy provides a unique context for the current inquiry (Acs, 2008). The investigation of entrepreneurial leadership in Pakistan is justified due to the country's demographic characteristics, including a substantial proportion (60%) of the population being under 30 years old, as well as significant levels of poverty and unemployment (24.3% living below the poverty line and 54.4% of the labour force being unemployed). Business incubators play a critical role in dealing with the challenges of poverty, unemployment, and poor economic development (Li et al., 2020; Shuhong and Zia-ud-Din, 2017; Wanyoko, 2013). The university-based incubators offer technical, financial, and technological support to young entrepreneurs, helping them turn their business ideas into successful ventures (Ogutu and Kihonge, 2016). By providing a supportive environment and offering training, coaching, and business support services, UBIs help minimise start-up costs and overcome business challenges, leading to long-term economic growth, job creation, and poverty reduction (Wanyoko, 2013).

Examining entrepreneurial leadership within a team context provides fresh theoretical perspectives and practical insights. The empirical evidence derived from this study contributes valuable knowledge to policymaking and practical implementation by pinpointing critical issues and competencies essential for entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs. This understanding facilitates the formulation of policies, training initiatives, and mentorship programs aimed at fostering entrepreneurial capabilities nationwide. Building on a systematic literature review and insights gathered from teams within UBIs, entrepreneurial leadership is defined as:

“Entrepreneurial leadership is a process of coping with complex entrepreneurial challenges and cocreating entrepreneurial opportunities in teams through innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactive behaviour.”

1.2 Scope of Study

Leadership studies have traditionally centred on developed countries, predominantly adopting a Western perspective. However, there has been a noticeable gap in research when it comes to exploring leadership within developing economies. This oversight is particularly significant given the distinctive socio-cultural, economic, and political dynamics that characterise these regions (Blunt and Jones, 1997; Harrison et al., 2016a). Despite the acknowledged importance of understanding leadership within developing economies, scholarly attention in this area has been limited (Harrison et al., 2016a). Therefore, it is imperative to address this gap and undertake comprehensive examinations of leadership in the context of developing economies, considering their unique socio-cultural nuances. This study focused on Pakistan, which, like other developing economies, confronting various challenges including political and economic instability, inadequate infrastructure, and corruption (Harrison et al., 2016a; Nkechi et al., 2012). The significance of this research lies in the pivotal role of UBIs in fostering the growth of start-ups and their leadership capabilities, while also facilitating job creation in Pakistan (Giordano et al., 2017). The findings reported from the study provide a nuanced understanding of entrepreneurial leadership challenges and competencies in relation to emerging start-ups and offer fresh insights to policymakers to assess, design, and improve entrepreneurial leadership development facilities through UBIs (Mahmood et al., 2015).

1.3 Research aim

This research aimed to explore entrepreneurial leadership in the context of business incubators by specifically focusing on UBIs in Pakistan. This study examined entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and entrepreneurial leadership development from a team perspective. The study was guided by an interpretivist-constructionist perspective to comprehend the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders from their subjective experiences. Based on empirical evidence, the study proposed a model for entrepreneurial leadership development in teams that expands the theoretical knowledge of entrepreneurial leadership by incorporating a team-based conceptualisation.

1.4 Research objectives

The following research objectives were established to achieve the research's stated purpose.

- To identify the challenges of nascent entrepreneurial leaders working as team in university-based business incubators of Pakistan.
- To identify the competencies required for teams in coping with the challenges of new venture creation.
- To explain the methods and process through which entrepreneurial leaders can learn and develop competencies in a team level.
- To propose a team-based competency model for nascent entrepreneurial leaders working at university-business incubators.

1.5 Research questions

The following research questions were addressed in this study aimed at understanding the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leadership and its development in a team context:

- What are the main challenges faced by nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-based business incubators in Pakistan?
- What entrepreneurial leadership competencies do entrepreneurial leaders require in order to overcome these challenges and become successful?
- How can these competencies be developed in a team setting within the context of university-business incubators in Pakistan?
- How do contextual factors influence the development of competencies for nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-business incubators, and how can these factors be integrated into a team-based competency model?

1.6 Methodology

This study aimed to examine the experiences of entrepreneurial leaders at UBIs from a team perspective. In doing so, the study employed a qualitative research method guided by an interpretivist-constructionist philosophy. The interpretivist constructionist philosophy emphasises that knowledge is subjective and shaped by individual experiences and interpretations (Crotty, 1998). An abductive approach was used to investigate the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders based on their lived experiences (Clark, 2020; Crotty, 1998; Harrison et al., 2016a; Lincoln and Guba, 1986). The interpretivist constructionist perspective is crucial in exploring the subjective experiences and perspectives of individuals

and teams in UBIs settings, which aligns with previous research on entrepreneurial leadership in developing economies (Harrison et al., 2016a).

This study focused on entrepreneurial leadership from a team context, and participants were selected through a purposive sampling method. Purposive sampling method is an appropriate sampling choice as it allows the researchers to study a specific population with the intention of gaining an in-depth understanding of their experiences and perspectives (Creswell, 2009). The data were collected through semi-structured interviews with entrepreneurial leaders – leading team start-up at UBIs. A total of 40 entrepreneurial leaders (in 18 teams) from four regions of Pakistan (Islamabad/Gilgit, Punjab, Sindh, and Balochistan) participated in the study. Semi-structured interviews were employed because they enable the researchers to understand the experiences and perspectives of entrepreneurial leaders in a more comprehensive manner while also allowing for some flexibility in the interview process (Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018; Kvale, 1994). The data were analysed using a three-stage thematic analysis as described by King et al. (2018), which is consistent with existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership skills (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016; Harrison et al., 2016a; Harrison et al., 2018). The data transcripts were organised and encoded using NVivo (version¹²), and a thematic analysis was performed to identify common themes and patterns in the qualitative data (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016). The researchers recognise thematic analysis as an appropriate data analysis method because it allows to create a narrative or story from the data in order to effectively communicate their findings (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Chapter 4 provides a detailed discussion of research methodology and its underlying philosophies.

1.7 Originality and contribution to knowledge

1.7.1 Originality

Originality is the primary consideration in evaluating an academic work (Harrison, 2016).

There are several criteria that can be used to determine the originality of a research, such as fulfilling one or more of the following criteria, as identified by Guetzkow et al. (2004):

1. Using a new approach, theory, method, or data
2. Studying a new topic
3. Researching the underexplored area
4. Providing new findings

According to Phillips and Pugh (1994), research is recognised as original if it meets any of the following criteria as shown in Table 1:

Table 1 Originality of research

1. Presenting new information that has not been written about before
2. Continuing work that was previously original
3. Conducting original research that was designed by a senior colleague
4. Providing a unique technique, observation, or result within a competent but unoriginal piece of research
5. Having numerous original ideas, methods, and interpretations that are carried out by others under the direction of the researcher
6. Demonstrating originality by testing someone else's idea through empirical research that has not been done before
7. Making a synthesis that has not been made before
8. Using already known material with a new interpretation
9. Testing something in one country that has previously only been done in other countries
10. Applying a well-known technique in a new area
11. Bringing new evidence to bear on an old issue
12. Being cross-disciplinary and using different methodologies
13. Examining areas that people in the discipline have not considered before
14. Adding to knowledge in a way that has not been done before

Source: Phillips and Pugh (1994)

This study meets the originality criteria as established by Guetzkow et al. (2004) in their third and fourth criteria and Phillips and Pugh (1994) in their fifth, eighth, eleventh, thirteenth, and

fourteenth criteria, as it contributes new knowledge in a unique manner. The following section explains the significance of these criteria and the originality of this research.

1.7.1.1 New dimensions to knowledge

The purpose of this study was to investigate the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders at the team level within the context of UBIs in Pakistan. In addition, this study proposed an empirical model of entrepreneurial leadership development in teams. Thus, it provides new insights into entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development and expands the theoretical scope of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and development in teams, which had not previously been explored.

1.7.1.2 Application of a methodological technique in a new area

This research employs a new methodological technique by conducting the first systematic literature review on entrepreneurial leadership competencies, their impact on organisations, and their development. The outcomes of this review offered fresh insights and enhanced our understanding of the topic, while also identifying research gaps and offering future research directions that have not been thoroughly addressed in prior studies.

1.7.1.3 Researching the underexplored area

This study aimed to fill the research gap by exploring entrepreneurial leadership competencies at the group level, with a focus on UBIs. The goal was to develop a comprehensive framework for the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies in teams. The model serves as a foundation for developing entrepreneurial leaders in a developing-economy context. This study represents a pioneering investigation into the competencies of entrepreneurial leadership,

specifically within the context of university-based business incubators in a developing economy.

1.7.1.4 Providing new findings

This study provides a novel contribution to the field of entrepreneurial leadership by exploring the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders working in teams at UBIs. Unlike previous research, which has mostly focused on individual-level competencies and the perspective of individual leaders or followers, this study expands the understanding of entrepreneurial leadership by offering a team-based conceptualisation within the context of UBIs, an area that has not been previously explored. The findings of this study deepen our comprehension of the complexities of entrepreneurial leadership challenges and competencies in a team context, thereby providing new perspectives on entrepreneurial leadership as a team phenomenon.

1.7.1.5 Using already known material but with a new interpretation

This study offered a novel interpretation of entrepreneurial leadership competencies at the group level and proposed ways in which these competencies could be learned and developed to enhance the process of creating new ventures and start-up development. These insights elucidate novel perspective to entrepreneurial leadership research from a team context.

1.7.1.6 New Evidence

This study aimed to contribute to the limited empirical knowledge base on entrepreneurial leadership by providing new insights on entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and their development from a team context in a developing economy perspective.

1.7.2 Contribution to knowledge

This study offered three important contributions to knowledge that are categorised as empirical, practical, and theoretical contributions. These contributions will be discussed in detail in the subsequent sections.

1.7.2.1 Empirical contribution

This study aimed to shed light on the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders working in teams at UBIs. The objective was to examine how entrepreneurial leaders effectively cope with challenges and develop their competencies to lead new ventures successfully. The study provided empirical insights from the perspectives of nascent entrepreneurial leaders in UBI settings, adding to the body of knowledge on entrepreneurial leadership practices within teams in a developing economy context.

1.7.2.2 Practical contribution

The findings of this study can inform policy decisions related to the promotion of an entrepreneurial culture, the identification of training needs, and the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies among aspiring entrepreneurial leaders in the country. These policy implications are relevant to stakeholders such as the Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan, the National Incubation Centre (NIC), the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Authority (SMEDA), higher education institutions (HEIs), and Social Education Environment Development (SEED) of Pakistan.

1.7.2.3 Theoretical contribution

This study offers prominent theoretical insights into the fields of entrepreneurial leadership, UBIs, and entrepreneurial leadership development. It expands the scope of entrepreneurial leadership by introducing a team-based perspective on entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study of its kind that focused on entrepreneurial leadership competencies from a team perspective and proposed an empirical competency model. This novel contribution to the literature on entrepreneurial leadership can be used by future researchers to explore entrepreneurial leadership development from a quantitative perspective, thereby increase the generalisability of the findings of this study.

1.8 Thesis Structure

This thesis is composed of seven chapters. Chapter 1 provides background information and context for the present study. It outlines the research aim, objectives, questions, and methodology used and explains the originality and contributions of the study to existing knowledge. Chapters 2 and 3 comprise literature reviews. In Chapter 2, a comprehensive review of the literature on entrepreneurial leadership is presented, examining the intersection of leadership and entrepreneurship, and critically analysing their existing approaches. This review adopts a systematic literature review (SLR) approach, which ensures a rigorous and evidence-based analysis of the existing body of literature. Chapter 3 discusses the role of entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy with a focus on Pakistan, including its

geographical, political, and economic landscapes, and the role of business incubators in entrepreneurial leadership development. The research methodology of the study, including the research design, sample, data collection and analysis, and philosophical stance, is presented in Chapter 4. The findings of the study, including the challenges, competencies, and development of entrepreneurial leadership from a team perspective, are covered in Chapter 5. In chapter 6, the findings are interpreted and analysed in relation to the existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership, business incubators, and entrepreneurial leadership development. Subsequently, a team-based empirical model of entrepreneurial leadership development and its outcomes is also discussed. In Chapter 7, an overview of the entire study, its key findings, insights into theoretical and practical implications, acknowledgment of its limitations, and recommendations for future research, are delineated.

2 Literature Review (Part One) – Entrepreneurial leadership

2.1 Introduction

Entrepreneurial leadership, as an emerging field of study, has evolved from the convergence of leadership and entrepreneurship (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018). To gain a deeper understanding of this emerging paradigm, it is crucial to examine leadership and entrepreneurship from a theoretical perspective (Clark, 2020). This chapter aims to provide a comprehensive overview of these concepts by comparing and critically analysing various approaches to leadership and entrepreneurship. Furthermore, this chapter also conducts a systematic literature review on entrepreneurial leadership competencies, their impact, and development to inform the current state of research on the topic and suggest future research directions.

The chapter is structured as follows: The first section delves into the concept of leadership and critically analyses different perspectives and approaches to leadership. The second section examines entrepreneurship, including its key approaches and characteristics. Subsequently, the chapter introduces the concept of entrepreneurial leadership and explores its varying perspectives. The chapter concludes with a systematic literature review on the significance of entrepreneurial leadership, its competencies, and development. The objective of SLR is to offer a comprehensive insight into the present state of research in the field of entrepreneurial leadership competencies, with a focus on identifying significant research gaps and proposing potential avenues for future investigation (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016; Harrison et al., 2016a).

2.2 Leadership

Research on leadership has witnessed a significant growth, with findings highlighting the existence of various theoretical approaches that attempt to elucidate the intricate nature of the leadership process (Northouse, 2019). Yet there is no universally accepted definition of leadership (Harrison, 2016; Harrison, 2018; Northouse, 2019; Yukl, 2010). Scholars generally agree that leadership involves an influential interaction between a leader and followers, shaped by the leader’s personality traits, behaviour, followers’ perceptions, and context (Northouse, 2019; Yukl, 2010). While some researchers view leadership as a behaviour and few scholars recognise it as a process (Day, 2000; Harrison, 2016; Stogdill, 1974). Despite the extensive body of research, the field of leadership remains a complex and diverse phenomenon, with some research gaps still existing (Harrison et al., 2018; Harrison, 2018). Existing conceptualisations of leadership span various contexts; therefore, it is impossible to provide a comprehensive definition of the notion. Table 2 below presents a range of definitions of leadership, covering its various perspectives.

Table 2 Leadership definitions

Author	Definition	Concept
Hemphill (1949)	“The behaviour of an individual while he is involved in directing group activities.”	Behaviour
Stogdill (1950)	“Leadership may be considered as the process (act) of influencing the activities of an organized group in its efforts toward goal setting and goal achievement.”	Process
Bennis (1959)	Leadership is “the process by which an agent induces a subordinate to behave in a desired manner.”	Process
Katz and Kahn (1978)	Leadership is “the influential increment over and above mechanical compliance with the routine directives of the organisation.”	Behavioural process
Smircich and Morgan (1982)	“Leadership is realised in the process whereby one or more individuals succeeds in attempting to frame and define the reality of other.” “It involves a complicity or process of negotiation through which certain individuals implicitly or explicitly surrender their power to define the nature of their experience to others.”	Process

Richards and Engle (1986)	“Leadership is about articulating visions, embodying values, and creating the environment within which things can be accomplished.”	Behaviour
Gardner (1990)	Leadership is “the process of persuasion or example by which an individual (or leadership team) induces a group to pursue objectives held by the leader or shared by the leader and his or her follower.”	Process
Jacobs and Jaques (1990)	“Leadership is a process of giving purpose (meaningful direction) to collective effort and causing willing effort to be expended to achieve purpose.”	Process
Kotter (1990)	Leadership “refers to a process that helps direct and mobilize people and/or their ideas...”	Process
Drath and Palus (1994)	“Leadership is the process of making sense of what people are doing together so that people will understand and be committed.”	Process
Clark and Clark (1996)	“Leadership is an activity or set of activities, observable to others, that occurs in a group, organisation, or institution, and which involves a leader and followers who willingly subscribe to common purposes and work together to achieve them.”	Process
Barnard (1997)	Leadership “refers to the quality of the behaviour of individuals guiding other people or their activities in organized efforts.”	Behaviour
Stogdill (1997)	Leadership is “the process of influencing the activities of an organised group in its efforts towards goal setting and goal achievement.”	Process
Robbins (1998)	Leadership is “the ability to influence a group toward the achievement of goals.”	Ability
Barker (2001)	Leadership is “a process of transformative change where the ethics of individuals are integrated into the mores of a community as a means of evolutionary social development.”	Process
Lussier and Achua (2001)	“Leadership is the influencing process of leaders and followers to achieve organizational objectives through change.”	Process
Northouse (2010)	“Leadership is a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal.”	Process
Yukl (2010)	“Leadership is the process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to accomplish shared objectives.”	Process

Source: Harrison et al. (2018)

2.2.1 A critical review of leadership approaches

Leadership research has made significant contributions to our understanding of this field, resulting in the emergence of new theories, approaches, and paradigm shifts. There are several

leadership approaches that have evolved over time, including the Great Man theory, trait theory, behavioural theory, contingency theory, transformational theory, transactional theory, servant leadership theory, authentic leadership theory, and entrepreneurial leadership theory. These different approaches offer varying perspectives on leadership and contribute to the rich and evolving body of knowledge in this area (Harrison, 2016; Harrison, 2018; Northouse, 2019).

The Great Man theory, originally proposed by Thomas Carlyle, posits that leaders are born with inherent personality traits rather than made, representing an early perspective on leadership that attributes leadership to those who have achieved significant success in various fields (Harrison, 2016; Northouse, 2019). The Great Man theory led to the development of the trait theory of leadership, which centres on the identification of personality traits that are believed to be associated with effective leadership (Harrison, 2016; Northouse, 2019; Stogdill, 1974). Behavioural theory, on the other hand, examines the actions and behaviours of effective leaders, whereas contingency theory argues that leadership does not occur in a uniform style and that various situations call for diverse leadership styles. In addition, transformational theory emphasises the leader's ability to inspire and motivate followers. While servant leadership theory underscores the importance of leaders serving and empowering their followers (Harrison, 2016; Northouse, 2019; Yukl, 2010).

Despite the theoretical significance of leadership and its various approaches, research in this field continues to evolve, with new theoretical approaches emerging regularly (Harrison, 2016). With the emergence of the theory of distributed leadership, leadership research has shifted dramatically in recent years towards a collective perspective. This approach acknowledges that leadership is a social process that emerges from the interdependent roles of multiple actors, particularly during 'post-heroic' leadership research (Harrison, 2016). In addition, the challenges posed by corporate scandals, terrorism, SARS, and pandemics have

demanded a leadership style characterised by greater integrity, character, and accountability. As a result, authentic leadership has gained prominence, emphasising the importance of self-awareness, genuineness, transparency, and ethical behaviour in leaders who foster positive relationships with their followers (Luthans and Avolio, 2003). This approach emphasises the importance of leaders embodying these qualities in their leadership style. Table 3 presents a critical analysis of various leadership approaches.

Table 3 A critical assessment to leadership approaches

Leadership approaches	Key Assumptions	Key Theorists	Limitations
Great Man theory	Focuses on the assumptions that leaders are born not made.	Carlyle (1840)	Limit leadership to a small number of individuals with an emphasis on inherent qualities, while ignoring the role of skills and process in leadership development.
Trait approach	Focuses on what makes certain individuals as great leaders; emphasises the personality traits of great leaders.	Kirkpatrick and Locke (1991), Lord et al. (1986), Dinh and Lord (2012), Stogdill (1948, 1974)	The trait approach of leadership presents inconsistent set of traits and attributes of leaders. It does not recognise the impact of context and situations (Harrison, 2016; Northouse, 2019; Stogdill, 1948).
Skill approach	Emphasis on the skills and abilities of leaders that can be learned and developed.	Katz (1955), Mumford et al. (2000), Yammarino (2000)	Skill models are broad and extend beyond the boundaries of leadership. Rather than being solely acquired through training or development, skills are often rooted in traits (Northouse, 2019).
Behavioural approach	Focuses on the behaviours of leaders i.e., what leaders do and how they act in a certain context.	Blake and Mouton (1964, 1978, 1985), Blake and McCanse (1991)	According to Bryman (1992) and Yukl (2010), the behavioural approach to leadership falls short of addressing leadership behaviour and its impact on performance outcomes. In addition, this approach is frequently limited to specific contexts and may not be readily applicable in larger or more diverse contexts, as Harrison (2016) and Northouse (2019) have pointed out.
Situational approach	Emphasise every situation demands different leadership styles.	Hersey and Blanchard (1969a, b), Blanchard (1985), Blanchard et al. (2013)	The situational approach to leadership lacks adequate theoretical and empirical validation, lacks a clear conceptual model for followers' development, and fails to recognise the significance of demographic factors in the leader-follower relationship (Northouse, 2019).
Path-goal theory	Path-goal theory discusses how leaders motivate followers to accomplish designated goals.	Evans (1970), House (1971), House and Dessler (1974), House and Mitchell (1975)	The path-goal theory of leadership lacks conceptual clarity and empirical validation, and it fails to account for gender differences in leader-follower behaviour and motivation.
Leader-Member Exchange Theory	Emphasises leadership as a relationship between leaders and followers.	Dansereau et al. (1975), Graen (1976), Graen and Cashman (1975)	The leader-member exchange theory lacks validated models for understanding the leader-member relationships, does not address conflicts of interest between in group and outgroup followers, and fails to consider fairness and equality in the treatment of followers, while ignoring contextual factors (Harrison, 2016; Northouse, 2019).

Transformational leadership	Concentrates on change and transforming people through emotions, values, ethics, standards, and long-term goals.	e.g., Northouse, (2019), Burns (1978, 1985, 1990), Bass and Avolio, (1994)	The concept of transformational leadership lacks clarity in its definition, and it may not be as suitable for corporations, as it is more focused on the political and social sectors. Additionally, there are limitations in measuring transformational leadership behaviour (Northouse, 2019).
Charismatic leadership	Emphasise on solving crisis and problems through vision and charisma.	e.g., Northouse, (2019), Conger and Kanungo (1987; 1998), House (1977), Weber (1947)	Leadership based on charisma tends to focus primarily on crisis situations and may not adequately address the application of leadership in routine business contexts. In addition, there may be a lack of differentiation between positive and negative charisma, with an undue emphasis on the perspectives of great leaders (Harrison, 2016).
Transactional leadership	Transactional leadership focuses on contingent rewards and management-by-exception.	Burns (1978) (cited in Northouse, 2019), Bass and Avolio (1990)	Transactional leadership provides a narrow perspective of leadership and does not consider entrepreneurial dimensions of leadership (Harrison, 2016).
Authentic leadership	Emphasise on leaders' authenticity and being real in their act of leadership.	George (2003), George and Sims (2007), Luthans and Avolio (2003)	Authentic leadership approach lacks theoretical clarity and is still considered to be in a formative stage. Additionally, moral aspects of authentic leadership may not be adequately explained, and there is a dearth of empirical evidence regarding the positive outcomes associated with authentic leadership (Northouse, 2019).
Servant leadership	Emphasises on the role of leaders to be attentive and show concerns to followers.	Greenleaf (1970), Blanchard and Hodges (2003)	Servant leadership lack precise dimensions and processes and not applicable to every context (Northouse, 2019).
Adaptive leadership	Focuses on how leaders encourage people to adapt, face and cope dynamic challenges.	Heifetz (1998), Heifetz et al. (2009)	Adaptive leadership lacks robust theoretical and empirical foundations, with an unclear and impractical process that often remains abstract and fails to incorporate a moral dimension (Northouse, 2019).
Distributed leadership	View leadership as a group and collective phenomenon occurs from the interactions between individuals and their context.	Gronn (2002), Spillane (2005)	Distributed leadership may not be suitable in smaller organisation settings (Harrison, 2016).

Despite their prominent contributions, the above leadership theories have received criticism. As a result, the ongoing discourse on leadership has prompted a shift in focus from traditional approaches to more dynamic and contemporary ones, which emphasise the recognition of leadership as a process that can be developed (Harrison et al., 2018). Various scholars have advocated the importance of leaders possessing specific competencies to effectively navigate the challenges of the dynamic business environment (Gupta et al., 2004; Kempster and Cope, 2010). Consequently, this shift has directed the focus of leadership research towards an entrepreneurial era, highlighting the importance of leadership competencies such as risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactive behaviours as key elements of entrepreneurial leadership (Clark and Harrison, 2017).

The research on entrepreneurial leadership is still in its early stages, with the concept lacking adequate theoretical foundations. Roomi and Harrison (2011) have explored entrepreneurial leadership and proposed four perspectives, including the convergence of leadership and entrepreneurship, psychological perspective, contextual perspective, and holistic perspective. Furthermore, Harrison (2016) and Clark (2020) have contributed to the field of entrepreneurial leadership research by conducting systematic literature reviews and extending the debate by presenting a skill-based perspective on entrepreneurial leadership in the context of developing and developed economies.

Despite the growing body of literature on entrepreneurial leadership, the concept remains somewhat elusive, and various perspectives, such as entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development in various settings, require further research to gain a deeper understanding. The topic of entrepreneurial leadership and its underlying dimensions will be addressed in subsequent sections of this chapter.

2.3 Entrepreneurship

The primary focus of this study is entrepreneurial leadership, which combines the elements of both entrepreneurship and leadership theories (Vecchio, 2003). To fully comprehend the subject, it is necessary to delve into the subject of entrepreneurship, conduct a critical examination of its various facets, and draw a parallel between entrepreneurship and leadership (Clark, 2020; Vecchio, 2003). The field of entrepreneurship has evolved and attracted a considerable body of literature covering various dimensions of the notion (Frederick et al., 2015). Yet, the concept remains elusive and complex and entails significant theoretical challenges (Harrison, 2016; Shane and Venkatamaran, 2000; Vecchio, 2003). One of the most significant challenges facing the field of entrepreneurship is the absence of a conceptual framework capable of predicting entrepreneurial outcomes (Shane and Venkatamaran, 2000). Furthermore, another challenge attributed to entrepreneurship is its conceptual proximity to other fields, such as leadership (Vecchio, 2003). This challenge has prompted attempts to distinguish entrepreneurship from other fields, as reflected in the various definitions proposed by various scholars. Another challenge arises from the overlapping characteristics of leadership and entrepreneurship, which can complicate efforts to differentiate the two domains (Clark, 2020).

Despite facing conceptual and theoretical challenges, the topic of entrepreneurship has been extensively debated, resulting in the emergence of various approaches and definitions. The earliest recognition of entrepreneurship as a distinct field can be traced back to the 18th century, when Richard Cantillon, an Irish French banker, defined entrepreneurs as individuals engaged in “risk-bearing” activities. Similarly, during the industrial revolution in England, the role of entrepreneurs was acknowledged as involving risk-taking and resource transformation (Frederick et al., 2015). Subsequently, other scholars and economists, such as Jean Baptiste Say and Joseph Schumpeter, in the 18th and 20th centuries, respectively, attributed significance

to entrepreneurship in economic development (Frederick et al., 2015). The economist Joseph Schumpeter defined entrepreneurship as the “carrying out of new combinations” in one of the earliest definitions (Schumpeter, 2003). This definition emphasises the role of entrepreneurs in introducing new products, technologies, and business models that both disrupt existing markets and create new ones. According to Schumpeter’s theory of creative destruction, this process of innovation drives economic growth. From the perspective of Kirzner’s theory of entrepreneurial discovery, entrepreneurs have a unique ability to identify market opportunities because they have a keen sense of alertness and can act quickly to capitalise on them (Kirzner, 1997).

Despite the ongoing discourse, there is still ambiguity in understanding the concept of entrepreneurship and its relationship to other related concepts such as entrepreneurial behaviour and personality (Cunningham and Lischeron, 1991; Harrison, 2016). Research in entrepreneurship is still in its early stages, and there is no universally accepted definition of entrepreneurship (Frederick et al., 2015; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000). The current literature presents various competing and overlapping concepts and theories, including entrepreneurial orientation (Covin and Slevin, 1991), cognitive alertness (Gaglio and Katz, 2001), and opportunity discovery and exploitation (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000). Cunningham and Lischeron (1991) proposed six entrepreneurship schools of thought. Frederick et al. (2015) presented seven schools of thought on entrepreneurship, comprising macro and micro views of entrepreneurship theories. Whereas Clark et al. (2019) proposed entrepreneurship research from 11 perspectives. Table 4 provides a critical analysis of various approaches to entrepreneurship.

Despite being recognised as an interdisciplinary field, entrepreneurship cannot be fully understood without exploring its concepts in conjunction with other fields of study, such as leadership (Frederick et al., 2015). Cunningham and Lischeron (1991) acknowledged that

entrepreneurs must possess leadership skills to envision organisational goals and effectively guide followers towards achieving those goals. Vecchio (2003) also advocated for viewing entrepreneurship as a form of leadership in a specific context. Furthermore, Clark et al. (2019) demanded the inclusion of the concept of entrepreneurial leadership in entrepreneurship research to extend the discourse on entrepreneurship. These assertions suggest that entrepreneurs should not only possess the ability to identify and exploit business opportunities but also possess leadership skills to guide new and established organisations to remain competitive in the dynamic business world. Therefore, adopting entrepreneurial behaviour to tackle challenges and identifying business opportunities is crucial for entrepreneurial success. Consequently, these debates provided a fresh perspective on entrepreneurship and leadership research which led to the emergence of entrepreneurial leadership. The next section will further discuss entrepreneurial leadership by examining the convergence of leadership and entrepreneurship.

Table 4 A critical assessment of entrepreneurship approaches

Entrepreneurship perspectives	Basic Assumption	Criticism
Economic perspective	How entrepreneurs create new business ventures and generate wealth.	The economic perspective lack of focus on social, cultural context, and negative externalities.
The psychological perspective	Focuses on entrepreneurs' personality traits, motivation, and cognition of entrepreneurs.	Limited to human attributes and overlook social and environmental complexity in entrepreneurial action.
The behavioural perspective	Focuses on the factors that influence entrepreneurs' decision-making and action-taking processes.	This perspective neglects impact of social and cultural environment on entrepreneurial behaviour.
The Great Man perspective	Person-centric and focuses on certain individuals possess unique qualities destined for entrepreneurship.	Limit entrepreneurship to few people and disregard the creative and entrepreneurial potential of ordinary individuals.
The sociological perspective	Emphasise on social and cultural factors impacting the entrepreneurial process.	Disregards the individual agency and decision-making role of entrepreneurs in the process.
The management perspective	Focus on processes, practices, and strategies of entrepreneurs as manager in the organisations.	Overlook the role of innovation and creativity in entrepreneurship. Fail to distinguish the competencies of managers and entrepreneurs.
The cognitive perspective	Concentrate on how entrepreneurs think and process information using their cognitive processes such as perception, attention, and reasoning.	Ignore practical aspects in entrepreneurial implementation process and role of emotions, motivations, and social influence.
Leadership perspective	Focuses on role of leaders in creating, developing, and managing new ventures.	Neglect the influence of external factors on entrepreneurial behaviour.
Process perspective	Emphasise on effectuation and co-creating opportunities with stakeholders.	Oversimplified the complex and dynamic entrepreneurial process i.e., idea generation, resource acquisition, and new venture creation.
New venture creation perspective	Emphasise on establishment of new businesses or ventures.	Fail to explain methods and strategies through which entrepreneurs identify market opportunities, conduct market research, and customer needs.
Opportunity recognition and exploitation perspective	Focus on process of recognising and seizing business opportunities.	Fail to describe the process and skills require for opportunity identification and exploitation. The perception of identifying and exploiting business opportunities is a complex social process.

2.4 Convergence of Leadership and Entrepreneurship: The Emergence of Entrepreneurial Leadership

Entrepreneurial leadership, which converges entrepreneurship and leadership, has gained increased attention in recent times. Although leadership and entrepreneurship were traditionally recognised as separate fields of study, recent scholarship has drawn parallels between both fields from conceptual and historical perspectives (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Bagheri et al., 2013a; Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Harrison et al., 2016a). Some researchers, like Vecchio (2003), recognised entrepreneurship as a type of leadership in a different context. The growing debate on the commonalities and differences between entrepreneurship and leadership led to the emergence of a new paradigm of inquiry known as ‘entrepreneurial leadership’ (Bagheri and Pihie, 2010; Harrison et al., 2018). Researchers have defined entrepreneurial leadership from various perspectives (Gupta et al., 2004; Hejazi et al., 2012; Renko et al., 2015; Surie and Ashley, 2008). Gupta et al. (2004) defined EL as “leadership that produces visionary scenarios that are used to gather and mobilise a ‘supporting cast’ of participants who get dedicated by the vision to the discovery and exploitation of strategic value creation” (p. 242). Hejazi et al. (2012) and Renko et al. (2015) defined entrepreneurial leadership as identifying and seizing business opportunities through entrepreneurial activity and influence. Surie and Ashley (2008) argued that entrepreneurial leadership is the best way to solve organisational issues in turbulent situations.

Despite growing scholarship, entrepreneurial leadership lacks a conceptual foundation and suitable instruments for assessing entrepreneurial leaders’ traits and behaviours (Renko et al., 2015). Based on existing conceptualisations, this study recognises EL as a process of coping with complex entrepreneurial challenges and cocreating entrepreneurial opportunities in teams through innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactive behaviour (Chen, 2007).

2.4.1 Perspectives on Entrepreneurial leadership research

The research on entrepreneurial leadership is constantly evolving, characterised by a growing body of literature that explores different aspects of this phenomenon. As scholarly interest in entrepreneurial leadership continues to grow, it has sparked significant academic debate, resulting in the emergence of multiple perspectives on this topic. In the following section, we will explore entrepreneurial leadership from four distinct perspectives, namely the psychological, context, behavioural, and competency perspectives.

2.4.1.1 Psychological perspective

Numerous studies have explored the concept of entrepreneurial leadership from a psychological perspective, identifying various personality traits that are associated with entrepreneurial leaders (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Darling and Beebe, 2007; Gupta et al., 2004; Karanian, 2007). For example, Cogliser and Brigham (2004) found that entrepreneurial leaders require traits such as vision, influence, creativity, and planning, while Karanian (2007) highlighted the importance of traits such as connection, imagination, cultural background, willingness to confront, and unique character. Fernald et al. (2005) noted that leaders and entrepreneurs share characteristics such as vision, problem-solving, decision-making, and risk-taking. Darling and Beebe (2007) emphasised the need for communication skills in entrepreneurial leadership.

However, some researchers have pointed out limitations to this perspective. For instance, Harrison et al. (2018) and Roomi and Harrison (2011) argued that the existing literature primarily focuses on comparing entrepreneurship and leadership without providing a comprehensive understanding of the characteristics of entrepreneurial leadership. This

perspective also tends to overlook the fact that entrepreneurial leadership competencies can be learned and developed, instead emphasising the innate personality traits of entrepreneurial leaders (Renko et al., 2015). Moreover, this perspective fails to consider the impact of contextual factors on entrepreneurial leadership, which could significantly influence its effectiveness and outcomes (Harrison et al., 2018).

2.4.1.2 Context perspective

A strand of literature explored entrepreneurial leadership from a contextual perspective such as gender (Galloway et al., 2015; Henry et al., 2015; Patterson et al., 2012), family business (Kansikas et al., 2012), research groups in universities (Hansson and Mønsted, 2008); indigenous businesses (Mapunda, 2007), retail pharmacy (Harrison et al., 2018; Harrison et al., 2016b); human, social, and institutional capital (Haynes et al., 2015; Leitch et al., 2013), aircraft industry (D'Intino et al., 2008), strategic management (Kuratko and Hornsby, 1999; Thompson, 1999; Kuratko, 2007), shared or distributed leadership (Cohen, 2004; Sklaveniti, 2017), and SMEs (Leitch et al., 2009; Simba and Thai, 2019).

Furthermore, some researchers have also investigated entrepreneurial leadership from cross-cultural and national perspectives (Choi, 2009; Bagheri and Harrison, 2020; Megheirkouni et al., 2020; Van Assche, 2005; Wang et al., 2012), while others have attributed entrepreneurial leadership to effective SMEs and ventures' performance (Agus and Hassan, 2010; Paudel, 2019; Rahim et al., 2015). Some scholars have examined entrepreneurial leadership education and development (Bagheri and Pihie, 2010; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Churchill et al., 2013; Hentschke and Caldwell, 2005; Kempster and Cope, 2010; Okudan and Rzasa, 2006; Roomi and Harrison, 2011).

Despite garnering growing scholarly attention, the context approach does not address the issues about the conditions that foster entrepreneurial leadership and does not inform whether they are best for a new venture or exist in established organisations (Clark et al., 2019). Moreover, how entrepreneurial leadership behaviours and their outcomes in organisations vary in cross-cultural settings, were not addressed within contextual perspective.

2.4.1.3 Behavioural perspective

The behavioural perspective of entrepreneurial leadership focuses on how entrepreneurial leaders act in certain circumstances. This perspective examines entrepreneurial leaders' strategy adoption and implementation (Darling and Beebe, 2007). The behavioural perspective of entrepreneurial leadership emphasises how entrepreneurial leaders add value to their organisations by integrating their own behaviours like communicating meaning, positioning for trust, and respecting others (Darling and Beebe, 2007). Gupta et al. (2004) assert that entrepreneurial leaders' two key roles include 'scenario enactment' and 'cast enactment'. Entrepreneurial leaders use 'scenario enactment' to visualise the organisation's future vision, while, through 'cast enactment', they inspire and persuade their supporters to achieve long-term commitment to accomplish that vision. Akin to this, Flamholtz (2011) contends that entrepreneurial leaders set vision, manage system development, coordinate operations, manage culture, and promote innovation and change.

Although this approach provides a relatively pragmatic perspective to entrepreneurial leadership, its applicability is limited due to the diverse and complicated entrepreneurial contexts (Harrison et al., 2018). Furthermore, the perception of followers towards entrepreneurial leadership behaviour and the meaning they ascribe to it, is a complex

phenomenon that lacks well-defined theoretical models.

2.4.1.4 Competency perspective

Recently, a growing corpus of literature has examined entrepreneurial leadership from a competency perspective (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Bagheri and Lope Pihie, 2013; Clark, 2020; Guo, 2009; Gupta et al., 2004; Harrison et al., 2018; Putsom et al., 2019a: 2019b; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002), which is supported by a set of skills, knowledge, and attitudes needed for entrepreneurial leaders to lead successful entrepreneurial initiatives (Aouni and Surlemont, 2009). As a result, several entrepreneurial leadership competencies were identified. For instance, Harrison et al. (2018) identified four entrepreneurial leadership skills—function/technical, conceptual, interpersonal, and entrepreneurial—needed for entrepreneurial leadership success in developing economies. Clark (2020) found that entrepreneurial leaders in Scottish SMEs require technical, conceptual, entrepreneurial, and interpersonal skills.

In addition, some scholars also identified key entrepreneurial leadership competencies by studying them in different contexts, such as human skills, managerial competency, entrepreneurial skills, interpersonal skills, and risk-taking skills (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Pihie and Bagheri, 2012; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Clark, 2020; Guo, 2009; Gupta et al., 2004; Harrison et al., 2018; Putsom et al., 2019a:2019b; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Ahmed and Harrison (2021) found that entrepreneurial leaders' personal, functional, interpersonal, technological, ethical, and environmental competencies are essential for DIY lab innovation. Guo (2009) discovered that health care leaders need interpersonal, organisational, and healthcare system and environment competencies to perform well. Swiercz and Lydon (2002) found that entrepreneurial leaders in high-growth companies must possess self- and functional

competencies, and Putsom et al. (2019) identified that entrepreneurial leaders' personal, managerial, proactive, and technological competencies create value in the automotive industry.

Arguably, the above perspectives may help to explore entrepreneurial leadership from various angles; further research is required to consolidate the theoretical landscapes and explore the facets of entrepreneurial leadership from an individualistic, team, and interorganisational perspective to obtain a more holistic understanding of entrepreneurial leadership (Leitch and Volery, 2017). As an emerging field of research, the current literature on EL is dispersed and fragmented (Clark et al., 2019). Specifically, the research on the impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies across organisations and their development lacks a conclusive picture within the existing literature. The extant literature highlights that entrepreneurial leadership competencies play a prominent role in identifying and exploiting business opportunities and coping with business challenges in uncertain environments (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Bagheri et al., 2013a; Harrison et al., 2018; Surie and Ashley, 2008).

Considering the limitations, this study recognises EL as a social process that occurs in a dynamic social setting and is influenced by the competencies (knowledge, skills, and behaviours) of entrepreneurial leaders. This, as a result, necessitates the investigation of EL competencies and their development that occurs between individuals and teams. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development across organisations, this study conducts a systematic literature review to draw a conclusive picture of the extant literature pertaining to EL competencies. Evidence from the review provides the knowledge base for developing a competency perspective on entrepreneurial leadership, thus broadening the theoretical base of the concept, and enhancing our understanding of the notion from a broader perspective. By synthesising extant literature, this study also ascertains key research gaps in relation to EL competencies and its development and proposes future research directions.

2.5 Exploring Entrepreneurial leadership competencies: A systematic literature review

The systematic literature review (SLR) is a widely recognised and reliable method for generating evidence-based knowledge (Harrison et al., 2016a). This section provides a comprehensive review of the literature on the impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies, followed by a thorough analysis of existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership development. The forthcoming part compares the quantitative findings of SLR with relevant literature, critically analyses existing approaches and models related to entrepreneurial leadership competencies and proposes key research directions for future research.

2.5.1 Defining competencies

Competence, a term widely used in various fields such as education, psychology, and human resources, refers to an individual's ability to effectively perform a task or function. However, there is no single, unified theory, or definition of competence that can encompass all its diverse applications, leading to confusion and debate among researchers and practitioners (Le Deist and Winterton, 2005). Various definitions and usage of the term "competence" and "competency" in various contexts and regions reflect the lack of clarity of this notion (Woodruffe, 1993). For instance, in Britain, "competence" is commonly used to describe the behaviour a person should be able to demonstrate, while in America, "competency" is often understood as an underlying set of personal characteristics that facilitate superior performance (Woodruffe, 1993). Other definitions of competence include the ability to perform tasks and roles according to expected standards. In effect, competencies encompass the characteristics of an individual that drive superior job performance, including knowledge, skills, traits, and motives, and the integrated set of capabilities arising from clusters of knowledge, skills, and attitudes (Eraut, 1994).

Furthermore, Mansfield (2004) distinguishes three types of competence: outcomes, tasks, and personal traits. Boyatzis defines competency broadly as “an underlying characteristic of a person” that encompasses motives, traits, skills, self-image or social roles, or a body of knowledge that an individual uses (Boyatzis, 1991, p. 28). On the other hand, Hornby and Thomas (1989), cited in Woodruffe (1993), defined competencies as the knowledge, skills, and qualities that are associated with effective leadership and managerial roles.

Despite the multiple definitions and perspectives coined by various researchers, it is yet unclear what competencies truly entail, and there is a call for a more holistic understanding of competencies that considers the combination of knowledge and skills. Therefore, the researchers call for more scholarly work on social competencies, including conceptual and operational competencies and meta-competencies, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the requirements for different occupations (Le Deist and Winterton, 2005). Hence, it is crucial to investigate how competencies are defined within a specific context and how contextual factors play a role in shaping these competencies of entrepreneurial leaders. In line with the above discussion, we recognise competencies as underlying knowledge, skills, and attitudes required for entrepreneurial leaders to carry out certain tasks in their entrepreneurial pursuits. These competencies include a broad range of personal and functional knowledge and skills that enable entrepreneurial leaders to achieve their entrepreneurial goals (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002).

2.5.2 SLR findings

This section presents the findings of a systematic review of the literature on entrepreneurial leadership competencies. The section proceeds as follows: The first section provides a descriptive analysis of 90 studies, including the geographical distribution of the studies, the

number of citations, journals with higher publications, types of studies, and data collection methods. The step-by-step process of SLR is presented in the methodology section (Chapter 4).

2.5.2.1 Descriptive analysis

Descriptive analysis describes the characteristics of studies based on their geographical distribution, paper types, methodological approach, mode of data collection, publication per year, most cited articles, and journals with the highest publication rate. These are detailed below.

2.5.2.1.1 Geographical distribution

The review's findings suggest that several studies focusing on entrepreneurial leadership competencies were conducted within the context of a developing economy, accounting for 65% (or 59 articles) of total studies. Malaysia contributed 19% (11 studies), Nigeria contributed 12% (7 studies), Indonesia contributed 8% (5 studies), Iran contributed 5% (3 studies), and Ghana, Thailand, Taiwan, and Pakistan each contributed 3% (2 studies). From a developed economy context, the United States of America contributed the most studies on entrepreneurial leadership competencies with eight studies, followed by the United Kingdom with six studies. According to the evidence from the review, studies on entrepreneurial leadership competencies are largely rooted in developing economies, despite the fact that research on entrepreneurial leadership primarily presents a western perspective (Clark et al., 2019; Harrison et al., 2018). The geographical distribution of the papers is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The geographical distribution of the papers

2.5.2.1.2 Types of study

The types of studies are classified as conceptual, review, and empirical papers. According to the findings of the review (as shown in Figure 2), 64% (58 articles) were empirical in nature, 28% (25 articles) were conceptual, and review papers accounted for 8% (7 articles) of total studies. The findings show that most conceptual papers were conducted between 2010 and 2020, with the major themes being conceptualisation of entrepreneurial leadership, attributes, skills, and characteristics of entrepreneurial leaders, and entrepreneurial leadership development in large, small, and medium organisations. Despite their valuable contributions to the literature, these papers failed to propose a consensus model of entrepreneurial leadership competencies.

Even though Harrison et al. (2018) proposed a skill-based model for EL, the model has limitations and confined within the context of developing economies. As a result, an agreed-upon model combining overlapping dimensions of EL from developed and developing

economies is required. More research is needed to identify specific entrepreneurial leaders' skills, characteristics, and capabilities (Bagheri et al., 2013a; Gupta et al., 2004).

Figure 2 Types of studies

2.5.2.1.3 Research method

Methodological approaches used in the empirical studies included quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods. According to the evidence from the review (as shown in Figure 3), existing studies on entrepreneurial leadership competencies widely used a quantitative method, accounting for 48% of all empirical studies. While 45% were qualitative, the remaining 7% used a mixed method of data collection. Figure 3 depicts the research methods used in the empirical papers in graphical form.

Figure 3 Research method adopted in studies

2.5.2.1.4 Mode of data collection

The data collection methods in existing studies include surveys, qualitative interviews, case studies, focus group discussions, and observation. According to the SLR findings (as illustrated in Figure 4), 38% of empirical studies used surveys to collect data. Qualitative studies used a variety of data collection methods, including interviews (40%), case studies (10%), and focus groups or observation (7%). The remaining 5% of studies mixed interviews, surveys, and other data collection techniques to collect data. Figure 4 depicts the empirical studies' data collection methods.

Figure 4 Modes of data collection

The reviewed publications span the years 1987 to 2022. Figure 5 depicts the papers' five-year interval distribution. As shown in the figure 5, research on entrepreneurial leadership competencies and development was scarce in the early years, i.e., from 1987 to 2005, with an increasing trend of studies beginning in 2006. During this stage, entrepreneurial leadership received substantial conceptual, empirical, and review papers that served as the conceptual foundation of the field. Most papers on entrepreneurial leadership were published between 2011 and 2020, accounting for 67% of all studies. This phase included 21 quantitative, 20 qualitative, 16 conceptual, and 5 review papers. According to the evidence, most of these

studies conceptually and empirically focused on entrepreneurial leadership competencies in the context of developing economies. As a result, it can be argued that aspects of entrepreneurial leadership competencies, particularly in the context of developed nations, justify further investigation.

Figure 5 Publication of studies in 5 years interval

2.5.2.1.5 Most cited articles

Figure 6 illustrates the top five most-cited articles on entrepreneurial leadership. Gupta et al. (2004) received the most citations among the existing studies, with 1047. Gupta's work is well-known in the literature because it was the first to develop a construct for entrepreneurial leadership (Harrison et al., 2016a), and the definition proposed by Gupta et al. (2004), supported by scenario and cast enactment, is widely accepted by scholars in the field of entrepreneurial leadership. Kuratko (2007) provides a theoretical discussion on entrepreneurial leadership from a global perspective, emphasising the importance of creativity and innovation in 21st-century organisations to uncover business potential, with 573 citations. Kempster and Cope (2010), with 310 citations, explored entrepreneurial leadership as a social learning process. Koryak et al. (2015) reviewed the existing literature and investigated the impact of entrepreneurial leadership capabilities on SMEs, resulting in 286 citations. Leitch et al. (2013),

who investigated entrepreneurial leadership skills through the lens of human, social, and institutional capital, were the fifth most cited paper. Despite their limitations, these papers have made significant contributions to the development of entrepreneurial leadership as an emerging construct.

Figure 6 Most cited articles

2.5.2.1.6 Journals with the highest number of publications

The existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership competencies is scattered across several journals. Journal of Entrepreneurship Education, Journal of Small Business Entrepreneurship, and International Review of Entrepreneurship each contributed three papers in this area, while the Journal of Leadership Studies, Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development, Leader to Leader, Leadership and Organisation Development, and Procedia Social and Behavioural Sciences each contributed two. The journal with the most publications is shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Journal with the most publications

Title of Journals	Number of papers published
Journal of Entrepreneurship Education	3 Articles
Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship	3 Articles
International Review of Entrepreneurship	3 Articles
Journal of Leadership Studies	2 Articles
Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development	2 Articles
Leader to Leader	2 Articles
Leadership & Organization Development Journal	2 Articles
Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences	2 Articles

2.5.2.2 Results

This section addresses three key review questions concerning the impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies on organisations, entrepreneurial leadership competencies, and their development. The following section presents a more in-depth discussion. The details of the SLR findings are discussed using a descriptive, quantitative, and qualitative analysis (Tranfield et al., 2003). Table 6 provides the details of the reviewed articles.

Table 6 Details of reviewed articles

Articles	Author(s)	Type of Study	Area focused
1.	Abbas (2014)	Conceptual	This paper theoretically discussed the challenges of entrepreneurial leaders within the context of Nigeria. The author argues that entrepreneurial leaders need to be academically prepared and gain entrepreneurial experience and managerial skills to cope with the challenges. However, the paper was entirely theoretical, and the discussion didn't cover the areas of entrepreneurial leadership skills development.
2.	Abbas and Tatfi (2010)	Conceptual	This article theoretically discussed the characteristics and skills of entrepreneurial leaders. The authors proposed that trust among employees, communication, self-improvement, technical skills, sense of responsibility, and decision-making skills are critical for entrepreneurial leaders. However, the paper was entirely theoretical and did not discuss how entrepreneurial leaders can develop these skills.
3.	Agbim (2013)	Empirical	This study explored the capabilities of entrepreneurial leadership essential for sustained entrepreneurial success of nascent and experienced entrepreneurial leaders. However, the paper did not discuss how entrepreneurial leaders can develop these capabilities.
4.	Ahmed and Harrison (2021)	Conceptual	This article discussed the challenges and competencies of DIY entrepreneurial leaders in driving innovation at DIY labs. The study proposed an integrated entrepreneurial leadership competency model comprising of personal, functional, interpersonal, technological, ethical, and environmental competencies. However, the paper lacks

			empirical justification to show how these competencies can be developed.
5.	Ahmed and Ramzan (2013)	Conceptual	This paper focused on entrepreneurial leadership competencies development adapting the model proposed by Bagheri et al. (2011).
6.	Akbari et al. (2020)	Empirical	This article explored the role of entrepreneurial leadership on innovative work behaviour of employees through support for innovation and creative self-efficacy within the context of Iranian SMEs. The authors argue that entrepreneurial leaders can enhance employees' innovative behaviour through developing their competencies by participating in entrepreneurship programs, training and coaching. However, the article didn't discuss the nature, structure, and the method of programs through which these competencies are developed.
7.	Almahdi (2019)	Empirical	The purpose of this paper was to explore the role of university adaptation techniques in developing entrepreneurial leadership in context of Saudi Arabia. The author proposes that adaptation of entrepreneurship learning is critical for Saudi Government sustainable economic development goals. However, the study didn't discuss the structure of entrepreneurial learning, and the competencies essential for human capital transformation.
8.	Ansari et al. (2014)	Conceptual	This article focused on entrepreneurial leadership learning to cope with the risk, uncertainty and unpredictability of graduates.
9.	Ariyani (2021)	Empirical	This study explored how school principals create an entrepreneurial learning environment in the school. The authors propose that an entrepreneurial learning environment can be developed through optimization, communication, motivation, monitoring, controlling, role model, and empowerment. School principals can drive innovation through vision building, staff development, and restructuring.
10.	Aziz and Abiddin (2022)	Review	This paper explored leadership styles of students in context of Malaysia. The paper proposed entrepreneurial leadership as an effective leadership style for students to cope with the challenges of 21 st century. The paper also stressed on entrepreneurial leadership development among students through training. However, the paper lack arguments on other entrepreneurial leadership learning and development strategies and the assertions are theoretical and lack empirical basis.

11.	Bagheri (2017)	Empirical	This paper explored the impact of entrepreneurial leadership on innovative work behaviour of high-tech entrepreneurial leaders. The findings show a significant positive relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and employee's innovative work behaviour. The author argues that high tech leaders should gain entrepreneurial training and courses to enhance their opportunity seeking and exploitation capabilities.
12.	Bagheri and Harrison (2020)	Empirical	This article explored the concept of entrepreneurial leadership by developing a multi-dimensional measurement scale in the context of Iran and Scotland. The study followed a comprehensive approach and identified the competencies, roles, and behaviours of entrepreneurial leaders.
13.	Bagheri and Pihie (2010)	Empirical	This article explored the role of family in entrepreneurial leadership competencies' development among university students within the context of Malaysia.
14.	Bagheri and Pihie (2011a)	Conceptual	This article explored entrepreneurial leadership competency development by adapting the competency model of Gupta et al. (2004) underpinned by scenario enactment (pro-activeness, risk taking, and innovativeness) and cast enactment (building commitment and specifying limits), however, the paper was theoretical and lacks empirical evidence.
15.	Bagheri and Pihie (2011b)	Empirical	This article explored entrepreneurial leadership competencies from the lens of university entrepreneurship programmes. The study proposed that entrepreneurial leaders can learn self-awareness, identity realisation, and self-efficacy capabilities through university's entrepreneurship programmes. However, this study was limited in context of two universities, hence the results cannot be generalised to other contexts.
16.	Bagheri and Pihie (2012)	Empirical	This article investigated how entrepreneurial leaders can learn leadership capabilities by participating in student and program related roles in universities. However, this model is only limited in context of university, however, how this model can be applied on experienced entrepreneurial leaders, lacks discussions.
17.	Bagheri et al. (2010)	Empirical	This article focused on entrepreneurial leadership learning from the lens of university students. This study proposed social interaction, observation, and reflection as a tool for entrepreneurial leadership competencies learning. However, the paper failed to outline

			specific mechanisms through which entrepreneurial leadership can be learnt.
18.	Bagheri et al. (2013a)	Empirical	This article examined the role of entrepreneurship programmes in developing entrepreneurial leadership competencies. However, the study failed to identify how entrepreneurial leadership programmes can develop the competencies of entrepreneurial leadership.
19.	Bagheri et al. (2013b)	Empirical	The purpose of this article was to explore the perception of entrepreneurial leaders toward their capabilities in leading new ventures in context of Malaysian university students. The authors propose that entrepreneurial leaders' self-efficacy is a multi-dimensional construct underpinned by various capabilities such as opportunity identification self-efficacy, relationship self-efficacy, management self-efficacy, tolerance self-efficacy, learning self-efficacy.
20.	Bahgeri and Pihie (2009)	Empirical	This article focused on entrepreneurial leadership development from the lens of entrepreneurship programs particularly focusing on student's creativity, innovativeness and risk taking. However, the paper lacks discussion about particular competencies required for entrepreneurial leaders.
21.	Ballein (1998)	Empirical	This paper explored the attributes of healthcare entrepreneurial leaders. The author identified various attributes and skills of senior nurse executives including vision, integrity, strategic thinking, decisiveness, risk taking, innovativeness, persistence, teamwork, confidence, coping with change, communication, financial, team building, and leadership.
22.	Bodolica et al. (2021)	Empirical	This paper explored the role of extracurricular and entrepreneurship club in developing the competencies of social entrepreneurial leaders in context of UAE. The authors argue that university leaders need to develop a sanction-free atmosphere in the university to uplift the social entrepreneurship and innovation skills of nascent entrepreneurial leaders. They further argue that entrepreneurial learning must focus on the employability, communication, innovation, planning, and networking skills of social entrepreneurs.
23.	Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz and	Conceptual	The purpose of this paper was to explore how can entrepreneurial leaders enhance the creativity and accountability in schools. In order to cope with the challenges of the external

	Pashiardis (2020)		<p>environment and capture business opportunities, entrepreneurial leaders in schools need to develop managerial, task handling, personnel selection and development and marketing skills.</p> <p>The authors propose that leadership training modules, internship, and developing cross-sectional networks facilitate effective school management.</p>
24.	Campos (2021)	Empirical	<p>This article examined entrepreneurial leader's characteristics and employee performance in context of MSME. The findings suggest that entrepreneurial leadership skills have positive impact on employee's productivity. The paper identified technical, conceptual, interpersonal, social intelligence, and emotional intelligence skills of MSME's owner as critical for enhancing the employee performance.</p>
25.	Carey et al. (2021)	Empirical	<p>The purpose of this study was to explore how multidisciplinary courses based on consumerism and sustainability can enhance the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in solving the social, economic, and environmental challenges. The authors proposed that sustainability education facilitate systems-thinking, anticipatory, normative, strategic, and interpersonal competencies development among students.</p>
26.	Carpenter (2012)	Empirical	<p>This article explored the attributes of entrepreneurial leaders within the context of librarians. The author argue that entrepreneurial leaders have certain abilities such as creating partnership, inspiring and sharing vision, interpreting human behaviour, risk taking and seeking opportunities which are critically important for librarians to create new organisational structure, generate income, develop information and technology solutions, build new partners and improve services.</p>
27.	Chen (2007)	Empirical	<p>This paper explored how the interaction of entrepreneurial leaders and their team member creativity influence innovative capability of the firm. The findings suggest the risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness capabilities of entrepreneurial leaders enhance the team creativity and firm's innovative capability.</p>
28.	Churchill et al. (2013)	Empirical	<p>This article explored the role of entrepreneurship programmes in developing entrepreneurial leadership skills of Polytechnic students. The authors proposed experiential learning, social interaction and opportunity</p>

			recognition as a means of entrepreneurial leadership development.
29.	Clark et al. (2019)	Review	This paper conducted a systematic literature review and a thematic analysis on entrepreneurial leadership and identified various themes such as the intersection of leadership and entrepreneurship, the gendered approach, the psychological approach, entrepreneurial leadership development, entrepreneurial leadership skills, entrepreneurial teams, the context approach, and entrepreneurial leadership and performance.
30.	Dardiri et al. (2018)	Empirical	This article explored the role of entrepreneurial leadership strategies in achieving academic excellence at technical and vocational educational institution in context of Indonesia. The findings suggest that school principal's capabilities such as articulating vision and mission, motivating and inspiring staff member are essential of achieving academic excellence in the school. The authors argue that school excellence framework should aim to develop hard and soft skills of students. However, the study didn't discuss the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in context of technical and vocational institutions.
31.	Darling and Beebe (2007)	Conceptual	This article explored the skills of entrepreneurial leaders and proposed communication skills as critically important for entrepreneurial leaders. However, the study was only confined to the communication skills and didn't discuss how entrepreneurial leadership skills can be learnt and developed.
32.	D'Intino et al. (2008)	Empirical	The purpose of this article was to highlight the characteristics and capabilities of entrepreneurial leaders associated with aircraft industry. The authors argue that aircraft entrepreneurial leaders can envision and develop the future through effective strategic anticipation and understanding. However, the study was limited to a single aircraft industry i.e., Boeing thus the assertions may not be generalised.
33.	Edmond et al. (2017)	Empirical	This paper explored the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership learning among undergraduate students via a gender perspective. The article explored the impact of pedagogy on students' entrepreneurial leadership skills learning.
34.	Fernald et al. (2005)	Conceptual	This paper draws on similarities and differences of entrepreneurship and leadership and

			identified vision, leadership style, and strategies as core characteristics of entrepreneurial leaders. The authors call for more theoretical and empirical work in relation to entrepreneurial leadership behaviours, ethics, and training and development.
35.	Freeman and Siegfried (2015)	Conceptual	This study theoretically discussed the challenges of entrepreneurial leaders and the capabilities required for entrepreneurial leaders to cope with the challenges of their venture during the growth stage. The study proposed strategic thinking, coaching and self-evaluation as necessary capabilities to overcome their challenges. However, the study was theoretical and lacks empirical underpinning.
36.	Greenberg et al. (2013)	Conceptual	This article proposed three principles that make basis of entrepreneurial leadership decision making. These include cognitive ambidexterity, commitment to social, environmental and economic value creation, and self-awareness. However, the assertions are entirely theoretical and lack empirical justification.
37.	Guo (2009)	Conceptual	This article explored the core competencies of healthcare entrepreneurial leaders and proposed that healthcare system and environment competencies, organisational competencies, interpersonal competencies are essential for healthcare entrepreneurial leaders. However, the competency model was based on previous literature and lacks empirical investigation.
38.	Gupta et al. (2004)	Empirical	This article examined entrepreneurial leadership and identified two different tasks and capabilities of entrepreneurial leaders: scenario enactment (innovativeness and proactiveness) cast enactment (commitment building specifying limitations).
39.	Halim and Razak (2014)	Empirical	This paper explored the communication strategies of female entrepreneurial leaders within the context of Malaysia. The article highlighted the key communication strategies of female entrepreneurial leaders which include mother as a gendered resource, rapport talk, negotiation, iron maiden as a gendered resource, report talk, assertiveness, confrontational communication, pet as a gendered resource, joking and mitigating hedges. The authors argue that focusing on relationship, symbolic communication, body language and cognitive complexity are integral parts of effective communication. However, the study lacks discussion on the impact of

			communication strategies and how female entrepreneurial leaders can develop these communication skills.
40.	Hansson and Mønsted (2008)	Empirical	The purpose of this article was to explore entrepreneurial leadership research strategies in universities. The authors propose that entrepreneurial leaders in universities have certain capabilities that facilitate research advancement and knowledge creation. These skills include charisma, capability of linking external contacts, supporting, and negotiating creativity, and developing an environment of self-confidence.
41.	Harrison et al. (2016a)	Review	The purpose of this paper was to review and synthesise the extant literature on entrepreneurial leadership and its attributes by conducting a systematic literature review. The findings of the SLR shows that entrepreneurial leadership attributes are contextual. The paper highlighted several attributes of entrepreneurial leaders these include vision, effective communication, risk taking, and creativity.
42.	Harrison et al. (2016b)	Empirical	This study explored the challenges and attributes of entrepreneurial leaders within retail pharmacy sector of Nigeria and proposed a skills-based model of entrepreneurial leaders. However, the study didn't discuss the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership skills development.
43.	Harrison et al. (2018)	Empirical	This paper explored entrepreneurial leadership skills in developing economies' context particularly focusing on the retail pharmacy in Nigeria. The paper proposed a skill-based model of entrepreneurial leadership skills underpinned by technical/ business skills, interpersonal skills, conceptual skills, and entrepreneurial skills. However, the results of this study are entirely contextual and limited to retail pharmacy industry and their generalisation to other sectors, require further research.
44.	Harrison et al. (2020)	Conceptual	This article theoretically discussed the concept of entrepreneurial leadership from the lens of entrepreneurship and leadership by drawing on attributes and skills of entrepreneurship, leadership, and entrepreneurial leadership. However, the authors call for more empirical and theoretical investigation about the skills and attributes of entrepreneurial leaders.
45.	He et al. (2017)		This article explored the overlapping characteristics of leadership and entrepreneurship. The findings suggest that

			vision, passion, integrity, and self-confidence are key attributes of entrepreneurial leaders. However, this article was limited to the characteristics of entrepreneurial leaders and didn't explore how these characteristics can be learned or developed.
46.	Horan (2007)	Conceptual	This article proposed an integrated leadership development program for developing entrepreneurial capabilities of entrepreneurial leaders. The author argued that an action based and integrated leadership development program play a vital role in developing the cross-cultural skills and diverse team management. The action learning method can develop the risk taking, innovation skills, and solve complex challenges of organisations. However, the paper is entirely theoretical and lacks an evidence-based entrepreneurial leadership skills development model.
47.	Hunter and Lean (2014)	Empirical	The article investigated the role of social capital on SME's competitiveness by using entrepreneurial leadership as an explanatory variable. The authors argue that entrepreneurial leaders in SMEs should develop specific personal and managerial skills to remain competitive in the changing business environment.
48.	Jawi and Izhar (2016)	Conceptual	This article explores how entrepreneurial leadership capabilities enhance the transformation of libraries. Drawing on leader-member exchange theory, the article proposes that strategic, communicative, personal, motivational, and moderator factors are essential in driving innovations in libraries. However, this article was entirely theoretical, and the assertions lack empirical justification.
49.	Jones and Crompton (2009)	Empirical	This article explored entrepreneurial leadership from a shared leadership perspective and proposed the concept of enterprise logic based on structure, communication and delegation, people management, and vision, authenticity, and enactment skills of managers, which are essential for effective organisational performance.
50.	Karol (2015)	Conceptual	This article explored the challenges and skills needed for corporate entrepreneurial leaders. The findings revealed that to achieve aligned vision, establishing the trust and commitment, and the skills such as perspective taking, influence and agility are essential for team entrepreneurial leaders.

51.	Kassai (2022)	Review	This paper reviewed entrepreneurial competencies and proposed a model of entrepreneurial leadership style for entrepreneurs. The paper adopted a case survey method in conducting the review and identified five competencies of entrepreneurial leaders – i.e., imagination (opportunity recognition and planning, execution, social, organisational, and personal). However, the paper mainly focuses entrepreneurial competencies rooted from the mainstream leadership and entrepreneurship literature and disregarded entrepreneurial leadership competencies.
52.	Kempster and Cope (2010)	Conceptual	This article focused on entrepreneurial leadership learning as a social process. However, the paper didn't discuss the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership competencies that can be learnt through a social process.
53.	Koryak et al. (2015)	Review	This article investigated entrepreneurial leadership capabilities and their influence on the growth of SMEs.
54.	Kuratko (2007)	Conceptual	This article discussed entrepreneurial leadership from a global context and discussed various dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership that affect the organisations of 21 st century. The authors proposed the need of entrepreneurial thinking in contemporary organisations to exploit business opportunities and achieve sustainable competitive advantage through adopting various entrepreneurial capabilities such as risk-taking, innovativeness and proactiveness.
55.	Kuratko and Hornsby (1999)	Conceptual	The purpose this paper was to explore entrepreneurial leadership in context of corporations. The author explored various dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership to define corporate entrepreneurship strategies that include developing vision, innovation, venture team, formation of entrepreneurial environment. However, the assertions are highly contextual and lack empirical justification.
56.	Lajin and Zainol (2015)	Empirical	This paper examined the role of entrepreneurial leadership dimensions on academic achievement of students. The findings suggest that the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership such as proactiveness, risk-taking, and competitive aggressiveness have a positive influence on academic grades of students.
57.	Leffel et al. (2016)	Empirical	The purpose of this article was to explore how entrepreneurial leadership helps in effective

			team management in entrepreneurial venture, particularly focusing on conflict management. The authors propose that four skillsets: assessment, intervention, resolution, and maintenance are essential for the long-term success of the firm.
58.	Leitch et al. (2009)	Empirical	This paper explored how entrepreneurial leadership can be developed in small and medium sized enterprises by proposing an action-based leadership development programme. The authors propose that action-based leadership learning programmes enable entrepreneurial leaders to acquire entrepreneurial knowledge, develop their skills and awareness to achieve organisational mission and vision.
59.	Leitch et al. (2013)	Conceptual	This article explored entrepreneurial leadership skills from the lens of human, social, and institutional capital.
60.	Lippitt (1987)	Conceptual	This article explored the characteristics and skills of entrepreneurial leaders such as risk taking, divergent thinking, sharp focus, personal responsibility, economic orientation, and learning from experience. Furthermore, the author argues that self-awareness, diagnostic skills, learning and getting advice and goal setting are important skills of entrepreneurial leaders. However, the study discussed these characteristics and skills from a conceptual perspective and the assertions lack empirical justification.
61.	Lubis (2017)		This study explored the importance of entrepreneurial leadership and law for the formation of entrepreneurial university within the context of Indonesia. Drawing on management competency inventory theory, the author proposed various attributes of entrepreneurial leaders such as problem solving, communications, planning ability, decision making, ethical competency ability, project management negotiating, management information systems, information technology, and the use internet and the attributes of law graduates such as the understanding of corporation, contracts, taxes, securities, patents, real estate, and bankruptcy are critical for entrepreneurial learning.
62.	Mars and Torres (2018)	Empirical	The purpose of this article was to examine the impact of entrepreneurial leadership course on student's proclivities towards leading change and their abilities. However, the study focused on the conceived abilities, knowledge and skills

			of entrepreneurial leader, the actual competencies of entrepreneurial leaders were beyond the scope of this study.
63.	Mawoli (2016)	Conceptual	This study theoretically discussed the challenges and prospects of entrepreneurial leaders in context of Nigeria. The authors argue that entrepreneurial leadership challenges can be cope with entrepreneurial leadership programs. Entrepreneurial leadership programs play an integral role in developing the skills and attitudes of entrepreneurial leaders, driving innovation and enhance government revenue generation capacities. However, the assertions are entirely theoretical and lack empirical justification.
64.	Mehmood et al. (2020)		This paper investigates the impact of entrepreneurial leadership on employee creativity through mediating role of psychological empowerment and psychological safety. The findings reveal that entrepreneurial leadership play a vital role in enhancing creativity thus facilitates opportunity identification and exploitation. The authors propose that communication and creative skills are important for entrepreneurial leaders to develop the confidence and competency level of employees.
65.	Mezher and Hamed (2020)	Empirical	This paper explored the impact of entrepreneurial leadership factors on developing capabilities of company managers. The author argues that entrepreneurial leadership factors such as strategic, personal, communication and motivational factors are essential for the success of companies. These factors enable the company leaders to clearly identify future events, motivate their employees, and take effective decisions.
66.	Ngigi et al. (2018)	Empirical	This study investigated entrepreneurial leadership competencies of mid-level CEOs in the context of Kenya and highlighted two categories of competencies, namely, relational competencies and task-oriented competencies. However, the study failed to discuss entrepreneurial leadership competencies development.
67.	Okudan and Rzasz (2006)	Empirical	This article explored entrepreneurial leadership courses in developing entrepreneurial leadership behaviour and suggests that entrepreneurial leadership courses are essential in developing motivation, innovation, communication skills, teamwork and writing

			business plans capabilities of entrepreneurial leaders.
68.	Olutade et al. (2015)	Empirical	<p>The purpose of this paper was to investigate the role of entrepreneurial leadership skills and employee interaction on employee performance and business productivity. This article analysed the mediating role of motivation on leader member exchange (LMX) theory and job satisfaction in a team perspective. The findings show a positive relationship between leader-follower's motivation, LMX and job satisfaction.</p> <p>The authors argue that motivation and talent retention skills of entrepreneurial leaders are necessary for the organisational competitiveness.</p>
69.	Omeihe et al. (2020)	Empirical	<p>This paper examined the role of entrepreneurial leadership, its attributes, and skills in context of Nigerian fashion SMEs. The paper identified various attributes such as hard work, long-term orientation, passion, length of service, creativity, innovation, vision; and skills such as technical, conceptual, interpersonal, entrepreneurial, and expectation management skills. However, the results are contextual to specific industry thus may not be generalised to other contexts.</p>
70.	Ordu (2020)	Empirical	<p>The purpose of this paper was to explore the role of entrepreneurial leadership on identifying and exploring business opportunities in context of start-ups. The authors proposed that a democratic style of entrepreneurial leadership is essential in gaining employee engagement and increased commitment. Therefore, the leaders in start-up should participate in trainings, conferences, seminars, and work projects to enhance their entrepreneurial competencies. However, the paper lacks a wider discussion on entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development.</p>
71.	Pihie and Bagheri (2013)	Empirical	<p>This article investigated school leaders' entrepreneurial leadership practices on school innovativeness from a teacher's perspective. The findings suggest that professional leadership development programmes in schools are critical for school innovativeness. However, the study presented a single dimension of entrepreneurial leaders from a teachers' perspective.</p>
72.	Prieto (2010)	Conceptual	<p>This study examined entrepreneurial leadership from the lens of proactive personality, organizational identification, and political skill.</p>

			The authors argue that entrepreneurial leaders need to develop effective bargaining and team building skills to meet the challenges of changing times.
73.	Putsom et al. (2019a)	Empirical	This article explored the effect of entrepreneurial leadership dimensions on value creation in automotive parts manufacturing in Thailand. The study proposed four competencies: personal competencies, managerial competencies, proactive competencies, and technological competencies.
74.	Putsom et al. (2019b)	Empirical	This study aimed to develop a measurement scale of entrepreneurial leadership competencies including personal competencies, managerial competencies, proactive competencies, and technological competencies.
75.	Quaye and Mensah (2019)	Empirical	This study examined the impact of entrepreneurial leadership attributes on the performance of SMEs owned by female entrepreneurial leaders in context of Ghana. The findings suggest that entrepreneurial leadership attributes such as innovation, proactiveness, and vision have significant influence on the firm's performance. The authors further argue that female entrepreneurial leaders need to develop self-motivation, knowledge, and skills by undertaking entrepreneurial training and education to enhance their creativity and exploit business opportunities.
76.	Ranjan (2018)	Review	This paper provides a review of entrepreneurial leadership literature. The results of the review highlight various dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership such as strategic factors, communicative factors, personal factors, motivational factors, and leadership behaviours. Human capital, social capital, entrepreneurial capital, social capital, entrepreneurial mindset, ambidexterity, and uncertainty absorbing, challenge framing, clearing path, commitment building and limit specification. The traits such as performance oriented, ambitious, informed, extra insight visionary foresight, confidence builder, diplomatic, effective bargaining, convincing, encourage, inspirational, enthusiastic, team builder, improvement-oriented, integrator, intellectual stimulation, and positive attitude, were also identified from the review.
77.	Renko et al. (2015)	Empirical	The purpose of this article was to develop the construct of entrepreneurial leadership. The study focused on how entrepreneurial leaders and their competencies can influence and direct

			group members in identifying and exploiting business opportunities.
78.	Roomi and Harrison (2011)	Review	This article focused on entrepreneurial leadership development by reviewing past literature. The authors argue that entrepreneurial leadership capabilities can be developed through socially interactive, critically reflective, and appropriate teaching materials.
79.	Rusliati et al. (2020)	Empirical	This study focused on how entrepreneurial leadership helps in micro-enterprise development within the context of Indonesia. The authors argue that entrepreneurial leaders by developing their business management, opportunity seeking, confidence building, communication, social and technical skills can facilitate development of micro enterprises. However, the study fails to highlight how these competencies can be developed within the context of micro enterprises.
80.	Siddiqui (2007)	Empirical	The purpose of this paper was to explore the role of entrepreneurship programmes in developing entrepreneurial leadership traits. The findings posit that entrepreneurial leadership traits and skills can be developed through an experience-based learning approach. An experienced based approach enables entrepreneurial leaders to take informed business decisions. However, the article was only confined to experience based entrepreneurial learning, other modes of entrepreneurial learning didn't receive considerable attention.
81.	Siilasmaa (2019)	Conceptual	This paper theoretically discussed how contemporary leadership theories such as entrepreneurial leadership enable the corporate leaders in planning and leading in unpredictable business environment. The author propose that entrepreneurial leaders should possess the capabilities of thinking and setting alternatives, building trust, encouraging accountability, leading by example, and adopting creative ways work. However, the paper lacks discussion on the development of these capabilities.
82.	Smith et al. (2017)	Empirical	This article explored the role of educator in fostering entrepreneurial leadership learning focusing on actor network theory. The authors argue that entrepreneurial leadership learning is a dynamic process that takes place in peer networks.

83.	Strubler and Redekop (2010)	Empirical	This article explores entrepreneurial leadership in context of human resource by identifying the entrepreneurial characteristics and capabilities of Dwight Carlson. The authors propose that the capacity of innovation, hard work, a sense of fun, and team spirit of entrepreneurial leaders determine the motivation and productivity of team members in wider organisational contexts.
84.	Sundararajan et al. (2012)	Empirical	The article explored entrepreneurial leadership by linking it to spiritual leadership. The study concludes that for effective and creative entrepreneurial thinking, entrepreneurial leaders need to adopt a non-thinking and silent meditative approach in new ventures. This study suggests that a reflective thinking course should be designed to develop entrepreneurial leadership skills.
85.	Swiercz and Lydon (2002)	Empirical	This article explored the competencies required for successful entrepreneurial leaders. The authors proposed that personal and functional competencies of entrepreneurial leaders are critical for their success. However, the article didn't discuss how entrepreneurial leaders can develop these competencies.
86.	Tian and Smith (2014)	Conceptual	This study explored entrepreneurial leadership in context of social enterprises and identified challenges and skills of social entrepreneurial leaders. The study concluded that acceptance, differentiation, and integration are key skills of social entrepreneurial leaders.
87.	Van Assche (2005)	Empirical	This article examined entrepreneurial leaders from international contexts and the author argues that entrepreneurial leadership is an important factor in the creation of economic and monetary union. The author maintained that entrepreneurial leaders require the capabilities such as setting agendas, popularising issues, devising adaptive innovation policies, dealing, and lining up support from stakeholders.
88.	Wahab and Tyasari (2020)	Empirical	This article focused on the issues and challenges of university leaders in the context of Pakistan. The authors proposed that an entrepreneurial style of leadership is needed in HEIs in Pakistan to overcome the challenges of HEIs. The paper suggests that managerial competency and learning orientation are essential for HEIs entrepreneurial leaders' performance.
89.	Wibowo and Saptono (2018)	Empirical	The purpose of this article was to investigate the impact of entrepreneurial leadership on creativity and innovation of elementary school teachers. The findings suggest that entrepreneurial leadership has a strong positive

			influence on teacher's creativity and innovation. The authors argue that elementary school's principals need to develop their entrepreneurial competencies by engaging in entrepreneurial courses, training, and workshops. However, the paper didn't highlight the specific competencies needed for school principals to drive innovation and creativity in the organisation.
90.	Yang (2018)	Empirical	This study explored the role of entrepreneurship education in developing entrepreneurial leadership among Korean university students drawing on three basic factors of entrepreneurial leadership namely, risk-taking, proactiveness, and innovativeness. The author argues that entrepreneurship education underpinned on knowledge, skills, and mental cognition play a critical role in the development of university entrepreneurial leaders.

2.5.2.3 RQ1: what is the impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies on organisations?

The research on entrepreneurial leadership is still growing and lacks definitional and theoretical clarity (Gupta et al., 2004; Harrison et al., 2018; Leitch et al., 2013). Despite the theoretical challenges, the concept has gained immense scholarship in different contexts in recent times. Particularly, research on entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development has gained much prominence recently. The findings of this review identified 54 papers that answered fully or partially review question 1. The findings of these papers are presented under the following broad themes:

2.5.2.3.1 *Entrepreneurial leadership competencies in dealing with business challenges*

A growing body of literature highlights entrepreneurial leadership as a distinct type of leadership and recognise the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders as essential to cope with emerging business challenges, create and sustain new ventures, and identify and exploit business opportunities (Agbim, 2013; Coglisier and Brigham, 2004; Harrison et al., 2016a; Koryak et al., 2015; Tian and Smith, 2014; Wahab and Tyasari, 2020). Even though scholars

have placed a significant emphasis on the effects of entrepreneurial leadership competencies on organisations, the existing literature does not succinctly describe the facets of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development.

2.5.2.3.2 Entrepreneurial leadership competencies and entrepreneurial leadership development

The role of entrepreneurial leadership competencies in developing entrepreneurial leadership has received considerable attention within the existing literature. Several authors have highlighted the influential role of entrepreneurial leadership capabilities such as business management, opportunity seeking, confidence building, and communication, social and technical skills, in entrepreneurial leadership learning and development (Bagheri et al., 2013a; Bagheri and Pihie, 2010; Bagheri and Pihie, 2009; Gupta et al., 2004); sensing and exploiting business opportunities in micro, small, and large organisations (Leitch et al., 2009; Leitch et al., 2013); and micro enterprise development (Rusliati et al., 2020; Leitch et al., 2013). The personal, functional, and mental cognition competencies of entrepreneurial leaders are pointed out as vital for entrepreneurial leadership development and performing critical roles in entrepreneurial ventures (Bagheri et al., 2013a; Gupta et al., 2004; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002).

Although these scholars stressed entrepreneurial leadership competencies as essential for entrepreneurial leadership development in various organisational settings, their assertions largely provide a descriptive and generic analysis of entrepreneurial leadership skills and lack empirical validation. Arguably, the dimensions of specific entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development in a dynamic organisational context require further exploration.

2.5.2.3.3 Innovation and creativity

A growing body of entrepreneurial leadership literature has focused on how entrepreneurial leadership competencies can enhance innovation and workplace creativity (Akbari et al., 2020; Pihie and Bagheri, 2014; Bagheri, 2017; Bagheri and Akbari, 2018; Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz and Pashiardis, 2020; Chen, 2007; Kuratko, 2007). For Pihie and Bagheri (2013), entrepreneurial leadership capabilities of principals enhance school innovativeness. Entrepreneurial leadership competencies such as managerial, task handling, personnel selection and development, and marketing skills are essential for enhancing accountability and creativity in schools (Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz and Pashiardis, 2020); developing employees' innovative work behaviours (Akbari et al., 2020); and fostering nurses' innovation behaviours (Bagheri, 2017). However, these studies largely explored the impacts of EL on innovation and creativity by adopting a quantitative approach and gave little prominence to the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership, creativity, and managing innovation in various organisational contexts from a qualitative perspective.

2.5.2.3.4 Performance

According to the findings of the review, entrepreneurial leadership competencies such as communication and delegation, people management, vision, authenticity, and enactment skills are crucial for effective organisational performance (D'Intino et al., 2008; Jones and Crompton, 2009; Koryak et al., 2015; Ngigi et al., 2018; Olutade et al., 2015; Quaye and Mensah, 2019; Tian and Smith, 2014). Risk-taking, recognising and exploiting opportunities, and communicating vision are determining factors for improving retail pharmacy performance (Harrison et al., 2018; Harrison et al., 2016b) and enhancing effective leadership development and personal and business outcomes (Leitch et al., 2009; Leitch et al., 2013; Olutade et al., 2015). Although the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders are claimed to be effective for

enhancing organisational performance, there is more confusion in relation to specific entrepreneurial leadership competencies that have enduring effects on individuals and organisations. There are still many unanswered questions regarding how EL abilities affect the behaviour and performance of entrepreneurial leaders (Bagheri et al., 2013a) at an individual and team level.

2.5.2.3.5 Achieving mission and vision

According to Gupta et al. (2004), entrepreneurial leaders must have the essential competencies to conceive, mobilise, and persuade a group of people to realise the organisation's goal. The competencies acquired from an action-based leadership learning programme enable entrepreneurial leaders to gain entrepreneurial knowledge and develop their skills and awareness to achieve the organisation's mission and vision (Leitch et al., 2009).

2.5.2.3.6 Effective decision making and value creation

The extant literature highlights that entrepreneurial leader, by learning specific entrepreneurial competencies, are better able to sense business opportunities and take informed business decisions as compared to traditional leaders (Bagheri et al., 2013a; Siddiqui, 2007). Consequently, these competencies enable entrepreneurial leaders to obtain sustainable success and create value for their businesses. Entrepreneurial leaders' personal, managerial, proactive, and technological competencies are vital for value creation (Putsom et al., 2019a). Similarly, these skills are important for students to identify opportunities and enhance social, environmental, and economic value creation (Carey et al., 2021).

Despite their prominent contribution to the literature, the above studies are not free from limitations. Most studies examined entrepreneurial leadership from a leader's perspective and

lacked followers' perceptions (Harrison et al., 2018). Some of the studies explored the competencies from conceptual standpoints (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Bagheri et al., 2013a; Guo, 2009); therefore, their assertions need empirical validity. While some studies did not specifically focus on the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders, they called for the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies for an effective business outcome. Most studies combine the attributes, characteristics, and skills of entrepreneurial leadership; as a result, the precise abilities, traits, and characteristics of entrepreneurial leaders are still undefined and lack a clear picture. Moreover, the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development at the team level have received little scholarly attention. The details of studies that focused on the impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies are presented in Table 7.

Table 7 Studies that focused on the impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies

Impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies	Author(s)
Employees innovative work behaviour	Akbari et al. (2019)
Academic and non-academic achievement	Ariyani (2021), Dardiri et al. (2018), Lajin and Zainol (2015)
Effective entrepreneurial climate and strategies for innovation development and innovative solution to healthcare organisation	Bagheri (2017), Guo (2009)
Leading company in growth stage	Freeman and Siegfried Jr (2015)
Scenario and cast enactment	Gupta et al. (2004)
Firm performance and growth	Koryak et al. (2015)
Employee performance and business productivity	Olutade et al. (2015)
Communication priorities on positive operational results	Leffel et al. (2012)
Business value creation	Putsom et al. (2019)
Effective decision making	Siddiqui (2007)
School effectiveness	Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz and Pashiardis (2020)
Growth orientation in high tech firms	Swiercz and Lydon (2002)
Development of university entrepreneurial leaders	Yang (2018)
Identify and exploit business opportunities	Wahab and Tyasari (2020)
Improving creativity and innovation	Chen (2007), Surie and Ashley (2008), Pihie and Bagheri (2013)
Enhancing business performance	D'intino et al. (2008), Quaye and Mensah (2019)

Organisational effectiveness	Jones and Crompton (2009), Mezher and Hamed (2020)
Minimising start-up failure	Sundararajan et al. (2012); Freeman and Siegfried (2015)
Coping with business and organisational challenges	Abbas (2014), Ansari et al. (2014), Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz and Pashiardis (2020), Carey et al. (2021), Freeman and Siegfried (2015), Wahab and Tyasari (2020), Prieto (2010)
Driving innovation in libraries	Jawi and Izhar (2016)
Organisational structure development, income generation, information, and technology solution development	Carpenter (2012)
Sustained entrepreneurial success of nascent entrepreneurs	Agbim (2013)
Driving innovation at DIY labs	Ahmed and Harrison (2021)
Research advancement and knowledge creation	Hansson and Mønsted (2008)
Achieving organisational mission and vision	Leitch et al. (2009)
Employee performance and business productivity	Olutade et al. (2015)
Business value creation	Putsom et al. (2019b)
Identifying and exploiting business opportunities	Renko et al. (2015), Mehmood et al. (2020), Ordu (2020)
Micro enterprise development	Rusliati et al. (2020)
Employee motivation and productivity	Strubler and Redekop (2010), Campos (2021)
Innovation and revenue generation in public organisation	Mawoli (2016)
Predicting and planning future events	Siilasmaa (2019)
Firm innovative capability	Chen (2007)

2.5.2.4 RQ2: What are the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders?

Entrepreneurial leadership competencies have been explored in 59 papers in the review, which represents 65% of the overall studies. These competencies have been explored in different samples and contexts, including students, SMEs' owners, CEOs, healthcare entrepreneurial leaders, managers, pharmacists, fashion entrepreneurs, and school principals (Agbim, 2013; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Bagheri, 2017; Bagheri and Akbari, 2018; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Bagheri et al., 2013a, Bagheri et al., 2013b; Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Harrison et al., 2016a; Koryak et al., 2015; Tian and Smith, 2014; Wahab and Tyasari, 2020). The first study that explored the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders was Lippitt's (1987), who proposed self-

awareness, diagnostic skills, learning and getting advice, and goal setting as crucial skills for entrepreneurial leaders.

Okudan and Rzasa (2006) stressed that communication, teamwork, and business plan writing skills are important for entrepreneurial leaders to lead organisations successfully. Abbas and Tatfi (2010) maintained that developing trust among employees, communication, self-improvement, technical skills, a sense of responsibility, and decision-making skills are critical for entrepreneurial leaders. Darling and Beebe (2007) argued that communication skills are critically important for entrepreneurial leaders. Jones and Crompton (2019) described entrepreneurial leadership as a shared leadership perspective and proposed the concept of enterprise logic. They argue that structure, communication, delegation, people management, vision, authenticity, and enactment skills are essential capabilities for effective organisational performance.

Moreover, business management, opportunity seeking, confidence building, communication, and social and technical skills are recognised as crucial for the development of microenterprises (Rusliati et al., 2020). Abbas (2014) argued that entrepreneurial leaders need to be academically prepared and gain entrepreneurial and managerial skills to cope with the challenges of turbulent times. Agbim (2013) emphasise technological, management, and entrepreneurial skills of entrepreneurial leaders. In addition, Harrison et al. (2018) proposed a skill-based model of entrepreneurial leadership in the context of retail pharmacy and identified technical and business skills, interpersonal skills, conceptual skills, and entrepreneurial skills as essential for retail pharmacy entrepreneurial leaders.

On the other hand, some scholars emphasised the personal and functional competencies of entrepreneurial leaders for developing and sustaining new ventures (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Gupta et al., 2004; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002); driving innovation in DIY labs (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021). For other scholars, risk-taking, innovativeness, and

proactiveness are critical for students' entrepreneurial success and effective task accomplishment (Ansari et al., 2014; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Gupta et al., 2004; Yang, 2018).

Nonetheless, there are still considerable limitations in existing studies on entrepreneurial leadership competencies. As highlighted by Harrison et al. (2018), most of the studies explored the competencies of EL from a leaders' perspective. How followers perceive entrepreneurial leadership competencies and how these competencies can be learned and developed among followers has gained little empirical and theoretical prominence. Existing studies widely stressed the competencies essential for entrepreneurial leaders and lack discussion about how these competencies are learned and developed. Most of these studies focused on students as entrepreneurial leaders, and the discussion about experienced entrepreneurial leaders has received little attention. Entrepreneurial leadership competencies from a group perspective remain understudied yet. The existing literature lacks a comprehensive and empirically validated model of specific entrepreneurial leadership competencies that covers a broader context. In this regard, Harrison et al. (2018), although they proposed a skills-based model for entrepreneurial leaders in the context of developing economies, their assertions are highly contextual to the retail pharmacy sector and could not be generalised to other sectors. Studies exploring the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders are shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Studies focused on the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders

Entrepreneurial leadership competencies	Author(s)
Entrepreneurial and managerial	Abbas (2014)
Building trust, communication, self-improvement, sense of responsibility, technical and decision-making skills	Abbas and Tatfi (2010)
Strategic, communicative, personal, motivational, and moderator skills	Jawi and Izhar (2016)
Personal, functional, interpersonal, technological, ethical, and environmental competencies	Ahmed and Harrison (2021)
Scenario enactment and cast enactment	Bagheri and Pihie (2011a)
Self-awareness, identity realisation, and self-efficacy capabilities	Bagheri and Pihie (2011b)
Managerial, task handling, personnel selection and development and marketing skills	Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz and Pashiardis (2020)

Systems-thinking, anticipatory, normative, strategic, and interpersonal competencies	Carey et al. (2021)
Creating partnership, inspiring, and sharing vision, interpreting human behaviour, risk taking and seeking opportunities	Carpenter (2012)
Envisioning future, strategic anticipation skills	D'Intino et al. (2008)
Communication skills	Darling and Beebe (2007)
Charisma, capability of linking external contacts, supporting, and negotiating creativity, and self-confidence.	Hansson and Mønsted (2008)
Imagination (opportunity recognition and planning, execution, social, organisational, personal)	Kassai (2022)
Strategic thinking, coaching and self-evaluation	Freeman and Siegfried (2015)
Healthcare system and environment competencies, organisational competencies, interpersonal competencies	Guo (2009)
Scenario enactment and cast enactment	Gupta et al. (2004)
Communication strategies	Halim and Razak (2014)
Risk-taking and opportunity recognition and exploitation.	Harrison et al. (2016a)
Vision, effective communication, risk taking, and creativity	Harrison et al. (2016b)
Technical/ business skills, interpersonal skills, conceptual skills, and entrepreneurial skills.	Harrison et al. (2018)
Personal and managerial skills	Hunter and Lean (2014)
Structure, communication and delegation, people management, and vision, authenticity, and enactment skills of managers	Jones and Crompton (2009)
Aligned vision, establishing trust and commitment, perspective taking, influence and agility	Karol (2015)
assessment, intervention, resolution, and maintenance	Leffel et al. (2016)
Risk taking, divergent thinking, sharp focus, personal responsibility, economic orientation, and learning from experience, self-awareness, diagnostic skills, learning and getting advice and goal setting	Lippitt (1987)
Relational competencies and task-oriented	Ngigi et al. (2018)
Motivation, innovation, communication skills, teamwork and writing business plans	Okudan and Rzasa (2006)
Motivation and talent retention	Olutade et al. (2015)
Personal competencies, managerial competencies, proactive competencies, and technological competencies.	Putsom et al. (2019a), Putsom et al. (2019b)
Business management, opportunity seeking, confidence building, communication, social and technical skills	Rusliati et al. (2020)
Innovation, hard work, sense of fun, and team spirit	Strubler and Redekop (2010)
Personal and functional	Swiercz and Lydon (2002)
Acceptance, differentiation, integration skills	Tian and Smith (2014)
Setting agendas, popularising issues, devising adaptive innovation policies, dealing and support	Van Assche (2005)
Managerial competency and learning orientation	Wahab and Tyasari (2020)
Risk-taking, proactiveness, and innovativeness	Yang (2018)
Communication and creative	Mehmood et al (2020)

Vision, passion, integrity, and self-confidence	He et al. (2017)
Employability, communication, innovation, planning, and networking skills	Bodolica et al. (2021)
Cognitive ambidexterity, commitment to social, environmental, and economic value creation, and self-awareness	Greenberg et al. (2013)
Optimization, communication, motivation, monitoring, controlling, role model, and empowerment.	Ariyani (2021)
Technical, conceptual, interpersonal, social, and emotional intelligence	Campos (2021)
Effective bargaining and team building skills	Prieto (2010)
Strategic factors, communicative factors, personal factors, motivational factors, and leadership behaviours. Performance oriented, ambitious, informed, extra insight visionary foresight, confidence builder, diplomatic, effective bargaining, convincing, encourage, inspirational, enthusiastic, team builder, improvement-oriented, integrator, intellectual stimulation, and positive attitude	Ranjan (2018)
Problem solving, communications, planning ability, decision making, ethical competency ability, project management, negotiation. management information systems, information technology and the Internet	Lubis (2017)
Articulating vision and mission, motivating and inspiring staff member	Dardiri et al. (2018)
opportunity identification self-efficacy, relationship self-efficacy, management self-efficacy, tolerance self-efficacy, learning self-efficacy	Bagheri et al. (2013b)
Innovation	Mawoli (2016)
Innovation, proactiveness, and vision	Quaye and Mensah (2019)
Strategic, personal, communication and motivational factors	Mezher and Hamed (2020)
Risk taking, innovation, and solving complex challenges	Horan (2007)
Proactiveness, risk-taking, and competitive aggressiveness	Lajin and Zainol (2015)
Thinking and setting alternatives, building trust, encouraging accountability, leading by example, and adopting creative ways of work.	Siilasmaa (2019)
Risk-taking, innovativeness, proactiveness	Chen (2007)
Personal and interpersonal leadership competencies, communication skills and creative skills	Bagheri and Pihie (2012)
Verbal and non-verbal communication skills; cultivate good personality traits; and motivational skills	Agbim (2013)
Growth capabilities and dynamic capabilities	Koryak et al. (2015)
Business and self-skills	Leitch et al. (2009)
Effectiveness skills and interpersonal communication skills in men	Edmond et al. (2017)

A further investigation into these competencies illuminates that the majority of the scholars reiterate communication skills as the most essential skill for entrepreneurial leaders, which has

been highlighted in 17 studies (Abbas and Tatfi, 2010; Agbim, 2013; Ariyani, 2021; Bagheri and Pihie, 2012; Bodolica et al., 2021; Darling and Beebe, 2007; Edmond et al., 2017; Halim and Razak, 2014; Harrison et al., 2016b; Jawi and Izhar, 2016; Jones and Crompton, 2009; Lubis, 2017). The details of the most frequently cited competencies are listed in Table 9.

Table 9 Most recurring competencies

Competencies	Authors
Networking and Team Building skills	Bodolica et al. (2021), Ranjan (2018), Prieto (2010), Okudan and Rzasa (2006), Edmond et al. (2017)
Interpersonal competence	Carey et al. (2021), Bagheri and Pihie (2012), Ahmed and Harrison (2021), Guo (2009), Harrison et al. (2018), Chen (2007), Omeihe et al. (2020)
Entrepreneurial skills	Abbas (2014), Harrison et al. (2018), Omeihe et al. (2020)
Managerial skills	Abbas (2014), Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz and Pashiardis (2020), Hunter and Lean (2014), Jones and Crompton (2009), Putsom et al. (2019a), Putsom et al. (2019b), Rusliati et al. (2020), Wahab and Tyasari (2020), Bagheri et al. (2013b)
Strategic orientation skills	Jawi and Izhar (2016), Carey et al. (2021), D'Intino et al. (2008), Freeman and Siegfried (2015), Mezher and Hamed (2020)
Personal competence	Jawi and Izhar (2016), Ahmed and Harrison (2021), Hunter and Lean (2014), Putsom et al. (2019a), Putsom et al. (2019b), Bagheri and Pihie (2012), Leitch et al. (2009); Kassai (2022)
Functional competence	Swiercz and Lydon (2002), Ahmed and Harrison (2021), Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz and Pashiardis (2020)
Motivational skills	Jawi and Izhar (2016), Okudan and Rzasa (2006), Ariyani (2021), Ranjan (2018), Mezher and Hamed (2020), Agbim (2013), Olutade et al. (2015), Dardiri et al. (2018)
Technological competence	Ahmed and Harrison (2021), Putsom et al. (2019a), Putsom et al. (2019b), Lubis (2017)
Technical competence	Omeihe et al. (2020), Harrison et al. (2018), Rusliati et al. (2020), Campos (2021), Abbas and Tatfi (2010)
Conceptual competence	Harrison et al. (2018), Campos (2021), Campos (2021), Omeihe (2020)
Communication skills	Abbas and Tatfi (2010), Jawi and Izhar (2016), Darling and Beebe (2007), Halim and Razak (2014), Harrison et al. (2016b), Jones and Crompton (2009), Okudan and Rzasa (2006), Rusliati et al. (2020), Mehmood et al. (2020), Bodolica et al. (2021), Ariyani (2021), Ranjan (2018), Lubis (2017), Mezher and Hamed (2020),

	Bagheri and Pihie (2012), Agbim (2013), Edmond et al. (2017)
Opportunity recognition and exploitation skills	Bagheri and Pihie (2011a), Carpenter (2012), Gupta et al. (2004), Harrison et al. (2016a)
Risk taking skills	Carpenter (2012), Harrison et al. (2016a), Harrison et al. (2016b), Lippitt (1987), Yang (2018), Horan (2007), Lajin and Zainol (2015), Chen 2007
Innovation and Creativity Skills	Harrison et al. (2016b), Okudan and Rzasa (2006), Strubler and Redekop (2010), Yang (2018), Bodolica et al. (2021), Mawoli (2016), Quaye and Mensah (2019), Horan (2007), Chen 2007, Bagheri and Pihie (2012), Omeihe et al. (2020)
Proactiveness skills	Putsom et al. (2019a), Putsom et al. (2019b), Yang (2018), Quaye and Mensah (2019), Lajin and Zainol (2015), Chen 2007
Articulating Vision	Bagheri and Pihie (2011a), Carpenter (2012), D'Intino et al. (2008), Gupta et al. (2004), Harrison et al. (2016b), Karol (2015), He et al. (2017), Ranjan (2018), Quaye and Mensah (2019), Omeihe et al. (2020)

2.5.2.5 RQ3: How do entrepreneurial leaders learn and develop the competencies?

Although there has been a growing scholarly focus on entrepreneurial leadership generally, the aspects of entrepreneurial leadership learning and development received little prominence (Harrison et al., 2016b; Roomi and Harrison, 2011). The findings of review show that 31 studies, or 35% of all studies, addressed review question 3. The majority of the studies underscore the importance of entrepreneurship-related programmes and curricula in developing entrepreneurial leadership competencies (Bagheri et al., 2013a; Ahmed and Ramzan, 2013; Bagheri, 2017; Bagheri and Akbari, 2018; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Freeman and Siegfried, 2015; Harrison et al., 2016; Koryak et al., 2015; Okudan and Rzasa, 2006; Tian and Smith, 2014; Wahab and Tyasari, 2020).

Conversely, some researchers believe that entrepreneurial leadership learning is a social and contextual phenomenon underpinned by a naturalistic learning process that occurs through

social interaction, observation, critical reflection, coaching, and training (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Leitch et al., 2013). Therefore, it is pertinent to induce entrepreneurial leaders towards a more practical learning approach in which they can participate in learning by doing, observing real-life scenarios, and performing various roles and tasks on entrepreneurial platforms (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Bagheri and Pihie, 2010; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Churchill et al., 2013; Freeman and Siegfried, 2015; Kempster and Cope, 2010; Leitch et al., 2013).

Although the theoretical and empirical prominence of these studies cannot be denied, they are limited on various grounds. For instance, most of the researchers emphasise traditional learning and teaching methods for developing the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders. The content and methods of traditional entrepreneurship pedagogy are still under development (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013) and may not fulfil the requirements of diverse and complex entrepreneurial learning processes (Kempster and Cope, 2010). As argued by Okudan and Rzasa (2006), traditional entrepreneurial leadership courses may be effective in developing basic entrepreneurial leadership; however, the specific competencies of entrepreneurial leadership can only be learned by adopting a comprehensive and combined learning approach. Moreover, the validity and impact of entrepreneurial leadership programmes in a cross-cultural setting are further researchable. The design, contents, and pedagogical method of entrepreneurial leadership courses and programmes need empirical validation (Okudan and Rzasa, 2006). Studies that focused on the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies are shown in Table 10.

Table 10 Entrepreneurial leadership competencies development

Entrepreneurial leadership competencies development	Author(s)
Entrepreneurship programs, training, and coaching	Akbari et al. (2020), Bagheri (2017), Aziz and Abiddin (2022)
Entrepreneurship programs	Bahgeri and Pihie (2009), Bagheri et al. (2013a), Bagheri and Pihie (2011b), Akbari et al. (2020)
Social interaction, observation, and reflection	Bagheri et al. (2010), Roomi et al. (2011)

Student related and program related roles in university club	Bagheri and Pihie (2012)
leadership training modules, internship, and developing cross-section networks	Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz and Pashiardis (2020)
Sustainability entrepreneurship programs	Carey et al. (2021)
Experiential learning, social interaction, and opportunity recognition learning	Churchill et al. (2013)
Social learning process	Kempster and Cope (2010)
Action-based leadership development program	Leitch et al. (2009)
Entrepreneurial leadership courses	Okudan and Rzasas (2006), Mars and Torres (2018)
Professional leadership development programs	Pihie and Bagheri (2013)
Experience-based learning approach	Siddiqi (2007)
Peer learning process	Smith et al. (2017)
Reflective thinking	Sundararajan and Henderson (2012)
Entrepreneurial courses, training, and workshops	Wibowo and Saptono (2018)
Extracurricular and entrepreneurship club	Bodolica et al. (2021)
Entrepreneurial learning	Almahdi (2019)
Integrated leadership development program	Horan (2007)
Trainings, conferences, seminars, and work project	Ordu (2020)
Professional development programmes	Pihie et al. (2014)
Experiential teaching methods	Kempster and Cope (2010)
Action-based leadership learning and development	Leitch et al. (2009)
Social capital-based leadership development process	Leitch et al., (2013)
Entrepreneurial leadership education programs	Bagheri and Harrison (2020)
Technical and traditional pedagogical tools, game-based simulation	Edmond et al. (2017)

2.5.3 Limitations

Although a systematic literature review is widely recognised as a legitimate process for conducting reviews and providing insightful understanding of subjects in business and management research (Harrison et al., 2016a; Tranfield et al., 2003), it has several limitations. Based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, review questions, and search duration, the inclusion of all records is not guaranteed. The search process was carried out only on published and peer-reviewed research articles; thus, conference papers, book chapters, and unpublished work that may potentially carry insightful theoretical depth, were not included in the review process. Yet, this study ensured optimal study inclusion by conducting backward, forward, citation, and

bibliography searches to identify further articles that addressed the review questions (Harrison et al., 2016a).

2.5.4 Summary and Recommendations for Future Research

The findings of the review highlight that entrepreneurial leadership competencies play a vital role in identifying and exploiting business opportunities and coping with the daunting challenges of turbulent times. These competencies enable entrepreneurial leaders to take calculated risks, enhance workplace creativity, and innovate to sustain their long-term competitiveness. The findings of the SLR suggest that EL competencies such as proactiveness, innovativeness, risk-taking propensity, articulating vision, motivation, communication, influence, teamwork, and creativity are important skills of entrepreneurial leaders and play a central role in the success of organisations.

While personal, interpersonal, functional, technological, human, and conceptual competencies are recognised as essential competencies of entrepreneurial leaders. The existing literature reveal that entrepreneurial leadership competencies can be learned and developed in various ways. Entrepreneurial leadership courses, project-based learning, co-taught multidisciplinary courses, entrepreneurship clubs, and co-curricular activities have been recommended as means of entrepreneurial leadership development. While some researchers believe that effective entrepreneurial leadership learning cannot be achieved through traditional learning strategies, they argue that entrepreneurial leadership is a social and contextual process underpinned by a naturalistic learning process. Therefore, learning by doing, experiential, reflective, and socially interactive learning strategies should be adopted to develop the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in different organisational settings.

The SLR's findings can guide several new directions for research in the field of entrepreneurial leadership. There is a paucity of studies in relation to specific EL competencies needed for the

success of large and small organisations. Entrepreneurial leadership competencies from a leader-follower perspective can be a potential research stream (Harrison et al., 2018). Entrepreneurial leadership competencies in a group context also lack theoretical and empirical discussion. Entrepreneurial leadership research lacks an integrated model of competencies from a leader-follower and group perspective. Furthermore, how entrepreneurial leadership competencies can be developed at individual and team level across organisations, lacks sufficient empirical underpinning. The extant literature widely focused on developing the competencies of student entrepreneurs through entrepreneurship education. Further research is required on how these competencies can be learned and developed among established entrepreneurial leaders. Furthermore, the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership courses, their content and designs, and their impact on the learning process of entrepreneurial leaders require further investigation.

The SLR offers significant insight into policy and practice. First, it draws a clear picture of entrepreneurial leadership competencies that can be used by various organisations, i.e., higher educational institutions, incubation centres, SMEs, and established organisations to identify and develop the skills to enhance entrepreneurial mindset in their organisations. Second, researchers, practitioners, and educators may use the evidence as a baseline in developing the content, curricula, and trainings for students and other professionals to enhance their entrepreneurial leadership learning. Third, the review offers valuable insights to educators in developing contemporary pedagogical methods in HEIs by combining various entrepreneurial learning strategies, i.e., classroom learning, social learning, and experiential learning. Finally, entrepreneurial leaders across organisations, by actively participating in entrepreneurship education, can identify and improve their entrepreneurial leadership competencies (Kempster and Cope, 2010).

3 Literature Review (Part Two) – Exploring the Entrepreneurial leadership Potentials of Pakistan

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a comprehensive review of the research on entrepreneurial leadership in Pakistan, addressing both the challenges encountered by entrepreneurial leaders and the avenues for entrepreneurial growth in the region. It delves into the contribution of business incubators to the development of entrepreneurial leadership and analyses the contextual factors that impact entrepreneurial leadership within the country. Moreover, it underscores the pivotal role of geographic location and context in shaping entrepreneurial leadership behaviour and the opportunities and activities available to entrepreneurs (Boettke and Coyne, 2009). Additionally, the chapter examines the constraints of university-business incubators, challenges of aspiring entrepreneurial leaders, and policy issues of BICs.

Pakistan, a developing country located in South Asia, has been gaining attention as a research context for entrepreneurship studies (Tariq, 2016) in general and entrepreneurial leadership (Soomro et al., 2019) in particular. Pakistan is the sixth most populated country in the world, with a population of 231 million people, accounting for 2.55% of the global population (Li et al., 2020). It is worth noting that Pakistan has a young population, with 60% of the population under the age of 30 (Li et al., 2020). According to a report by the World Bank (2022), Pakistan has a high potential for entrepreneurship growth due to its large and growing population, favourable demographic trends, and a rapidly expanding middle class. Despite its large population, Pakistan has a significant proportion of poor and unemployed individuals due to its low daily income, with 24.3% of the population earning less than USD 1.25 per day (Li et al., 2020). According to Pakistan Bureau of Statistics reports (2018), 54.4% of the labour force, which amounts to 3.7 million people, remained unemployed (Li et al., 2020). The above data

indicate the pressing need for job creation in the country (Shuhong and Zia-ud-Din, 2017). Business incubators play a crucial role in addressing unemployment, reducing poverty, and promoting economic growth (Wanyoko, 2013). However, like other developing countries, several challenges contribute to Pakistan's lack of entrepreneurial leadership growth, including insufficient infrastructure, a lack of access to capital, entrepreneurial knowledge, and limited market access (World Bank, 2022). The following section explores the geographic dynamics of the country and their impact on entrepreneurial growth.

3.1.1 Geographic landscape of Pakistan

Pakistan gained independence from the Britain on August 14, 1947. Its geographic and political significance stems from its borders (as shown in Figure 7) with China, Afghanistan, Iran, and India, with the southern border connecting to the Arabian Sea (CIA World Fact Book, 2023). Punjabis make up 44.7% of the population, followed by Pashtuns at 15.4%, Sindhis at 14.1%, Saraikis at 8.4%, Muhajirs at 7.6%, Balochs at 3.6%, and others at 6.3% (CIA World Factbook, 2020). These ethnic groups are separated into four provinces: Punjab, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Sindh, and Baluchistan, with each having its own regional language such as Punjabi, Pashtu,

Sindhi, and Balochi. The national language is Urdu, while English is the official language (CIA World Factbook, 2023).

Figure 7 Map of Pakistan Source: CIA World Factbook (2023)

Pakistan's geographical location at the crossroads of South Asia, Central Asia, and the Middle East provides potential avenues for cross border trade and stimulate entrepreneurial opportunities in the country. The country's enormous natural resources, which include fertile agricultural land, minerals, and hydropower potential, serve as the foundation for a wide range of entrepreneurial activities, including agribusiness and energy-related industries. Despite Pakistan's advantageous geographical characteristics, several hindrances impede entrepreneurial activities in the country. The lack of an efficient border management mechanism, limited access to sophisticated technologies, and a deficiency in entrepreneurial skills pose significant challenges to entrepreneurial growth. In response to these deficits, the government has expanded incubation programs aimed at training young talent's entrepreneurial skills to promote entrepreneurial knowledge and technological transfers to industries at national and international level. However, these programs have yet to yield the desired outcomes,

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indicating the need for further refinement and effectiveness in addressing the identified challenges.

3.1.2 Political landscape

The historical, social, and economic context of Pakistan have all played a role in shaping its diverse and multifaceted political landscape. The country is governed by a federal parliamentary democratic republic system, with a president serving as the ceremonial head of state and a prime minister serving as the head of government. Members of the National Assembly, Senate, and Provincial Assemblies vote to elect the president. The National Assembly appoints the Prime Minister (CIA World Factbook, 2023). Pakistan's bicameral legislative system comprised of the National Assembly and the Senate. The National Assembly, the lower house, has 342 members, while the Senate, the upper house, has 104 members. The National Assembly is elected for five years, and the Senate is elected for six years (CIA World Factbook, 2023). The judiciary in Pakistan comprises the Supreme Court, the Federal Sharia Court, and the Provincial High Courts. The Supreme Court is the final appellate court and can examine judiciary rulings (CIA World Factbook, 2023).

Pakistan has experienced significant political instability since its independence, including various military rules and several failed civilian governments. Corruption continues to be a major issue, impeding progress in a variety of areas. Furthermore, sectarian violence between Muslims of the Shia and Sunni sects, as well as insurgency in Baluchistan and religious extremism in the KPK, have undermined the country's political foundation (Atiq, 2014). These issues have contributed to the country's persistent political instability, which has resulted in economic instability and stagnant entrepreneurial growth.

3.1.3 Economic landscape

Pakistan's economy is primarily agricultural, with its main exports including house linen, rice, non-knit men's suits, non-retail pure cotton yarn, and heavy pure woven cotton (OEC, 2021). Among the most important imports are refined petroleum, crude petroleum, petroleum gas, palm oil, and scrap iron (OEC, 2021). Despite its growth potential, Pakistan's economy has been plagued by severe insecurity and instability in recent decades. The country's major flaws include a low tax-to-GDP ratio, a low savings rate, and minimal export growth with negligible value addition. Ineffective monetary policy and overvalued exchange rates have also widened the fiscal and current account deficits of the economy (ESP, 2021). Pakistan's unsustainable GDP growth of 5.97% in FY2022 has exacerbated macroeconomic imbalances, which have resulted in exchange rate depreciation, rising inflation, and expanded twin deficits, pushing the country to the brink of a financial disaster (ESP, 2021). According to the International Monetary Funds (IMF), Pakistan's GDP per capita in 2022 was 1.66 USD, with a 19.9 percent inflation rate and a 6.4 percent unemployment rate. Pakistan has had to seek multiple IMF bailouts over the years, the most recent of which were in 2019 and 2023. To address economic challenges, the government has implemented a variety of structural reforms and austerity measures, with a focus on promoting foreign investment and export-oriented growth to improve the country's trade balance. Despite these efforts, the country faces serious economic challenges. The country ranks 108th out of 190 countries in the World Bank's 'Ease of Doing Business' index for 2020, with a doing business score of 61.0 (DB, 2020). According to the report, Pakistan is placed 72nd in terms of starting a business, indicating that starting a business in the country is not sophisticated due to a lack of transparency in business registration processes.

3.2 Business Incubators in Pakistan

Business incubators are globally acknowledged for their vital role in economic development, fostering entrepreneurial knowledge and skills among aspiring entrepreneurs to stimulate innovation and entrepreneurship (Mahmood et al., 2015). Despite the existence of various types of incubators, each with distinct objectives, they typically share common functions that revolve around creating a conducive entrepreneurial environment, providing access to advanced technology, enhancing managerial capabilities, offering financial support, providing early-stage entrepreneurial assistance, reducing start-up costs, selecting suitable tenants, and providing support services for business planning and development (Jamil et al., 2016). However, regardless of their global recognition, the concept of business incubators remains relatively nascent in developing economies. These centres often struggle to meet international market standards due to limitations in technical and business expertise, infrastructure, and insufficient resources to achieve their objectives (Al-Mubarak and Busler, 2015). Pakistan is no exception to this trend, although the concept of business incubators has gained momentum in recent years within the country, little is known about current health and practices of BICs in the country (Hafeez et al., 2021).

The Government of Pakistan, through the Higher Education Commission of Pakistan, established various business incubators across public and private universities in 2005 with the aim of achieving economic development, job creation, and innovation and commercialization of research and development (Jamil et al., 2016). According to the Higher Education Commission (HEC) Incubation Policy (2020), university business incubators serve two key objectives: firstly, fostering an entrepreneurial spirit at universities and encouraging students and faculty to create new enterprises, and secondly, supporting the development of an

innovation ecosystem at universities. The key parameters of the BIC policy outlined by the HEC are shown in the Table 11 below.

Table 11 BIC Policy Parameters

BIC Policy Parameters HEC (2020)	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering an entrepreneurial spirit at universities and encouraging students and faculty to create new enterprises. • Supporting the development of an innovation ecosystem at universities
Services offered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BICs provide guidance, including lectures, mentoring, access to materials, and technical advice on launching start-ups, selecting business strategies, protecting their intellectual property, mobilizing resources, and generally converting innovative ideas into successful enterprises. • Facilitating access to laboratories, libraries, ICT-facilities, technical workforce, subject matter experts, and seed-funding opportunities. • Ensuring that the start-ups can generate opportunities for students to get internships or part-time jobs, as well as to apply their knowledge to real business problems as case studies. • Transferring the skills and lessons from the incubators to the universities, in order to enhance the competitiveness and societal relevance of universities, by enabling them to attract and retain entrepreneurial students as well as employees, and forging connections with industrial and governmental organizations.
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of Faculty Start-ups Encouraged / Opportunities Discussed • Number of Faculty Start-ups Created / Start-up Revenue Earned by Faculty Start-ups • Number of Jobs Created and Retained Over 2 years of Faculty Start-up Founding • Number of Student / Alumni Start-ups Created • Start-up Revenue Earned by Student / Alumni Start-ups • Number of Students Placed in University Start-ups • Funding Secured for Faculty / Student / Alumni Start-ups • BIC available facilities and human resource • Start-up Business Plan / Pitching Competition / Bootcamps • Number of License Agreements, NDA, MTAs, Consultancy Agreements, IP Rights signed by Start-ups • Venture Capitalist / Angel Investment / Seed Funding ensured by Start-ups • University Awareness Seminars / Entrepreneurial Awareness Campaigns / Investor Connect Events / Open Houses for
Tennent Selection Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through Business Plan Competition (top ten winners of the BPC will be incubated) • Through routine incubate selection procedure, i.e. advertising call for proposals (CFPs) conducting pitching event, conducting selection committee meeting, final selection, starting incubation process.
BIC Management Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIC Director / Manager (or similarly named as per HEIs own nomenclature) should ideally be a business graduate with 10 years plus managerial experience preferably in entrepreneurial / incubation management environment.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The BIC Manager in consultation with the VC and BIC Steering Committee may hire a dedicated Human Resource and support team for effective functioning of BIC which may include, Start-ups Support Executive(s), Admin & Finance Executive(s), and Office Assistant(s).
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Source: HEC incubation policy (2020)

3.2.1 Challenges of Business Incubators in Pakistan

The research of business incubators and their health is still in its infancy, with little empirical evidence available to inform the effectiveness and policy issues of various private and government business incubators (Hafeez et al., 2021). Mahmood et al. (2015) conducted a study on the challenges of BICs in Pakistan and offered key policy recommendations, including on issues of ownership and sponsorship, legal status, BICs and industry linkages, tenant selection, and management structure. According to the National SMEs Policy (2021), emerging start-ups in the country face significant barriers, including limited access to formal financial institutions, skilled labour, and technology, as well as challenges with product and service development, business development, inter-institutional linkages, and infrastructure constraints (SMEDA, 2021). The World Bank’s report titled “Doing Business in Pakistan 2020” presents a comprehensive overview of the business environment in Pakistan, along with recommendations for enhancing the ease of doing business. The report encompasses various aspects, including starting a business, obtaining construction permits, accessing electricity, registering property, paying taxes, engaging in cross-border trade, and enforcing contracts.

According to Li et al. (2020), the main challenges that BICs face in Pakistan are a lack of technical and educational skills, inadequate facilities and infrastructure, and inadequate support systems. Furthermore, the administrative aspects of starting a business, such as the cost, time, and number of procedures required, are unrelated to the rate at which new businesses are created. According to Hassan (2020), university incubators have a broader purpose beyond just supporting start-ups. They also play a vital role in promoting leadership and cultivating an

entrepreneurial culture. In addition to providing instruction to students, advancing research, and sharing knowledge and spin-offs, university incubators must focus on building the necessary infrastructure to foster innovation, entrepreneurial mindset, organisational development, and entrepreneurial leadership skills. Mahmood et al. (2015) argued that the primary challenges encountered by business incubators in Pakistan encompass limited private sector participation, inadequate management structure, ineffective government policies, insufficient funding, a lack of planning, and the absence of clear objectives. In developing economies, most entrepreneurial endeavours fail in their infancy or very early stages. Therefore, business incubation facilities are considered the most vital support for a start-up, which is especially important in developing nations that lack necessary administrative and financial infrastructure to support firms in their early phases (Hafeez et al., 2021).

3.2.2 Types of business incubator in Pakistan

The Higher Education Commission of Pakistan provides support to business incubators in both private and public universities. These incubators have the goal of creating job opportunities, fostering technological innovation, and contributing to regional economic development (Mahmood et al., 2015). The table 11 below contains a list of functional UBIs registered with Pakistan’s Higher Education Commission.

Table 12 Established business incubators in public and private HEIs

Name of Universities	
1	Abbottabad University of Science & Technology, Abbottabad
2	Abdul Wali Khan University, Mardan
3	Bahria University, Islamabad
4	Balochistan University of Information Technology, Engineering and Management Sciences, Quetta
5	COMSATS University, Islamabad
6	DOW University of Health Sciences, Karachi
7	Fatima Jinnah Women University, Rawalpindi
8	Government College University, Faisalabad
9	Government College University, Lahore
10	Institute of Management Science, Peshawar

11	Institute of Space Technology, Islamabad
12	International Islamic University, Islamabad
13	Karakoram University, Gilgit
14	Khyber Medical University, Peshawar
15	Kinnaird College for Women University, Lahore
16	Lahore College for Women University, Lahore
17	Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro
18	Muhammad Nawaz Shareef University of Agriculture, Multan
19	National Textile University, Faisalabad
20	National University of Modern Languages, Islamabad
21	National University of Sciences and Technology, Islamabad
22	NED University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi
23	Pakistan Institute of Engineering and Applied Sciences, Islamabad
24	Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad
25	Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam
26	Sukkur Institute of Business Administration, Sukkur
27	University of Agriculture, Faisalabad
28	University of Azad Jammu & Kashmir
29	University of Engineering and Technology, Lahore
30	University of Engineering and Technology, Peshawar
31	University of Gujrat, Gujrat
32	University of Haripur, Haripur
33	University of Malakand, Malakand
34	University of the Punjab, Lahore
35	University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore

Source: Higher Education Commission of Pakistan

Pakistan has a diverse range of business incubators that cater to different types of businesses and entrepreneurs. Some typical examples of business incubators in the country are:

3.2.2.1 Technology-based incubators

Technology-based incubators support start-ups and entrepreneurs in developing technology-based products and services. These incubators provide technology-based start-ups with resources such as funding, mentorship, and networking opportunities.

3.2.2.2 Sector-specific incubators

In Pakistan, some incubators are specialised in specific industries such as agriculture, energy, or health. These incubators provide assistance and resources to entrepreneurs working in these sectors, such as funding, mentorship, and networking opportunities.

3.2.2.3 Social enterprise incubators

Social enterprise incubators are specifically designed to support social enterprises and impact-driven start-ups. They provide resources and assistance to entrepreneurial leaders who are launching businesses with a focus on creating positive social impact.

3.2.2.4 Government-funded incubators

The Pakistani government has also established business incubators that offer funding, mentorship, and networking opportunities to entrepreneurs. Typically, these incubators are focused on specific industries or regions (Mahmood et al., 2015). One example of a government-funded business incubation initiative is Pakistan's National Incubation Centre (NIC). The NIC, established in 2017, is dedicated to supporting and nurturing the growth of new businesses. It provides resources to entrepreneurs, including office space, mentorship, networking opportunities, and funding. The NIC has centres located in major cities across Pakistan, such as Karachi, Lahore, Islamabad, Peshawar, and Quetta.

3.2.3 Enhancing Entrepreneurial Growth in Pakistan: The Role of Business Incubators

Pakistan, as a developing economy, has emerged as a popular research context in entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial leadership research due to its unique socio-cultural dynamics (Mahmood et al., 2015; Soomro et al., 2019; Wahab and Tyasari, 2020). However, the existing body of literature on business incubators and their impact on entrepreneurial leadership development lacks a holistic understanding from a contextual perspective. Numerous studies have highlighted the significance of entrepreneurial leadership knowledge and skills as key drivers of entrepreneurial success (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011; Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018). This importance is particularly pronounced for early-stage entrepreneurial leaders who are navigating the process of transforming their initial business idea into a viable start-up. Scholars have suggested that adopting an entrepreneurial leadership style is essential for success, as it empowers leaders to recognise and capitalise on business opportunities while effectively managing uncertainties through innovative, risk-taking, and proactive behaviours (Gupta et al., 2004; Renko et al., 2015).

Nonetheless, entrepreneurial leadership is widely acknowledged as a phenomenon shaped by various economic, social, cultural, and political factors in both developed and developing nations (Harrison et al., 2018). Despite its significance, research on entrepreneurial leadership within the context of developing economies is still in its early stages, leaving many aspects of this notion understudied. There is a lack of comprehensive knowledge regarding current practices, challenges, and the overall state of business incubators, as well as their impact on entrepreneurial outcomes in developing economies (Acs and Audretsch, 1988; Etemad, 2013; SMEDA, 2021). Moreover, cultural and social norms, government regulations, and the political landscape play crucial roles in shaping the behaviour of entrepreneurial leaders and the performance of emerging enterprises. Consequently, these unique socio-cultural dynamics

necessitate specific entrepreneurial leadership competencies to effectively navigate dynamic challenges and capitalize on emerging business opportunities (Chen, 2007; Gupta et al., 2004; Kuratko, 2007; Surie and Ashley, 2008).

Entrepreneurial leaders have specific personal and functional competencies that enable them to effectively lead entrepreneurial endeavours within their own businesses or within established organisations (Gupta et al., 2004; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Pro-activeness, innovativeness, and risk-taking are considered crucial characteristics of entrepreneurial leaders (Chen, 2007; Gupta et al., 2004; Kuratko, 2007; Surie and Ashley, 2008). In a recent study conducted by Harrison et al. (2018), four distinct categories of entrepreneurial leadership skills were identified within a developing economy context. These categories include technical/business skills, interpersonal skills, conceptual skills, and entrepreneurial skills. They argued that these skills play a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurial success among retail pharmacy entrepreneurial leaders in Nigeria. In contrast, exploring entrepreneurial leadership in Scotland, Clark (2020) identified a different set of crucial skills for the success of Scottish SME entrepreneurial leaders. These include entrepreneurial, interpersonal, technical, and conceptual skills. Despite the widespread recognition of entrepreneurial leadership competencies in various settings, the existing literature lacks a comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurial leadership challenges and the competencies required to address them within dynamic team environments. Specifically, prior studies have not examined entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and their development within the context of business incubators, which are recognized as crucial for creating job opportunities and fostering economic development (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Harrison et al., 2018; Ngigi et al., 2018).

Some recent studies have found positive relationships between entrepreneurial leadership and outcomes in the context of Pakistan, such as employee creativity (Mehmood et al., 2021) and employee innovative behaviour (Iqbal et al., 2022). Other studies have identified factors such

as strategic, personal, communicative, and motivational skills as crucial for entrepreneurial leaders in leading organisations in the context of Pakistan (Soomro et al., 2019). In addition, Wahab and Tyasari (2020) pointed out that entrepreneurial leadership plays a crucial role in mediating the relationship between managerial competency, learning orientation, and job performance in higher education institutions. Despite the importance of entrepreneurial leadership in Pakistan, as demonstrated by the preceding studies, our knowledge is limited about entrepreneurial leadership practices, challenges, and development in context of Pakistan (Hayat et al., 2019; Mehmood et al., 2021; Mehmood et al., 2022; Soomro et al., 2019; Wahab and Tyasari, 2020). There has been limited theoretical and empirical confirmation of how entrepreneurial leadership is practiced in business incubators at higher education institutions in the country. This research provides a comprehensive exploration of the subject matter, offering valuable insights into the phenomenon. Exploring the dynamics of the challenges faced by business incubators and aspiring entrepreneurial leaders thus significantly contributes to the literature while also providing empirical evidence to policymakers to improve the country's entrepreneurial ecosystem.

3.3 Summary

This chapter underscored the pivotal role of entrepreneurial leadership and business incubators in propelling economic development in Pakistan. It provides a comprehensive analysis of the country's geographic, political, and economic landscape, emphasising the importance of entrepreneurial leadership within this framework. Additionally, the chapter explores the challenges encountered by business incubators and aspiring entrepreneurial leaders, including issues such as funding constraints, insufficient infrastructure, and limited access to mentorship and networking opportunities. Furthermore, various types of business incubators are discussed, along with their associated policy concerns, offering a comprehensive overview of the landscape surrounding entrepreneurial endeavours in Pakistan.

4 Research Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This study aimed to explore the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders within a team context, with a focus on understanding how entrepreneurial leaders can acquire the competencies to successfully navigate obstacles in their entrepreneurial journey. The research objectives and questions were established to gain in-depth insights from participants about their experiences as entrepreneurial leaders and to learn about the competencies they require to overcome challenges.

This study addressed the following research questions to achieve the aim:

4.1.1 Research questions:

- What are the main challenges faced by nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-based business incubators in Pakistan?
- What entrepreneurial leadership competencies do entrepreneurial leaders require in order to overcome these challenges and become successful?
- How can these competencies be developed in a team setting within the context of university-based business incubators in Pakistan?
- How do contextual factors influence the development of competencies for nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-business incubators, and how can these factors be integrated into a team-based competency model?

This chapter is organised as follows: The first section explains the study's methodological approach. The following section provides an overview of various research paradigms and their relevance to business and management research, as well as the reasoning behind choosing an

interpretivist research philosophy for this study. The third section discusses the study's philosophical stance, and the fourth section justifies the use of a qualitative research design by citing previous studies that took a similar approach. The following section describes sampling techniques and data collection methods. This is followed by a discussion of the SLR's key findings, research evaluation, and ethical considerations. The final section concludes the chapter by providing an overview of methodological assumptions and their relevance to the current study. Figure 8 represents a graphical representation of the current study's methodological underpinnings.

Research Approach -----	Abductive
Research Paradigm -----	Interpretivist
Research Philosophy -----	Interpretivism
Research Method -----	Qualitative
Sampling -----	Purposive Sampling
Data Collection Method -----	Semi-structured interviews
Data Analysis -----	Thematic analysis

Figure 8 Methodological underpinning of study

4.2 Research Approach

A research approach involves the careful selection and implementation of research methods and techniques, following a systematic plan and methodology, to investigate research questions and objectives (Saunders et al., 2012). The research approaches include the deductive, inductive, and abductive approaches. The deductive approach, which is commonly used in scientific research, involves forming hypotheses based on a theoretical framework and measuring the relationship between variables using questionnaires (Saunders et al., 2012). On

the other hand, the inductive approach focuses on understanding subjective phenomena by observing a smaller population and developing a conceptual framework (Saunders et al., 2012).

The abductive approach, which is a combination of the deductive and inductive approaches, begins with the observation of a surprising fact and seeks the simplest and most likely explanation for that observation (Reichert, 2007). This approach alternates between theory and data and allows for the emergence of new patterns and the testing of plausible theories during the research process (Van Maanen et al., 2007). According to Harrison (2016), it is unrealistic to view research solely as deductive or inductive, as it ignores pre-existing ideas and theories and the emergence of new patterns during the research process.

The aim of this study was to uncover new insights into the concept of entrepreneurial leadership within a group setting, with a focus on business incubators in Pakistan. Given the interaction with entrepreneurial leaders in a group setting, it is anticipated that new ideas, thoughts, and patterns will emerge through subjective investigation of the phenomenon. An abductive approach, therefore, is useful to identify patterns and trends in the data that are not immediately obvious and can lead to the formation of new and unexpected hypotheses (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016). An abductive approach “allows for new discoveries to be made in a logically and methodologically ordered way” (Reichert, 2004, p. 160). Previous research on entrepreneurial leadership in both developing and developed economies, such as Harrison (2016) and Clark (2020), employed and supported the abductive approach in exploring entrepreneurial leadership skills. Therefore, the current study employed an abductive approach to examine the challenges faced by nascent entrepreneurial leaders and the competencies required for overcoming these challenges while working in a group.

This study employed various strategies to navigate the transition between the deductive and inductive phases, ensuring a balance integration of both methodologies. Firstly, the deductive

approach facilitated the establishment of theoretical frameworks by drawing upon existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and development, supplemented by a systematic literature review. Subsequently, the inductive phase provided an opportunity to explore empirical data and capture the subjective experiences of entrepreneurial leaders within the realm of business incubators. Through this iterative process, a profound and comprehensive understanding of the understudied phenomenon was achieved, revealing unique insights into the role of business incubators in entrepreneurial leadership development and the contextual factors influencing it within the context of a developing economy.

4.3 Research Paradigms

The research paradigm is an important aspect of conducting research, as it lays the foundation for the philosophical and theoretical foundations of a study. A research paradigm encompasses a researcher's beliefs, assumptions, and worldview that shape the way research is conducted and the types of evidence that are acceptable (Saunders et al., 2012). The term "paradigm" comes from the Greek word "paradeigma," which means "a pattern, model, or plan" (Johnson and Duberley, 2000, p. 68). According to Fossey et al. (2002, p. 718), a paradigm is "a set of ideas or worldviews used by a community of researchers to generate knowledge." The research paradigm determines the ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological assumptions of a study and provides a comprehensive belief system that guides research and practice in a field (William et al., 2007).

Burrell and Morgan (1979) proposed four research paradigms, namely, functionalism, interactionism, conflict theory, and radical humanism (Figure 9), and they represent different perspectives on society, human behaviour, and the role of the researcher in conducting research

(Burrell and Morgan, 1979). These paradigms provide a sociological perspective on social science research and demonstrate the diversity of approaches and philosophical beliefs that shape the research.

Functionalism, as defined by Burrell and Morgan (1979), views society as a stable and harmonious system where each part contributes to the overall stability of society. Interactionism, or “interpretivism, on the other hand, focuses on understanding social behaviours as a result of face-to-face interactions between individuals. Conflict theory, or structuralism, views society as a dynamic system marked by conflicts and competitions among various social groups. While radical humanism views individuals as creators of their own social reality and sees society as a site of struggle for individual freedom and liberation. This study sought to explain the complexities of entrepreneurial leadership practices in teams and to develop an understanding of the challenges, competencies, and their development from the lens of social actors; therefore, an interpretivist paradigm was adopted as it aligns with the investigation of the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders within university-based incubators from a team perspective (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2106). The interpretivist paradigm has an interpretivist ontological assumption that knowledge is socially constructed and an epistemological assumption that reality can be understood through the perspectives of social actors. This aligns with the study’s goal of investigating how entrepreneurial leaders shape their worldview (Burrell and Morgan, 1979).

Figure 9 Paradigm in social sciences

4.4 Research Philosophy

Saunders et al. (2012) defined research philosophy as “a system of beliefs and assumptions about the development of knowledge” (p. 124). To comprehend research, a researcher must make several assumptions, including epistemological (assumptions about human knowledge), ontological (assumptions about realities), and axiological (assumptions about researchers’ influence on research) assumptions. The main research philosophies in business and management research include positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, and pragmatism; each one has its own ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological assumptions.

Positivism, also known as the functionalist approach, views physical objects and human beings as subjects that can be studied in the same way and focuses primarily on uninfluenced data and facts (Bell et al., 2022; Saunders et al., 2012). This philosophy assumes that social reality can be objectively verified through reason and evidence and that knowledge can be objectively verified (King et al., 2018). On the other hand, interpretivism, also known as subjectivism, views reality as subjective and shaped by the personal interpretation and experiences of social

actors (Saunders et al., 2012). The interpretivist approach in business research proposes viewing an entity or organisation through the eyes of different individuals and groups, and this philosophy assumes that the course of research must be evaluated subjectively by the researcher as social reality can be better understood from the perspectives of various social actors (Blumberg et al., 2014).

Ontology investigates the nature of existence, while epistemology concerns what is considered acceptable knowledge within a discipline (Bell et al., 2022; Saunders et al., 2012). Objectivism holds that reality exists independently of our perception and interpretation, while subjectivism believes that knowledge is subjective and shaped by personal bias and experience (Bell et al., 2022; Saunders et al., 2012). Table 12 below presents the perspectives of positivism and interpretivism.

Table 13 Perspectives of positivism and interpretivism

Assumption	Positivism	Interpretivism
Ontological	Singular reality, separate from the researcher.	Multiple realities that are interpreted by the researcher.
Epistemological	Research subject is independent from the researcher.	Interaction between research subject and researcher.
Axiological	Value-free and unbiased.	Value laden and biased.

Source : MacLaren, (2015, p. 125)

This research primarily focuses on the concept of entrepreneurial leadership, which is still in its early stages of development and lacks clear theoretical foundations, making it theoretically complex (Harrison et al., 2018; Roomi and Harrison, 2011). To fully grasp the multidimensional and socially constructed nature of entrepreneurial leadership and its effects on business and society, it is crucial to thoroughly investigate the contextual factors associated with the concept, as noted by Anderson and Smith (2007), which can be achieved through the principles of the interpretivist constructionist philosophy, which implies that reality is formed

through the interactions and interpretations of individuals and groups within a social and cultural context (Saunders et al., 2012). By adopting an interpretivist constructionist perspective, it becomes possible to examine the interplay between individuals' actions and the broader contextual factors of culture, society, economy, and politics (Fletcher, 2006). An interpretivist constructionist philosophy provides a deeper understanding of entrepreneurial activities within a dynamic social and environmental context (Anderson and Smith, 2007; Fletcher, 2006; Harrison, 2016). This study sought to examine the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders operating in teams. To gain a deeper insight into how these leaders perceive and construct their world view in comprehending entrepreneurial leadership process and its associated challenges, an interpretivist-constructionist perspective was employed in this study. This approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of the contextual factors that influence the entrepreneurial process and its implications for business and society (Harrison, 2016).

However, it is worth noting that the use of a constructionist perspective in research may face criticism regarding the reliability of findings due to the subjective nature of participants' perspectives, as highlighted by Harrison et al. (2016a). Nonetheless, since the purpose of this research is to explore entrepreneurial leadership challenges and competencies from a contextual perspective, the coherent use of this perspective can provide valuable and rich insights into the multifaceted nature of entrepreneurial leadership and its social dynamics. Therefore, the use of an interpretivist-constructionist approach in this study is a legitimate approach to explore the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in a group setting.

4.5 Research design

The research design describes how a researcher responds to research questions; it enables the researcher to collect appropriate data to test a theory or answer key research questions (Lee and Lings, 2008). According to Saunders et al. (2012, p. 122), a research design is “the general plan of how you will go about answering your research question(s). It contains clear objectives derived from your research question(s), specify the sources from which you intend to collect data, how you propose to collect and analyse these, discuss ethical issues, and outline the constraints you will inevitably encounter.” The key components of research design include units of analysis, research questions, data collection instruments, classification, presentation, and data analysis (Al-Khalifah, 2014). A research design is a structure that moves from collecting empirical data to answering research questions and leading to conclusions (Yin, 2003). The research design of the present study comprises the following components:

4.5.1 Scoping study

A scoping study was conducted to assess and map the existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership challenges and competencies. The purpose of the scoping study was to understand the existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership competencies. The scoping study sought to answer two key research questions.

- What are the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders face?
- What competencies do entrepreneurial leaders require to overcome challenges?

4.5.2 Literature review

The purpose of a literature review as stated by Tranfield et al. (2003), is to evaluate the existing research on a topic and establish research questions that advance knowledge in that field. According to Higgins (2011), a literature review is often used to provide an overview of a subject and highlight areas in need of further investigation. A narrative literature review, as described by Bryman (2011), is a comprehensive examination of the literature on a specific subject that aims to deepen the understanding of a particular topic rather than just accumulating knowledge. This type of review is commonly used in established fields such as entrepreneurship and leadership.

Entrepreneurial leadership research is evolving. Despite growing studies on entrepreneurial leadership, the current knowledge base about entrepreneurial leadership's challenges, competencies, and development is limited due to dispersed literature. Thus, a systematic literature review (SLR) of the existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development is imperative to gain a comprehensive understanding of the subject. The traditional narrative approach to conducting literature reviews in business management has received criticism for its lack of criticality (Harrison et al., 2016a). Consequently, there have been calls for a literature review process in the domain of business and management that is more methodical and evidence-based (Harrison et al., 2016a; Harrison et al., 2018).

A systematic literature review is considered a rigorous, repeatable, and transparent process that provides a comprehensive overview of the literature in a specific field (Tranfield et al., 2003). SLR is particularly useful in emerging fields such as entrepreneurial leadership, which has a dispersed and fragmented literature (Harrison et al., 2018; Clark et al., 2019). Therefore, this study conducted a systematic literature review by adopting the three-stage SLR process outlined by Tranfield et al. (2003).

4.5.3 The process of SLR

4.5.3.1 Stage 1: Planning the Review

The first stage of SLR as proposed by Tranfield (2003) entail planning the review. During this stage, the researcher defines the scope and objectives of the review, set review questions, and articulate inclusion and exclusion criteria for selecting relevant studies on a topic. The planning phase of the review was completed by implementing the subsequent procedures. First, the review was planned through the development of a review protocol in collaboration with experts in the field of entrepreneurial leadership. Second, the panel determined the need for the review and developed the review questions and protocol. The SLR review protocol was created by drawing on various aspects of entrepreneurial leadership competencies, as well as their learning and development. Following that, a scoping study was conducted based on the review questions listed below, followed by inclusion and exclusion criteria.

- What is the impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies on organisation?
- What are the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders?
- How can entrepreneurial leaders learn and develop these competencies?

The evaluation of relevant literature was based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria as mentioned in Table 14.

Table 14 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

<i>Details</i>	<i>Description</i>
Purpose of study	This SLR aims to identify entrepreneurial leadership competencies, explore their impacts on various contexts, and identify how these competencies can be developed.
Review Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the impact of entrepreneurial leadership competencies on organisation? • What are the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders? • How can entrepreneurial leaders learn and develop these competencies?
Inclusion Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Papers must be in English. • The focus of the paper must be entrepreneurial leadership competencies or their development. • The paper directly addresses one or more of the review questions. • Papers published between 1985 and 2022
Exclusion Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Papers not in peer reviewed publications (i.e., conference proceedings or book chapters)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Papers focused on other styles of leadership. • Papers not in English language
Databases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emerald • Ingenta connect • Sage Journals • Science direct • Springer link • Taylor and Francis • Web of Science • Wiley Online

The research on entrepreneurial leadership spans over 30 years (Clark et al., 2019), the first paper on EL was published by Lippitt (1987). Therefore, this study chose 1985 to 2022 as its timeframe for article search.

4.5.3.2 Stage II: Conducting the Review

The implementation of the review phase involved carrying out the review protocols, applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and addressing the review questions established in the initial stage. Finding keywords derived from the review questions was the first step in conducting the review. The following keywords and search strings (shown in Table 15) were used to search the relevant studies across various online databases (see Table 14) that are recognised as the most reputable databases for management research (Harrison et al., 2018).

The review process employed a systematic approach to ensure the quality of selected papers from various databases. In screening potential articles, priority was given to journals with high rankings and rigorous peer review processes, ensuring credibility and reliability. Additionally, emphasis was placed on selecting papers that were properly referenced and highly cited within the entrepreneurial leadership literature, further validating their significance and contribution. Furthermore, each paper was assessed to ensure it provided sound evidence and theoretical assertions that effectively addressed the review questions, ultimately enhancing the overall quality and relevance of the study's findings (Harrison, 2016).

Table 15 Search strings and Keywords

Search Strings	
Search string 1	Entrep*
Search string 1a	Lead*
Search string 1b	Develop* OR Learning
Search string 1c	“Entrepreneurial leadership”
Search string 2	“Lead*”
Search string 2a	Entrep*
Search string 2b	Develop* OR Learning
Search string 2c	“Entrepreneurial leadership”
Search strings 3	“Entrepreneurial leadership”
Search strings 3a	Skills OR Competencies OR Capabilities OR attributes
Search strings 3b	Develop* OR Learning
Search string 4	Entrepreneurial leadership (for Google Scholar)

4.5.3.3 Stage III: Reporting and Dissemination

The final phase of SLR known as reporting and dissemination. This stage involves data extraction, analysis, and synthesis. Following that, a rigorous evaluation and classification of identified literature was carried out to derive significant conclusions and detect recurring patterns and trends in the dataset. The details of the SLR findings were discussed previously (see Chapter 2) by using a descriptive, quantitative, and qualitative analysis (Tranfield et al., 2003).

4.5.3.4 Screening and selection criteria

The initial search yielded 851 papers that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria by using keywords and specified search strings on the selected databases that are well known in business and management. Duplicate screening was carried out from the initial search result using title, year, and author screening; as a result, 362 duplicate records were excluded. After duplicate screening, title screening was conducted on the remaining results, and 345 papers were excluded that were not specifically focused on entrepreneurial leadership competencies.

After the title screening, an abstract screening was performed, and 66 studies were excluded as they were not directly addressing the review questions. Then the full text of the articles was screened, and nine articles were excluded as they did not answer any of the review questions. Consequently, 69 papers were selected for the review from the database search. In addition, articles were identified from citations and bibliographies (inclusive). Lastly, an article search was carried out on Google Scholar, which yielded 14 articles relevant to the review questions that were thus added to the literature pool. In sum, 90 articles were selected for the review and further analysis. The search was concluded on August 8, 2022. The details of article screening and selection criteria are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Article Screen Process

4.5.4 Research Method

A research method refers to the strategies used by researchers to collect, analyse, and interpret data (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). There are two main types of research methods: quantitative and qualitative. The quantitative method, based on positivism philosophy, adopts a deductive approach and use statistical tools to examine objective realities and explain the relationship between variables (Saunders et al., 2012). The qualitative method, on the other hand, is rooted in interpretivism, social constructionism, and radical humanism philosophies and adopts an inductive approach, using interviews and individual interactions to explore subjective realities (Burrell and Morgan, 2017). In this study, the researcher adopted a qualitative method as it is suited for exploring the multiple perspectives and lived experiences of individuals (Molina-Azorn et al., 2012). The rationale for selecting a qualitative research method and prior investigations employing a comparable approach in the discipline will be elaborated upon in the subsequent section.

4.5.4.1 Qualitative research method

Choosing quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-method research is based on various ontological, epistemological, and axiological assumptions. As a result, before embarking on a research project, a researcher must recognise various philosophical assumptions about each research method. Table 15 compares qualitative and quantitative studies as well as their philosophical assumptions.

Table 16 Philosophical assumptions of quantitative and qualitative research

	Quantitative	Qualitative
<i>Principal orientation to the role of theory in relation to research</i>	Deductive: testing of theory	Inductive; generation of theory
<i>Epistemological orientation</i>	Natural science model, namely positivism	Interpretivism
<i>Ontological orientation</i>	Objectivism	Constructionism

Source: Bryman (2011, p. 27)

Qualitative research, as suggested by Guba and Lincoln (1994), offers deeper insights into human behaviour by allowing the researchers to analyse it in a subjective manner. Conducting interviews, for instance, provides a rich understanding of a phenomenon that cannot be obtained through large-scale surveys. Although surveys provide general opinions, face-to-face interviews provide more value in observing participants' gestures and body language, which enhances understanding of their social world (Wegner, 2002). Entrepreneurial leadership is a multifaceted notion that occurs within a dynamic social context and involves the interaction of numerous social actors; thus, a comprehensive understanding of the topic requires a subjective analysis. Quantitative methods can form a general opinion but cannot justify participants' perceptions, motives, or answers to "why" questions during the research process (Wegner, 2002). Therefore, observing individuals' perceptions and social interactions in a specific context, a qualitative approach is widely acknowledged as it provides a deeper understanding of the complexities of entrepreneurial leadership challenges and competencies (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011; Harrison et al., 2018). Table 17 presents various studies on entrepreneurial leadership that adopted a qualitative method.

Table 17 Studies on entrepreneurial leadership employed a qualitative approach

Authors	Year	Topic	Method
Swiercz and Lydon	2002	Entrepreneurial leadership in high-tech firms: a field study.	Semi-structured interviews
Currie et al.	2008	Entrepreneurial Leadership in the English Public Sector: Paradox or Possibility?	Semi-structured interviews
D'Intino et al.	2008	Visionary entrepreneurial leadership in the aircraft industry: The Boeing Company legacy	Case Study
Hansson and Mønsted	2008	Research leadership as entrepreneurial organizing for research.	Case Study
Surie and Ashley	2008	Integrating Pragmatism and Ethics in Entrepreneurial Leadership for Sustainable Value Creation.	Case Study
Leitch et al.	2009	Leadership development in SMEs: an action learning approach.	Semi-structured interviews
Kempster and Cope	2010	Learning to lead in the entrepreneurial context	Qualitative phenomenological interviews with entrepreneurs

Bagheri and Pihie	2011	Student Entrepreneurial Leaders: Challenges and Competencies of Leading University Entrepreneurship Programs.	Semi-structured interviews
Kansikas et al.	2012	Entrepreneurial leadership and familiness as resources for strategic entrepreneurship.	Case Study
Harrison	2016	Entrepreneurial leadership in developing economy: A study in Nigeria	Semi-structured interviews
Clark	2020	Entrepreneurial leadership: a study of Scottish small and medium-sized enterprises.	Semi-structured interviews

4.5.5 Sampling and Data collection strategy

Sampling is the process by which a researcher selects and studies specific elements of a population (Thietart, 2001). The nature and objectives of a study heavily influence the sampling technique chosen. As a result, it is critical for researchers to select appropriate sampling techniques that effectively answer their research questions (Saunders et al., 2012). There are two types of sampling methods that are commonly used in research: probability or random sampling and non-probability or non-random sampling. Figure 11 below illustrates methods of sampling.

Figure 11 Sampling Methods

4.5.5.1 Probability or random sampling

Probability sampling provides an equal chance for every item in the population to be included in the sample. This sampling method is known for being highly reliable and unbiased. However, this sampling method is the most expensive in terms of time and energy spent on level sampling errors (Taherdoost, 2016). Simple random sampling, systematic sampling, cluster sampling, and multi-stage sampling are the most common types of probability sampling.

4.5.5.2 Non- probability or non- random sampling

Non-probability sampling is commonly used in case study and qualitative research design. Case study research design aims to target small samples and is carried out to investigate a real-life phenomenon that does not necessitate statistical inferences to cover a larger population (Yin, 2003). Non-probability sampling methods include quota sampling, snowball sampling, convenience sampling, and purposive sampling (Taherdoost, 2016). Each sampling method has its own advantages and disadvantages, and the choice of method depends on the type of study and the nature of the phenomenon being studied. The aim of this research is to explore the challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders and the competencies they require to overcome these challenges from a team perspective in context of UBIs. Accordingly, the researcher selected nascent entrepreneurial leaders as research participants who may provide valuable insights into the topic by adopting a purposive sampling strategy to address the research questions (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016). The strength of purposive sampling, as noted by Shaw (1999, p. 63), is rooted in its ability to select cases that are “rich in information about the substantive research problem.” This sampling method enables the researcher to select samples that are likely to be informative and assist in meeting study objectives. It is preferred for exploratory investigations that intend to select samples based on pre-specified criteria (Al-Khalifah, 2014).

Dess et al. (1997) suggest that purposive sampling is suitable for exploratory research as it allows for the selection of samples based on specific criteria. Consequently, this research adopted purposive sampling to investigate the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders within the context of UBIs in a team context. This sampling method aligns with the research objectives and is consistent with the current literature on entrepreneurial leadership (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Bagheri and Pihie et al., 2013a; Clark, 2020). Table 18 summarises the advantages and disadvantages of various sampling techniques.

Table 18 Advantages and disadvantages of various sampling techniques

Technique	Strengths	Weaknesses
Convenience sampling	Least expensive, least time consuming, most convenient	Selection bias, sample not representative, not recommended by descriptive or casual research
Judgment sampling	Low-cost, convenient, not time consuming, ideal for exploratory research design	Does not allow generalisation, subjective
Quota sampling	Sample can be controlled for certain characteristics	Selection bias, no assurance
Snowball sampling	Can estimate rare characteristics	Time-consuming
Simple random sampling	Easily understood, results projectable	Difficult to construct sampling frame, expensive, lower precision, no assurance of representativeness
Systematic sampling	Can increase representativeness, easier to implement than simple random sampling, sampling frame not always necessary	Can decrease representativeness
Stratified sampling	Includes all important subpopulation, precision	Difficult to select relevant stratification variables, not feasible to stratify on many variables, expensive
Cluster sampling	Easy to implement, cost-effective	Imprecise, difficult to compute an interpret results

Source: Taherdoost (2016, p. 23).

4.5.5.3 Sampling process

The purpose of this qualitative study was to examine entrepreneurial leadership in a team context. The criteria for participant selection were restricted to entrepreneurial leaders working in business incubators. To ensure depth and rigor in the sample selection, a purposive sampling technique was employed, as suggested by Bagheri and Pihie (2011) and Harrison et al. (2018), alongside specified selection criteria (Patton, 2002). Entrepreneurial leaders leading start-ups in teams at UBIs were considered entrepreneurial leaders as they were selected based on stringent criteria such as innovation, business feasibility, start-up cost, and other factors established by the UBIs. This aligns with previous research on entrepreneurial leadership (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018). Hence, the following criteria were adopted for choosing research participants:

- A start-up must be being managed by an entrepreneurial team at UBIs.
- The start-up must be cofounded by a group with a minimum of two and a maximum of five individuals.
- The members must actively manage regular start-up tasks at the business incubator.
- The start-up must be recently founded and have not been in existence for more than a year.

To establish a focused and insightful sample for the research study, these criteria have been meticulously chosen. The research aims to conduct a more comprehensive analysis of the strategies, challenges, and mechanisms utilised by nascent entrepreneurial leaders as they navigate their start-ups. Investigating entrepreneurial leadership within a team context at UBIs yields distinct and specific insights for several reasons. Firstly, UBIs are renowned for their nurturing environment that fosters entrepreneurial leadership on a global scale. Nonetheless, there remain unresolved questions regarding why certain UBIs outperform others. Hence, it becomes imperative to comprehend the contextual factors that influence entrepreneurial leadership within UBIs. Secondly, the selection of entrepreneurial teams consisting of two to five members is justified by the fact that a majority of start-ups are founded by teams. The evidence indicates that start-ups led by teams are intricate, and a significant portion of early-

stage failures can be attributed to challenges that arise within these teams (Eisenhardt, 2013; Kaplan and Strömberg, 2004). Thus, understanding team dynamics and challenges is pivotal in comprehending team processes, responsibilities, and the requisite skills for effective teamwork and success.

Furthermore, it is justifiable to mandate that entrepreneurial leaders actively manage start-ups. This is in contrast to alternative studies that focus on entrepreneurial leadership development through coursework, extracurricular activities, and student projects (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a, Okudan and Rzasa, 2006, Roomi and Harrison, 2011). While these components are crucial in fostering entrepreneurial leadership knowledge and abilities, they do not inherently offer practical experience of launching and managing a real-world start-up. Consequently, an examination of the intricacies inherent in real-world business operations offers a more comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurial leadership development (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013).

Finally, this study concentrates on the challenges and competencies of aspiring entrepreneurial leaders, an area that has received limited research attention compared to established entrepreneurial leaders that received extensive examination in entrepreneurial leadership literature (Chen, 2007; Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018, Ngigi et al., 2018; Putsom et al., 2019a, Putsom et al., 2019b). This criterion offers a unique insight into the challenges faced by aspiring entrepreneurial leaders in relation to market entry, resource acquisition, and network establishment. By selecting ventures less than a year old, this study illuminates the critical challenges confronted by entrepreneurial leaders in the early stages of development and provides insights into the strategies and approaches they employ to transition their start-ups into fully-fledged enterprises. Given that the majority of start-ups fail during their formative

years due to underlying challenges in teams, it is prudent to investigate the aspects of entrepreneurial endeavours carried out in teams (Chen, 2007).

The selection of participants for this study was carried out by using the directory of 35 well-established university business incubators maintained by the Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan, which regulates HEIs in the country. The list of UBIs was obtained from the HEC website, and the contact information of the managers (UBIs) were obtained from the respective university websites. The managers were contacted via phone, email, or met in-person to discuss the research objectives. To prevent sample bias, UBIs managers were instructed to choose entrepreneurial teams at random (Golafshani, 2003).

To ensure maximum validity and richness in the research, a data saturation process was employed, following the methodology outlined by Harrison et al. (2018) and Bryman (2015). Initially, 25 UBIs agreed to participate in the study from four regions of Pakistan (Gilgit/Islamabad, Punjab, Sindh, Balochistan). The researcher intended to continue the interview process until no fresh insights emerged from new data (Harrison et al., 2018). However, after the 15th series and 31 interviews, theoretical saturation was observed, indicating that no new insights were forthcoming from participants' accounts. Despite this, as interviews had already been scheduled, an additional nine interviews were conducted, including two female and seven male entrepreneurial leaders. In total, 36 in-person interviews and four online interviews were conducted, involving 18 teams comprising 30 male and 10 female entrepreneurial leaders. Each interview lasted between 45 to 120 minutes and was conducted among the 18 entrepreneurial teams at UBIs. The specifics of the entrepreneurial leaders engaged in the interview process are provided in Table 19, with 1A representing the first entrepreneurial leader interviewed and 18B representing the last.

Table 19 Specifics of research participants

Entrepreneurial Teams	Entrepreneurial leaders	Gender	Age	Qualification
Team 1	1A	Male	20-29	BS (Economics and Finance)
	1B	Male	20-29	BSCS
	1C	Male	20-29	BSCS
Team 2	2A	Male	20-29	MBA (Project Management)
	2B	Male	20-29	BSCS
	2C	Male	20-29	MBA (Finance)
	2D	Female	20-29	MBA (Finance)
Team 3	3A	Male	30-39	BSCS
	3B	Male	20-29	Bioscience
Team 4	4A	Male	20-29	MBA
	4B	Male	20-29	BSIT
Team 5	5A	Female	20-29	MS (Software Engineering)
	5B	Male	20-29	BS (Education)
Team 6	6A	Male	20-29	BS Electronics
	6B	Male	30-39	BS electrical Engineering
Team 7	7A	Male	30-39	BS (Electrical Engineering)
	7B	Male	20-29	BS (English)
Team 8	8A	Male	20-29	BS (Software Engineering)
	8B	Male	20-29	BS (Software Engineering)
Team 9	9A	Female	20-29	BS (Microbiology)
	9B	Female	20-29	BS (Environmental Science)
	9C	Female	20-29	BS (Microbiology)
Team 10	10A	Male	20-29	BS (Software Engineering)
	10B	Male	20-29	BSIT
Team 11	11A	Male	20-29	MBA
	11B	Male	20-29	MBA
Team 12	12A	Male	20-29	BS (Biochemistry)
	12B	Male	20-29	BS (Biochemistry)
Team 13	13A	Male	20-29	BS (Physics)
	13B	Male	20-29	BSCS
Team 14	14A	Male	20-29	BSCS
	14B	Male	30-39	BSCS
Team 15	15A	Male	20-29	MBA
	15B	Female	20-29	MBA
Team 16	16A	Female	20-29	BBA
	16B	Female	20-29	BBA
Team 17	17A	Male	20-29	BBA
	17B	Female	20-29	MBBS
	17C	Female	20-29	MBA
Team 18	18A	Male	20-29	BBA
	18B	Male	20-29	BBA

4.5.6 Data collection

This research aimed to gain deeper insights into entrepreneurial leadership challenges and competencies in a dynamic team context, which can be achieved by applying a qualitative research method (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013). Using a qualitative method provides an opportunity to attain a more profound comprehension of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their developmental processes, as pointed out by Kempster (2009) and Swiercz and Lydon (2002). The qualitative interview is a data collection technique that uses open dialogue to delve deeply into a topic (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008) and is widely used as a method of data collection in qualitative research (Bell et al., 2022; Blumberg et al., 2014). Among the different types of interviews, in-depth interviews are often considered ideal for business research, as they allow researchers to observe participants' experiences and their interaction in a social context (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2011). Furthermore, qualitative interviews, as explained by King et al., (2018), not only help in understanding respondents' opinions but also provide insights into the underlying reasons for their perspectives.

Qualitative interviews are classified into three types: structured, semi-structured, and unstructured interviews. Structured interviews are commonly used to collect numerical data in quantitative studies (Johnstone, 2007). Structured interview, also referred to as a "standardised interview," is a type of interview where predetermined questions are administered and scheduled by the interviewers. The aim of a structured interview is to pose the same set of questions to all participants and subsequently aggregate their responses based on consistent cues (Bell et al., 2022). This type of interview is commonly used in quantitative studies and is distinguished by low variability in research questions. Structured interviews' major strengths include their consistency in generalising data, low risk of bias, applicability for large sample

sizes, time efficiency, and ease of conduct (MacLaren, 2015). Structured interviews are primarily used to obtain quantifiable results using a limited approach. Therefore, they may not be appropriate for the current study, which aims to investigate entrepreneurial leadership in a group context and requires a deeper understanding of the research participants' perspectives. This can only be achieved through a flexible order of questions that facilitates discussion with participants.

Unstructured interviews, on the other hand, are a non-standardised and informal form of interview that allows the interviewer to ask any question on the topic in order to gain a deeper understanding of events and behaviour on the topic (Saunders et al., 2012). However, unstructured interviews are criticised because they are thought to ask different questions to each participant, making it difficult to analyse the emerging patterns (Gray, 2020). To avoid these limitations, researchers suggest using a hybrid form of structured and unstructured interviews known as "semi-structured interviews" to maintain a flexible order of interview questions based on interviewee interest (Easterby-Smith et al., 2008).

Semi-structured interviews are preferred in understudied research areas that require a more in-depth discussion to address research questions and objectives in a concise manner (Saunders et al., 2012). Semi-structured interviews primarily comprised of open-ended questions designed to elicit the participants' comprehension of the phenomenon (Bell et al., 2022). According to Blumberg et al. (2014, p. 258), semi-structured interviews serve two purposes: "on one hand, the researcher wants to know the informant's perspective on the issue; on the other hand, the researcher wants to know if the informant can confirm insights and information that the researcher already has." Therefore, adopting a semi-structured interview is useful in gaining a deeper insight into the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders operating in UBIs (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013) and is widely employed in existing literature on

entrepreneurial leadership (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013, Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016; Harrison et al., 2018). Table 20 presents a comparative analysis of three forms of interviews.

Table 20 Comparative analysis of interview types

	Strength	Weaknesses	Applicability
Unstructured	Provides rich information. Explores unique themes Creates relationships which may lead to more information. Uses natural language.	Time consuming. Resource intensive. Lack generalisability. Generate irrelevant data. Susceptible to interviewer bias.	Exploratory research investigating past events when subjective views and experiences are sought in conjunction with other research methods.
Semi-structured	Entail organised questions to cover critical points, useful when the researcher is inexperienced. Flexibility in asking further questions. Increased reliability and scope for comparability. Interviewee can respond in language natural to them.	Time consuming. Resource intensive. Needs good interview Skills to keep on topic. Interview questions are open to researcher bias. May lack in generalisability.	Multiple interviewers. Only one chance to conduct the interview. Researcher has some knowledge of the topic. In conjunction with other research methods.
Structured	Can produce consistent generalizable data. Minimal risk of bias. Large sample size. Can be conducted quickly. Sophisticated interviewing skills not required.	Little opportunity for feedback. Question responses are limited and restrictive. Little scope to cater for the unforeseen. Real-time changes to the interviews cannot be made.	Clear focus and a question to be answered. High level of knowledge on a topic to allow for appropriate question formulation. A well-developed literature

Source; MacLaren (2015, p. 135)

4.5.6.1 Interview guide

An interview guide or protocol seeks to elicit rich, focused, and meaningful data that, to the greatest extent possible, captures participants' experiences (Castillo-Montoya, 2016). An interview protocol is a guide that includes key research themes and questions to be addressed during the interview (Harrison, 2016). A comprehensive framework for conducting interviews typically comprises four distinct stages.

Phase 1: Ensuring interview questions align with research questions.

Phase 2: Constructing an inquiry-based conversation.

Phase 3: Receiving feedback on interview protocols.

Phase 4: Piloting the interview protocol.

Each phase should ensure that the research instrument is appropriate for the participants and is in line with the research objectives (Castillo-Montoya, 2016). An interview guide is intended to serve as a “memory list for the interviewer to ensure that the same issues are addressed in every interview” (Blumberg et al., 2011, p. 266). The primary goal of the interview guide is to improve the dependability and credibility of the research (Saunders et al., 2012).

Present study focused on the challenges and competencies of emerging entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs, an interview guide concentrating on entrepreneurial leadership challenges and competencies was developed based on the findings of a thorough literature review, research questions, and objectives. The developed interview guide was validated by soliciting feedback from the subject experts and ensuring its alignment with overall research objectives and questions. Flexibility is maintained throughout the interview process to encourage maximum participation and discussion from the participants. According to King et al. (2018), flexibility is critical for capturing perspectives from participants that are valuable to the study and would otherwise be missed if a restricted interview guide is used. Various steps be taken during the interview process to ensure the study’s flexibility, dependability, and credibility. For example, if respondents were given the option of answering the interview questions of their choice, it was ensured that all questions remained consistent, unambiguous, and understandable to all participants. In addition, steps were taken to ensure no leading questions were asked to participants to avoid bias during the interview process.

4.5.7 Data analysis

Data analysis is defined as “the process of dividing aggregated texts (oral, written, or visual) into smaller segments of meaning for careful consideration, reflection, and interpretation” (Ellingson, 2013, p. 595). While qualitative data can be considered rich data, qualitative data collection methods can be difficult to analyse due to content distraction and a lack of universal methods (Bryman, 2011). Although qualitative researchers use a variety of data analysis tools such as content analysis, grounded theory, and narrative analysis to analyse qualitative data (Cameron and Price, 2009), thematic analysis is widely recommended for sense-making by facilitating the identification of patterns developed through the synthesis of qualitative data (Braun and Clark, 2006; King et al., 2018). The patterns that emerge from a thematic analysis facilitate formulating themes, which can be manifest or latent, and can be identified using either a deductive or an inductive approach (Boyatzis, 1998). King et al. (2018) proposed a three-stage process for analysing qualitative data using thematic analysis. According to King et al. (2018), thematic analysis entails the following steps: descriptive coding, interpretive coding, and defining overarching themes. These stages are illustrated in detail as follows.

4.5.7.1 Stage 1: Descriptive coding

Descriptive coding is the first step in King et al.’s (2018) framework. Descriptive coding, as defined by Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 88), is the “production of initial codes from the data”. Essentially, it entails categorising data into meaningful groups (Tuckett, 2005). Descriptive coding is a method of describing participant accounts without attempting to interpret them (Braun and Clarke, 2006; King et al., 2018; Tuckett, 2005). In descriptive coding, the following steps were adopted in this study: In the first stage, all recorded interviews were transcribed. The researcher then reread all the transcripts in order to become acquainted with the data

without making any interpretations. Then, in a Word document, key points and comments were highlighted pertaining to relevant interview questions. Finally, all documents were imported into QSR-NVivo (version¹²) for encoding, and descriptive codes based on highlighted points and comments were used to encode the entire transcripts. This method is consistent with previous studies that used a three-stage thematic analysis (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016). Table 21 below shows an example of descriptive coding process.

Table 21 Illustration of descriptive coding

<i>Interview extracts</i>	<i>Descriptive codes</i>
One of the biggest challenges is the electricity issues in our area	Electricity issues
The incubation centres should be open during day and night and basic facilities at least should be there	Access to UBIs/ Availability of facilities
We are unclear about what the steps are, where we have to start our idea and where we have to get it registered.	Registration issues
Some specific challenges require specific skills such as IT issues	IT issues/skills
As a team the biggest challenge is to find the good member and make a good team	Finding team members
Finding leadership opportunities such as managing specific projects or teams and requesting feedback on your performance helps us to improve these skills.	Learning through experience

4.5.7.2 Stage 2: Interpretive coding

The second step in the thematic analysis is the interpretive coding process. Interpretive coding refers to the process of defining “codes that go beyond describing relevant features of participants’ accounts and focus more on your interpretation of their meaning” (King et al., 2018, p. 154). Descriptive codes are grouped together based on perceived similarities or emerging patterns to facilitate interpretation (King et al., 2018; Tuckett, 2005). Interpretive codes are words or phrases that aim to provide meaning to participants’ accounts and are not always related to descriptive codes (King et al., 2018). The below Table 22 shows how

interpretive codes were generated from the transcript.

Table 22 Illustration of Interpretive coding

<i>Interview extracts</i>	<i>Descriptive codes</i>	<i>Interpretive codes</i>
One of the biggest challenges is the electricity issues in our area	Electricity issues	Infrastructural constraints
The incubation centres should be open during day and night and basic facilities at least should be there	Access to UBIs/ Availability of facilities	BIC accessibility/ Lack of resources
We are unclear about what the steps are, where we have to start our idea and where we have to get it registered.	Registration issues	Start-up registration
Some specific challenges require specific skills such as IT issues	IT issues/skills	IT skills
As a team the biggest challenge is to find the good member and make a good team	Finding team members	Team selection
Finding leadership opportunities such as managing specific projects or teams and requesting feedback on your performance helps us to improve these skills.	Learning through experience	Experiential learning

4.5.7.3 Stage 3: Overarching theme

Creating overarching themes is the final stage of thematic analysis. In this stage, descriptive and interpretive codes are combined to identify common themes and patterns in the data. Theoretical knowledge is now included in order to develop more abstract themes from those identified through interpretive coding (King et al., 2018). All descriptive and interpretive codes with similar meanings were merged during this process, while irrelevant themes were discarded. An illustration of the coding process encompassing all three stages is shown below in Table 23.

Table 23 Illustration of coding process and generating overarching themes

Coding Steps	Themes/subthemes
Overarching Theme	Self-competencies
Interpretive codes	Self-Management skills
Descriptive codes	Self-awareness Balancing work and life

		Time management
Overarching Theme	→	Organising competencies
Interpretive codes	→	Business function skills
Descriptive codes	→	Accounting and Finance knowledge Marketing ability Team selection
Overarching Theme	→	Interpersonal competencies
Interpretive codes	→	communication skills
Descriptive codes	→	Verbal communication ability Written communication skills
Overarching Theme	→	Entrepreneurial competencies
Interpretive codes	→	Opportunity identification and exploitation skills
Descriptive codes	→	Pursuing new business opportunities Fulfilling existing market needs Sensing business opportunities
Overarching Theme	→	Conceptual competencies
Interpretive codes	→	Analytical skills
Descriptive codes	→	Analytical thinking Objective decision making Business assessment

4.6 Evaluation of the research

The rigour of the study, which aims to ensure that research findings are consistent with the adopted research paradigm, determines the credibility of qualitative research (Atiq, 2014). In this regard, self-reflective dimensions such as responsibility and honesty are critical in qualitative research. The rigour of a study is concerned with the extent to which research's findings are credible and worthy of attention. As a result, a researcher must develop 'evaluative criteria' based on fundamental principles to guide the assessment of a study's integrity or trustworthiness (Baxter and Eyles, 1997). A variety of criteria devised by scholars are applied to assess the quality and robustness of research outcomes in both qualitative and quantitative domains. King et al. (2018) state that the evaluation of quantitative studies' quality is predicated on the criteria of validity, impartiality, generalisability, and reliability. These criteria are predominantly linked to the positivist research paradigm and are specifically designed for scientific inquiry (Lincoln and Guba, 1986). Therefore, using a quantitative or positivist criteria

to assess the rigour of qualitative studies is inappropriate because they are incompatible with qualitative research philosophies (Tracy, 2010). Alternatively, Denzin and Lincoln (2011) proposed four alternative trustworthiness criteria for qualitative studies to avoid the challenge of assessing the rigour of qualitative studies which include credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. These are discussed as follows:

4.6.1 Credibility

Credibility is used as an alternate criterion for internal validity—the extent to which the findings of qualitative research are accurate, reliable, representative, and widely acceptable (Bryman, 2011; Lincoln and Guba, 1985). Since the purpose of this research was to explore the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders as manifested by interpretivist philosophy, the reality can be understood through the lens of multiple social actors (Denzin and Lincoln, 2011), thus it is vital for the researchers to ensure the credibility of these realities from multiple sources. This study adopted various methods to ensure the credibility of the research, which include prolonged engagement, member validation, and data triangulation.

Prolonged engagement refers to the amount of time the researcher invests with research participants and their research context. The researcher invested a sufficient amount of time with participants and their research context by visiting their labs and offices and analysing their project prototypes in person to gain first-hand experience of the phenomenon occurrence. In addition, semi-structured interviews, participant observation, and context analysis were conducted to obtain a holistic understanding of the phenomenon during the data collection process and were reflected during data analysis process. Member validation is a method in which researchers share interview transcripts with research participants to ensure their

consistency with participant accounts (Creswell, 2009). This research ensured member validation by resending interview transcripts to participants to verify their perspectives and narrated accounts during interview. These transcripts were further validated from subject experts to assess their richness and compliance with research questions.

Finally, in order to enhance the rigour of the findings, data triangulation was carried out to enhance the study's credibility (Creswell, 2009). Along with interviews, the perspectives, behaviours, and life experiences of group members were considered. Alongside, the findings were validated in reference to existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership.

4.6.2 Transferability

Transferability describes the extent to which the outcomes of one context are transferable to another (King et al., 2018; Schofield, 1993). The transferability of present research manifests in several ways. For instance, the criteria of sample selection, data collection and analysis, data saturation criteria, and construction of theoretical frameworks were replicable in other contexts (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018). These criteria may be useful for future researchers exploring the notion in other contexts. Since this research is contextualised in UBIs, the findings surround a specific context of UBIs and aspiring entrepreneurial leaders; thus, may not be generalised to other sectors. However, this research extends the transferability and validates the empirical models of other studies conducted on entrepreneurial leadership challenges and competencies (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Clark, 2020; Guo, 2009; Harrison et al., 2018; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Furthermore, these rigorous criteria for participant selection (sample selection criteria), development of interview protocols (interviews themes, questions, process), and implementation of data triangulation techniques

(member validation, subject experts' assessment) can serve as reference for future researchers investigating comparable phenomena.

4.6.3 Dependability

The degree to which a study is logical, traceable, and documented, explains its dependability (Neergaard and Uthøi, 2007), which is used as an alternative to reliability in quantitative research (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Unlike quantitative research, replication of qualitative findings is not possible from one context to another due to subjective realities that are inconsistent and unstable (King et al., 2018). Qualitative researchers ensure dependability by crafting robust, reliable, and trustworthy criteria for the research process, findings, and their consistency with other studies falling under the spectrum. This study took several measures to ensure transparency by employing various dependable methods that include audit trails for documenting all research activities and processes during data collection, coding, analysis, data saturation criteria, and field notes (King et al., 2018). In addition, to validate the dependability measure, triangulation was applied to check whether the processes are consistent with other studies on the subject through an external validation process by including subject experts.

4.6.4 Confirmability

According to Bell et al. (2018), “confirmability is concerned with ensuring that, while recognising that complete objectivity is impossible in business research, the researcher can be shown to have acted in good faith; in other words, it should be obvious that he or she has not overtly allowed personal values or theoretical inclinations manifestly to sway the conduct of the research and findings derived from it” (p.130). The confirmability of the qualitative research explains the extent to which researchers adopted a responsible, transparent, and

unbiased approach during the data collection and analysis process (King et al., 2018; Thomas and Magilvy, 2011). This research adopted various methods of confirmability which include: the researcher’s reflexivity (awareness of potential biasness); an audit trail to ensure all data collection and analysis processes align with existing studies, data triangulation to validate the findings from multiple sources critically and analyse their consistencies and discussing the findings from external validation sources. Table 23 compares the trustworthiness of elaboration in quantitative and qualitative studies.

Table 24 A comparison of qualitative and quantitative study trust worthiness criteria

Positivist criteria for assessing rigour	Qualitative Criteria of assessing trustworthiness
Internal validity	Credibility
Generalisability	Transferability
Reliability	Dependability
Objectivity	Confirmability

Source: Atiq (2014, p. 77)

4.7 Reflexivity

The research process was significantly influenced by various contextual factors, which in turn provided unique insights into the research findings. For instance, the impact of Covid-19 restrictions was evident in the data collection process, with some business incubators implementing Covid safety measures that prevented in-person meetings. Consequently, adjustments were made to adopt online interviews. The pandemic also had a notable effect on start-ups and their operations (Liu et al., 2020). Many entrepreneurial leaders postponed their start-up activities due to restrictions, while others faced challenges in monitoring team progress remotely due to a lack of technological facilities. Some start-ups adapted their business models to operate virtually. For example, a tech-based start-up originally focused on IT solutions developed a centralised platform to connect clients with tech experts. Similarly, a start-up offering language and translation services created a virtual platform to engage with clients and developed digital content such as videos and courses.

Moreover, the impact of Covid-19 extended beyond operational challenges to affect the personal and economic conditions of entrepreneurial leaders, further influencing their growth and success. The Covid-19 pandemic notably affected business incubators, particularly in their ability to invite experts for training and mentorship to uplift entrepreneurial skills among aspiring entrepreneurs. As a result, there was a dynamic shift in entrepreneurial leadership learning, transitioning from traditional mechanisms to online platforms. These insights are thoroughly reflected within the findings section of this thesis, providing a new direction for entrepreneurial leadership learning in a disruptive environment (Pal et al., 2014).

During the research process, the researcher noted various social, cultural, and institutional norms pertaining to entrepreneurship. From the accounts of the participants, it became evident that family pressure and societal attitudes toward entrepreneurial endeavours were not supportive, leading to demotivation among aspiring entrepreneurial leaders. Additionally, institutional challenges were observed, such as cumbersome security measures for accessing UBIs, inadequate workspace, and insufficient training and learning resources to foster entrepreneurial knowledge and skills among leaders. Moreover, the experiences and perspectives of women entrepreneurial leaders highlighted unique and context-specific insights. Women face significant obstacles in accessing UBIs, conducting entrepreneurial activities outside of office hours, and balancing family responsibilities.

Additionally, the researcher's position during the pandemic, including follow-up meetings with participants and travel restrictions, also influenced the data collection process. These diverse socio-cultural challenges not only impacted the research process but also provided valuable insights into entrepreneurial leadership practices during times of crisis. In line with reflexivity principles, the researchers acted in good faith, adhering to ethical guidelines to capture a holistic understanding of the phenomenon. This approach ultimately facilitated a rich and context-focused understanding of entrepreneurial leadership within the context of a developing economy.

4.8 Research Ethics

A researcher must consider research ethics practices before beginning the data collection process. These ethical considerations are critical at all stages of the research process, especially when the researcher is investigating the daily lives of participants (Miller and Besser, 2003). This study ensured that ethical principles such as non-maleficence and beneficence, autonomy, justice, and confidentiality and anonymity were followed, as outlined by the University of the West of Scotland (UWS, 2016) ethics committee guidelines.

4.8.1 Non-maleficence and beneficence

The principle of non-maleficence dictates that research participants should not be subjected to physical or emotional harm, while the principle of beneficence emphasises the need to promote well-being and do good throughout the research process (Kesidou, 2021; Saunders et al., 2012; UWS, 2016). The present study ensured that research participants were not subjected to any mental or physical stress. The researcher explicitly communicated to the participants that they were free to choose whether to respond to the research questions. Moreover, participants were reminded that their participation was entirely voluntary and that there were no obligations to answer sensitive questions. In addition, the beneficence was ensured by protecting the participants wellbeing, providing them emotional support, giving them more time to understand interview questions, and obtaining their consent to obtain documentation evidence (picture, signature) for research processes. The participants were assured that the findings of this study would serve as a guide for policymakers and institutions to develop practical and policy-informed strategies to address the obstacles faced by aspiring entrepreneurial leaders.

Additionally, the research would contribute to the development of entrepreneurial leadership and the establishment of a sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem.

4.8.2 Autonomy

The voluntary participation of research participants is referred to as autonomy. The participants were made aware of the overall scope of the study and its implications. As a result, this study took participant autonomy into account by obtaining both written and verbal consent from participants. Before asking participants for permission, the researcher informed them about the nature of the study and its implications so that they could understand the research and make an informed decision to participate. Participants received a final invitation and consent form via email. By disclosing the overall research process and its implications, the current study promoted participant autonomy. Prior to the interview, participants provided written and verbal consent, stating that they were aware of the overall goals of the research and that their participation was voluntary (Kesidou, 2021). Furthermore, the participants were provided with the assurance that they retained the right to disengage from this research at any point without providing any justification.

4.8.3 Justice

Justice entails treating research participants fairly and equally; it requires researchers to share the same information and equally distribute the benefit and burden of research (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016). The current study ensured that all research participants were treated fairly and given equal time and opportunity to answer research questions. The researcher took several steps to ensure fairness and equitable treatment for all participants. For instance, the research participants were selected through a stringent and consistent criterion followed in every case.

All participants were given equal chances and the same level of opportunity to express themselves during interview process. The researcher ensured the utmost diversity to obtain rich insights from the team members. All participants were given sufficient time and consideration in discussing the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits involved in the research process (King et al., 2018). All participants were assured of their voluntary participation in the study, and their involvement, anonymity, and confidentiality were ensured throughout the data collection process. The researcher clearly explained to participants that the collected data will be stored in safe custody and their anonymity is ensured for the purpose of reporting and publication, and the researcher presents participants accounts in their true sense, avoiding any form of deception and manipulation for publication purposes. The participants were assured of the benefits of their participation, and all findings would be shared with them and their institutions to benefit participants and the community.

4.8.4 Confidentiality and anonymity

The principle of confidentiality and anonymity, as underscored by UWS (2016), seeks to respect individuals' privacy rights. It is closely linked with informed consent, as the extent of privacy and confidentiality provided to participants must be explicitly stated in the consent agreement. Anonymity implies that the researcher does not identify the participants' personal information, whereas confidentiality means that no third party has access to the participants' personal information (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016; Kesidou, 2021; Miller and Besser, 2003). Confidentiality involves protecting the identity and personal details of participants (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016; Kesidou, 2021; UWS, 2016).

In order to achieve confidentiality in the research process, the researchers adopted transparent and traceable measures. For instance, digital data (audio recording, pictures) were encrypted through passwords and kept in safe lockers with limited access to only authorised persons. While physical data (interview transcripts, field notes, and participant consent forms) were kept in safe lockers by removing their personally identifiable information (PII), which includes names, addresses, emails, phone numbers, and location, to ensure their confidentiality. The anonymity was ensured by assigning pseudonyms to all participants, their institutions, and locations to avoid potential biases in data analysis. The researcher ensured all these measures were in line with UWS ethical guidelines and duly signed by the researcher and participants to ensure confidentiality and anonymity.

4.9 Summary

The purpose of this study was to investigate the challenges, competencies, and development of nascent entrepreneurial leaders associated with university-based business incubators in Pakistani public and private HEIs. The methodological underpinnings of the current study were presented in this chapter. This chapter outlined the research approach, paradigm, and philosophical instance and provided a rationale for selecting a qualitative study to investigate the phenomenon of entrepreneurial leadership. Furthermore, this chapter discussed the research design, including sample selection, data collection, and data analysis methods (thematic analysis). This chapter also assessed the credibility of the findings, researchers' reflexivity, and ethical considerations. The following chapter presents research findings.

5 Findings

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the results of in-person interviews with 40 entrepreneurial leaders affiliated with 18 entrepreneurial teams at UBIs. The results are broken down into three sections (see Figure 13); the first section discusses the challenges confronting entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs. The second section explores the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in addressing the challenges that arise during the management of their start-ups and the creation of new ventures. The final section spotlights the methods and procedures by which entrepreneurial leaders can learn and hone their competencies in a team environment.

Each participant is assigned a pseudonym, and the names of their organisations are anonymised to ensure that the ethical criteria of the research were upheld in line with UWS ethical considerations (UWS, 2016). Extracts from participant comments regarding their experiences about challenges, competencies, and their development are provided throughout this chapter. All interviews are recorded and transcribed. In order to maintain anonymity, participants are referred to as numbers and alphabets, with numbers denoting the team number and alphabets denoting each member of the respective team.

This chapter addresses the following research questions and objectives.

5.1.1 Research Questions

- What are the main challenges faced by nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-based business incubator (UBIs) in Pakistan?
- What entrepreneurial leadership competencies do entrepreneurial leaders require in order to overcome these challenges and become successful?

- How can these competencies be developed in a team setting within the context of university-based business incubators in Pakistan?
- How do contextual factors influence the development of competencies for nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-business incubators, and how can these factors be integrated into a team-based competency model?

5.1.2 Research Objectives

- To identify the challenges of nascent entrepreneurial leaders working as team in university-based business incubator of Pakistan.
- To identify the competencies required for team in coping with the challenges of new venture creation.
- To explain the methods and processes through which entrepreneurial leaders can learn and develop competencies in a team level.
- To propose a team-based competency model for nascent entrepreneurial leaders working at university-based business incubators.

Figure 13 Composition of finding chapter

5.1.3 Overview of Findings, Generalisability, and Contributions to Knowledge

In this chapter aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurial leadership within team contexts, focusing on challenges, competencies, and development. This chapter also explore how contextual factors influence entrepreneurial leadership development within university-based business incubators (UBIs). Drawing on insights from aspiring entrepreneurial leaders leading start-ups at team UBIs, the chapter uncovers a nascent and unique perspective of entrepreneurial leadership in team setting.

5.1.3.1 Understanding Entrepreneurial Leadership Challenges in Team Context: Addressing Research Question One

The first section of the findings explores entrepreneurial leadership challenges in teams within UBIs. Challenges encompass a broad range of difficulties encountered by entrepreneurial leaders at personal, organisational, and contextual level. Addressing research question one, we seek to identify the main challenges faced by nascent entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs in Pakistan. These challenges not only impact personal performance but also hinder team growth and success in entrepreneurial pursuits. The details of these challenges are discussed in more detail in the forthcoming section. Personal challenges align with existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership. For example, challenges related to attitudes towards work, social responsibility, infrastructure, technology, and the role of government resonate with the findings of Clark (2020) and Harrison (2016).

Similarly, challenges related to business functions, family roles, societal culture, and access to entrepreneurial facilities are consistent with the findings of Bagheri and Pihie (2011) and Harrison (2016). This evidence illustrates the generalisability of the findings. Additionally, this research uncovers some unique perspectives that contribute significantly to the literature. For

instance, the perspectives of entrepreneurial leaders regarding the entrepreneurship process, the impact of government policies, societal culture, and the risk-averse behaviours of family members, as well as access to entrepreneurial facilities, emerged as key themes. These insights provide a novel perspective on entrepreneurial leadership research within the context of developing economies.

5.1.3.2 Exploring Entrepreneurial Leadership Competencies in Team Context: Addressing Research Question Two

In the subsequent section of the findings, Entrepreneurial leadership competencies, which encompass the knowledge, skills, and abilities deemed essential for navigating personal, functional, and contextual challenges while seizing entrepreneurial opportunities, are discussed (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Research question two focuses on identifying the entrepreneurial leadership competencies required for overcoming these challenges and achieving success. When participants were asked about the crucial competencies essential for entrepreneurial success, they highlighted several personal, business function, entrepreneurial, interpersonal, and conceptual competencies. These competencies are recognised as cornerstones for addressing personal and functional challenges and navigating the complexities of team dynamics. These competencies align with existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership and can be generalised to contexts with similar characteristics. For instance, self-competencies resonate with the findings of Bagheri et al. (2013) and Swiercz and Lydon (2002), who emphasised the importance of personal competencies for entrepreneurial leaders across developed and developing countries.

Similarly, entrepreneurial, interpersonal, and conceptual competencies are supported by literature such as Clark (2020) and Harrison et al. (2018). Moreover, the organising competencies, which emphasise the development of business functional knowledge and skills, are consistent with existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership (Bagheri et al., 2013;

Harrison et al., 2018; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). However, this research uncovers unique insights into entrepreneurial leadership competencies that have not been extensively covered in existing literature. For example, interpersonal competencies were deemed most crucial for women entrepreneurial leaders working in male-dominated teams, while self-confidence, communication, and risk-taking skills were highly emphasised among male entrepreneurial leaders. These findings suggest that the dynamics of entrepreneurial leadership competencies are complex, particularly from a gendered perspective, meriting further exploration.

5.1.3.3 Entrepreneurial Leadership Development in Team Context: Addressing Research Question Three

Research question three focuses on entrepreneurial leadership development in teams within the context of university-based business incubators in Pakistan. The insights obtained from entrepreneurial teams revealed various team-based learning strategies, including classroom-based learning, project-based learning, social learning, and self-regulated learning. These findings align with existing literature. For example, Roomi and Harrison (2011) and Bagheri and Pihie (2011) identified entrepreneurship courses as crucial for entrepreneurial leadership skill development, supporting our findings on classroom-based learning. Similarly, project-based learning, which emphasises practical role-taking and experiencing entrepreneurial activities in real-life scenarios, resonates with the assertions of Bagheri and Pihie (2011) and Okudan and Rzasa (2006), who argued that experiential learning is vital for entrepreneurial leadership development.

Social learning emerged as another facet of entrepreneurial leadership development, emphasising observation and social interaction as crucial for leadership development in teams. These findings are supported by existing literature, including Bagheri and Pihie (2011) and Kempster and Cope (2005). Furthermore, some unique insights emerged from the perspective of entrepreneurial leaders, highlighting the importance of self-regulated learning, online

learning, and entrepreneurial leadership learning through internships, boot camps, and entrepreneurial competitions. These assertions provide a unique perspective on entrepreneurial leadership learning that has not been captured in prior studies.

5.1.3.4 Examining the Influence of Contextual Factors on Entrepreneurial Leadership within Teams: Addressing Research Question Four

Research question four delves into how contextual factors influence the development of competencies for nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-business incubators and how these factors can be integrated into a team-based competency model. Insights from entrepreneurial leaders identified several personal, business functional, and contextual factors that hinder their growth and success in becoming established entrepreneurial leaders. They identified a broad range of personal difficulties, such as lack of knowledge and experience, as well as business functional challenges, including a lack of expertise in accounting, finance, marketing, and human resources.

Additionally, contextual challenges such as a lack of learning and development facilities, infrastructural limitations, and societal support were identified as key hindrances to entrepreneurial growth in the country. These challenges, including infrastructure deficits, technological limitations, and familial obstacles, align with the findings of Harrison (2016), who explored entrepreneurial leadership within the retail pharmacy sector of Nigeria. However, this research reveals some crucial contextual insights specific to the Pakistani context, such as security and accessibility challenges faced by business incubators, societal perception toward entrepreneurial endeavours, and the risk-averse behaviour of entrepreneurial leaders' families. Furthermore, issues such as the lack of transparent business registration policies were identified as significant barriers to entrepreneurial leadership development and entrepreneurial outcomes within the context of a developing economy. These insights highlight the multifaceted nature of contextual factors influencing entrepreneurial leadership development and underscore the

importance of integrating them into a comprehensive team-based competency model tailored to the unique challenges faced by nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-business incubators. These assertions could be generalised to other developing nations with similar socio-cultural dynamics. The discussion chapter provides a comprehensive analysis of the influence of contextual factors (addressing research question four) on entrepreneurial leadership, offering detailed insights into its impact. Following this examination, a competency-based model is presented, outlining strategies for effective entrepreneurial leadership development in teams.

5.2 Challenges Faced by Entrepreneurial Leaders in Running Team Start-Ups at UBIs

This section presents the findings of the challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders associated with business incubators. The findings presented in this section are consistent with research question one: *What are the main challenges faced by nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-based business incubators (UBIs) in Pakistan?* It also correlates with research objective one, i.e., *to identify the challenges of nascent entrepreneurial leaders working as teams in university-based business incubators in Pakistan.*

Entrepreneurial leaders were asked about the challenges they faced in leading start-ups as teams. The evidence of the interviews from entrepreneurial leaders associated with teams provided a range of perspectives on the difficulties, which are divided into three categories, as illustrated in Figure 14. The first portion addresses the personal challenges that entrepreneurial leaders faced which include: lack of qualification and experience, interpersonal, financial, entrepreneurial, and operational issues.

Table 25 presents an illustration of interview extracts pertaining to various challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders. Entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged that they had acquired a range of competencies to cope with these challenges. The next category of the challenges concerns problems with core business operations, referred to as business function challenges, such as managing marketing, human resources, as well as dealing with accounting and finance concerns of start-ups. The third section of the challenges presents contextual challenges that are related to numerous sociocultural, governmental, and BIC issues that limit the growth of entrepreneurial leadership in UBIs.

Figure 14 Composition of challenges

Table 25 Interview extracts of entrepreneurial leadership challenges at UBIs

Personal challenges	
Lack of qualification and experience	<i>“The first challenge I faced was about the irrelevant experience as I am bio scientist, and this is a tech-based start-up, so I did not have any exposure about how to write content or even write a blog. The first few months were challenging I had to write blogs so struggle with finding the keywords, SEO, and rank math.” (3B)</i>
Interpersonal issues	<i>“As a team there were challenges like communication gap, or I would like to call this a gender-based communication gap. We used to be with each other during university timings but after that every member left for where they were staying, as female and male members stayed in different hostels and females were not comfortable taking male members’ contact number so there were challenges to discuss various activities and tasks.” (17A)</i>
Entrepreneurial issues	<i>“When I applied in the business incubation centre, I didn’t know what it is basically, after getting in, I came to know what the incubation centre is and how it works.” (12A)</i>
Financial issues	<i>“Getting your business funded is one of the fundamental issues that all entrepreneurs face at individual level.” (17C)</i>
Operational issues	<i>“The first challenge we faced is time management. Now we must work more hours to develop networks and connections with other stakeholders. As we are only three members in team, and we must give a lot of time.” (14A)</i>
Business function challenges	
Accounting and Finance issues	<i>“Everyone can generate ideas, if we start, every idea is unique, and at the stage of implementation, the idea becomes useless or less viable. There are several reasons or lack of expertise behind this. Most of the entrepreneurs lack account management and financial skills to make accurate cost projections, and due to lack of business model flexibility, the initial idea gets changed at the time of implementation on the ground.” (11A)</i>
Marketing issues	<i>“Actually, there are some hurdles and problems because our main targeted customers are the farmer and we know that most of the farmers in our country are illiterate and it’s actually difficult for them to use an online web application on mobile phones or laptops, this is the kind of biggest challenge for us and in our start-up.” (2A)</i>
Human resource management issues	<i>“To be specific we need skilled workers, developers and computer system engineers as we are working on an online application and android application for farmers, so we need software engineers and developers.” (2A)</i>
Contextual challenges	
Lack of government support	<i>“Another issue is obtaining finances for the start-up. Only a few can get investment for their ventures, and those who are deprived, get demotivated. To avoid these issues, the government should support and promote young entrepreneurs. As practised in foreign countries, the government should provide subsidised loans to entrepreneurs to grow the entrepreneurial culture in the country.” (11B)</i>
Infrastructural constraints	<i>“Key factors that are affecting our entrepreneurial development are internet issues. If we are searching for some sort of jobs and contacting the clients, we mostly do these tasks on a remote basis, internet and electricity issues are the most shared challenges that are faced by entrepreneurs.” (1C)</i>
Societal challenges	<i>“There are some external issues in terms of pressure from family and friends. Most of the friends and family member chant negative comments about the project by saying it do not work, there is not market for such business ideas. These are some of the demotivating factors commonly observed with new start-ups.” (8A)</i>

5.2.1 Personal challenges

All Entrepreneurial leaders associated with 18 entrepreneurial teams acknowledged that overcoming personal challenges had been a key obstacle to their success as entrepreneurial leaders. These challenges are related to a lack of qualification and experience, as well as interpersonal, entrepreneurial, financial, and operational issues (see Figure 15). These are detailed as follows.

Figure 15 Composition of personal challenges

5.2.1.1 Lack of qualification and experience

Lack of qualification and experience concerns entrepreneurial leaders' educational backgrounds and previous entrepreneurial experience. 16 entrepreneurial leaders identified a lack of training, education, expertise, or previous job experience as their biggest obstacle to pursuing their entrepreneurial goals. They emphasised several underlying causes for this difficulty. For instance, when pursuing their degrees, most university graduates simply acquire theoretical knowledge and lack practical experience about entrepreneurship. Second, there are insufficient opportunities for recent graduates to develop their job-related skills through internships and industry placement. Thirdly, most entrepreneurial leaders lack relevant business training and experience. This is reflected in Entrepreneurial leader 3B's comments.

“The first challenge I faced was irrelevant experience as I am a bioscientist, and this is a tech-based start-up, so I did not have any exposure about how to write content or even write a blog. The first few months were challenging as I had to write blogs so struggle with finding the keywords, search engine optimisation SEO, and rank math.”

Because most start-ups are run by aspiring entrepreneurial leaders at business incubators, they mostly lack real-world business experience. Limited availability of industry placements and internships for aspiring entrepreneurial leaders during their degree programs was cited as a contributing factor to this challenge. Entrepreneurship, according to Entrepreneurial Leader 18A, is all about starting from nothing and creating an empire, and it can be particularly difficult for someone to succeed if they have no prior business experience. Limited business and entrepreneurship degree programs offered by colleges and universities contribute to another facet of the lack of business experience as argued by Entrepreneurial leader 11A. Opting for an entrepreneurial career from a markedly different background was acknowledged as a significant factor impeding the development of entrepreneurial leadership. Reflecting on this challenge, Entrepreneurial Leader 17A maintained:

“I personally faced many challenges, as it was a completely new experience, and everything was actually happening for the first time.”

5.2.1.2 Interpersonal issues

Interpersonal issues concern entrepreneurial leaders' ability to work in a dynamic team environment and to deal with interpersonal relationships. All entrepreneurial leaders recognised this difficulty and emphasised numerous interpersonal problems, including interacting with peers and finding one's own motivation and self-confidence. They identified several underlying interpersonal difficulties that contribute to team conflict and disagreement. Communication issues were recognised as a key obstacle for entrepreneurial leaders in teams.

They recognised the importance of various modes of communication abilities such as presentation, writing, and listening skills as catalysts for effective team performance. For Entrepreneurial leader 4A, effective communication skills are essential for entrepreneurial leaders to win over investors and forge bonds with their teams as well as with other start-ups. He maintained, “If you have excellent technical skills but weak communication skills, you can’t complete team assignments”, Due to communication hurdles, female team members in entrepreneurial teams have experienced significant challenges. This is partly due to lack of women participations in entrepreneurial pursuits and cultural constraints. When asked about communication problems, Entrepreneurial leader 17A narrated:

“As a team there were challenges like communication gap, or I would like to call this a gender-based communication gap. We used to be with each other during university timings but after that every member left for where they were staying, as female and male members stayed in different hostels and females were not comfortable taking male members’ contact number so there were challenges to discuss various activities and tasks.”

Lack of self-confidence and team-motivation among entrepreneurial leaders were a significant interpersonal challenge. Most emerging start-ups hire new people for various roles, thus boosting their confidence and motivation was recognised as a major concern for them. Increasing his team’s enthusiasm and self-confidence was the most difficult task for Entrepreneurial leader 10B because his employees were regularly disappointed. This can be attributed to the absence of prompt return on investment and lack of foresight. Another factor contributing to a lack of motivation is the perceived difficulty and lack of interest in engaging in specific tasks. Entrepreneurial leaders 7A and 7B, who run a translation start-up argued that it is difficult to keep employees engaged when performing a task like translation. Entrepreneurial leader 7A narrated:

“People’s attitude is a big challenge for me. You must motivate them all time.”

Building individual and team confidence was recognised as an essential component of successful teamwork. Entrepreneurial leaders agreed that increasing team confidence results in innovative ideas and increases team creativity. Lack of self-confidence, however, was cited as a major obstacle for pitching business ideas to investors, offering creative solutions to challenges in the workplace, and sustaining team engagement. Entrepreneurial leader 12B maintained his introverted nature and expressed difficulty in articulating his thoughts with assurance. These skills were obtained subsequent to his enrolment in the business incubator. Entrepreneurial leaders have emphasised the significance of the team leader's role in enhancing team confidence, motivation, and leadership skills, hence improving their interpersonal competencies. For Entrepreneurial leader 2D, in order to resolve interpersonal challenges within a team, entrepreneurs need to develop several abilities including boosting their team's motivation, confidence, dedication, and leadership skills. The recognition of enhancing team confidence and addressing communication barriers has been acknowledged as a catalyst for enhancing team performance, fostering greater creativity, and facilitating the exchange of novel ideas to effectively address complex business challenges working as a team. This is reflected from Entrepreneurial leader 17A's comments:

"I was an introvert or lacking confidence and was reluctant to share any statement or idea that immediately came to mind; I thought it would not work or was not helpful to be shared."

5.2.1.3 Entrepreneurial issues

A recurring theme emerged from entrepreneurial leaders' perspectives identified several entrepreneurial issues such as lack of entrepreneurial understanding, acute vision, risk-taking propensity, and lack of patience among entrepreneurial leaders. When asked about their level

of entrepreneurial awareness, the majority of entrepreneurial leaders confessed that they were not aware of the UBIs' opportunities for learning and training about entrepreneurship and leadership roles. While some entrepreneurial leaders claimed they had no idea about the activities and process of UBIs. As narrated by Entrepreneurial leader 12A:

“When I applied to the business incubation centre, I didn't know what it was basically. After getting in, I came to know what the centre was about and how it worked.”

Lack of vision and direction among entrepreneurial leaders has been acknowledged as a significant difficulty in executing entrepreneurial pursuits. The aforementioned obstacles might be ascribed to the nascent entrepreneurial culture at UBIs and insufficient entrepreneurial education and guidance. Entrepreneurial leader 12A cited that an entrepreneurial leader must have a clear idea and vision as their priority. Initiatives are destined to fail without a clear business plan, the ability to foresee the future, and an entrepreneurial vision. Entrepreneurial leader 3A supported this claim as follows:

“I also ran a project at individual level before, and I know how I misconceived things and did not consider the minor mistakes in my project. I was going in the wrong direction without a proper business plan.”

In Pakistan, where 60 percent of the population comprise young individuals with great potential for innovative business ideas; however, the absence of adequate support in terms of business incubation facilities, combined with a prevailing tendency toward risk aversion and a deficiency in leadership skills, poses a significant challenge to their entrepreneurial growth. For Entrepreneurial leader 12B, taking risks is an essential component of entrepreneurial success. The prevalence of choosing a government employment among graduate is mostly attributed to the absence of an entrepreneurial culture, limited access to resources at UBIs, and insufficient government backing for entrepreneurial endeavours. Drawing on risk-averse behaviour, Entrepreneurial leader 18B emphasised that people prefer working for the government to starting a new business.

“The next factor is risk. As in business, it’s all your investment, and if your business fails then your entire investment is gone. But if you are doing a job then you will only lose your job. The risk factor affects a lot of people.”

Lack of patience and long-term orientation have become another aspect of the entrepreneurial dilemma. The need of resilience and patience in relation to entrepreneurial outcomes has been widely acknowledged as a significant hurdle faced by aspiring entrepreneurial leaders. Entrepreneurial endeavours demand patience and resilience to navigate through setbacks, as they often take time to yield fruitful results. Entrepreneurial leader 11B stated, “if you want to pursue entrepreneurship, you should speak with your seniors, involve your family if you run into problems, and maintain pushing forward despite any setbacks.” The aspiring entrepreneurial leaders expressed significant concern about the need for rapid outcomes and an anticipation of a quick return on their investment. Consequently, most fresh graduates avoid pursuing entrepreneurial careers and prefer other career options. Arguing on entrepreneurial mindset, Entrepreneurial leader 4A confirmed:

“What I think is that start-ups need time and energy, and people think that this start-up will be converted into a multimillion-dollar business overnight, which is their short-sightedness.”

5.2.1.4 Financial issues

The financial challenges concern lack of financial backing from sources like the government, business incubators, family, and financial institutions. 20 entrepreneurial leaders contended that overcoming financial obstacles have been a significant challenge for them. Financial challenges manifest through inconsistent revenue streams, limited access to governmental aid,

and the challenges of sustaining household's expenses during entrepreneurial journey. As a student, Entrepreneurial leader 17A, faced financial challenges and could not sustain their start-up due to financial constraints. In response to this challenge, she opted to utilise her scholarship endowment fund to support their start-up. The slow progression of entrepreneurial culture within UBIs is attributed to the perception of insufficient government backing for emerging start-ups. Drawing on funding challenges, Entrepreneurial leader 17C explained; "getting your business funded is one of the fundamental issues that all entrepreneurs face at the individual level." Numerous entrepreneurial leaders stressed the importance of offering ongoing grants and stipends to support early-stage entrepreneurial leaders, ensuring their continued involvement, and facilitating the successful launch of their start-ups, as evidenced by the remarks of Entrepreneurial leader 1C:

"I want to mention some issues, for example, I was doing freelancing and earning some sort of money, there are many start-ups here which are just on their early stages, they don't have any sort of earning, so I guess, at this stage, entrepreneurs should be financially stable to work on their business ideas. During this stage individual should be given basic resources to launch their start-ups."

Entrepreneurial leaders have acknowledged that provision of regular grants and financial aid to prospective entrepreneurial leaders enables them to cultivate more inventive ideas and overcome financial burdens of their families. Balancing the financial demands of running a start-up with personal financial responsibilities can be daunting for entrepreneurial leaders, posing a significant challenge to their entrepreneurial journey. This is confirmed by the remarks of Entrepreneurial leader 1C, "We don't have any sort of income, so I guess, at this stage, entrepreneurs should be financially stable to work on their business ideas."

Due to the financial constraints described above, many entrepreneurial leaders are forced to seek funding from their personal sources, which can often present a significant obstacle to their entrepreneurial endeavours. Entrepreneurial leader 12A highlighted that arranging finances for conducting chemical tests and accessing laboratories posed a major barrier for him, with each test costing a substantial amount of 30 thousand PKR. These accounts provide insights into the financial hurdles encountered by entrepreneurial leaders, including the necessity of using personal funds and the substantial expenses associated with essential resources, which can hinder the seamless functioning and expansion of their start-ups. As highlighted by Entrepreneurial leader 17B:

“Another big problem was the beginning step to arrange the finance because we lack sufficient funds. Finding source of funding and working on the start-up simultaneously, is stressful.”

5.2.1.5 Operational issues

Entrepreneurial leaders identified several operational difficulties, such as time management, task management, and resource management, as significant impediments to fulfilling start-up responsibilities within a team setting. Operational challenges are linked to an entrepreneurial leader’s personal abilities, qualifications, and prior employment experiences. Given that responsibilities and functions within a team can be dynamic, effective time management and the capacity to prioritise multiple tasks simultaneously become essential. Entrepreneurial leader 14A agreed that achieving greater productivity in a shorter timeframe is a challenging endeavour:

“The first challenge we faced was time management. Now we must work more hours to develop networks and connections with other stakeholders. We are only three members in the team, and we must give a lot of time.”

The majority of entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs are currently enrolled as students while simultaneously overseeing their start-up ventures. Balancing academic coursework and start-up obligations is a notable challenge for them. Entrepreneurial leader 16A agreed that it can be difficult to balance start-up duties with academic obligations. They perceived that doing more tasks in less time might lower the quality of their work. Time management, according to Entrepreneurial leaders 17A and 17B, is crucial for achieving the most without sacrificing the calibre of the task.

Securing and handling business resources emerged as the primary operational challenge faced by entrepreneurial leaders. This challenge centres around the entrepreneurial leaders' ability to acquire business resources through various avenues. Entrepreneurial leaders expressed that their initial tasks often faced difficulties in execution due to a deficiency in task management skills. For instance, locating the proper equipment, tools, and other raw materials on time and within allocated budget was cited as a complex process. Entrepreneurial leader 1A stated that in order to perform multiple tasks in start-up, we need basic resources; more importantly, how you develop your capacity to obtain these resources, is challenging. One of the main problems that entrepreneurial leaders face, is the high cost and time involved in getting supplies from other locations, which is unaffordable for start-ups. Entrepreneurial leader 16A pointed out, “When I started, I lack resources because the region I belong to, is an underdeveloped area and the raw materials were not available in the local market. I used to get the materials from Karachi, which is 200 kilometres away from our town. So, finding the right material, managing orders, and their transportation were challenging for us.” Some of the tools and supplies must be imported since they are in short supply in the local marketplaces. The identification of

overseas suppliers, completion of necessary documents, and sourcing funding arrangements were identified as significant hurdles for entrepreneurial leaders. This is supported by Entrepreneurial leader 9B's comments:

"In our project, we need some machinery to treat the sewage water, which is highly costly and not available in the local market, thus we need a sponsor to fund us to import that machinery."

Furthermore, entrepreneurial leaders recognised difficulties in task management, particularly when it came to their ability to effectively oversee a multitude of responsibilities and administrative tasks within their start-ups. Given the limited number of team members at the start-up stage, the necessity to juggle multiple roles concurrently is vital for maintaining efficient operations, underscoring the importance of task management skills. His primary duties, according to Entrepreneurial leader 18A, include taking care of tourists, their lodging and food arrangements. Therefore, since he was the only person coordinating these chores, negotiating with cooks, and managing tourists' reservations, were some of the operational difficulties he encountered. In order to effectively navigate the growing market competition, it is imperative for individuals to cultivate adept time management skills and proficiently mobilise resources within the context of a start-up, contended Entrepreneurial leader 1C. Gaining task management skills is of great importance for entrepreneurial leaders who are simultaneously juggling academic commitments and other responsibilities in their start-ups. This is evident from Entrepreneurial leader 12A's comments:

"Initially, I faced difficulties finding the team and completing the tasks. You can say that in the beginning I experienced some management challenges because I was doing my studies, meeting with industries, and managing the start-up."

5.2.2 Business Function Challenges

Business function challenges are the constraints that entrepreneurial leaders encounter while managing essential start-up operations such as accounting and finance, human resource management, and marketing (see Figure 16). All 40 entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged this difficulty and its significance in relation to the growth and success of the start-ups. These are discussed further below.

Figure 16 Composition of business function challenges

5.2.2.1 Accounting and Finance issues

Accounting and finance issues are concerned with entrepreneurial leaders' ability to deal with finance and accounting matters of the start-ups. They identified several issues pertaining to accounting and finance including the preparation of financial proposals, the establishment of budgets and cost projections, and the maintenance of business records. The evidence of the interviews reveals that possessing accounting and finance expertise is indispensable for the success of start-ups. Without these skills, entrepreneurial leaders experienced imprecise cost estimations, resulting in unnecessary expenses for their start-ups. As described by Entrepreneurial leader 11A, "Everyone can generate ideas, when we start, every idea is unique, and at the stage of implementation, the idea becomes useless or less viable. There are several

explanations for this challenge. Most of the entrepreneurs lack account management and financial skills to make accurate cost projections, and due to lack of business model flexibility, the initial idea gets changed at the time of implementation on the ground.”

Lack of relevant training, qualifications, and certifications at UBIs were ascribed as key factors for entrepreneurial leaders accounting and finance difficulties. Entrepreneurial leader 5A experienced cost management and budgeting difficulties due to lack of training and support at UBI. Supporting the claim of 5A, Entrepreneurial leader 12A pointed out that they need to have a clear vision and the capacity to evaluate business ideas using statistical data. The lack of accounting and finance acumen among entrepreneurial leaders may be attributed to the omission of these academic disciplines from their degree curricula as several entrepreneurial leaders have graduated from different degree programmes. Entrepreneurial leader 2D claimed that because she was a new member of the team, she was given a task that was beyond her capacity, i.e., writing financial reports. Entrepreneurial leaders have underscored the need of training programmes that focus on the development of accounting and finance skills. Making financial projections and entering a new market require crucial accounting and finance skills, as confirmed by Entrepreneurial leader 18B:

“Nobody has offered tourism services in Gwadar district, so I had to calculate and estimate the packages. I had to collect information and make an estimation. How many people can join the adventurous venture?”

5.2.2.2 Human resource management issues

A dominant theme that emerged from the data highlighted human resource management issues within entrepreneurial teams. These problems include recruitment and team selection, performance assessment, leading and people management, and trust and privacy issues in teams. These are explained as below.

5.2.2.2.1 Recruitment and team selection

Recruitment and team selection challenges were highlighted as critical barriers affecting start-up operations. Entrepreneurial leaders have highlighted several hurdles related to recruitment and team selection. These obstacles include challenges in locating team members with the necessary skills and recruiting individuals who are suitable for fulfilling the team's objectives. They highlighted that a key hinderance to starting a business was the scarcity of skilled labour in the market. This difficulty was prominently noted in underdeveloped regions that suffer from a dearth of adequate educational institutions and firms capable of offering relevant employment experience to individuals. Due to the remote location of Gilgit (the city name), Entrepreneurial leader 2A stated that when he first posted job openings, he was unsure he would be able to attract skilled candidates. Several start-ups were founded based on complex ideas i.e., IT (information technology) related start-ups that necessitate the expertise of highly skilled technical personnel. However, recruiting such experts at the first stages of a start-up proved unattainable for emerging entrepreneurial leaders due to high cost. Consequently, hiring qualified IT staff was one of the fundamental challenges facing aspiring start-up leaders. Entrepreneurial leader 2A confirmed, "To be specific, we need skilled workers, developers, and computer system engineers as we are working on an online android application for farmers, so we need software engineers and developers."

Another problem contributing to the labour shortage in the workforce was linked to the insufficient practical experience among workers. This challenge is associated with the absence of hands-on exposure during degree programs. Most job candidates lack the necessary job skills. Referring to this difficulty, Entrepreneurial leader 11B stated that selecting the right team with the necessary talents is a time-consuming and challenging process. Likewise,

Entrepreneurial leader 11A maintained that hiring specialists is expensive and out of reach for start-ups. Citing a shortage of skilled labour, Entrepreneurial leader 7A asserted:

“The major challenge for me is good human resource. People say that there is no job in Pakistan, what I believe is that there is lack of skilled labour in Pakistan.”

5.2.2.2.2 Performance assessment

A dominant theme that emerged from the data was related to performance assessment issues for entrepreneurial leaders. Performance assessment challenges encompass effectively monitoring team performance and delivering positive feedback in both on-site and off-site work environments. This issue was further exacerbated due to COVID-19 and remote working. Entrepreneurial leaders highlighted that they had a difficult time forming a team and keeping track of their progress because of COVID-19. As confirmed by Entrepreneurial leader 1C, “There is not any particular platform where I can get some sort of confirmation about the job status of my team, and some members may not perform their duties as per the requirement remotely.” They encountered considerable challenges as a result of the intricate dynamics within teams and the considerable variation in individual perspectives and approaches. These problems not only have an impact on the performance of individuals, but also significantly affect the overall performance of the team. The COVID-19 outbreak and lockdown measures, according to Entrepreneurial leader 3A, made it difficult for their team to make physical contact with one another, which had a substantial impact on team performance. One of the main challenges identified by entrepreneurial leaders was the lack of a centralised platform for monitoring distant activities of their teams. Entrepreneurial leader 5A asserted that a significant obstacle to effective teamwork is guaranteeing accurate progress assessments and remotely monitoring team performance.

5.2.2.2.3 *Leading and people management*

The significance of leading and people management was acknowledged by all entrepreneurial leaders. Entrepreneurial leaders agreed that working on an entrepreneurial project as a team is a complicated phenomenon that involves several difficulties, including team engagement and motivation, managing disagreements, and maintaining effective communication. Entrepreneurial leaders emphasised the importance of team engagement and motivation in order to get optimal team performance. Entrepreneurial leader 7A confirmed, “In my team, the most challenging issue is dealing with the motivation of the staff. As we are doing difficult task of translation, they become demotivated often, which affects their work quality.” Furthermore, managing a diverse workforce necessitates robust interpersonal and leadership abilities.

Therefore, the importance of the team leader’s role is centred on skilfully managing different viewpoints and promoting cooperation throughout the entrepreneurial undertaking. For Entrepreneurial leader 10A, managing a diverse team with a range of viewpoints can be difficult, and a lack of cooperation and support among team members frequently leads to contradictory circumstances that undermine team performance. Continuous team support and clear communication between team members were recognised essential to preventing problems within the team. Although team members often have varying viewpoints on certain issues, Entrepreneurial Leader 9A maintains that conflicts within the team can be prevented by cultivating increased coordination and mutual comprehension. To avert conflicts, it is vital for team leaders to understand and acknowledge the different viewpoints. This is reflected in the comments of Entrepreneurial leader 17C:

“Personality conflict is one of the major challenges, as all individuals have their own preferences and personalities. This can lead to situations wherein team members tend to disagree with each other.”

5.2.2.2.4 *Trust and privacy issues*

Entrepreneurial leaders recognised building trust and protecting team privacy as key challenges at the team level. The privacy concerns might be ascribed to inadequate space inside UBIs for entrepreneurial teams, as well as a lack of trust among newly inducted team members. Entrepreneurial leaders 7A and 7B, who oversee a language translation start-up, claimed that the lack of dependable and trustworthy human resources is a prime factor causing trust and privacy deficits in the teams. Lack of space at UBIs was also acknowledged as a concern that impacts team privacy. Drawing on this difficulty, Entrepreneurial leader 1A confirmed, “There are some other related issues, such as the fact that we are all working at this incubation centre and all teams are using the same hall, which is congested, so it creates some privacy issues, particularly about your business idea.” Entrepreneurial leaders have indicated that they faced significant difficulties in securing trade secrets and other sensitive information due to a lack of trust and privacy within their teams. Referring to concerns over confidentiality and trust, Entrepreneurial leader 5A described:

“If I talk about the team, I faced challenges with coordination in the group. On every team, there are members who are against privacy. For example, some team members leaked confidential information about the company such as trainers’ details.”

5.2.2.3 **Marketing issues**

Marketing challenges were highlighted as a critical business function challenge. 20 entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged that they encountered a range of marketing-related challenges, including locating customers, gauging demand for a product or service, locating

marketing professionals, and pitching business ideas to investors. Despite having received some basic marketing trainings, several entrepreneurial leaders encountered difficulties in effectively addressing the marketing challenges faced by their start-ups. This difficulty can be linked to a lack of relevant educational background and work experience. Due to his vastly different educational background, entrepreneurial leader 5A remarked that managing marketing-related activities was a significant challenge. Further compounding the marketing challenges was the impact of COVID-19, which prohibited entrepreneurial leaders from conducting face-to-face consultations with customers. Entrepreneurial Leader 14B underscored that because of COVID-19, they encountered increased challenges in marketing their product, including difficulties in connecting with customers and clients, such as reaching out to schools to promote their initiative.

According to Entrepreneurial leader 15A, COVID-19 caused a significant interruption, forcing them to halt all product launch preparations, “When our work was just going to launch, it was stopped due to COVID-19.” Entrepreneurial leaders identified a related marketing challenge in persuading their target audience to embrace the use of their innovative products. For instance, Entrepreneurial leader 2A involved in an agricultural start-up expressed challenges in persuading farmers with limited literacy skills to adopt mobile applications and other digital technologies for marketing agricultural products, this can be confirmed from his comments below:

“Actually, there are some hurdles and problems because our main target customers are the farmer and we know that most of the farmers in our country are illiterate and it’s actually difficult for them to use an online web application on mobile phones or laptops, this is the kind of biggest challenge for us and in our start-up.”

The ability of entrepreneurial leaders to understand the process of product development, its marketing requirements, niche identification, and the ability to capture markets was recognised essential for entrepreneurial success. Emphasising the need for marketing skills, Entrepreneurial leader 14A postulated, “I think as entrepreneurs we need to learn some key skills such as marketing, product development, market assessment, and capturing skills.” To craft an effective marketing campaign, entrepreneurial leaders have acknowledged that communication skills rank among the most crucial elements. This not only helps in attracting valuable customers but also supports entrepreneurial leaders in their endeavours to persuade investors to support their start-ups. Entrepreneurial leader 2C claimed that one of the main obstacles to resolving marketing problems was entrepreneurial leader’s lack of effective communication skills. Drawing on the significance of communication skills, Entrepreneurial leader 18B narrated:

“The other skill would be communication skills to attract as many customers as possible. If you have good communication skills, you can keep your customer intact with you for a long time, and that customer will bring other customers to you. You can also know the demand of the customer.”

5.2.3 Contextual Challenges

Contextual challenges encompass a range of socio-cultural and environmental obstacles that have a dual effect on the development of entrepreneurial leadership and the entire entrepreneurial environment. These challenges were found to stem from various institutional, governmental, and societal factors, including infrastructural constraints, business incubators issues, societal challenges, and a lack of government support (Figure 16). Entrepreneurial

leaders pinpointed contextual challenges as significant impediments to entrepreneurial leadership development.

Figure 17 Composition of contextual challenges

5.2.3.1 Infrastructural Constraints

Infrastructural constraints pertain to the absence of physical, technological, and institutional infrastructures that hinder the development of entrepreneurial leadership. 11 entrepreneurial leaders cited inconsistent power supplies and internet connectivity problems as significant obstacles to the sustainable functioning of their start-ups. Even if these issues are addressed within UBIs, some start-ups are client-based or tech-based and run remotely; for these start-ups, inconsistent electricity and a poor internet connection were identified as major challenges. Entrepreneurial leader 1A emphasised, “Since we are a client-based business, our entire workload is dependent upon our clients. We require constant electricity and internet connectivity to contact our clients.” Entrepreneurial leader 16A, who is operating a bakery start-up, asserts that, “My ability to complete orders on time is frequently hampered by frequent electrical outages; my entire line of work is dependent on electricity.” Drawing infrastructural challenges, Entrepreneurial leader 1C commented:

“Key factors that are affecting entrepreneurial development are internet issues. If we are searching for some sort of job and contacting the clients, we mostly do these tasks

on a remote basis; internet and electricity issues are the most common challenges that are faced by entrepreneurs.”

5.2.3.2 Business incubator issues

The findings revealed a consistent theme relating to business incubators issues. These challenges are further divided into two subthemes that relate to UBIs’ accessibility and functionality. The issue of accessibility pertains to accessing the UBIs’ facilities without any interruption. On the other hand, functionality challenges concern the health of UBI and their operations, such as the availability of resources, training opportunities, and infrastructures. Entrepreneurial leaders underscored the significance of UBIs’ accessibility and functionality as crucial for launching successful start-up and entrepreneurial leadership development. The aforementioned themes are further elaborated in the subsequent section.

5.2.3.2.1 Accessibility of UBIs

The issue of accessibility concerns the ability of entrepreneurial leaders and stakeholders to access UBIs without encountering the limitations imposed by academic institutions. Entrepreneurial leaders and external stakeholders faced significant hurdles in fulfilling specific admission clearance requirement for gaining access to UBIs because these programs are under the jurisdiction of universities and are located on university campuses. UBIs accessibility issues are rooted to security concerns, as identified by entrepreneurial leaders. Entrepreneurial Leader 7A mentioned that the entry-exit procedures at UBIs mandated prior notification when someone wishes to visit a start-up. Entrepreneurial leader 3A, acknowledging 7A viewpoints commented, “There is only one issue, which is that if one of our clients suddenly wants to visit us, they cannot reach us directly. At first, they come to the main gate to seek permission, which

has a negative impact, especially on the start-ups.” Furthermore, along with tight admission requirements, rigid working hours were cited a major barrier for entrepreneurial leaders to carry on their start-up operations. This problem is primarily concerned with regional time zone constraints, which make it challenging for entrepreneurial leaders to engage with clients from other countries. Drawing on this challenge, Entrepreneurial leader 7A narrated, “Another issue is the timing. They have specific opening hours. We are working around the globe, and sometimes our client’s time differs from our local time.” Entrepreneurial leaders pursuing degree programmes often face significant challenges in managing their time effectively due to the restrictive nature of UBIs’ opening hours. These individuals encounter difficulties in balancing their academic commitments and entrepreneurial pursuits. This is reflected from the comments of Entrepreneurial leader 8A:

“The students are overburdened with academic work, and there are no flexible working hours for the students to get engaged in business incubation activities.”

5.2.3.2.2 *Functionality of UBIs*

A dominant theme that emerged from entrepreneurial leaders’ experiences highlights the functional issues of UBIs. The incubation culture in Pakistan is an emerging phenomenon, especially among newly established UBIs, which face substantial challenges fostering entrepreneurial leadership development due to limitations in both physical and human resources. 20 entrepreneurial leaders endorsed several obstacles regarding the health and functionality of UBIs, including a lack of resources, privacy and space, and networks issues. Lack of resources, training and mentorship opportunities were cited crucial factors affecting the growth of entrepreneurial leadership development. Entrepreneurial leader 8B concurred that the most crucial elements of entrepreneurial learning are mentoring and assistance. UBIs

provide some general training and mentoring in areas like marketing, IT, and other fields, but they don't deal with the specific needs of each start-up, Entrepreneurial leader 1B maintained. Since most of the incubators were recently established, they lack sufficient resources to facilitate fostering entrepreneurial leadership and new venture creation. This is evidenced from the comment of Entrepreneurial leader 13A:

“Unfortunately, the concept of incubation centre in Pakistan is not developed. If I share my own experience in Karachi, here you can only get a working space nothing else. For instance, if you are facing some issues, there is no proper guidance available to tell you how to resolve that issue. We have limited training opportunities available in the incubation centre.”

Space and privacy concerns were two significant obstacles faced by entrepreneurial leaders at UBIs. Entrepreneurial leaders attribute these challenges to lack of full-fledged infrastructures for UBIs and sufficient space to facilitate maximum incubates. Entrepreneurial leader 1A claims that due to crowded workspace, there are privacy concerns because most start-up share the same hall, which raises questions about the privacy of their business ideas and other trade secrets. Some start-ups have trouble adding more team members to handle their start-up roles due to a lack of available space. Entrepreneurial leader 1B agreed that they must maintain a small team size due to space constraints because they are unable to accommodate more than six people in one team. Entrepreneurial Leader 8A concurred that the primary challenges for entrepreneurial leaders revolve around the absence of a fully functional UBI and insufficient space for incubators:

“We have a major issue with incubation centres since they are not completely operational, they lack adequate room for incubates.”

The lack of networks and linkages between entrepreneurial leaders, industry, and other stakeholders were identified key concerns by entrepreneurial leaders. Entrepreneurial leaders

underscored UBIs to play a wider role than simply providing workspace; they should foster partnerships between start-ups to enable optimal learning and support, and they should connect entrepreneurial leaders with industry. Entrepreneurial leader 4A asserted that the role of UBIs should not be restricted to the provision of fundamental amenities but also include connecting aspiring entrepreneurial leaders with investors and mentors as well as forming partnerships with other incubators to promote maximum learning. Entrepreneurial leader 10A concluded that the IT sector can be a potential growth area for entrepreneurial leaders if backed by the government through proper connections and networking. These findings suggest that UBIs should assume a more substantial role, not only in meeting the training requirements of start-ups but also in cultivating their entrepreneurial networks with stakeholders. Reflecting on the significance of networking and learning, Entrepreneurial leader 5A postulated:

“Networking and connections between entrepreneurs and with other stakeholders are essential for early-stage entrepreneurial leaders to develop their ventures. There should be a platform where entrepreneurial leaders can share their issues and get advice from other entrepreneurial leaders.”

5.2.3.3 Societal challenges

Societal challenges refer to the common perception, attitudes, and behaviours of society towards entrepreneurship – that have a substantial impact on entrepreneurial leaders’ performance. 14 entrepreneurial leaders highlighted that they encountered obstacles in the form of discouraging and demotivating remarks from friends, family, and the public at some point throughout their entrepreneurial journey. The introduction of novel ideas, products, or services is often met with resistance from society. As acknowledged by Entrepreneurial leader 6B, “It is a major problem that our society does not encourage and support innovation. Young

entrepreneurs lack the support and motivation they require.” Promoting entrepreneurial endeavours among recent graduates was significantly impeded by adverse criticism received from social circles. It is extremely concerning for the growth of an entrepreneurial culture when individuals express discouragement towards start-up endeavours. Entrepreneurial leader 8A acknowledged this in his remarks:

“There are some external issues in terms of pressure from family and friends. Most of the friends and family members make negative comments about the project, saying it will not work and that there is no market for such business ideas. These are some of the demotivating factors commonly observed with new start-ups.”

In addition, when starting their businesses, entrepreneurial leaders experienced a lot of pressure from their families. The social pressures and criticism are attributed to several factors such as lack of prior entrepreneurial experience, family business backgrounds, and societal perception towards entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial leader 9B claimed that the idea of entrepreneurship has not taken off in Pakistan. As a result, he had trouble persuading his family to support his start-up idea. One of the factors linked to familial reluctance towards entrepreneurship can be ascribed to their preference for secure career paths, such as government employment. As endorsed by Entrepreneurial leader 13A:

“We mostly live in the large family system, and most of the time they are risk averse and prefer safe and secure professions as compared to taking risks and starting a new venture. So, convincing the family about starting any new venture is the basic challenge I have faced as an entrepreneur. Most of the family think about the financial aspects rather than social responsibilities.”

5.2.3.4 Lack of government support

Lack of government support was identified as a key barrier preventing entrepreneurial leaders from starting and maintaining their start-ups. There are various explanations for this difficulty. First, there is no mechanism in place to provide start-ups with finances they need through government subsidies or low-interest loans from concerned authorities or financial institutions. Second, there is a lack of enough government agencies dedicated to assisting entrepreneurial leaders with matters like funding, training, and business registration. Third, because most business incubators are university-run, they lack necessary resources to build extensive networks with the corporate sector and other governmental organisations to promote entrepreneurship. Due to lack of viable source of funding, entrepreneurial leaders had to find finances from their own sources, which can be challenging for aspiring entrepreneurial leaders.

Entrepreneurial leader 11B emphasised:

“Another issue is obtaining finances for the start-up. Only a few can get investment for their ventures, and those who are deprived, get demotivated. To avoid these issues, the government should support and promote young entrepreneurs. As practiced in foreign countries, the government should provide subsidised loans to entrepreneurs to grow the entrepreneurial culture in the country.”

Entrepreneurial leader 2C claimed that due to a lack of entrepreneurial culture and government support, entrepreneurs have failed to bring innovative business solutions to the market. Entrepreneurial leader 11C has expressed concerns with the current registration process for start-ups. According to him, this process lacks a coherent and transparent structure, particularly in relation to the registration and documentation procedures. Based on these points, one may contend that the government plays a crucial role in the provision of essential resources, including training, financial assistance, and support in the process of registering a start-up. The

provision of centralised services to emerging enterprises is crucial in fostering an entrepreneurial culture and cultivating the development of entrepreneurial leadership capabilities among prospective entrepreneurs in the nation.

5.3 Entrepreneurial Leadership Competencies

This section of the findings focuses on entrepreneurial leadership competencies that entrepreneurial leaders have identified as critical for starting, managing, and maintaining their start-ups in UBIs. The competencies of entrepreneurial leaders described in this section satisfy research question two: What entrepreneurial leadership competencies do entrepreneurial leaders require in order to overcome challenges and become successful? It is also consistent with research objective two: To identify the competencies required for the team to cope with the challenges of new venture creation. Five categories of competencies (as shown in Figure 18), namely, self-competencies, organising competencies, interpersonal competencies, entrepreneurial competencies, and conceptual competencies, were identified based on the themes that emerged from semi-structured interviews with 40 entrepreneurial leaders affiliated with 18 entrepreneurial teams. Interview extracts covering various dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership competencies are presented in Table 26.

Figure 18 Composition of entrepreneurial leadership competencies

Table 26 Interview extracts of entrepreneurial leadership competencies

Self-Competencies	
Self-management skills	<i>"I worked more than 12 hours work daily basis, after coming from incubation centre I did some work in my home. Then after my family restriction, I limited myself from 9 to 5 jobs and I assured them during family time I will not do anything. One of the things I learned while doing entrepreneurship in this incubation centre is time management." (9C)</i>
Self-confidence skills	<i>"They should believe in their self-potential and believe in their skills.... Finally, they should be confident to face the men and other stake holders." (16B)</i>
Self-motivation skills	<i>"Everyone is voluntarily motivated, and we are determined to achieve the specific tasks on the day and then go home." (11B)</i>
Self-development skills	<i>"In order to perform these tasks, we have to develop our capacities and obtain the resources which can only be provided by business incubation centres." (1C)</i>
Organising competencies	
Business function skills	<i>Accounting and finance skills "We need to learn basics of business and entrepreneurship. Particularly, we must learn accounting and finance knowledge to move our business further." (2C) Marketing skills "Other skills would be communication skills to attract as many customers as you can. If you have effective communication skills, then you can keep your customer intact with you for a long time and that customer will bring other customers to you. You can also be able to know the demand of the customer." (18B) HR management skills "One must have human resource management skills or team management skill. They should know which team member is right fit for which tasks. If you have these two skills, you can sustain otherwise won't get the desired results." (13A)</i>
Technical skills	<i>"If you are a graphic designer you have to know the guts of graphic designing and if you are working in account section, you need to have the knowledge of accountancy." (1A)</i>
Technological skills	<i>"We are in a technological era, so in this digital world, every entrepreneurial leader needs to learn basic IT skills to run their projects successfully." (1A)</i>
Interpersonal competencies	
Communication skills	<i>"The communication skills should be strong for individuals as we are entrepreneurs so we should be strong enough to communicate well to share what are our problems and how we can solve them." (1C)</i>
Networking and People Management skills	<i>People management skills "Managing team combined with best leadership skills bring out the most from employee." (17A) Team building skills "The team leader should have conflict management skills. Since there is no formal structure in the start-up to handle everything through a proper mechanism, therefore, the issues should be resolved by team member themselves through proper communication and engagement." (14B)</i>
Entrepreneurial competencies	
Opportunity identification	<i>"We should observe our surroundings to find what our issues are. The issues are our opportunities we need to pursue them." (14A)</i>

and exploitation skills	
Innovation and creativity skills	<i>".... In contrast, if you are working as team, you get motivation from your team member; they share ideas with each other because more minds bring out more perspectives and innovative ideas." (11A)</i>
Risk management skills	<i>"I was mentally prepared that all disruptions are temporary and can be tackled if we are ready to face them. Because it is business you sometimes get profit and make a loss as well." (13B)</i>
Conceptual Competencies	
Analytical skills	<i>"You must be a keen observer and attentive person. Practice is the key to analysis. To achieve the best of you doing a SWOT analysis is must. You should recognize your natural strengths and weaknesses, and work on weakness until they become strength." (17A)</i>
Problem solving skills	<i>"I guess at some point there is difference between team and individual skills because if we face a big problem working in team it is more easily resolved and the time is saved by dividing the problem or tasks." (1C)</i>
Business planning skills	<i>"We should be aware of systematic process of implementing something in the project; either it is related to finance, plan execution or assessment. The completion should not be focused we should consider each stage and emphasis on minimal viable product MVP." (4A)</i>
Envisioning skills	<i>"The product is gradual process it takes time. We need to pick a team that prioritise the cause above monetary benefits" (8A)</i>

5.3.1 Self-competencies

Self-competences, which are less concrete and non-functional capabilities of entrepreneurial leaders (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002), were the first to emerge from entrepreneurial leaders' perspectives. These competencies focus on the unique personal abilities of entrepreneurial leaders that impact the effectiveness of the entire team. In order to carry out the assigned tasks and responsibilities in teams, all entrepreneurial leaders associated with 18 start-ups agreed that they require some level of self-competencies to work effectively in a dynamic team environment. The self-competencies of entrepreneurial leaders can be classified into four categories (as shown in Figure 19): self-management, self-confidence, self-motivation, and self-development skills.

Figure 19 Composition of self-competencies

5.3.1.1 Self-management skills

Entrepreneurial leaders identified self-management skills as vital for entrepreneurial success. All entrepreneurial leaders concurred that to perform well in a dynamic team environment, they should possess self-management skills such as self-awareness, balancing work and life, and time management. For most entrepreneurial leaders, academic and entrepreneurial pursuits coexist, necessitating the development of excellent self-management and prioritisation abilities. Self-management skills are equally important for carrying out multiple

responsibilities and establishing interpersonal connections with team members. This ability was recognised essential in managing entrepreneurial leaders' business and personal-life obligations simultaneously. Entrepreneurial leader 17C stated that they must be self-aware in order to understand personality differences, assign duties, and avoid conflict situations. Early-stage entrepreneurial leaders encountered significant challenges in managing the obligations of their start-ups alongside their domestic duties, resulting in psychological distress and strained familial relationships. To avoid work-life stress, entrepreneurial leaders should maintain a work-life balance. Entrepreneurial leader 9C narrated:

“I worked more than 12 hours daily, and after coming from the incubation centre, I did some work at home. Then, after my family restriction, I limited myself to 9 to 5 jobs, and I assured them that during family time I would not do anything. One of the things I learned while doing entrepreneurship in this incubation centre is time management.”

Time management abilities were another aspect of self-management, and they were recognised as being crucial to entrepreneurial success. 11 entrepreneurial leaders stressed the critical importance of time management in their entrepreneurial endeavours. Entrepreneurial leader 9B emphasised that the most important skills to cultivate, in his opinion, are patience, commitment, and time management. The ability to effectively manage one's time is necessary for entrepreneurial leaders who want to succeed in today's growing competitive business environment. This ability enables entrepreneurial leaders to keep up with the latest technological developments and compete effectively with other businesses in their industry. Individuals who can manage their time effectively are able to improve the efficiency of their teams, which in turn leads to the growth of sustainable start-ups. Entrepreneurial leader 1C maintained, “It is essential to accomplish tasks promptly to remain competitive in the market.” The ability to successfully navigate complex team assignments requires good time management. Entrepreneurial leaders recognised carrying out multiple entrepreneurial

responsibilities within the allotted time are vital for entrepreneurial success, As argued by Entrepreneurial leader 17A:

“In less time with maximum speed, I felt the quality of my work was compromised, which could have been better if I could do better time management.”

5.3.1.2 Self-confidence skills

Entrepreneurial leaders highlighted self-confidence as a critical component of self-competencies – vital for promoting effective teamwork and team success. Entrepreneurial leaders may make courageous judgements while carrying out their assigned responsibilities when they have self-assurance and self-belief. They can also develop networks and interpersonal relationships both within team and with external stakeholders. Entrepreneurial leader 2D believed that they must be capable of instilling team confidence, motivation, commitment, and perseverance, as well as communication and leadership skills. The belief in one’s own capabilities has been found to boost an entrepreneurial leader’s sense of self-efficacy, which in turn leads to improved team performance, as argued by Entrepreneurial leader 18B, “Your success depends on how much you believe in yourself.” Self-confidence abilities were found to be most important for women entrepreneurial leaders working in a male-dominating teams. Entrepreneurial leader 16B asserted that working in a world where men predominate takes a strong level of self-belief and confidence for women entrepreneurial leaders:

“They should believe in their potentials and their skills. Finally, they should be confident to face the men and other stakeholder.”

5.3.1.3 Self-motivation skills

Self-motivation skills concern entrepreneurial leaders' ability of inner drive and determination in executing entrepreneurial pursuit in teams. The significance of self-motivation and passion for entrepreneurial endeavours was emphasised by 15 entrepreneurial leaders. Entrepreneurial leader 4A maintained that start-ups require time, effort, and inspiration, he stated, "People expect that this start-up will be converted into millions of dollars of business overnight, which is their short-sightedness." In order to have a prosperous career in entrepreneurship, the willingness to perform multiple roles and passion for learning are crucial. Entrepreneurial leader 11A believed that self-motivation enhances their capacity for self-improvement. Participating voluntarily in a variety of team assignments requires a passion for learning, which in turn improves both individual entrepreneurial capabilities and the overall performance of the team. The success of a team is fundamentally rooted in the motivation and voluntary commitment of its members. This is confirmed from the comments of Entrepreneurial leader 11B:

"Everyone is voluntarily motivated, and we are determined to achieve the specific tasks on the day and then go home."

5.3.1.4 Self-development skills

Self-development skills, in the context of entrepreneurial leadership, pertain to the capacity of entrepreneurial leaders to enhance their knowledge, competencies, and personal attributes actively and persistently. This ongoing effort is geared towards their valuable contributions to the team's objectives and overall success. Entrepreneurial leaders recognised self-development as an essential component of self-competencies. For Entrepreneurial leader 11A, personal

development—the ability to develop oneself—is paramount to entrepreneurial success. According to him, in order to be a successful entrepreneurial leader, they should receive training and upgrade their knowledge constantly. The primary emphasis in self-development is on identifying key deficiencies and working for their improvement. Entrepreneurial leader 18B confirmed that they need to be aware of their areas for growth and be motivated to learn more. For Entrepreneurial leader 1A, developing self-capabilities is vital for entrepreneurial success, he narrated:

“In order to perform these tasks, we have to develop our capacities and obtain the resources, which can only be provided by business incubators.”

5.3.2 Organising competencies

Along with self-competencies, organising competencies were identified as crucial for entrepreneurial success. Organising competencies cover entrepreneurial leaders’ ability to play a variety of roles within the functional domains of their start-ups (as shown in Figure 20). They include business function skills (finance, marketing, and human resource management), technological skills, and technical skills. All entrepreneurial leaders recognised the importance of organising competencies in the successful execution of their entrepreneurial endeavours.

Figure 20 Composition of organising competencies

5.3.2.1 Business function skills

Business function skills are the specialised knowledge, skills, and abilities that entrepreneurial leaders require to successfully carry out duties and obligations within a variety of functional areas of their start-ups (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). They recognised three key business function skills as being essential to their success: accounting and finance, marketing, and human resource management skills.

5.3.2.1.1 Accounting and Finance skills

Accounting and finance skills were recognised crucial business functional competencies to effectively accomplish responsibilities and tasks across functional domains of the start-ups (Swiercz & Lydon, 2002). Since entrepreneurial teams include members hailing from different educational backgrounds, learning the fundamentals of accounting and finance was recognised cornerstone to performing accounting and finance-related jobs within a start-up. Entrepreneurial leader 2A, who operates an agricultural start-up, confirmed that their team has trouble in organising their financial responsibilities because they lack business education and experience related to accounting and finance. Acquiring fundamental accounting and finance abilities empowers entrepreneurial leaders to evaluate their ongoing financial operations and determine project costs. This exercise is crucial for assessing the breakeven analysis and other expenses associated with the project in order to determine its viability prior to market launch.

For Entrepreneurial leader 4A, starting a business is a difficult and complicated process. They must understand and ensure that each phase of the business idea implementation is consistent with the minimum viable product (MVP) and align with related costs, this process necessitate

a deep understanding of accounting and finance. Without these skills, they may miscalculate project expenses, potentially adding extra financial pressure to their start-up's cost structure. Entrepreneurial leader 5A repeated that most start-ups fail because they ignore financial and cost restrictions. Entrepreneurial leader 2C, drawing on this skill, asserted, "We need to learn the basics of business and entrepreneurship. Particularly, we must learn accounting and finance knowledge to move our business further." For Entrepreneurial leader 11A, they must be proficient at negotiating the financial aspects of start-ups. Overly optimistic cost projections can lead to the start-up's failure:

"Most of the incubates lack account management and finance skills to make accurate cost projections, due to lack of business model flexibility, the initial idea may change at the time of implementation on ground."

5.3.2.1.2 Marketing skills

Marketing skills comprise knowledge and abilities that are fundamental for promoting entrepreneurial offerings to customers. This includes assessing both present and future demands for their offerings, as well as persuasively communicating the value of their products and services to potential customers, suppliers, and investors. 15 entrepreneurial leaders agreed that marketing skill is essential for start-up success. Finding customers, determining demand, and dealing with market competition were identified as key marketing challenges that necessitate proficient marketing skills. Entrepreneurial leader 2A maintained that finding customers and persuading the illiterate farmers about their product—i.e., e-farming—was a big challenge. It was particularly difficult to reach out to female clients in a remote location like Gilgit, so they had to hire female staff members to persuade the female target demographic. The comprehension of the demand and seasonal patterns of agricultural products poses a

significant challenge for emerging entrepreneurial leaders. In order to effectively sell their products to diverse stakeholders, they must refine their marketing abilities.

According to Entrepreneurial leader 2C, understanding seasonal product demand, crop timing, and market demand estimation are significant marketing issues that demand essential marketing skills. Furthermore, entrepreneurial leaders recognised the importance of acquiring fundamental marketing techniques, product development skills, and evaluation methods. Entrepreneurial leader 14A confirmed that they must hone marketing, product development, market assessment, and capturing skills. For effective marketing, profound communication skills are crucial, Entrepreneurial leader 18B narrated:

“Other skills would be communication skills to attract as many customers as possible. If you have effective communication skills, you can keep your customer intact with you for a long time, and that customer will bring other customers to you. You can also know the demand of the customer.”

5.3.2.1.3 Human Resource Management skills

Entrepreneurial leaders recognised human resource management as a critical business function skill to address HR difficulties, including performance evaluation, team engagement, and team support. They acknowledged that the capacity to effectively lead a heterogeneous team is critical for the success of a team-driven start-up. Entrepreneurial leader 11A maintained that the selection of the appropriate individual for the role underlies team performance and sustainability at the start-up level. Team leaders must be capable of assessing the skills and calibre of each member. Entrepreneurial leader 13A reaffirms this:

“One must have human resource management skills or team management skills. They should know which team member is right for which task. If you have these two skills, you can sustain; otherwise, you won’t get the desired results.”

Furthermore, Entrepreneurial leader 1C recognised the importance of performance evaluation for the success of teams: “There is not any particular platform where I can get some sort of confirmation about the job status of my team, and some members may not perform their duties as per the requirement remotely.” Team engagement and collaboration are the cornerstones of team success. According to Entrepreneurial leader 6A, team-level start-up require dedicated team management skills; the team leader must be able to engage the team members throughout the start-up process. Entrepreneurial leader 11B argued that for a team to succeed, team collaboration abilities must be developed and maintained.

Entrepreneurial leaders recognised team support as a key component of team success. A dependable and supportive team is essential for the success of an entrepreneurial venture, according to entrepreneurial leader 11B. Entrepreneurial leaders 12A and 3B concurred that constant team support was necessary in order to complete challenging tasks. “As a woman, I did not feel at ease working in a team where men predominated. However, as time went on, I noticed how supportive and cooperative my team members are,” confirmed by Entrepreneurial leader 2D. Working as a team is extremely difficult; in order to accomplish team goals, one requires the appropriate emotional support from teammates. Drawing on this, Entrepreneurial leader 17A stated:

“At some instances I felt like I ran out of ideas, and nothing was working, I cope with this challenge with persistent emotional support and backing from my team members.”

5.3.2.2 Technical skills

Entrepreneurial leaders identified technical skills as critical to the long-term viability and the success of their start-ups. Technical skills are the specialised knowledge and proficiency needed to carry out activities and make use of equipment and programmes in practical settings (Harrison, 2016). According to Entrepreneurial leader 6B's experience, a person can accomplish the required objectives more quickly if they are technically sound and have excellent communication abilities. The success of a start-up is attributed to the level of technical expertise of its team members. Entrepreneurial leader 14B maintained that individual's skills are determined by the role they play. For example, "I work in IT, I need to be technically adept." Nonetheless, one benefit of teamwork is the opportunity to perform a variety of responsibilities, thereby gaining experience in those areas. The data evidenced the importance of possessing technical skills in order to effectively accomplish complex tasks that require specific knowledge and abilities working as a team. For instance, Entrepreneurial leader 8B, who runs an educational start-up, confirmed that he struggled with creating and editing instructional videos. Technical skills are role-specific and must be developed in order to carry out start-up responsibilities effectively, as stated by Entrepreneurial leader 1A:

"If you are a graphic designer, you have to know the guts of graphic design, and if you are working in the accounting section, you need to have knowledge of accountancy."

5.3.2.3 Technological skills

Another crucial element of organising competencies was the capability of entrepreneurial leaders to effectively leverage technology and remain flexible in embracing technological advancements within their start-ups. This skill was recognised by all entrepreneurial leaders.

Entrepreneurial leader 10B agreed that aspiring entrepreneurs should explore IT sector as a possible growth area, stressing the relevance of IT for future enterprises. Some start-ups struggled to complete IT-related tasks due to a lack of IT capabilities. Entrepreneurial leader 2B confirmed that they have web development and mobile application development issues due to a scarcity of qualified coders and programmers. The start-up viability is attributed to proficient use of IT; this is confirmed by the remarks of Entrepreneurial leader 1A:

“We are in a technological era, so in this digital world, every entrepreneurial leader needs to learn basic IT skills to run their projects successfully.”

In addition to basic IT capabilities, several entrepreneurial leaders recognised technological adoption for the start-up success and competitiveness. Entrepreneurial leader 2B, operating an e-farming start-up, highlighted the importance of technological adaptation. They argued that leveraging technology is crucial for directly connecting farmers with consumers, thereby enhancing the benefits for both parties. Likewise, Entrepreneurial leader 12A, who criticised the excessive usage of plastic garbage, suggested using technology to create an environmentally friendly road carpeting:

“From my initial research, I learned that the existing companies are not using this technology for road carpeting. Even though there is no plastic waste management control in Pakistan, only 30 thousand tonnes of plastic are dumped daily.”

5.3.3 Interpersonal Competencies

Another key finding emerged from the data was the recognition of the significance of interpersonal competencies in entrepreneurial teams. Interpersonal competencies refer to the capacity of entrepreneurial leaders to comprehend the thoughts, feelings, and motivations of team members. This competence is supported by knowledge of human behaviour and group

dynamics (Harrison, 2016). The data demonstrates that communication skills and networking and managing people skills (as depicted in Figure 21) are the primary interpersonal competencies exhibited by entrepreneurial leaders.

Figure 21 Composition of interpersonal competencies

5.3.3.1 Communication skills

All entrepreneurial leaders affiliated with 18 entrepreneurial teams at business incubators agreed that effective verbal and written communication skills are crucial to leading entrepreneurial endeavours. Entrepreneurial leader 2C mentioned, “if you have a novel idea but you cannot explain it well, it’s pointless.” Communication skills are paramount for comprehending team roles and achieving team success. Entrepreneurial leader 14A stated that oral communication skills are catalysts for potential entrepreneurial leaders to perform multiple roles within the team. The significance of communication skills has been acknowledged in the context of establishing connections with stakeholders and addressing and resolving team difficulties, as confirmed by Entrepreneurial leader 1C, “communication skills should be strong, as we are entrepreneurs, so we should be strong enough to communicate well to share what our problems are and how we can solve them.”

In addition to verbal communication skills, entrepreneurial leaders also stressed the importance of written communication skills. An entrepreneur must be able to communicate well in writing in order to persuade stakeholders, as stressed by Entrepreneurial leader 11A, “entrepreneurs

need to develop their writing skills. Everything should be done in written form. If you present your idea to a sponsor, you should have facts and figures to convince the panel.” Furthermore, listening skills were identified as an important part of communication skills, which lead to improved team understanding, collaboration, and minimise team conflicts. This was confirmed by Entrepreneurial leader 9A as follows:

“There is still some disagreement on some points, but we are quite supportive. We listen to each other and respect the opinions of others. We assess everyone’s opinion and work on the idea that is most logical and viable.”

5.3.3.2 Networking and People Management skills

The networking and people management abilities of entrepreneurial leaders were cited as crucial interpersonal competencies. All entrepreneurial leaders emphasised the importance of networks and relationships between teams. In particular, they identified three fundamental networking and people management skills, which include: people management, team building, and networking skills. These are explained below.

5.3.3.2.1 People management skills

People management skill is concerned with leading people and ensuring teamwork to achieve common start-up objectives. All entrepreneurial leaders agreed that a leader’s capacity for motivating and steering a team towards organisational goals is essential for business success. For Entrepreneurial leader 6A, excellent team management is the solution to every problem that an entrepreneurial team face. According to him, successful entrepreneurial leaders must be able to keep their team members motivated in the venture. “To me, an entrepreneur is one

who can lead,” asserted Entrepreneurial leader 8B. Likewise, Entrepreneurial leader 17A agreed that effective leadership is necessary for teams to produce the best results, “Managing a team, combined with the best leadership skills, brings out the most from employees.” Going a step further, Entrepreneurial leader 4A believed that a team leader must have previous similar experience and leadership knowledge to lead a team effectively:

“The one who is leading must have some leadership knowledge and have undertaken similar projects before. There should be an assessment mechanism to identify the loopholes and train them accordingly.”

5.3.3.2.2 *Team-building skills*

All entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged that teamwork is a complicated social phenomenon and pointed out several difficulties in teams, including selecting the right team, handling conflicts, and establishing trust and privacy. These complexities necessitate the acquisition of essential team-building skills which include team selection, conflict management, teamwork, and team motivation skills. These are further discussed in subsequent sections.

Entrepreneurial leaders identified team selection skills as a crucial component of team success. They posited that for effective teamwork, a team leader must have tasks and skills assessment abilities to choose the right person for the right job, as reflected in the remarks of Entrepreneurial leader 1C, “In a team, it’s critical to understand each member’s primary area of expertise and tasks should be assigned in accordance with each member’s area of expertise.” Supporting the notion of Entrepreneurial leader 1C, Entrepreneurial leader 2A maintained that having team members with specialised field knowledge is crucial for team success, he narrated, “The major issues I face in leading this team include finding the specialist and expert human

resources to perform the key tasks. For instance, my start-up is related to agriculture, and I have some difficulties finding experts related to the agriculture field.” They data extracted from interviews also confirmed that choosing the right team requires leadership knowledge, analytical thinking, team engagement, and effective communication. As evidenced by Entrepreneurial leader 4A:

“The person in charge needs to have experience with similar initiatives and some leadership experience. To find the gaps and give them the necessary training, there should be an assessment procedure. The value of team building, and team communication abilities cannot be overstated”

Additionally, entrepreneurial leaders agreed that communication between team members is essential for effective teamwork and avoiding team conflicts. The performance of the entrepreneurial team suffers due communication hurdles and disagreement. Entrepreneurial leader 14B narrated, “The team leader should have conflict management skills. Since there is no formal structure in the start-up to handle everything through a proper mechanism, the issues should be resolved by the team members themselves through proper communication and engagement.”

According to Entrepreneurial leader 5A, conflicts frequently arise because of a lack of clear task structure and communication among team members; as a result, the success of the team depends heavily on the team leaders’ capacity to foster team understanding and clear task distribution. Entrepreneurial leader 15A supports the claim stated by 5A, arguing that a lack of trust and strained relationships among team members are significant factors affecting team performance. “I think trust is one of the basic things, because when we trust something or someone, then we have the potential to achieve everything and if there are conflicts and each one thinks differently, sure, each one should think differently but in a positive way; if there is

a negative conflict, then the goal can't be achieved.” Entrepreneurial leader 4A also argued that effective teamwork and communication are essential to obtaining the best results because emerging start-ups typically have new team members, which could potentially lead to trust deficit issues.

Another important theme that emerged in the context of a dynamic team was motivational skills. This skill relates to entrepreneurial leaders' capacity to inspire and engage their team members throughout an entrepreneurial endeavour. According to Entrepreneurial leader 6A, the viability of a business idea and receiving ongoing encouragement from team members are fundamental for a successful start-up. Entrepreneurial endeavours cannot be realised without motivation and devotion. Entrepreneurial leader 10B argued that the motivation and love for the work are fundamental components that every entrepreneurial endeavour. Aside from motivation, entrepreneurial vision is also crucial in keeping the team engaged and motivated, as highlighted by Entrepreneurial leader 12A:

“The first thing is the idea; the entrepreneur needs to have a clear idea and vision. There should be persistence and patience during the project from the starting until implementation. He should be motivated.”

5.3.3.2.3 *Networking skills*

Networking skills can be defined as the capacity of entrepreneurial leaders to establish enduring connections and interpersonal ties with teams and other stakeholders. This point of view contends that networking and long-term relationships between team members and other stakeholders are essential to the success of entrepreneurial leaders. Drawing on the significance of team connections, Entrepreneurial leader 11B explained that the active engagement,

participation, and networking abilities of entrepreneurial leaders with fellow entrepreneurs enable them to recognise their challenges and effectively address them. Networks are crucial in learning and developing entrepreneurial leadership skills; Entrepreneurial leader 4A emphasised, “I think connecting people and making networks is one of the crucial skills through which we can induce entrepreneurs towards learning.” Entrepreneurial leader 6B believed that networks are vital for sharing, accepting, and developing creative ideas and solving complex challenges in teams. The significance of entrepreneurial leadership platforms, such as business incubators, cannot be overstated in fostering enduring connections among entrepreneurial leaders and facilitating the successful establishment of new ventures. Entrepreneurial leader 5A reflected on the significance of networking as follows:

“Networking and connections between entrepreneurs and with other stakeholders are essential for early entrepreneurs to develop their ventures. There should be a platform where entrepreneurial leaders can share their issues and get advice from other entrepreneurial leaders.”

5.3.4 Entrepreneurial Competencies

One distinctive theme that emerged from entrepreneurial leaders’ responses was entrepreneurial competencies. The responses evidenced that entrepreneurial competencies such as innovation and creativity, opportunity identification and exploitation, and risk management skills (as shown in figure 22) are paramount to entrepreneurial success (Harrison, 2016). The importance of entrepreneurial competencies in creating a sustainable start-up was acknowledged by all 40 entrepreneurial leaders. The subsequent section provides a more comprehensive analysis of entrepreneurial competencies.

Figure 22 Composition of entrepreneurial competencies

5.3.4.1 Innovation and creativity skills

Innovation and creative skills refer to entrepreneurial leaders' capacity of introducing novel ideas, products, and services, as well as generating distinctive solutions to prevailing entrepreneurial obstacles within a team environment. 11 entrepreneurial leaders emphasised the importance of innovation and creativity for the success of start-ups. They referred entrepreneurship as providing unique solutions to existing problems in the business world. According to Entrepreneurial leader 4A, they should choose simple business ideas with potential for uniqueness rather than concentrating on complex and big ideas. In order to cope with competition, offering unique business solutions is what determines entrepreneurial success. Entrepreneurial leader 5A maintained, "We must compete and offer clients competitive products and services." Innovative thinking is crucial in identifying the limitations of existing business models and improving them with innovative ideas. Entrepreneurial leader 6A believed that in order to improve their ability to innovate, they need to examine their rivals critically. Likewise, Entrepreneurial leader 17A also attributed business uniqueness to innovative customer support; he stated, "Every business must have long-term consumer support to be successful, which can only be achieved by standing out at the top and doing better and different than the competitors." An essential component for the success of team start-ups involves the capacity to draw out numerous innovative ideas from the team members when

addressing a particular issue. This is a key benefit of working together as a team as confirmed by Entrepreneurial leader 11A:

“In contrast, if you are working as a team, you get motivation from your teammate; they share ideas with each other because more minds bring out more perspectives and innovative ideas.”

5.3.4.2 Opportunity identification and exploitation skills

The capacity to identify and capitalise on entrepreneurial opportunities has emerged as a vital entrepreneurial competence. This skill pertains to entrepreneurial leaders’ ability to identify, exploit, and leverage business opportunities within their environment. Every challenge has an opportunity dimension. Entrepreneurial leader 2C, upon reflecting on their experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic, contemplated the idea of providing virtual IT services to clients. Similarly, Entrepreneurial leader 4A, the owner of an IT start-up, formed his business concept by monitoring his surroundings because no one was providing IT services related to satellite channels at the time. For him, looking at people’s problems and providing a solution makes up a potential business idea:

“We should observe our surroundings to find what our issues are. The issues are our opportunities we need to pursue them.”

Entrepreneurial leader 9A observed that Quetta (the name of the city) is seriously lacking in drinking water, and experts predict that groundwater will reach to its lowest point in the next 8 to 10 years. She thus came up with a business proposal to save groundwater for future generations and proposed the idea of water retreatment for general use.

In addition, entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged opportunity exploitation as a crucial skill for entrepreneurial leaders. The goal of this skill is to take advantage of unexplored commercial

prospects. For instance, providing parents with information about their children's academic performance was a significant challenge. Entrepreneurial leader 14B converted this challenge into a business by developing a digital platform that connects parents with schools. Furthermore, Entrepreneurial leader 16A turned her hobby of creating cakes for special occasions for family members into a business by preparing cakes for clients at her house. Drawing on opportunity identification and exploitation skills, Entrepreneurial leader 14C confirmed:

“There are various challenges in school management, such as maintaining school records, assets, and accounts. There is software that addresses such issues. However, there was a gap between teacher and parent communication and interaction through online communication systems. So, our team found this as a business opportunity and developed our basic idea from this.”

Referring to opportunity identification and exploitation, entrepreneurial leaders recognised the role of UBIs in setting up meetings, locating experts, and widening the reach of aspiring entrepreneurial leaders to seize business opportunities. The identification of numerous entrepreneurial opportunities is one aspect of opportunity recognition and exploitation that is attributed to inter-team networks and UBIs' mentorship. In a research session, as per Entrepreneurial leader 9C, the UBI founders demonstrated keen interest in becoming a part of the business incubator after being introduced to their business idea and realising its economic potential. Consequently, they reached out to other start-ups within UBI and refined their business model.

5.3.4.3 Risk Management Skills

The ability of entrepreneurial leaders to manage risk was recognised as an essential aspect of entrepreneurial competencies. Nine entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged the significance of risk management in the beginning and ongoing stages of business development. Due to this extraordinary skill, entrepreneurial leaders can pursue business opportunities by taking a reasonable risk. According to Entrepreneurial leader 13A, most of us live in large families and people tend to be risk-averse and favour risk-free careers over taking a risk and starting a new business. Entrepreneurial leader 10A overcame his family's fear of taking risks by securing funds and demonstrating his accomplishment at UBI. Entrepreneurial leaders take courageous risks and think outside the box, which distinguishes them from ordinary individuals. Entrepreneurial leader 12A suggested that those who possess the capacity to envision a broader perspective and take well-considered risks can overcome their challenges and achieve success. Entrepreneurial leaders keep moving despite facing failure and setbacks. According to Entrepreneurial leader 11B, facing failures and taking the initial step toward a challenge are crucial entrepreneurial abilities. Additionally, Entrepreneurial leader 13B affirmed that he possessed the mental strength to endure setbacks and undertake risks throughout his entrepreneurial career:

“I was mentally prepared for the fact that all disruptions are temporary and can be tackled if we are ready to face them. Because it is business, you sometimes get profit and make a loss as well.”

5.3.5 Conceptual Competencies

Conceptual competencies focus on entrepreneurial leaders' capacity to resolve complex organisational problems (Harrison et al., 2018). All entrepreneurial leaders agreed that the conceptual competencies were crucial to their success as entrepreneurs. These abilities include analytical, problem-solving, envisioning, and business planning skills (see Figure 23).

Figure 23 Composition of conceptual competencies

5.3.5.1 Analytical skills

Analytical skills were frequently mentioned as being essential to the success of entrepreneurial leaders. They recognised the significance of conducting a strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) analysis, thinking objectively, making informed decisions, and assessing staff talents and job requirements. Entrepreneurial leader 11A underscored that analytical skills are crucial to critically analyse their business ideas and convince the panel of investors by presenting their idea based on facts. Entrepreneurial leader 4A confirmed that they must be able to create an evaluation system to identify the start-up's weaknesses. Analytical skills are not only important in assessing tasks and training needs of team members, but also crucial for entrepreneurial leaders to bring constant improvement to their business models to remain competitive. Entrepreneurial leader 9A believed that analytical skills were crucial for conducting research and personality assessments to determine the training needs of their team members. While Entrepreneurial leader 8B acknowledged that analytical skills enable early-

stage entrepreneurial leaders to enhance their business models, anticipate future events, and increase their adaptability. The significance of analytical skills is reflected from the comments of Entrepreneurial leader 17A:

“You must be a keen observer and an attentive person. Practice is the key to analysis. To achieve the best results, a SWOT analysis is a must. You should recognise your natural strengths and weaknesses and work on the weaknesses until they become strengths.”

5.3.5.2 Problem solving skills

Problem-solving skills were recognised as important conceptual competencies vital for overcoming the complex issues faced entrepreneurial leaders in new ventures formation. Entrepreneurial leaders must be capable to recognise business challenges and find their practical fixes. The findings emerged from the interviews acknowledged the significance of UBI’s training sessions in helping entrepreneurial leaders hone their problem-solving abilities. Entrepreneurial leaders 17A and 9A concurred that problem-solving capabilities underpinned by analytical thinking and research skills are necessary for developing cost-effective solutions to difficult business problems. For Entrepreneurial leader 2B, business incubators provide a variety of training programs to address ongoing start-up issues that subsequently enhance their problem-solving skills. Effective teamwork was recognised critical for achieving optimal team success and resolving complex start-up challenges, as narrated by Entrepreneurial leader 1C:

“I guess at some point there is a difference between team and individual skills because if we face a big problem working in a team, it is more easily resolved in teams, and time is saved by dividing the problem or tasks.”

5.3.5.3 Envisioning skills

The ability to envision the future and anticipate new possibilities was acknowledged as a significant conceptual competence. Entrepreneurial leaders emphasised that one of the secrets to their success is their ability to motivate and inspire their team and assist them comprehend the start-up's long-term goals. Entrepreneurial leader 12A and 4A mentioned that they must have a clear vision for the project and be aware of their target market. Entrepreneurial leaders distinguish themselves from ordinary individuals by exploring and seizing opportunities in everyday situations through their leadership qualities and prophetic insight, as described by Entrepreneurial leader 12B. They possess a strong drive to lead entrepreneurial activities and achieve success. Entrepreneurial leaders are goal-oriented individuals and have a deep enthusiasm for their pursuits. According to Entrepreneurial leader 12A, this ability enables them to lead entrepreneurial efforts amid uncertainties. Entrepreneurial leaders identified long-term thinking, perseverance, and patience as crucial envisioning skills – vital for successful teamwork. Entrepreneurial leaders produce societal benefits that transcend mere financial gains by introducing innovative products and services. Entrepreneurial leader 8A supports this claim as follows:

“The entrepreneurial process is gradual and takes time. We need to pick a team that prioritise the cause above monetary benefits.”

5.3.5.4 Business planning skills

Entrepreneurial leaders agreed that business development and planning skills were essential for a start-up's success. They agreed that, in order to achieve long-term success, they must promote team participation and engagement in business planning and execution. They

confirmed that UBIs play crucial roles in developing and refining their business plans that maximised their odds of success. Entrepreneurial leader 3A acknowledged that he had personally managed a commercial endeavour before. He realised how he had misunderstood business operations in his project after joining the business incubator programme. Participatory planning plays a pivotal role in the generation of creative business solutions. Entrepreneurial leader 6A emphasised that efficient and inclusive planning throughout the start-up process is essential for team success. Entrepreneurial leaders 18A and 18B, who are associated with a start-up in the private healthcare industry, acknowledged that despite having a potentially unique business concept, they were unable to capitalise on it without collaboration, planning, and teamwork. Entrepreneurial leaders follow a methodical approach to business planning and implementation which distinguishes them from ordinary entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial leader 4A maintained:

“We should be aware of the systematic process of implementing something in the project, whether it is related to finance, plan execution, or assessment. The completion should not be focused on; we should consider each stage and place emphasis on a minimally viable product MVP.”

5.4 Entrepreneurial Leadership Development

This section of the findings focuses on the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies to effectively cope with the challenges of their start-up while working as a team. This section satisfies research objective three: to explain the methods and processes through which entrepreneurial leaders can learn and develop competencies in a team level. It is also in line with research question three: How can these competencies be developed in a team setting within the context of university-business incubators in Pakistan? Entrepreneurial leaders

acknowledged that entrepreneurial leadership development is a complex learning process that supports a variety of learning styles, broadly divided into four categories (as shown in Figure 24): classroom-based learning, project-based learning, social learning, and self-regulated learning. The following section provides an in-depth illustration of these categories, accompanied by interview extracts (as shown in Table 27).

Figure 24 Composition of entrepreneurial leadership development

Table 27 Interview extracts of entrepreneurial leadership development

Classroom-based learning (CBL)	
Entrepreneurial leadership courses and diploma	<i>"I personally learned many things from my incubation manager, who helped me in refining my business idea and vision. They taught me how to patent my idea and legalise it."</i> (12A)
Training, Workshop, Seminars	<i>"University can enhance the capacities of students by organising various sessions and learning activities through training and mentorship from experts. They can bring role model who had achieved entrepreneurial success to motivate and inspire the nascent entrepreneurial leaders."</i> 8B
Project-based learning (PBL)	
Experiential Learning	<i>"I guess we can develop these skills by gaining experience by doing the things. I think we cannot develop the competencies by just reading the books or getting entrepreneurship courses. I think it will not work anymore. In entrepreneurial set up, doing things, or learning by doing matter most."</i> (1C)
Business plan competition	<i>"I remember there was a bio competition when I was in 5th semester. Our idea was the benefit of algae; we made a complete model of this and won the prize. From there, the incubation staffs have seen our idea and recommended for its materialisation. They took us on board to launch this business idea."</i> (9A)
Boot camps and Internship	<i>"The students should be given internship opportunities in multibillion project such as CPEC. This internship can boost up the skills of entrepreneurs."</i> (10A)
Social learning	
Observational learning	<i>"Here you can get a full-fledged business environment with all support. The environment broadens our minds and enhances our confidence skills. We can also enhance our innovativeness through looking at the competitors."</i> (6B)
Social Interaction	<i>"Because I know if I am stuck to some point on an individual level, some of my team members would help me in sorting it out. If the problem persists, I have a social circle and friends from similar backgrounds who can help me in sorting the problems."</i> (3A)
Self-Regulated Learning (SRL)	
Identifying self-learning needs	<i>"After coming here, we have seen people and learned about their success stories we got to know what can happen and how people are changing their lives through innovation. This as result, evokes our inner thirst for knowledge and learning, I understood what my strengths and weakness are and what areas need further improvement."</i> (9C)
Setting learning goals	<i>"During the start-up, the manger should give session and mange a policy team member follows this policy for example there are two team working in different works then each team have policy and rules and regulation which everyone should follow and make habit to develop this skill."</i> (5A)
Monitoring self-learning	<i>"Such as (member 'C') is the founder, but someone must be a content writer. Everyone must be mentally ready for the diverse nature of work. These are some sort of challenges. Initially, when you join, you are supposed to do certain tasks but at the end of the day, you will learn the skill of that task"</i> (2A)

5.4.1 Classroom-based Learning (CBL)

Classroom-based learning underpin traditional instructional design learning approach in which learners attend physical or online classrooms learning sessions and gain feedback about their progress. Entrepreneurial leaders emphasised that they have learned and developed entrepreneurial leadership competencies through various classroom-based learning techniques, as shown in Figure 25. These techniques include training, workshops, seminars, entrepreneurial leadership courses, and diplomas, which are explained in more detail in the following section.

Figure 25 Composition of classroom-based learning

5.4.1.1 Training, Workshops, Seminars

A dominant theme emerged from the responses of entrepreneurial leaders recognised the crucial role of trainings, workshops, and seminars in fostering entrepreneurial leadership knowledge and skills. The training programmes were facilitated by a diverse panel of experts and successful entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurial leaders 1A, 2B, 2C, 3A, 5A, 7A, 7B, and 8B acknowledged that by participating in various training programmes offered at UBIs, they significantly improved their entrepreneurial knowledge and skills. These training programmes focused on various functional areas such as marketing, accounting, and entrepreneurship –

were widely acknowledged crucial for fostering entrepreneurial leadership competencies to navigate the complexities of start-ups. Entrepreneurial leader 1A maintained that he learned marketing, accounting, management, and entrepreneurship from the training sessions offered by UBI. By providing training and mentorship opportunities, universities could improve their students' entrepreneurial skills and enhance their entrepreneurial success. Entrepreneurial leader 8B confirms:

“The university can enhance the capacities of students by organising various sessions and learning activities through training and mentorship offered by experts. They can bring a role model who has achieved entrepreneurial success to motivate and inspire nascent entrepreneurial leaders.”

However, despite the effectiveness of physical classroom learning strategies, few entrepreneurial leaders maintained that learning should not be restricted to certain parameters of classroom learning. Rather, flexible and online learning methods are both effective and practical for developing entrepreneurial leadership competencies in today's rapidly changing world. Entrepreneurial leader 10A confirmed, “I think in today's world everyone can develop their skills and capabilities because online sources are the best teachers. You can get easy resources and learning material across online websites free of costs. Even though our own instructors get help from the online resources, so it is easy and convenient for developing the competencies. We can learn from the courses offered by Google, Facebook, and other eLearning platforms.” Even though entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged the critical role that workshops and trainings play in helping entrepreneurial leaders build their skills, some entrepreneurial leaders raised concerns about the effectiveness of the training and the quality of the learning materials being offered at UBIs. Entrepreneurial leader 10B cited that rather than emphasising lengthy sessions, business incubators should concentrate on the effectiveness of training programmes while taking the needs of each participant into account. Some start-ups

need specialised trainings that are not offered in UBIs. Entrepreneurial leader 1A reflected on this as follows:

“For instance, in our project we got training on e-commerce business development and business registration. However, the incubation centre only provides some generic training that is essential for all entrepreneurial leaders. We need to learn some specific skills, such as graphic design, marketing, and digital marketing.”

5.4.1.2 Entrepreneurial leadership courses and diploma

The significance of entrepreneurial leadership courses and diploma programmes were recognised paramount for entrepreneurial success. Entrepreneurial leaders underscored the importance of incorporating a diverse range of degree programmes, short courses, and certificates that centre around entrepreneurship and leadership within higher education institutions. The primary aim was to facilitate the development of entrepreneurial leadership skills among aspiring entrepreneurial leaders. This view implies that entrepreneurial leaders can acquire new knowledge and skills by registering for entrepreneurial leadership courses and diploma programmes.

All entrepreneurial leaders agreed that attending these specialised courses is an effective way to develop entrepreneurial knowledge and skills. According to entrepreneurial leaders, participating in entrepreneurship courses and the acquisition of relevant certificates greatly increased their entrepreneurial competencies. Entrepreneurial leaders 8B, 12A, 13B, and 17C agreed that certifications, degrees, and short courses could contribute to the development of entrepreneurial leadership. Entrepreneurial leader 12A who completed a certificate in entrepreneurship, claimed that his participation in the programme has significantly improved his capabilities:

“I personally learned many things from my incubation manager who helped me refine my business idea and vision. They taught me how to patent my idea and legalise it.”

In addition to short courses and diplomas, some entrepreneurial leaders highlighted the importance of incorporating entrepreneurial education and offering degree programmes focused on entrepreneurial leadership development in universities and colleges. Entrepreneurial leader 6B stated that universities are the basis for learning and developing entrepreneurial leadership; however, most Pakistani universities lack the necessary resources and structures to support entrepreneurial leadership development programs. Due to a lack of entrepreneurial education, they face substantial obstacles in their practical entrepreneurial careers such as figuring out business registration processes, marketing channels, and documentation processes to launch successful start-ups.

For Entrepreneurial leader 8B, the absence of thorough documentation related to product and service offerings pose a serious challenge to early-stage entrepreneurial leaders. Consequently, they often struggle with acquiring guidance on business processes and ensuring the sustainability of their business models. In view of this, it was suggested that conducting expert-led seminars would be a prudent approach to equipping entrepreneurial leaders with the requisite skills. This is confirmed by the comments of Entrepreneurial leader 1C:

“We are unclear about the steps, where we need to initiate our idea and where we should get it registered. We have only worked on the basic idea and have recently discovered that there is a government platform that provides registration facilities.”

5.4.2 Project-based Learning (PBL)

Project-based learning exposes entrepreneurial leaders to real-world business scenarios through participation in real world business challenges. Contrary to traditional entrepreneurial leadership learning approaches, such as classroom-based learning, a project-based learning approach supported by various practical learning strategies was recognised crucial for fostering entrepreneurial knowledge and skills in teams. As shown in Figure 26 below, entrepreneurial leaders underscore the critical importance of various ‘learning by doing’ methods, including experiential learning, boot camps and internships, and business plan competitions in EL development. These are further discussed in the subsequent section.

Figure 26 Composition of project-based learning

5.4.2.1 Experiential Learning

Experiential learning refers to gaining entrepreneurial leadership competencies through direct experiences and active participation in entrepreneurial endeavours. Entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged that undertaking team assignments and practical start-up responsibilities was crucial for developing entrepreneurial leadership competencies. Entrepreneurial leader 5A acquired entrepreneurial skills gradually by taking on various start-up responsibilities. While Entrepreneurial leader 12A learned marketing skills by participating in university

entrepreneurial competitions. Entrepreneurial leader 9A and 9B asserted that developing entrepreneurial skills requires learning from mistakes, previous experiences, and self-evaluation. Entrepreneurial leaders predominantly emphasised learning by doing as a crucial method for acquiring entrepreneurial leadership competencies. For instance, Entrepreneurial leaders 3B noted that, being a bioscientist, he had several challenges in writing blogs, finding keywords, and operating search engine optimisation (SEO) techniques. He learned these skills by executing practical roles within the team. Entrepreneurial leader 10A emphasised the following when criticising conventional entrepreneurial leadership learning strategies, “There should be practical exposure for the learner, and the courses taught in the universities should have a more practical outlook, as practiced developed nations such as Japan and Korea. In Pakistan, we usually teach theoretical knowledge to students that lacks practical exposure.”

Reflecting on the significance of practical experience, Entrepreneurial leader 10A asserted that their previous entrepreneurial experience on other projects, such as e-construction, led to the successful execution of their current start-up, i.e., e-vision. Drawing on the significance of experiential learning, Entrepreneurial leader 1C narrated:

“I guess we can develop these skills by gaining experience through practical application. We cannot develop these competencies by just reading books or taking entrepreneurship courses. I believe this approach is no longer effective. In an entrepreneurial setting, the importance of hands-on experience and learning by doing matters the most.”

5.4.2.2 Bootcamps and internships

Bootcamps are educational programmes that are characterised by their rigorous and short-term nature. These programs are specifically designed to provide aspiring entrepreneurial leaders with practical skills, knowledge, and hands-on experience. The curriculum of bootcamps is condensed, allowing participants to acquire the necessary expertise within a limited timeframe. While internships in the realm of entrepreneurial learning encompass the participation of aspiring entrepreneurial leaders in practical endeavours across business settings that fosters entrepreneurial activities. These programmes provide nascent entrepreneurs to apply theoretical knowledge into real-world scenarios in a practical manner, acquire insights from seasoned entrepreneurs, and make meaningful contributions to the functioning of a start-up.

Entrepreneurial leaders 8B, 8A, 10A, and 12B emphasised that boot camps and internships had a substantial impact on the development of their leadership skills. For Entrepreneurial Leader 12A, boot camps enable him to develop practical business experience and knowledge in conjunction with their academic coursework and degree programme. Furthermore, this initiative offered aspiring entrepreneurial leaders the opportunity to connect with established leaders in the field of entrepreneurship, as well as a diverse range of professionals. Entrepreneurial leader 8A had a similar viewpoint, suggesting that boot camps are an excellent way to inspire the young generation to pursue business as a career path. Conversely, several entrepreneurial leaders place significant emphasis on the importance of internships in augmenting their entrepreneurial capacities. Entrepreneurial leader 7B, drawing on the significance of internships confirmed that UBIs should give internship opportunities to graduates by allowing the companies to open their camp offices at UBIs. This, as a result,

enhances industry linkages with the university and incubation centre. Entrepreneurial leader 10A emphasised internship as follows:

“The students should be given internship opportunities in multibillion-dollar projects such as China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). Such internship opportunities can boost the skills of entrepreneurs.”

5.4.2.3 Business plan competition

A business plan competition refers to a structured event or contest enabling aspiring entrepreneurial leaders showcase their business concepts and strategies to a panel of evaluators or potential financiers. Participants commonly engage in the process of developing a complete business plan, which serves as a detailed document outlining their business concept, market analysis, financial predictions, and overall strategic approach. These competitions provide entrepreneurial leaders with the opportunity to use their theoretical knowledge in practical business circumstances.

Entrepreneurial leaders 9A, 17A, and 18A emphasised that by participating in real-world situations, such as business plan competitions, they can develop various business-related competencies by undertaking practical business roles. Entrepreneurial leader 17A, who runs an event management start-up, mentioned how entering a business plan competition at their university helped them refine their original business idea and convert it into a start-up. Entrepreneurial 9A confirmed how business plan competition enable them to launch a start-up:

“I remember there was a bio competition when I was in the 5th semester. Our idea was the benefit of algae; we made a complete model of it and won the prize. From there, the incubation staff has seen our idea and recommended its materialisation. They took us on board to launch this business idea.”

5.4.3 Social Learning

The concept of social learning within a business incubator pertains to the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and insights by entrepreneurial leaders through their engagement in interactive, collaborative, and observational learning activities within the social milieu of the incubator. Entrepreneurial leaders can enhance their entrepreneurial competencies through the use of peer-to-peer learning, networking, and the exchange of experiences within entrepreneurial teams. As shown in Figure 27 below, entrepreneurial leaders endorsed observational and social interaction as two crucial methods of social learning that play a vital role in entrepreneurial leadership development in teams.

Figure 27 Composition of social learning

5.4.3.1 Observational learning

Observational learning pertains to the cognitive process through which entrepreneurial leaders acquire new knowledge, skills, behaviours, and attitudes by actively observing and replicating the actions, behaviours, or experiences of others accomplished entrepreneurial leaders within UBIs and their surroundings. The shared workspaces offered by business incubators create an ideal learning environment. Several entrepreneurial leaders confirmed that working in a shared

environment enables them to observe and learn from the experiences of other entrepreneurial leaders at UBIs. According to Entrepreneurial leader 17B, the environment is important in the formation of entrepreneurial leadership competencies. Acknowledging Entrepreneurial leader 17B's remarks, Entrepreneurial leader 6B also confirmed the significant role of a learning atmosphere in facilitating entrepreneurial leadership development at UBIs:

“Here you can get a full-fledged business environment with all the support you need. The environment broadens our minds and enhances our confidence skills. We can also enhance our innovativeness by looking at our competitors.”

Nine entrepreneurial leaders working in various teams have affirmed that peer learning is the key to improving their networking, confidence, problem-solving abilities, and other business function skills, such as marketing, finance, and IT capabilities. For Entrepreneurial leader 2D, he learned the core business skills required for his position through education, practical experience, and observing other entrepreneurs at UBI. In addition to personal observation, gaining feedback from experienced entrepreneurial leaders was acknowledged as an indispensable component of social learning inside teams.

Entrepreneurial leader 6A believed that seeking feedback and help from senior entrepreneurial leaders helped him learn various entrepreneurial leadership competencies, he maintained; “When you start meeting with people, the skills they teach you start to develop. Seniors who have experienced this process, can also help develop various entrepreneurial skills.” Since the types of start-ups at UBIs vary greatly, they are not direct competitors and can benefit from one another's experiences. Entrepreneurial leader 9C confirmed this in the quote below:

“Yes, there are many start-ups at this incubation centre, and they come from various sectors including IT, biotechnology, engineering, and design. There is a strong sense of connection among the incubates and they actively assist one another. This

collaborative spirit fosters learning; since each start-up is unique, we don't view each other as direct competitors. As a result, we receive valuable help and guidance from fellow entrepreneurs. Meeting with other incubates has also opened up numerous channels for our business development. For instance, we have connected with experts in specific domains who were instrumental in introducing us to the right people. Furthermore, we provide support to other incubates in matters related to research, as we have gained expertise in this field.”

5.4.3.2 Social Interaction

Social interaction in the context of entrepreneurial leadership development pertains to the deliberate act of actively engaging and interacting with fellow members of a team. Entrepreneurial leaders have the opportunity to refine their entrepreneurial knowledge and skills by engaging in various activities such as learning from peers, establishing entrepreneurial networks, and exchanging ideas and feedback with fellow entrepreneurs. According to eight entrepreneurial leaders, an important aspect of developing entrepreneurial leadership is asking for assistance from those in the neighbourhood, industry professionals, and friends. Social interaction is crucial in developing entrepreneurial networks and connection.

According to Entrepreneurial leader 5B, for early-stage entrepreneurial leaders to grow their start-ups, networking and connections with other stakeholders are crucial. Learning entrepreneurial leadership competencies from internal sources such as UBIs and other external experts was cited as crucial for entrepreneurial leadership development. Entrepreneurial leader 11B believed that team engagement and networking helped them recognise and handle entrepreneurial problems collectively that consequently kept them motivated to remain competitive. These networks provide opportunities for entrepreneurial leaders to become acquainted with many facets of start-up operations and help the development of skills in those

specific areas. Entrepreneurial leader 3A argued that he gained knowledge about various aspects of starting a business from his social circles:

“I know that if I ever encounter an issue at individual level, some of my team members would be there to help me resolve it. If the problem persists, I also have a social circle and friends from similar backgrounds who can assist me in finding a solution.”

5.4.4 Self-Regulated Learning (SRL)

Self-regulated learning (SRL) was identified as an important method for developing entrepreneurial leadership competencies. SRL refers to the capacity of entrepreneurial leaders to comprehend and manage their learning needs in a particular environment by themselves. Eight entrepreneurial leaders confirmed that they believe in self-regulated learning strategies in the development of entrepreneurial leadership which involve identifying self-learning needs, setting learning goals, and monitoring self-learning in a dynamic team environment (see Figure 28).

Figure 28 Composition of self-regulated learning

5.4.4.1 Identifying self-learning needs

The process of identifying self-learning requirements involves evaluating and acknowledging the specific areas in which entrepreneurial leaders requires additional information, skills, or personal growth. The process entails engaging in introspective analysis of entrepreneurial leaders' existing competencies, objectives, and the areas of further improvement. The objective of determining self-learning needs is to ascertain the particular areas or subjects that entrepreneurial leaders need to enhance while executing their entrepreneurial pursuit in teams.

Entrepreneurial leaders stressed the significance of identifying self-learning needs and discovering one's own learning style. Most entrepreneurial leaders at UBIs consist of adult learners who are enrolled or recently graduated as aspiring entrepreneurial leaders, known for their quick learning ability. They are adept at identifying their learning needs, setting learning goals, and monitoring their progress. Entrepreneurial leader 1A believes that the world is full of learning opportunities; all one must do is get out of one's comfort zone. They acknowledged the existence of several continuous learning prospects within UBIs environment. Consequently, the adoption of a tailored learning approach becomes crucial for achieving entrepreneurial success in UBI contexts. Entrepreneurial leader 1C maintained that there are various events and learning opportunities occurring at UBIs and that by participating in these events, we can identify our weak areas and improve them. The SRL process includes planning, observing, and evaluating the entrepreneurial learning experience through introspection.

Entrepreneurial leaders reported that participating in business incubators increased their desire to learn and their ability to recognise their weaknesses by observing others. Entrepreneurial leader 9C confirmed:

“After coming here, we've had the opportunity to meet people and hear about their success stories. This experience has shown us what is possible and how individuals are transforming their lives through innovation. It has ignited our thirst for knowledge and learning, allowing us to gain a deeper understanding of our strengths, weaknesses, and the areas that require further improvement.”

5.4.4.2 Setting learning goals

The process of setting learning goals in the realm of entrepreneurial leadership development involves specifying clear, measurable, and achievable goals related to the acquisition of new knowledge, skills, and experiences. These objectives aim to improve entrepreneurial leaders' effectiveness and success in teams. Working as a team is a complex process, similarly, team learning differs significantly from individual learning. Entrepreneurial leaders emphasised their ability to set learning goals and align their skills with specific tasks of their respective start-ups. Entrepreneurial leader 3B confirmed, “we must be aware of what is expected of us and how we can develop job-related skills.” During COVID-19, for example, he learned various IT skills such as WordPress and search engine optimisation (SEO) through online platforms.

Entrepreneurial leaders have demonstrated that the accomplishment of team success is a critical factor in achieving effective learning goals for team members. It also enhances their motivation to acquire new knowledge and skills. Entrepreneurial leader 4A maintained that participatory learning in teams is critical for team success and team members must motivate and encourage one another to learn. The incorporation of planning into the learning process is crucial in enabling self-assessment and the adoption of a customised learning approach to foster the personal development of entrepreneurial leaders. Entrepreneurial leader 9A believed that planning is important in learning and that one should conduct a personality assessment test to

identify one's deficiencies and work on them. Developing team policies and synchronising their skills, according to Entrepreneurial leader 5A, are critical to team learning:

“During the start-up phase, the manager should conduct a session and oversee a policy for team members to follow. For instance, if there are two teams working on different projects, each team should have its own set of policies and rules that everyone must adhere to and develop as a habit to enhance their skills.”

5.4.4.3 Monitoring self-learning

The notion of monitoring self-learning in entrepreneurial leadership development refers to the ongoing process of evaluating, assessing, and tracking the progress and growth of entrepreneurial leaders in acquiring knowledge, skills, and experiences relevant to enhancing their effectiveness and achieving success. This process enables entrepreneurial leaders to evaluate self-learning goals and keep track of their progress to determine their alignment with team objectives. Entrepreneurial leaders agreed that their ability to monitor and track self-learning growth is critical to their success as entrepreneurs. The key prerequisites for a project, according to Entrepreneurial leader 10B, are learning motivation and a person's love for executing a given work. Entrepreneurial leader 18B claims that working in a start-up is a difficult process. As a result, encouraging team members to believe in their roles and duties will assist them in improving existing skills, learning new ones, and tracking their progress.

Entrepreneurial leader 5A concurred that while managers can establish rules and regulations, adhering to them and accomplishing intended goals rely on team members developing a habit of self-regulated learning. They emphasised that having a clear vision and defined learning objectives is paramount for entrepreneurial success. Entrepreneurial leader 17C underscored

that having a specific aim should serve as the starting point for all learning and skill development. According to him, self-regulated learning enables them to set learning goals, do research, act, and acquire knowledge from others. The roles and responsibilities in teams are dynamic; to perform well in teams, one must learn multiple skills. This is confirmed by the comments of Entrepreneurial leader 2A:

“Such as member (C) is the founder, but someone must be a content writer. Everyone must be mentally ready for the diverse nature of work. These are some sort of challenges. Initially, when you join, you are supposed to do certain tasks, but at the end of the day, you will learn the skill of that task.”

5.5 Summary

This chapter discussed the results of 40 interviews with entrepreneurial leaders from 18 start-ups. The aim of the study was to investigate the experiences of leaders within university-based business incubators, with a specific focus on the challenges they encounter, their competencies, and the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies within those contexts. Three research questions were addressed in this chapter: what are the challenges faced by nascent entrepreneurial leaders at university-based incubators? What entrepreneurial leadership competencies do entrepreneurial leaders require in order to overcome these challenges and become successful? How can these competencies be developed in a team setting within the context of university-business incubators in Pakistan? Entrepreneurial leaders confirmed that they faced a variety of challenges, including personal, business function, and contextual challenges. They also identified several competencies to cope with these challenges, including self-competencies, organising competencies, interpersonal competencies, entrepreneurial competencies, and conceptual competencies.

Additionally, the findings reported in this chapter confirmed that entrepreneurial leadership development is a complex social process. Entrepreneurial leaders can learn their entrepreneurial competencies by adopting a variety of team-based learning strategies, such as classroom-based learning, project-based learning, social learning, and self-regulated learning. The next chapter analyse findings in relation to existing literature on the topic. It compares the findings of the study with previous studies on entrepreneurial leadership, entrepreneurial leadership competencies and development, and business incubators.

6 Discussion

6.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an in-depth examination and evaluation of the study's findings regarding entrepreneurial leadership in dynamic team settings in the context of university-based business incubators. The chapter also triangulates the research findings in relation to existing literature. It addresses three research questions on the challenges, competencies, and development of entrepreneurial leadership. Furthermore, the chapter proposes an empirical model that examines the development of entrepreneurial leadership within teams.

This chapter is structured as follows: The chapter begins by discussing the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders face, then examines the required competencies in the following section. The next section presents a team-based competency model for developing entrepreneurial leadership in teams. The chapter concludes by summarising the challenges, competencies, and development of entrepreneurial leadership in a dynamic team context.

6.2 Challenges of entrepreneurial leaders

This study aimed to explore the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in dynamic team settings at university-based business incubators. Leading an entrepreneurial project involves many complexities and unique challenges; therefore, entrepreneurial leaders must possess specific competencies to overcome these obstacles and achieve their goals (Anderson and Jack, 2008; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Gupta et al., 2004; Harrison et al., 2018; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). The findings revealed that entrepreneurial leaders at UBIs face a variety of challenges, which are classified into three broad categories: personal challenges, business function challenges, and contextual challenges. These challenges are interconnected

and significantly affect the entire team performance. For example, personal challenges such as self-management, creativity, and an understanding of the entrepreneurship process can affect the team's ability to identify and capitalise on entrepreneurial opportunities (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a). The subsequent discourse presents a comprehensive exposition of the aforementioned challenges and their pertinence to the extant body of literature.

6.2.1 Personal Challenges

All entrepreneurial leaders stated that they faced personal obstacles in their journey as entrepreneurial leaders. These obstacles included a lack of education and experience, as well as interpersonal, entrepreneurial, financial, and operational difficulties that hindered their progress in establishing and leading their businesses within teams. The evidence regarding challenges faced in entrepreneurial leadership aligns with the established body of knowledge on entrepreneurial leadership in multiple ways. To illustrate, the personal challenges observed are in line with the discoveries made by Bagheri and Pihie (2011a) and Gupta et al. (2014).

These researchers identified several personal challenges encountered by entrepreneurial leaders, including issues such as a lack of commitment and confidence when leading entrepreneurial endeavours which necessitate possessing significant personal competencies. Entrepreneurial leaders' personal challenges in reference to existing literature are discussed in the subsequent section.

6.2.1.1 Lack of education and experience

Entrepreneurial leaders confirmed that a lack of formal education and business experience made it difficult for them to carry out their start-up responsibilities at both individual and team level. They also identified having irrelevant qualifications as a key hindrance to the development of entrepreneurial leadership skills. These findings support Clark's (2020) claims that possessing relevant business skills and qualifications is crucial for entrepreneurial success in Scottish SMEs. Okudan and Rzasa (2006) also acknowledged that a project-based entrepreneurial leadership course is paramount for the success of entrepreneurial leaders. According to Yi (2018) and Bagheri and Pihie (2013), university students with prior work experience had higher entrepreneurial intentions than those with no prior work experience. Students become more convinced and better prepared to deal with entrepreneurial challenges by gaining experience in the entrepreneurial sphere because they are already familiar with the business environment.

This perspective is also supported in the mainstream entrepreneurship literature. Ekpe et al. (2011) assert that education and experience are critical for entrepreneurship development and success. Zhao et al. (2005) pointed out that entrepreneurs who had education in entrepreneurship had greater levels of entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Likewise, prior job-related experience also enhances entrepreneurial efficacy and success. Frazier and Niehm (2006) discovered that a student's university major, family business presence, and internship experience all influence entrepreneurial intention and play a key role in their success. Entrepreneurial leaders also emphasised the importance of increasing entrepreneurial activities within UBIs to enhance their self-competencies and address academic and entrepreneurial deficiencies. Business incubators should focus on improving the abilities of entrepreneurial leaders through information dissemination in collaboration with universities and other

educational institutions (Qamar et al., 2020).

6.2.1.2 Interpersonal issues

Interpersonal issues for entrepreneurial leaders include managing connections with people and functioning effectively in a dynamic team environment. All entrepreneurial leaders stated that working in entrepreneurial teams brings substantial challenges, including inadequate communication, self-motivation, and self-confidence issues. They highlighted communication skills as essential interpersonal competencies for overcoming communication hurdles within teams and forging connection with external stakeholders. These views are consistent with Harrison's (2016) and Darling and Beebe's (2007) assertions that effective communication skills are critical for achieving desired entrepreneurial outcomes. According to Mumtaz et al. (2017), one of the major challenges facing budding entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs is their inability to establish proper connections with stakeholders and acquire the necessary communication expertise. Both Clark (2020) and Harrison et al. (2018) recognised the significance of entrepreneurial leaders' interpersonal skills in effectively handling interpersonal relationships and comprehending the emotions and motives of their employees when leading entrepreneurial ventures.

The findings revealed a significant correlation between the confidence skills of entrepreneurial leaders and their communication skills. It was recognised that fostering individual and group confidence is necessary for productive teamwork. Entrepreneurial leaders agreed that boosting team confidence increases innovative and creative ideas in teams. However, the absence of confidence skill was identified as a significant obstacle to establishing connections with teammates, generating innovative solutions to workplace problems, and effectively pitching business ideas to potential investors. These endeavours necessitated proficient interpersonal

communication skills within team settings. Bagheri and Pihie's (2011a) discovered that the most significant issue encountered by aspiring entrepreneurial leaders was a lack of confidence while leading entrepreneurial endeavours. Creating team enthusiasm and motivation to achieve entrepreneurial goals was a significant challenge. This necessitated strong team-building skills such as team engagement, self-confidence, and clear direction. Qamar et al. (2020) maintained that a team leader must be proactive enough to comprehend the goal and intent of team members in order to form a team and then keep it together.

6.2.1.3 Entrepreneurial issues

At business incubators, entrepreneurial leaders encountered various entrepreneurial challenges that include a lack of entrepreneurial knowledge, clear vision, and a propensity to take risks. One of the explanations for the insufficient entrepreneurial awareness among entrepreneurial leaders has been attributed to the absence of entrepreneurial leadership courses and the limited availability of entrepreneurial leadership training resources within UBIs (Mubaraki and Busler, 2015). Entrepreneurial leaders also pointed out that while UBIs offer physical infrastructure and tangible services to budding entrepreneurs, the demand for entrepreneurial leadership development extends beyond mere physical resources.

Acquiring fundamental entrepreneurial knowledge through a variety of entrepreneurial learning methods at UBIs was recognised crucial to entrepreneurial success. Although there is a lack of empirical evidence supporting the nexus of UBIs and entrepreneurial leadership competencies in the existing entrepreneurial leadership literature, these views corroborate with existing research in business incubator and mainstream entrepreneurship literature. For instance, Todorovic and Suntornpithug (2008) and Mubaraki and Busler (2015) argued that university-based incubators should concentrate on developing the personal competencies of

entrepreneurs to create an entrepreneurial culture rather than simply providing services for new venture creation. Furthermore, previous studies have emphasised that aspiring entrepreneurs at UBIs in developing economies lack sufficient entrepreneurial skills (Gibb et al., 2013; Peters et al., 2004). Bagheri and Pihie (2013) emphasised the significance of incorporating entrepreneurial leadership courses into business curricula and establishing entrepreneurial leadership programmes and clubs at business schools. These learning facilities are essential for enhancing entrepreneurial leadership competencies of aspiring entrepreneurial leaders, thereby enabling them to launch successful businesses.

Lack of a clear goals and plan of action was cited as a significant barrier by entrepreneurial teams at UBIs. They emphasised that having a distinct idea and vision should be a top priority for any entrepreneurial leader. A clear business plan, the ability to anticipate the future, and an entrepreneurial vision are essential for business initiatives to succeed (Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018). Mahmood et al. (2015) observed that a lack of objective tenant selection criteria, political associations, and an unclear sense of purpose and direction in business incubators had a substantial negative impact on potential entrepreneurs. Similarly, Qamar et al. (2020) noted that due to a lack of mentorship and direction, aspiring entrepreneurs lack guidance on how to achieve sustainable and long-term benefits from social enterprises.

Lack of entrepreneurial intent and risk aversion among fresh graduates was highlighted another obstacle to the development of an entrepreneurial culture. Entrepreneurial leaders argued that due to a lack of government assistance and an entrepreneurial climate, most fresh graduates prefer pursuing government positions over choosing an entrepreneurial path. Bagheri and Pihie (2011a) found that one of the challenges facing student entrepreneurial leaders in running university entrepreneurship programmes was a lack of interest and commitment among group members in entrepreneurial activities. To address this challenge, they recommended that the government should augment the quantity and expand the network of business incubators, grant

them access to advanced infrastructure, and furnish them with expert human resources. According to Hewitt and van Rensburg (2020), business incubators can foster entrepreneurial intent among aspiring entrepreneurs by reducing the risks associated with new ventures and start-up formation. These acknowledgments suggest that for entrepreneurial leaders to thrive in their start-up ventures, they need to nurture a clear and enduring vision. Consequently, UBIs and the government should collaborate to create a comprehensive action plan, along with providing essential resources, to nurture the skills and abilities of aspiring entrepreneurial leaders at UBIs.

6.2.1.4 Financial issues

Lack of financial assistance for running and sustaining start-ups was cited as a major challenge by entrepreneurial leaders. Financial issues were attributed to a lack of government support and financial assistance from UBIs, absence of subsidised loans, and difficulties in obtaining funding from private financial institutions. According to Hassan (2020), there are few programmes available to provide financial assistance to emerging start-ups; however, majority of them have specific requirements that some projects cannot meet. While the current incubator's financial resources such as seed capital, are insufficient to meet the needs of start-ups. Entrepreneurial leaders affirmed that their progress as potential entrepreneurial leaders is hindered by the absence of necessary financial and other resources within UBIs. The primary issues that aspiring entrepreneurs at UBIs face, according to Mavi et al. (2019) include lack of organisational, financial, and technological resources. Khan et al. (2018) maintained that the availability of financial resources plays a crucial role in the establishment and long-term viability of business ventures. This notion is further substantiated by Li et al. (2020), who contend that Pakistan is currently grappling with a financial crisis, making it challenging to

secure funding from private sources. Additionally, fledgling entrepreneurs often lack the capital and entrepreneurial expertise required to succeed in today's highly competitive business landscape.

6.2.1.5 Operational issues

Entrepreneurial leaders reported several operational difficulties, which include managing time, tasks, resources, and business operations while working as a team. They faced significant challenges in dealing with start-up operations due to operational issues that are linked to a lack of technical understanding as well as prior job experience and exposure. The need for efficient time management and prioritisation skills was cited as paramount for achieving entrepreneurial outcomes such as managing multiple jobs within a start-up and meeting personal and academic obligations. These findings are widely endorsed in entrepreneurial leadership literature. Harrison et al. (2018) and Clark (2020) underscored the importance of the interpersonal, conceptual, and technical skills of entrepreneurial leaders as the foundation for achieving entrepreneurial success. These findings are further corroborated in the mainstream entrepreneurship literature. Sathya and Vithyapriya (2016) and Nasir et al. (2019) argued that personal characteristics of entrepreneurs, such as family and personal devotion, have an impact on their performance, and balancing a dual role, family support, time management, and travel while pursuing an entrepreneurial venture is challenging.

Entrepreneurial leaders expressed difficulties in locating cost-effective resources for their businesses and managing a variety of tasks and organisational resources. This is due to the substantial time and money required, hindering their ability to operate their ventures efficiently. According to Putsom et al. (2019), managerial competencies are crucial in providing entrepreneurial leaders with the capabilities needed to create value and achieve outstanding

business performance. While there is a lack of substantial evidence to back up these claims in entrepreneurial leadership literature, these assertions are consistent with the findings of mainstream entrepreneurship literature. Anesta et al. (2004) stated that entrepreneurs' abilities to acquire and use organisational resources to capitalise on business opportunities are catalyst for entrepreneurial success. Furthermore, Ihua (2009) argued that a lack of managerial skills leads to insufficient resource management by owner-managers (entrepreneurs) of small businesses, exacerbating the difficulties associated with business growth. Nieman and Nieuwenhuizen (2009) argued that entrepreneurs are more likely to recognise and capitalise on attractive business opportunities if they have gained relevant work experience and management skills. Therefore, based on these findings, it can be contended that the success of teams in combining various resources, establishing, and sustaining new businesses greatly depends on the team members' essential management and administrative skills.

6.2.2 Business function challenges

Entrepreneurial teams face a range of challenges pertaining to key business function responsibilities such as marketing, finance, and human resources management. All these challenges require effective business function skills (Harrison et al., 2018). These challenges were also acknowledged by other scholars in entrepreneurial leadership (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Harrison et al., 2018; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Ahmed and Harrison (2021) and Swiercz and Lydon (2002) stressed the importance of having essential functional skills when carrying out challenging functional responsibilities, such as marketing, finance, and human resource management. These challenges are explained as follows:

6.2.2.1 Accounting and finance issues

Entrepreneurial leaders stressed the importance of training and specialised skill development, particularly in the areas of accounting and finance. They highlighted key challenges related to managing start-up financial accounts, developing financial proposals, and estimating ongoing project costs. These findings are consistent with existing literature that advocates for the development of specialised skills for entrepreneurial leaders in business incubators to support emerging businesses (Harrison, 2016; Harrison et al., 2018; Mubaraki and Busler, 2015; Tunio et al., 2021). For example, Tunio et al. (2021) argued that business incubators should focus on offering general business services such as accounting, advertising, legal, and financial assistance to support new enterprises. Mubaraki and Busler (2015) also highlighted the importance of developing specialised skills such as business and marketing plans and establishing management teams to support entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs. By providing these resources and specialised training, UBIs can help emerging entrepreneurial leaders overcome accounting and finance related challenges and increase their chances of success (Harrison, 2016; Harrison et al., 2018).

6.2.2.2 Marketing issues

Entrepreneurial leaders identified several marketing challenges, which include finding clients, gauging demand for their products or services, locating marketing specialists, and pitching ideas to investors. Existing literature supports these observations (Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018; Mahmood et al., 2017; Mumtaz et al., 2017; Shahzad et al., 2012). Clark (2020) and Harrison et al. (2018) both acknowledged that marketing abilities are paramount for the success of entrepreneurial leaders in SMEs and retail pharmacy sectors. The significance of marketing

skills is also acknowledged within UBIs literature. For instance, Mumtaz et al. (2017) noted that most start-ups at UBIs lack expertise in various areas, including marketing channels. Similarly, Mahmood et al. (2017) argued that while UBIs offer networking and consultation services, they lack marketing, infrastructure, training, and other resources for entrepreneurial leaders. To enhance the performance of UBIs and meet the tenants' expectations, incubators should hire more qualified and experienced marketing professionals. Entrepreneurial leaders emphasised the need for marketing-related exposure in UBIs to improve their marketing skills, which is also supported by Shahzad et al.'s (2012) findings that UBIs can develop entrepreneurial leaders' marketing skills through various marketing services such as exhibitions, displays, and exploring new market prospects.

6.2.2.3 Human Resource Management issues

Entrepreneurial leaders emphasised a range of human resource management challenges within teams, such as team selection and management, performance monitoring, and conflict resolution. Hiring difficulties were identified as a critical factor affecting start-up operations due to a lack of available and competent labour. Eshun (2009) asserts that human resource management skills are crucial for businesses' success. Leadership's ability to build an organisation relies on the availability of resources, particularly human capital (Leitch et al., 2013). SMEs' entrepreneurial leaders face significant challenges in hiring skilled labour at reasonable costs (Clark, 2020). These findings are also consistent with Pakistan's National SMEs Policy (2021), which states that human capital is a critical aspect of a country's productivity and competitiveness, and a competent workforce is especially necessary for start-ups to function efficiently. According to Global Competitiveness Report (2020), lack of team management skills and training are key hinderance to business growth. Leading entrepreneurial

projects in teams is challenging, requiring support, involvement, and communication to overcome conflicts (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Chen, 2007). Financial management issues, inadequate skill development, a lack of teamwork, and entrepreneurial abilities are significant contributors to business failures in developing countries (Agbenyegah, 2013). Hence, possessing a deep comprehension of human resource management is of utmost importance for entrepreneurial leaders who aspire to excel in a dynamic team environment (Chen, 2007; Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018).

6.2.3 Contextual Challenges

The development of entrepreneurial leadership within UBIs is impeded by a variety of systemic and institutional factors referred to as contextual challenges, which include the lack of government support, infrastructural constraints, societal challenges, and business incubator issues (SMEDA, 2021). Harrison (2016) noted that entrepreneurial leaders' interactions with their environment are influenced by various contextual factors such as traits, family dynamics, culture, followers, resources, and experience, all of which impact entrepreneurial leadership growth and their ability to lead in developing economies. The next section provides a detailed discussion of these contextual challenges.

6.2.3.1 Lack of government support

Entrepreneurial leaders identified a lack of government support as a major challenge to their entrepreneurial leadership growth. Despite the establishment of numerous business incubators, entrepreneurial leaders indicated that there is no mechanism in place to meet the financial needs

of entrepreneurs through government grants or low-interest loans. Additionally, there are not enough organisations with sophisticated mechanisms for registering new businesses, providing consulting services, and addressing their operational needs. University-run business incubators lack funding and sufficient government support to expand their operations and connect with businesses across the country. Research conducted in the context of business incubators in Pakistan and other developing countries supports these claims, suggesting that the country's entrepreneurial climate and government policies have a significant impact on entrepreneurship, poverty reduction, and economic development (Eshun, 2009; Mahmood et al., 2017; Qamar et al., 2020). The significance of government support in fostering entrepreneurial leadership development is also acknowledged in existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership (Clark, 2020, Harrison, 2016a; Harrison et al., 2018). Clark (2020) and Harrison et al. (2016a) identified inadequate capital as a key hinderance for SMEs and retail pharmacy entrepreneurial leaders. Government involvement in evaluating the effectiveness of business incubator is critical and serves as a stimulus for increasing entrepreneurship (Eshun, 2009; Mahmood et al., 2017). Entrepreneurial leaders pointed out significant challenges faced by business incubators in Pakistan that require continuous government support, such as including a lack of clear direction, planning, implementing operational strategies, and conducting performance evaluations. Furthermore, lack of a transparent business registration process forces was identified as a crucial factor affecting the growth of new venture creation among aspiring entrepreneurial leaders. Qamar et al. (2020) support these claims by implying that aspiring entrepreneurs use unethical means to register their start-ups due to the complex and time-consuming registration process in Pakistan.

Although the government established some autonomous bodies, such as the National Incubation Centre (NIC) and the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Authority (SMEDA), to regulate entrepreneurial practices and support entrepreneurial initiatives in the

country, more needs to be done to strengthen these organisations by enlisting public-private partnerships to promote incubation culture throughout the country. According to Kwapisz (2019) and Saberi and Hamdan (2018), enacting and implementing entrepreneurial rules and regulating entrepreneurial practices are crucial to achieve sustainable entrepreneurship goals.

6.2.3.2 Infrastructural constraints

Infrastructural constraints include a lack of basic services and resources that facilitate efficient start-up creation such as the internet and electricity, as well as efficient access to UBIs. Entrepreneurial leaders identified intermittent power supply and internet access as key barriers to a sustainable start-up operation. Even though UBIs have made significant progress in addressing these issues, internet and power outages have significantly hampered remote start-ups. It is widely acknowledged that infrastructural facilities have an impact on the entrepreneurial environment and the growth of entrepreneurial leadership among aspiring entrepreneurial leaders. Harrison (2016) concludes that context is a significant determinant of entrepreneurial leadership development and its outcome. Harrison et al. (2016) argued that the growth of entrepreneurial leadership is influenced by environmental factors, including proper infrastructure and a stable political and economic system. Factors like gas and energy expenses, economic meltdown, rental fees and taxes, and political elements like strikes and demonstrations all exert a substantial influence on the entrepreneurial environment in a region (Nasir et al., 2019; SMEDA, 2021).

According to Harrison et al. (2016) and Nkechi et al. (2012), insufficient power supply is a major challenge for entrepreneurial leaders in developing economies such as Nigeria. The provision of infrastructure services by business incubators, such as internet, phone, and fax services, is critical for launching economic activity more swiftly (McAdam and Marlow, 2007).

In light of above discussion, it could be argued that supporting the development of entrepreneurial leadership in UBIs is influenced by several infrastructural limitations. Providing essential amenities to aspiring entrepreneurial leaders not only improves the effectiveness of their start-ups but also plays a crucial role in establishing a sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem essential for economic growth in developing nations.

6.2.3.3 Societal challenges

The findings revealed that sociocultural constraints are a significant hindrance to entrepreneurial culture and growth of aspiring entrepreneurial leaders in the country. Entrepreneurial leaders described a lack of social encouragement and support, family pressure, and lack of conducive entrepreneurial culture as major barriers to the development of entrepreneurial leadership in UBIs. Extant literature recognises the importance of societal support and the role of social circles in developing entrepreneurial culture (Hewitt and Van Rensburg, 2020; Renko et al., 2012). Hewitt and Van Rensburg (2020) and Renko et al. (2012) highlighted the significance of a favourable business environment in developing entrepreneurial leadership. Entrepreneurial leaders confirmed that family, friends, and social circle encouragement is a catalyst for developing entrepreneurial intent and drive in aspiring entrepreneurial leaders.

Furthermore, Harrison et al. (2016) argued that contextual factors such as traits, family dynamics, culture, followers, resources, and experience of entrepreneurial leaders influence entrepreneurial outcomes in developing countries. Tunio et al. (2021) concluded that family and social support are significant factors in fostering an entrepreneurial attitude. These findings are consistent with the entrepreneurship economic theory, which emphasises the importance of a favourable economic environment for a sustainable entrepreneurial culture (Li et al., 2020).

6.2.3.4 Business incubator issues

The findings revealed that rigid work schedules, strict entry requirements, complicated registration procedures, limited resources, and networks within UBIs all hindered the development of nascent entrepreneurial leaders. These findings support previous research in the business incubator literature which recognise five key roles that business incubators play, including defining success criteria, fostering entrepreneurial leadership, offering value-added services to start-ups, streamlining start-up selection processes, and providing sufficient human and financial resources (Mubaraki and Busler, 2015; Wiggins and Gibson, 2003). However, business incubators in Pakistan and other developing countries often fall short in these areas.

Li et al. (2020) argued that lack of technical and educational skills, poor facilities and infrastructure, and weak support systems within UBIs are critical barriers to entrepreneurial leadership development in developing economies. Furthermore, the administrative burdens of starting a business, such as the cost, duration, and number of registration procedures do not correspond to the rate of new business creation (Hassan, 2020). According to Hassan (2020), university incubators should aim to do more than simply assisting start-up creation. They should foster leadership, strengthen entrepreneurial culture, and develop the infrastructure necessary to cultivate innovation, entrepreneurial thinking, organisational development, and entrepreneurial leadership skills. The findings indicate that providing fundamental resources, building entrepreneurial leadership skills, and expanding entrepreneurial networks have a significant impact on entrepreneurial success. Ratten and Usmanij (2021) stressed that an incubator can serve as a broker by creating networks and linkages, while universities can act as hubs that connect actors in the triple helix of government, businesses, and academic institutions. In light of these assertions, it could be argued that UBIs are not only crucial in

fostering the growth of start-ups and developing entrepreneurial leadership skills among aspiring entrepreneurial leaders, but with government support, they can also play a vital role in expanding the entrepreneurial culture at a national level.

6.3 Entrepreneurial Leadership Competencies

Competencies, which combine knowledge, abilities, and attitudes are crucial for successfully launching and operating businesses (Aouni and Surlemont, 2009; Politis, 2005). This section addresses research question two, which investigates entrepreneurial leadership competencies from a team perspective. These competencies are closely linked to the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders face, as previously discussed. Moreover, the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders are interdependent. For instance, self-competencies enhance entrepreneurial leaders' ability to carry out business operations and team responsibilities, while their interpersonal competencies, such as effective communication skills, improve their ability to obtain seed money, present their products and services to target markets, and sustain team interaction. In essence, five essential categories of competencies were identified: self-competencies, organising competencies, interpersonal competencies, entrepreneurial competencies, and conceptual competencies. The competencies of entrepreneurial leaders are consistent with existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a, Harrison et al., 2018; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). These competencies are discussed in detail in the following section:

6.3.1 Self-Competencies

Self-competence refers to the unique skills, knowledge, and attitude of entrepreneurial leaders that have a substantial impact on the effectiveness of the entire team. Self-competencies are less tangible and non-functional entrepreneurial leadership capabilities (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002), but these are essential for completing tasks and responsibilities assigned to entrepreneurial teams. Entrepreneurial leaders unanimously agreed on the importance of self-competencies for team success. They identified four dominant self-competences: self-management, self-confidence, self-motivation, and self-development skills, which are discussed in more detail below.

6.3.1.1 Self- management skills

Self-management skills encompass a diverse set of abilities and behaviours that enable entrepreneurial leaders to effectively govern and regulate their cognitive processes, emotional states, and behavioural patterns operating within a dynamic team context. The development of self-management abilities is crucial for achieving personal and professional success in an entrepreneurial context. Entrepreneurial leaders identified self-awareness, work-life balance, and time management skills essential for entrepreneurial success and effective leadership in teams. The literature on entrepreneurial leadership consistently recognises self-management skills as critical interpersonal abilities for the success of entrepreneurial leaders (Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018; Harrison et al., 2016a; Jones and Crompton, 2009). They also acknowledged the importance of time management and prioritisation skills for balancing work and life and fulfilling academic and entrepreneurial responsibilities effectively. Effective time management and prioritisation abilities are catalysts for efficient resource allocation and

mobilisation, as argued by Carpenter (2012) and Hejazi et al. (2012). Creating priorities and having effective time management techniques assists entrepreneurial leaders in balancing their personal and professional lives, as well as enhancing their ability to handle start-up responsibilities and improve team performance.

In addition to time management and prioritisation skills, self-awareness was cited as a critical self-management skill for entrepreneurial leaders. It allows them to recognise personality differences, delegate work, and avoid difficult situations that consequently enhance team effectiveness. Greenberg et al. (2013, p. 59) claim that entrepreneurial leaders need “a deep understanding of who they are to guide their actions” in order to inspire commitment in their workforce. While Ratwani et al. (2010) believed that self-awareness is necessary for effective leadership because it realigns the goals, actions, and behaviours required for entrepreneurial success.

6.3.1.2 Self-confidence skills

Self-confidence is considered a critical self-management skill for entrepreneurial success in teams (He et al., 2017). Entrepreneurial leaders highlighted the importance of self-confidence, which refers to an individual’s belief in their abilities to perform specific entrepreneurial activities as part of a team. Entrepreneurial leaders who possess self-confidence may be more willing to take risks while carrying out their responsibilities and can build networks and connections with team members and external stakeholders. Additionally, self-confidence is seen as essential in overcoming communication and presentation challenges. Clark (2020) identified that successful entrepreneurial leaders are confident and willing to talk about themselves and their companies. Renko et al. (2015) suggest that entrepreneurial leaders

empower their employees by offering essential support to help maximise their entrepreneurial capabilities. Mumford et al. (2000) underscored that confident leaders are better equipped to distribute resources effectively in complex business environments. While Lord and Hall (2005) argued that self-confidence is necessary for recognising areas for improvement and seeking the best ways to upskill oneself or delegate tasks to others.

6.3.1.3 Self-motivation skills

Self-motivation was cited as a crucial skill for entrepreneurial leaders. During the entrepreneurial journey, entrepreneurial leaders must be passionate, resilient, and self-motivated to inspire their team and gain their commitment to accomplishing team goals (Gupta et al., 2004). They also emphasised the significance of self-motivation in the self-development of entrepreneurial leaders. Existing literature acknowledge these premises suggesting that entrepreneurial leaders excel at inspiring others (Fernald et al., 2005; Gupta et al., 2004; Kansikas et al., 2012), and they can persuade their followers to take on start-up responsibilities and accomplish organisational objectives by inspiring them (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Gupta et al., 2004; Renko et al., 2012). Self-motivation abilities were recognised as crucial for team performance and sustainable entrepreneurial success, in addition to individual performance. These views also align with Agbim (2013) claim, which asserts that the motivational characteristics of entrepreneurial leaders contribute to long-term success. Entrepreneurial leaders motivate their followers and encourage teamwork, which results in the production of creative ideas and the identification of opportunities. Chen (2007) confirmed that entrepreneurial leadership fosters a favourable environment in the workplace and encourage workers to participate in the investigation and utilisation of opportunities. In addition,

entrepreneurial leadership promotes autonomy so that team members can use their creativity to generate and implement new ideas, which enhances proactive behaviour.

6.3.1.4 Self-development skills

Self-development skills are essential for entrepreneurial leaders' personal growth, leadership effectiveness, and entrepreneurial success. These competencies enable entrepreneurial leaders to navigate the challenges and uncertainties of entrepreneurial pursuits and enhance their success. Entrepreneurial leaders recognised the significance of identifying their weaknesses and have a persistent desire to improve both their personal and entrepreneurial skills (Harrison, 2016). These views align with previous literature on entrepreneurial leadership, which emphasises the importance of self-development. Entrepreneurial leaders continuously seek ways to improve their behaviour, whether through formal education at business incubators or independent reading (Harrison, 2016). Bagheri et al. (2013a) and Gupta et al. (2004) suggest that entrepreneurial leaders seek opportunities for mentorship programmes in business incubators and entrepreneurship clubs to sustain continuous learning. Similarly, Leitch et al. (2013) advocate for the development of human capital through leadership development programmes. These assertions were also supported by Day (2000), who states that effective leadership occurs through the development of individual leaders. Therefore, leadership training programmes can provide leaders with the necessary skills for effective leadership (Mumford et al., 2000).

6.3.2 Organising Competencies

Organising competencies pertain to the abilities of entrepreneurial leaders in addressing business function challenges, including accounting and finance, marketing, and human resource management, as well as technical and technological matters. These competencies focus on the business function challenges confronting entrepreneurial leaders, as well as those linked to the ongoing operations of a start-up. The findings confirmed that there is a strong correlation between the self-competencies of entrepreneurial leaders and their organising competencies. All entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged the significance of organising competencies in enhancing the performance of entrepreneurial leaders working as teams. The subsequent discussion provides a comprehensive overview of the organising competencies.

6.3.2.1 Business function skills

Business function skills refer to the specific competencies and expertise of entrepreneurial leaders necessary to perform effectively in various functional areas within start-up. These competencies are tailored to the specific responsibilities and duties associated with various start-up functions (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Entrepreneurial leaders collectively recognised the importance of possessing business function skills in areas such as accounting and finance, marketing, and human resource management to achieve success in their endeavours (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Harrison et al. (2018) confirmed that business function skills are vital for the success of retail pharmacy entrepreneurial leaders.

Entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged that roles and responsibilities within entrepreneurial teams are dynamic, requiring the development of diverse skillsets to effectively navigate the core operational tasks of start-ups and overcome operational challenges. They demonstrated the acquisition of knowledge and skills in these domains through engagement in training programs offered by business incubators and by assuming hands-on roles in start-up ventures. Additionally, they indicated substantial enhancements in their start-up operations as a result of developing proficiency in business functions, encompassing a deeper understanding of accounting, finance, marketing, and human resource processes (Guo, 2009; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002).

6.3.2.1.1 Accounting and Finance skills

Accounting and finance skills were identified by entrepreneurial leaders as essential business function skills to cope with challenges of accounting and finance of start-ups. They emphasised the significance of developing accounting and finance skills to address start-up budgetary and financial demands, track start-up activities, and create financial requests to obtain funding from investors. Although less common among those with business and management qualifications, dealing with accounting and finance activities was a major concern for most entrepreneurial leaders. Accounting and financial management are critical business skills for effectively managing organisational financial resources (Katz, 1974; Zaccaro and Klimoski, 2002).

Harrison et al. (2018) validated the importance of accounting and finance skills for entrepreneurial leaders in the retail pharmacy industry. In Addition, Clark (2020), Guo (2009), and Swiercz and Lydon (2002) suggest that financial management is a fundamental competence for entrepreneurial leaders. While Hentschke (2010) stated that entrepreneurial leaders must have a basic understanding of finance and accounting individually and

collectively to develop and present a business plan, secure funding, and manage financial resources efficiently.

6.3.2.1.2 Marketing skills

Entrepreneurial leaders unanimously agreed that handling marketing-related issues, such as forecasting demand for goods and services, managing market competition, and promoting product and service ideas to customers, are crucial challenges that require effective marketing knowledge and skills. The findings revealed a clear correlation between entrepreneurial leaders' marketing capabilities and communication skills. Entrepreneurial leaders asserted that persuasive and clear communication skills are crucial for convincing investors and other stakeholders while at the same time selling products and services. These findings reinforce the viewpoints of Harrison et al. (2018) and Clark (2020) that marketing expertise is vital for running a successful business. Swiercz and Lydon (2002) also reinforced that entrepreneurial leaders must possess marketing skills, including customer service, to meet and exceed consumers' expectations and retain them over time. Mumtaz et al. (2017) argued that aspiring entrepreneurs within UBIs lack the marketing skills necessary to carry out their entrepreneurial endeavours effectively.

6.3.2.1.3 Human Resource Management skills

Entrepreneurial leaders emphasised the significance of human resource management skills in dealing with HRM issues such as recruitment and staffing, performance evaluations, team engagement, and team motivation. These perspectives are consistent with existing literature

(Clark, 2020; Chen, 2007; Harrison et al., 2018; Katz, 1974). Katz (1974) concluded that effective organisational management requires human, conceptual, and technical skills.

Moreover, all entrepreneurial leaders recognised that teamwork and entrepreneurial success are contingent upon team management and leadership. Harrison et al. (2018), Chen (2007), and Clark (2020) also stressed the prominence of human skills and argued that entrepreneurial leaders must refine their human skills to succeed. These premises also align with Guo's (2009) assertion that healthcare leaders must acquire people management skills to provide effective healthcare services. Swiercz and Lydon (2002) referred to these abilities as functional competencies that determine entrepreneurial success in performing core entrepreneurial activities. El-Sabaa (2001) further emphasised the importance of human skills over technical skills. These premises validate the importance of entrepreneurial leaders possessing dynamic HR skills to effectively manage team performance, foster team motivation, and facilitate continuous learning, all of which are crucial for achieving long-term start-ups' goals.

6.3.2.2 Technical skills

Technical skill is the comprehensive knowledge and expertise in doing a certain activity, especially one that involves methods, processes, procedures, or techniques (Harrison, 2016; Katz, 1974). Entrepreneurial leaders identified technical skills as critical to the efficient operation of their start-ups. This skill necessitates a thorough understanding of the business, its products and services, as well as its tools and procedures. Entrepreneurial leaders agreed that they must understand the fundamentals of each role they play in a team. Despite the critical importance of technical skills in enhancing a leader's effectiveness (Haq, 2011; Katz, 1974; Lord and Hall, 2005), technical skills are viewed differently by researchers; for example, Katz (1974) considers technical skills as basic business skills or independent leadership skills. While

Harrison et al. (2018) annexed them into business function skills. However, according to the findings of this study, technical skills are essential for entrepreneurial leaders to understand the complexities of businesses at all stages in new ventures and established organisations, regardless of the organisational layer and type (Clark, 2020; McCall and Lombardo, 1983).

6.3.2.3 Technological skills

Technological skills are the abilities or behaviours needed to proficiently use technology and advanced equipment (Murphy et al., 2012). Entrepreneurial leaders recognised technological skill as a crucial component of organising competencies critical for effective teamwork and start-up success. They highlighted that cutting-edge technology is essential for dealing with competition and increasing start-up competitiveness with minimal costs. The extant literature supports the importance of firms employing innovative technologies, with Putsom et al. (2019) highlighting technological skills as essential entrepreneurial leadership competencies with a significant impact on the auto industry. The significance of technological proficiency is also acknowledged broadly in the mainstream entrepreneurship literature. Technological proficiency promotes creativity, profitability, and successful corporate operations (McEvily et al., 2004).

Additionally, entrepreneurial leaders recognised the importance of technological adaptation to remain competitive in dynamic business environment. Candolfi-Arballo et al. (2022) conclude that effective use of technology enhances business operations, influences an organisation's potential for innovation, and maintains and strengthens its competitive advantages. For aspiring entrepreneurial leaders to produce innovative products and services and remain competitive in the face of intensifying market competition, technological proficiency is indispensable.

6.3.3 Interpersonal Competencies

Entrepreneurial leaders recognised effective communication, interpersonal networks, and people management as critical interpersonal competencies required for successful entrepreneurial teams. These assertions are consistent with the findings of Clark (2020) and Harrison et al. (2018), who argued that interpersonal skills are crucial for understanding human behaviour and group processes. Entrepreneurial leaders identified communication and networking and people management as key factors in achieving team success. The following section discusses each of these competencies in more detail.

6.3.3.1 Communication skills

Entrepreneurial leaders need strong communication skills to establish and maintain relationships at work. According to Guo (2009), communication competence is the ability to effectively use communication behaviours, such as verbal and written communication, to exchange thoughts, ideas, emotions, and understanding between senders and receivers. All 18 entrepreneurial teams recognised the significance of effective communication skills in leading entrepreneurial endeavours and promoting team success. Entrepreneurial leaders emphasised that task delegation, creative idea generation, teamwork, and reducing communication barriers are some of the critical areas where excellent communication skills are essential. These findings corroborate the existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership (Chen, 2007; Clark, 2020; Darling and Beebe, 2007; Gupta et al., 2007; Harrison et al., 2018).

Furthermore, written communication skills were recognised crucial for developing business and financial proposals and communicating with various stakeholders. To achieve

entrepreneurial success, Harrison et al. (2018) stated that entrepreneurial leaders must improve their oral, written, and listening skills. Entrepreneurial leaders also recognised communication skills fundamental for developing interpersonal relationships and expanding entrepreneurial networks. Clark (2020) argued that information sharing, active listening, and collaboration are crucial communication skills for entrepreneurial leaders. While Hentschke (2010) emphasised that motivation and communication skills are crucial for entrepreneurial success. This view also aligns with Bagheri et al.'s (2013a) perspective that practical entrepreneurial endeavours improve entrepreneurial leaders' interpersonal skills and enable them to connect with industry experts.

6.3.3.2 Networking and People Management skills

Networking and people management skills refer to entrepreneurial leaders' ability to establish and maintain positive links with other stakeholders and facilitate information, resource, and support sharing. This skill enables entrepreneurial leaders to interact, guide, motivate, and engage entrepreneurial teams through effective communication, task delegation, and engagement. Entrepreneurial leaders unanimously recognised these skills as crucial factors for achieving effective team performance and entrepreneurial success. Networking and people management skills are categorised into the following sub-themes:

6.3.3.2.1 People management

People management refers to motivating team members and encouraging teamwork to achieve common start-up goals. All entrepreneurial leaders agreed that inspiring and guiding a team towards a shared vision is critical for entrepreneurial success. This is consistent with Gupta et

al.'s (2004) finding that entrepreneurial leaders inspire and motivate their followers to achieve organisational goals. Entrepreneurial leaders emphasised the significance of resilience and patience to maintain motivation and manage their teams in order to realise their entrepreneurial ideas. This supports the claim of Guo (2009) that entrepreneurial leaders recognise the value of human resources and their role in creating an environment in which people are valued and given the freedom to perform to the best of their abilities. Entrepreneurial leaders stressed that developing a team's understanding of and caring for team members' emotions is important for team effectiveness. Entrepreneurial leaders instil confidence, emotions, beliefs, values, and behaviours in others and persuade a group of people to achieve their goals (Clark, 2020; Darling et al., 2007; Gupta et al., 2004; Harrison et al., 2018; Hejazi et al., 2012).

6.3.3.2.2 Team building skills

Entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged the significance of team-building skills such as selecting the right team, managing team conflicts, delegating tasks, tracking team performance, and building trust and privacy, vital for team success. They confirmed that choosing the right team with the right skills determines team success (Larson and Schaumann, 1993). Task delegation has also been identified as a critical skill for entrepreneurial leaders to ensure enhanced teamwork while meeting team goals, which is consistent with Weingart's (1992) perspectives. The importance of cultivating a sense of teamwork and collaborative efforts was highlighted a critical factor for team success. These views are widely acknowledged in the extant literature (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Chen, 2007; Harrison et al., 2018; Strubler and Redekop, 2010). Ensuring trust and privacy in teams was recognised critical for achieving long-term goals and entrepreneurial success. Harrison et al. (2018) and Clark (2020) argued that fostering trust and cultivating teamwork are indispensable skills for entrepreneurial leaders. Developing an

entrepreneurial network was identified as a critical team-building skill that must be learned to improve entrepreneurial leaders' relationships with other stakeholders, which resonates with existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership (Jones and Crompton, 2009; Leitch et al., 2013; Li et al., 2020; Surie and Ashley, 2008).

6.3.4 Entrepreneurial Competencies

Entrepreneurial competencies are concerned with entrepreneurial leaders' abilities of innovation and creativity, the identification and exploitation of opportunities, and risk management skills. All entrepreneurial leaders unanimously recognised entrepreneurial competencies as essential to navigate the challenges of new product development, business opportunity identification and exploitation, and prudent risk-taking. These findings align with the assertions of Harrison et al. (2018), who emphasised the significance of entrepreneurial skills in identifying and capitalising on business opportunities in developing economies. Furthermore, Clark (2020) emphasised that entrepreneurial leadership success crucially depends on possessing essential entrepreneurial skills such as opportunity identification and exploitation, innovation, risk-taking, and intuition.

6.3.4.1 Innovation and creativity skills

Innovation and creativity skills refer to entrepreneurial leaders' ability to think creatively and find innovative solutions to existing challenges and business problems, as well as recognise entrepreneurial opportunities (Chen, 2007; Mattare, 2008). Entrepreneurial leaders agreed that in order to solve their current organisational challenges and capitalise emerging market

opportunities, they must possess innovation and creativity skills. This is consistent with Chen's (2007) findings that entrepreneurial leaders take risks and are proactive and innovative. Entrepreneurial leaders foster their teams' creativity and innovation through their innovative qualities. They promote collaborative thinking and innovative ideas while sharing a common goal.

Flamholtz (2011) asserted that entrepreneurial leadership entails setting the vision, controlling organisational culture, coordinating activities, supervising system development, and guiding innovation and transformation. Entrepreneurial leaders maintained that participating in team initiatives promotes collaborative learning, which is critical for team success. This viewpoint endorses the findings of Bagheri and Pihie (2013), who discovered that co-curricular entrepreneurial learning promotes collaborative learning and team creativity. Also corroborate with Chen (2007) assertions that creative entrepreneurial teams identify market opportunities by putting their innovative ideas into action.

6.3.4.2 Opportunity identification and exploitation skills

Entrepreneurial leaders' ability to identify and exploit market opportunities is crucial for their success in business (Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018). Entrepreneurial leaders recognised this skill as one of the most important entrepreneurial competencies. This is consistent with Chen's (2007) views that entrepreneurial teams' ability to capitalise on business opportunities through interpersonal skills and industry knowledge distinguishes them from ordinary leaders. According to Harrison et al. (2018), the identification and exploitation of opportunities are distinct entrepreneurial leadership skills that are of paramount importance for achieving success in entrepreneurial leadership. Chen (2007) argued that successful entrepreneurial teams use creativity to gather and control resources and identify business opportunities.

Moreover, entrepreneurial leaders' success is more dependent on opportunity recognition than intelligence (Darling and Beebe, 2007). Entrepreneurial leaders believed that they could anticipate and seize future business opportunities to gain a first-mover advantage. This is consistent with Renko et al.'s (2012) acknowledgement that entrepreneurial leaders identify and pursue new business opportunities through innovative, prudent risk-taking, and creative methods. Koryak et al. (2015) and Surie and Ashley (2008) noted that entrepreneurial leaders envision their teams by identifying and exploiting future opportunities to generate value for their firms. In order to excel in opportunity identification and exploitation, entrepreneurial leaders need to possess industry knowledge and stay informed of market trends. Moreover, an effective strategy for identifying opportunities necessitates strong networking skills which enable them to gather valuable information and identify potential business prospects (Leitch et al., 2013).

6.3.4.3 Risk Management skills

Entrepreneurial leadership is often associated with managing risk, which is seen as a critical skill essential for entrepreneurial success (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Chen, 2007; Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018) and distinguish entrepreneurial leaders from other types of leaders. According to Chen (2007), entrepreneurial leaders are known for their willingness to take risks in uncertain business environments. Fernald et al. (2005) described risk-taking as an entrepreneurial leader's inclination to take prudent risks while investing and taking strategic actions in the face of uncertainty. Entrepreneurial leaders agreed that taking advantage of business opportunities requires the ability to take calculated risks (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a).

Entrepreneurial leaders face several critical challenges that require effective risk management skills. These include persuading families to become entrepreneurs, being resilient and patient,

and accepting failures and setbacks. As Bagheri and Pihie (2011a) emphasised, entrepreneurial leaders deal with business uncertainties and innovation through proactive, creative, and risk-taking behaviour. Furthermore, entrepreneurial leaders mentioned that reducing the risk of failure involves assessing the viability of start-up initiatives and refining business models with advice from experts at incubation centres (Renko et al., 2015). Moreover, entrepreneurial leaders are known for taking calculated risks while being imaginative, visionary, and inspiring (Harrison et al., 2018). Chen (2007) argued that the risk-taking characteristics of entrepreneurial leaders distinguish them from other types of leaders, which also correlates with mainstream leadership literature. According to Hassan et al. (2020), good leaders are identified by their ability to manage risks, highlighting the importance of risk management skills in leadership.

6.3.5 Conceptual Competencies

Entrepreneurial leaders play a crucial role in the success of team-led start-ups, and their conceptual competencies are vital to this process. These competencies enable them to gather, analyse, and communicate information effectively (Mumford et al., 2007), which in turn enhances their ability to handle complex business situations (Harrison, 2016). According to Katz (2009), conceptual competencies refer to a leader's ability to see the organisation as a whole and consider how it interacts with the outside world.

Entrepreneurial leaders widely agreed that analytical, problem-solving, business planning, and envisioning skills are essential conceptual competencies that enable them to succeed in the fast-paced and ever-changing business environment. By possessing these skills, they can make informed decisions, identify opportunities, and take calculated risks to ensure the growth and success of their venture (Chen, 2007; Harrison et al., 2018). Furthermore, the ability to apply

conceptual competencies is particularly important for entrepreneurial leaders perform well dynamic and uncertain environment. This requires them to be adaptable and agile in their decision-making processes and to continuously evaluate and adjust their strategies to stay competitive (Harrison, 2016). The components of conceptual competencies are discussed in the following section.

6.3.5.1 Analytical skills

In order to achieve entrepreneurial success in teams, entrepreneurial leaders emphasised the importance of analytical and logical thinking skills (Yukl, 2010). They agreed that honing these skills is crucial for visualising the overall business, evaluating its strengths and limitations, assessing the team's abilities and performance, and making objective decisions. According to Harrison et al. (2018), entrepreneurial leaders must think analytically to take risks, make business decisions, and cope with competition. The importance of analytical skills is also acknowledged in the mainstream entrepreneurship literature, which highlights the importance of logic in weighing the benefits and drawbacks of various business opportunities to achieve entrepreneurial success (Gillen and Carroll, 1985; Mumford et al., 2007). Furthermore, entrepreneurial leaders concurred that providing unique products and services is essential to competing with other businesses, which can be achieved through analytical and logical thinking. This viewpoint is consistent with Harrison's (2016) conclusions that entrepreneurial leaders must think logically and objectively to deal with market competition challenges.

6.3.5.2 Problem solving skills

Entrepreneurial leaders confirmed that they must think objectively and logically based on factual data to solve complex organisational challenges. By weighing the benefits and drawbacks of various alternatives, they can make informed decisions before putting them into action. This viewpoint is consistent with the findings of Harrison (2016) and Clark (2020), who found that entrepreneurial leaders use cognitive processes to identify problems and develop solutions. The importance of problem-solving skills is also validated in mainstream leadership literature. Connelly et al. (2000) suggest that a leader's experience influences their ability to solve problems, while Mumford et al. (2000b) found that a leader's ability to solve problems has a significant impact on their effectiveness.

In entrepreneurial teams, where there is no boss, everyone is autonomous in taking initiative and solving problems. Entrepreneurial leaders cited problem-solving skills as critical for entrepreneurial teams' success because it enables them to divide difficult tasks among team members and bring innovative solutions to existing problems. This view is supported in the existing literature, which acknowledges that problem-solving abilities are especially important in self-managed teams, where employees are expected to take the initiative to resolve issues on their own (Hackman, 1987; Levine and Moreland, 1990). Harrison et al. (2018) found that entrepreneurial leaders adopt a logical and analytical approach to solving their business problems. Clark (2020) viewed problem solving as a key factor in entrepreneurial leadership success.

6.3.5.3 Business planning skills

Business planning skills were identified as critical conceptual competencies for team success. Entrepreneurial leaders identified participatory planning as critical to effective team performance. Participatory planning enables entrepreneurial teams to develop clear objectives and integrate tasks with common team objectives. Strategic planning skills enable leaders to perform better in difficult and changing environments (Mumford et al., 2002; Yukl, 2010), and team leaders' ability to organise and manage tasks and information is critical to team success (Weingart, 1992). Harrison et al. (2018) and Roomi and Harrison (2011) recognised strategic planning skills as crucial entrepreneurial leadership abilities and vital for their success.

Carpenter (2012) also acknowledged that entrepreneurial leaders act as master strategists by evaluating existing resources and devising pathways to realise their organisational vision. Entrepreneurial leaders' capacity to define tasks and roles and align team members' skills and knowledge has a considerable influence on team success and overall effectiveness. This view concurs with Gladstein's (1984) conclusion that team performance improves significantly when team members' tasks and responsibilities are clearly defined, and work procedures are planned and controlled. These claims are further reinforced within entrepreneurial leadership literature, which confirms that using resources to address system, community, and stakeholder issues in an organisation's environment requires strategic planning (Carpenter, 2012; Guo, 2009; Hejazi et al., 2012).

Furthermore, entrepreneurial leaders agreed that while working as a team, they must oversee the entire business process and ensure that each planning step results in the desired outcome. Entrepreneurial leaders can make plans, anticipate changes, and manage their time effectively (Harrison et al., 2018). This underscores the importance of developing strong entrepreneurial

leadership skills to succeed in today's rapidly changing business environment.

6.3.5.4 Envisioning skills

Envisioning is defined as “creating a picture of what the future state will be like” (Flamholtz, 2011, p. 7). Entrepreneurial leaders identified potential foresight and visionary abilities as crucial conceptual competencies. In order to capitalise on business opportunities, entrepreneurial leaders must understand their organisations' long-term goals and objectives and communicate them effectively to the team members. Gupta et al. (2004), Clark (2020), and Harrison et al. (2018) support these claims by arguing that entrepreneurial leaders lead organisations by exploring new opportunities, fostering the development of new ideas, and putting those ideas into action to realise the vision. Furthermore, entrepreneurial leaders recognised that articulating a shared vision within a team result in significant organisational breakthroughs and improvements. This view is widely acknowledged within entrepreneurial leadership literature – entrepreneurial leaders must be able to paint a clear picture of the future to create value for the organisation (Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Fernald et al., 2005; Harrison et al., 2018).

Having a clear vision and direction improves entrepreneurial leaders' ability to anticipate and capitalise on future business opportunities. When the vision is understood and shared, it instils energy and drive in employees while also increasing their trust in the organisation (Harrison et al., 2018; Karanian, 2007; Roomi and Harrison, 2011). This is also consistent with mainstream leadership literature, which asserts that a leader inspires followers to work towards a common vision and set of goals (Zaleznik, 1990). Therefore, the ability to create and communicate a clear vision is a crucial conceptual competence for entrepreneurial leaders to drive success in their organisations.

6.4 Entrepreneurial leadership development

This section focuses on research question three, which examines entrepreneurial leadership development. It builds upon the preceding section, which emphasised the essential competencies necessary for entrepreneurial leaders to overcome challenges in their ventures. Within this section, we delve into four primary methods of entrepreneurial leadership development: classroom-based learning, project-based learning, social learning, and self-regulated learning. The subsequent section provides a detailed explanation to each of these methods.

6.4.1 Classroom-based learning

Classroom-based learning is a conventional educational method utilised by entrepreneurial leaders, taking place in either physical or virtual classroom environments. Under this approach, an expert or field instructor facilitates the learning process, providing immediate feedback and valuable suggestions to the learners regarding their progress. Entrepreneurial leaders identified entrepreneurial leadership courses, diplomas, training, workshops, and seminars as crucial methods of EL learning and development in UBI settings. The significance of these assertions is widely recognised in the entrepreneurial leadership literature, as evident from various studies (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011b; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Galloway et al., 2014; Harrison et al., 2016a; Kempster and Cope, 2010; Koryak et al., 2015; Okudan and Rzasa, 2006). Although classroom-based learning has proven effective, some entrepreneurial leaders have identified that a more dynamic learning approach, which combines formal and informal learning methods, yields better results in team learning. Kempster and Cope (2010) and Okudan and Rzasa (2006) contend that traditional courses, training, and diplomas in

entrepreneurial leadership may not be effective in a constantly evolving learning environment. Therefore, it is essential to adopt a contemporary learning approach that facilitates group participation, observation, critical reflection, and interaction to ensure effective entrepreneurial leadership development.

6.4.2 Project-based learning

Entrepreneurial leaders have recognised the significance of project-based learning compared to traditional classroom-based approaches, which mainly focus on theoretical knowledge. They emphasised that engaging in real-world projects and navigating through the complexities of start-up challenges are essential for honing entrepreneurial leadership competencies. They recognised experiential learning, internship and bootcamps, and entrepreneurial competition crucial for developing entrepreneurial leadership competencies.

Entrepreneurial leaders affirmed that experiential learning is essential for acquiring key entrepreneurial competencies. They reaffirmed that engaging in actual business endeavours, learning from mistakes, and self-evaluation, are essential for entrepreneurial success. Experiential learning opportunities provide entrepreneurial leaders with practical insights into launching and operating a business, fostering their entrepreneurial competencies required for effectively leading their ventures working as a team. These observations are not only reflected in the experiences of entrepreneurial leaders but are also supported by existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership (Ahmed and Harrison, 2002; Anderson and Air, 2022; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011b; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Cogliser and Brigham, 2004; Kempster and Cope, 2010; Koryak et al., 2015; Leitch et al., 2013; Okudan and Rzasa, 2006). Scholars such as Bagheri and Pihie (2011b) and Kempster and Cope (2010) have emphasised the significance of practical

learning experiences in developing entrepreneurial leadership skills. According to Ahmed and Harrison (2022) and Pittaway and Cope (2007), presenting real-world scenarios and promoting group-based learning have proven highly effective in entrepreneurial leadership development. Furthermore, Anderson and Air (2022) assert that relying solely on formal content-based learning is not sufficient, leveraging practical knowledge and experiences is far more impactful in fostering entrepreneurial leadership development.

Entrepreneurial leaders also highlighted business plan competitions, boot camps, and internships as crucial to their success because they exposed them to real-world business situations and helped them solve complex business challenges with innovative and creative entrepreneurial skills. The aforementioned techniques have gained significant recognition in the academic literature as indispensable for fostering entrepreneurial leadership (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011b; Buller and Finkle, 2013; Kuratko et al., 2015). The curriculum and co-curriculum learning methods that the students are exposed to have a vital role in entrepreneurial leadership development. These activities enable entrepreneurial leaders to utilise their leadership knowledge and skills to identify and exploit business opportunities and benefit society (Buller and Finkle, 2013).

Effective entrepreneurial behaviour is stimulated by learning entrepreneurial leadership through practical experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualisation, and active experimentation (Okudan and Rzasa, 2006). Business plan competitions, boot camps, and internships are recognised team phenomena that enable relational learning and engagement. This perspective is supported by Kempster and Cope's (2010) findings that entrepreneurial leaders' communication, creativity, and problem-solving abilities are improved through social, interactive, and reflective learning.

6.4.3 Social learning

Social learning emphasises the significance of social interaction and observation in the context of entrepreneurial leadership development. Entrepreneurial leaders have recognised that observing the actions and behaviours of others and integrating them into their own practices effectively enhances their entrepreneurial leadership competencies, especially in team settings. These observations are well-supported by the existing entrepreneurial leadership literature (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Kempster, 2009; Kempster and Cope, 2010; Surie and Ashley, 2008). Kempster (2009) highlights that social interaction and observation not only play a crucial role in leadership development but also influence the leadership styles of aspiring entrepreneurial leaders. Bagheri and Pihie (2011b) suggest that engaging in dynamic social interactions creates an environment conducive to learning entrepreneurial leadership capabilities. Additionally, Surie and Ashley (2008) acknowledged that undertaking diverse entrepreneurial responsibilities and engaging in socialisation with other entrepreneurial leaders contribute to the development of effective entrepreneurial leadership competencies. For Bagheri and Pihie (2011b), social interaction enables entrepreneurial leaders to improve their communication and networking skills. The process of learning and acquiring entrepreneurial leadership capabilities is significantly facilitated through active engagement with others and learning from their experiences in a social learning context (Kempster and Cope, 2010). These findings imply that creating a supportive learning environment within UBIs is essential for fostering entrepreneurial leadership development among entrepreneurial teams. This can be achieved by promoting inter-team and intra-team learning through observation and self-reflection.

6.4.4 Self-regulated learning

Entrepreneurial leaders widely acknowledged the significance of self-regulated learning strategies for entrepreneurial leadership development. They highlighted the importance of actively tracking their own learning progress through identifying self-learning needs, developing learning goals, and monitoring self-learning progress within teams. These observations are well supported by the existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022; Cheng, 2011). In contrast to traditional learning approaches, self-regulated learning empowers entrepreneurial leaders to acquire new skills while considering their personal and socio-cultural factors, leading to enhanced intrinsic motivation for learning (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022; Cheng, 2011). According to Cheng (2011), self-regulated learning enables learners to take charge of their learning process by employing various strategies like self-regulation, monitoring their activities, assessing the content, identifying learning needs, predicting outcomes, and managing time and information effectively.

It is argued that self-regulated learning can be particularly effective in the dynamic team context, where entrepreneurial leaders face multiple challenges while handling a diverse range of entrepreneurial responsibilities. Entrepreneurial leaders acknowledged that SRL is essential for fostering mutual learning among team members and accomplishing the long-term objectives of entrepreneurial endeavours undertaken by teams. According to Ahmed and Harrison (2022), self-regulated learning is paramount for team success as it enables the learner to align their thoughts, emotions, and actions with their learning objectives to attain larger team objectives. This method of learning can be effective for early-stage entrepreneurial leaders where overall group success is contingent upon individual collaboration. However, despite its crucial importance, there remains a gap in the existing literature regarding a widely accepted model on how self-regulated learning can facilitate new venture creation among entrepreneurial

leaders at both individual and team levels. Further exploration and research in this area are needed to better understand the dynamics of self-regulated learning in the entrepreneurial context.

6.5 Entrepreneurial Leadership Development: An Empirical Model

This study aimed to explore the challenges and competencies faced by entrepreneurial leaders within team environments at UBIs, while also proposing an empirical model for entrepreneurial leadership development. This section focuses on addressing the fourth research question: How do contextual factors impact the development of competencies for emerging entrepreneurial leaders in university-business incubators, and how can these factors be incorporated into a team-based competency model? This question aligns with the fourth research objective: *to propose a team-based competency model for entrepreneurial leadership development.*

A model for developing entrepreneurial leadership is proposed based on empirical assertions extracted from 40 entrepreneurial leaders' perspectives associated with 18 entrepreneurial teams at UBIs (see Figure 31). The proposed model is supported by a variety of learning strategies. According to the model, developing entrepreneurial leadership is a complex social phenomenon influenced by a several sociocultural factors. As a result, entrepreneurial leadership learning cannot be confined to a single learning strategy; rather, entrepreneurial leaders must use a combination of learning mechanisms to develop their entrepreneurial skills and cope with business challenges in a dynamic team context. The model implies that entrepreneurial leadership learning is a cyclical process, and entrepreneurial leaders may use a combination of learning strategies to improve their entrepreneurial competencies (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022). This model is compatible with prior studies that explored entrepreneurial

leadership development across settings (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011b; Okudan and Rzasa, 2006; Roomi and Harrison, 2010, Leitch et al., 2013). As previously discussed, four broad categories of entrepreneurial leadership learning methods emerged from the perspectives of entrepreneurial leaders, which include classroom-based learning, project-based learning, social learning, and self-regulated learning.

The model offers new insights into entrepreneurial leadership development literature, particularly in the context of UBIs. The suggested model establishes the groundwork for viewing entrepreneurial leadership through the lens of competencies. This implies that entrepreneurial leadership is seen as a process, and it suggests that these competencies are something that can be acquired, nurtured, and are interconnected (Baron and Ensly 2006; Lans and Mulder 2009). The model recognises contextual factors that shape entrepreneurial behaviours – validating the findings of earlier studies on EL contending that socio-economic factors can influence entrepreneurial leadership learning and development (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022; Bagheri and Pihie, 2022; Harrison, 2016; Leitch et al., 2013). This model contributes to assessing entrepreneurial leadership development in teams by providing an empirical foundation for research based on an all-inclusive approach to competencies. Figure 30 illustrates how competencies can be acquired and developed through interconnected team-based learning strategies (Baron and Ensly, 2006; Lans and Mulder, 2009).

Figure 30 Illustration of entrepreneurial leadership development model

Entrepreneurial leadership in teams is a multifaceted process dependent on an intricate interplay of individual, business function, and contextual factors. While several authors have underscored the significance of entrepreneurial teams, emphasising their superior performance compared to individual efforts (Schjoedt and Kraus, 2009), However, the existing literature lack precise knowledge in comprehending the intricacies of team leadership development and its impact on team success (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022; Chen, 2007). This research aims to bridge this gap by proposing a model that elucidates the dynamics of team learning and its influence on overall team success.

Team learning is a multifaceted social process closely connected to various socio-cultural factors. Teams, although they have the advantage of quicker learning compared to individuals, grapple with heightened uncertainty and the structured team framework which is closely connected to their surrounding environment (McMullen and Shepherd, 2006). Thus, entrepreneurial teams are compelled to devise strategies and objectives to augment the knowledge and skills of their members, thereby optimising team success and enhancing overall team effectiveness (Cope, 2003). An effective leader plays a pivotal role in this endeavour by establishing a clear vision and empowering each member to contribute to its realisation (Cardon et al., 2005).

Entrepreneurial leadership is distinguished by its innovative, proactive, and risk-taking attributes, enabling entrepreneurial teams to identify and exploit business opportunities within a competitive environment (Gupta et al., 2004; Harrison et al., 2018). However, there is a paucity of discussion in the existing literature regarding how entrepreneurial leadership manifests within teams and how learning-oriented entrepreneurial leaders influence team outcomes. This issue assumes paramount significance for entrepreneurial teams, as their journey typically commences with a vague business idea and culminates in a shared vision, fostering creativity, and enhancing team participation throughout the entrepreneurial journey

(Ensley et al., 2006). Thus, it becomes crucial to recognise the contextual conditions under which team leadership foster entrepreneurial performance (Stewart et al., 2011).

Despite being a crucial research phenomenon, the nexus between team leadership and entrepreneurial outcomes has received limited theoretical attention (Horvatinovic et al., 2023). Morgeson et al. (2010) contends that the leadership process within a team hinge on the functional capabilities of the team, contingent upon contextual factors. These contingencies are broadly categorised into three main types in mainstream leadership literature, encompassing task characteristics, team characteristics, and team member characteristics (Greer and Van Kleef, 2010). However, this conceptualisation of understanding team complexities remains abstract and lacks a precise view of the elements defining team processes and their learning outcomes. Fiedler (1978) posits that leadership does not emerge in vacuum; therefore, to gain a richer understanding of team performance, an understanding of leader traits within situational factors is crucial. As a result, contemporary research has begun to explore how contextual factors might influence leadership and its outcomes, particularly within a team context. However, contextual leadership is a broad concept, and how these factors influence leadership practices, and how leadership unfolds within contextual settings, remains understudied (Day and Antonakis, 2012).

Given the growing body of research in this area, there exists limited knowledge about dominant paradigms for studying contextual leadership and little agreement on the best strategies for its development and exercise (Hackman and Wageman, 2007). John (2006) proposed a categorisation of leadership into two contexts: the omnibus context, which involves a broad consideration of contextual or environmental influences on leadership, and the discrete context, which deals with specific situational variables influencing the leadership process, such as task, social, and physical context. Despite its applicability in organisational behaviour research, John's conceptualisation of leadership does not address how it facilitates team leadership, team

learning, and their impact on team outcomes. Hence, it is imperative to conduct a comprehensive analysis of leadership learning that encompasses factors at both the micro and macro levels that affect leadership learning in teams. This study, through an examination of the personal, business function, and contextual factors of entrepreneurial leaders, offers a nuanced comprehension of entrepreneurial leadership development, drawing insights from these factors. Personal and business function factors are recognised as micro-level elements involving personal qualifications, experience, self-awareness, and functional competencies (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011b; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). In contrast, contextual factors encompass broad macro-level influences, including the social, institutional, and governmental factors that shape entrepreneurial leadership development within dynamic team contexts. Osborn et al. (2002) noted that macro perspectives were one of the most frequently overlooked areas of leadership research, and they emphasised the significance of considering the leadership context using macro-level variables (e.g., external environment, technological developments) and theoretical perspectives.

On the other hand, micro factors underpinned by entrepreneurial leaders' personal factors also have a significant impact on the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies. These factors comprise a lack of entrepreneurial knowledge and skills, experience, and education. Developing entrepreneurial leaders' personal competencies enable them to cope with complex team challenges and achieve entrepreneurial success in dynamic business environment (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Likewise, the importance of business function factors in the development of entrepreneurial leadership is widely acknowledged as key determinant of entrepreneurial success (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021, Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Entrepreneurial leaders must have a comprehensive understanding of marketing, finance, and human resources, among other business functions to perform well in team settings (Clark,

2020; Harrison et al., 2018; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). This necessitates provision of training, workshops, and mentoring opportunities to entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs to develop their functional competencies to cope with business functional challenges and remain competitive (Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). In addition, sociocultural factors significantly influence an individual's leadership style and their performance in team. The importance of cultural norms, values, and societal expectations in determining how individuals perceive leadership and leadership competencies cannot be overstated (Oc, 2018; Leitch et al., 2013). Different cultures may place a premium on distinct leadership qualities, making it essential for aspiring entrepreneurial leaders to navigate this complex environment. These dynamics determine how entrepreneurial leaders communicate, build networks, and obtain resources to uplift their entrepreneurial ventures and achieve entrepreneurial success.

Contextual factors, such as the industry in which an entrepreneurial leader operates, the competitive landscape, and the regulatory environment, play a crucial role in determining leadership competencies. Entrepreneurial leaders must be attuned to their particular context in order to make informed decisions and effectively navigate obstacles. The role of government in providing essential business resources, registration services, and suitable environment that nurture entrepreneurial endeavours determine the success of emerging start-ups. The significance of contextual factors is widely acknowledged as critical determinant of entrepreneurial success. According to Harrison et al. (2018), contextual factors have a significant impact on the potential risk-taking, innovativeness, opportunity spotting, and exploitation abilities of entrepreneurial leaders. Therefore, it is important to consider the influence of these factors on entrepreneurial leadership learning and development. The study findings validate that organisational culture, learner attitudes, communication channels, pre-existing values, family dynamics, resources, experience, and the role of institutions all play a role in shaping entrepreneurial leadership learning in UBI teams (Harrison et al., 2018).

Although these factors are of utmost importance, their empirical validity in entrepreneurial contexts is limited.

The model implies that entrepreneurial leadership learning in teams is a simultaneous learning process that combines classroom-based learning, project-based learning, social learning, and self-regulated learning methods. Traditional classroom-based learning serves as the foundation for fostering the development of entrepreneurial leadership. This conventional classroom setting allows learners to garner insights from instructors and experts, while also receiving valuable feedback on their entrepreneurial challenges and prospects. Project-based learning plays a pivotal role in nurturing entrepreneurial leadership skills as it involves actively participating in real-world entrepreneurial situations, gaining practical experience in the process. In contrast, social learning involves observing the behaviours and actions of other entrepreneurial leaders and adopting their strategies as part of the entrepreneurial leadership development journey. Meanwhile, self-regulated learning empowers entrepreneurial leaders to employ flexible, self-monitored learning strategies. This approach aids them in identifying areas where they need improvement and tracking their learning progress through meticulous planning and the establishment of learning objectives. This approach to cultivating entrepreneurial leadership competencies is in line with earlier research (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022; Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Bagheri and Pihie, 2011b; Okudan and Rzasa, 2006; Roomi and Harrison, 2011), which has advocated for combining traditional and modern learning strategies as effective methods for developing entrepreneurial leadership competencies.

Drawing upon the aforementioned premises, it becomes apparent that entrepreneurial leadership development is a multifaceted concept shaped by various contextual factors. Consequently, it is imperative for educators and policymakers to take these factors into account

when formulating strategies for enhancing entrepreneurial leadership knowledge and skills among emerging leaders. By doing so, they can effectively contribute to fostering new venture creation and achieving entrepreneurial success.

Figure 31 Entrepreneurial leadership development model

6.6 Summary

This chapter presented the findings of the present study in relation to existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership, covering the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and their development in a dynamic team context. The chapter addressed research questions based on empirical findings and highlighted how contextual factors shape and influence entrepreneurial leadership development in university-based business incubators. Personal, business function, and contextual factors were identified as key determinants of entrepreneurial leadership development in UBIs from a developing economy's context.

The chapter also discussed the core challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders, which include personal, business function, and contextual challenges as key barriers impeding entrepreneurial growth in UBIs. To address these challenges, entrepreneurial leaders identified self-competencies, organising competencies, interpersonal competencies, entrepreneurial competencies, and conceptual competencies as core entrepreneurial leadership competencies in the context of a dynamic team.

Finally, the chapter presented key methods and processes of entrepreneurial leadership development in teams. The findings revealed that entrepreneurial leadership learning and development is a complex and concurrent learning process supported by a variety of learning strategies such as classroom-based learning, project-based learning, social learning, and self-regulated learning. In conclusion, the results indicate that when fostering entrepreneurial learning among future leaders in team settings, it is essential to consider the sociocultural factors of the learners. The findings provide a foundation for conceptualising entrepreneurial leadership as a team process. The proposed model enriches the debate on existing models of

entrepreneurial leadership learning and development and highlights the importance of contextual factors in shaping and influencing entrepreneurial leadership development in UBIs.

7 Conclusion

7.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to provide a thorough overview of the thesis, including its objectives, research questions, theoretical, empirical, and methodological contributions. The key findings of this study are presented and discussed in terms of policy and research implications. Furthermore, this chapter identifies key research gaps and makes recommendations for future research while acknowledging the limitations of the study.

7.1.1 Thesis overview

This research aimed to explore entrepreneurial leadership in the context of business incubators by specifically focusing on UBIs in Pakistan. This study examined entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and entrepreneurial leadership development from a team perspective. The findings of the study have expanded our understanding of entrepreneurial leadership from an individualistic towards a team perspective and have contributed to the broadening of the theoretical understanding of the concept that remained underexplored.

7.1.2 Aim, objectives, and research questions

This research aimed to explore entrepreneurial leadership in the context of business incubators by specifically focusing on UBIs in Pakistan. This study examined entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and entrepreneurial leadership development from a team perspective. The study was guided by an interpretivist-constructionist perspective to comprehending the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders from their

subjective experiences. Based on empirical evidence, the study proposed a model for entrepreneurial leadership development in teams that expands the theoretical knowledge of entrepreneurial leadership by incorporating a team-based conceptualisation.

To achieve the above aim, the following research objectives were outlined:

1. To identify the challenges of nascent entrepreneurial leaders working as teams in university-based business incubators in Pakistan.
2. To identify the competencies required for teams to cope with the challenges of new venture creation.
3. To explain the methods and processes through which entrepreneurial leaders can learn and develop competencies at the team level.
4. To propose a team-based competency model for nascent entrepreneurial leaders working at university-business incubators.

This study sought to address following four research questions:

1. What are the main challenges faced by nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-based business incubators in Pakistan?
2. What entrepreneurial leadership competencies do entrepreneurial leaders require in order to overcome these challenges and become successful?
3. How can these competencies be developed in a team setting within the context of university-business incubators in Pakistan?
4. How do contextual factors influence the development of competencies for nascent entrepreneurial leaders in university-business incubators, and how can these factors be integrated into a team-based competency model?

7.2 Literature review

The research objectives were achieved through a comprehensive review of the literature on the theoretical evolution of entrepreneurial leadership, its various perspectives, and their limitations. A systematic literature review was also conducted in order to map and assess the existing literature on entrepreneurial leadership competencies, their impact on organisations, and entrepreneurial leadership development. The existing literature on EL competencies, as well as current models for EL development, was methodically reviewed, and significant gaps in the research were identified.

7.2.1 Systematic literature review

The findings of the review highlight the importance of entrepreneurial leadership competencies in identifying business opportunities, overcoming challenges, and maintaining long-term competitiveness (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013). The findings of SLR confirmed that entrepreneurial leadership competencies such as proactivity, innovativeness, risk-taking proclivity, vision-articulation, motivation, communication, influence, teamwork, creativity, and risk-taking are critical to organisational success (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Bagheri et al., 2013a; Chen, 2007; Clark, 2020; Gupta et al., 2004; Harrison et al., 2018).

Personal, interpersonal, functional, technological, human, and conceptual competencies were recognised as key competencies for entrepreneurial leaders in the literature (Ahmed and Harrison, 2021; Guo, 2009; Swiercz and Lydon, 2002). Entrepreneurial leadership courses, project-based learning, multidisciplinary courses, entrepreneurship clubs, and cocurricular activities were identified as main sources for developing entrepreneurial leadership competencies (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Okudan and Rzasa, 2006; Roomi and Harrison, 2011).

The SLR found that research on entrepreneurial leadership competencies is evolving and understudied in various contexts. More research is required to investigate, for example, EL competencies from a leader-follower perspective, EL competencies in a group context, an integrated model of competencies from a leader-follower and group perspective, and the development of EL competencies at both individual and team levels across organisational settings. Furthermore, dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership courses, their content and design, and their impact on entrepreneurial leaders' learning processes, as well as how these competencies can be developed among established entrepreneurial leaders, may provide novel insights into the literature on entrepreneurial leadership.

7.3 Methodology

The purpose of the research was to examine the challenges, competencies, and development of entrepreneurial leadership from the perspective of nascent entrepreneurial leaders affiliated with UBIs. The study adopted a qualitative research method, with an abductive approach employed to comprehend the experiences of entrepreneurial leaders. An interpretivist constructionist perspective was adopted to understand the reality of entrepreneurial leadership from the perspectives of the nascent entrepreneurial leaders (Clark, 2020; Harrison, 2016).

To collect data from participants, an interview protocol was developed based on the literature review, research aims, objectives, and questions (Harrison, 2016). Data were obtained through semi-structured interviews with 40 entrepreneurial leaders from 18 teams operating at UBIs using a purposive sampling method. The study's findings revealed that personal, business function, and contextual challenges are the most common difficulties encountered by entrepreneurial leaders in university-based business incubators. To overcome these challenges, entrepreneurial leaders identified key competencies such as self-competencies, organising competencies, interpersonal competencies, entrepreneurial competencies, and conceptual

competencies as essential for effective team performance and success. A thematic analysis of entrepreneurial leaders' perspective revealed that entrepreneurial leadership learning and development can take place in a variety of ways, including classroom-based learning, project-based learning, social learning, and self-regulated learning (King et al., 2018).

7.4 Contribution to knowledge

This research provides a methodical and in-depth examination of the complexities of entrepreneurial leadership within teams. It serves as a foundation for transforming the concept of entrepreneurial leadership from an individual to a more inclusive and collective phenomenon. The empirical model proposed in this study provides a framework for analysing entrepreneurial leadership competencies in a team setting underscoring contextual factors. By incorporating a team-based competency approach, the study broadens the understanding of entrepreneurial leadership which has received little theoretical and empirical consideration in the existing literature.

7.4.1 Theoretical contributions

This study aimed to explore entrepreneurial leadership within teams, marking a paradigm shift in entrepreneurial leadership research by introducing a team-based framework. It offers a comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurial leadership within the context of team start-ups at UBIs, shedding light on the subjective experiences of entrepreneurial leaders. Moreover, it breaks new ground by presenting an empirical model for entrepreneurial leadership development within teams from a developing economy context.

Prior research has somewhat neglected the significance of entrepreneurial leadership within team settings (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022; Chen, 2007; Cai et al., 2018). Chen (2007) investigated the relationship between team creativity and entrepreneurial leadership in enhancing new venture innovation. Although their findings demonstrated a positive correlation between entrepreneurial leadership and team creativity, its quantitative methodology through surveys fell short in providing a deep understanding of entrepreneurial leaders' practices within teams. Similarly, Cai et al. (2018) explored entrepreneurial leadership's impact on workplace creativity, revealing that teams led by entrepreneurial leaders tend to generate superior creative outcomes compared to those led by traditional leaders. However, their reliance on quantitative methods limited the depth of analysis regarding entrepreneurial leaders' experiences within teams and lacked an empirical model specific to team contexts. Conversely, Ahmed and Harrison (2022) proposed a team-based model for entrepreneurial leadership development, albeit lacking sufficient empirical support.

In contrast, this study offers a fresh perspective on the challenges, competencies, and developmental aspects of entrepreneurial leadership within teams. Additionally, this research is a pioneering qualitative study that introduces an empirical competency model for entrepreneurial leadership development within team environments, contributing significantly to the literature by considering contextual factors. Early models of entrepreneurial leadership (EL) development, such as those proposed by Bagheri and Pihie (2011) and Ahmed and Ramzan (2013), offered a narrow view by emphasising individualistic approaches and lacking empirical support. Similarly, while our conceptual model (Ahmed and Harrison, 2022) aimed to provide a comprehensive team-oriented perspective on EL development, it too relies primarily on theoretical frameworks. The proposed model in this study underpinned by contextual factors present a holistic understanding of EL development and its outcome from a developing economy context, thus provides a nuanced understanding of EL development from a contextual perspective. The proposed model in this study serves as a foundation for future

research endeavours, encouraging further exploration of entrepreneurial leadership development through quantitative approaches and enhancing the generalisability of findings across diverse contexts.

7.4.2 Empirical contributions

This study offers important empirical insights that provides a nuanced understanding of the challenges, competencies, and development of entrepreneurial leadership, taking into account contextual variables from the context of UBIs, an area remained understudied in the existing literature in both developed and developing economy's context.

The challenges identified through empirical evidence extend beyond UBIs to encompass similar socio-cultural contexts. Similarly, the competencies and development of entrepreneurial leadership are applicable to various entrepreneurial platforms striving to cultivate leadership skills among both emerging and established leaders. Moreover, this study highlights a clear correlation between entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development, emphasising the significance of contextual factors in shaping leadership outcomes (Harrison, 2016). This research stands as a pioneering effort, offering a comprehensive examination of entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and their development through an in-depth analysis of team leadership processes. Additionally, the empirical findings from this study contribute to a better understanding of the significant challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders and competencies required for their success, particularly within the context of a developing economy. This insight informs both policy and practice in the field (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Harrison, 2016).

7.4.3 Methodological contributions

This study makes important contributions to the field of entrepreneurial leadership by providing a comprehensive and systematic examination of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development. By conducting the first systematic literature review in entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development, this study provides a nuanced and profound understanding of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and validates the empirical and theoretical assertions of prior studies (Bagheri and Pihie, 2011a; Bagheri and Pihie 2013; Clark, 2020; Harrison et al., 2018). By conducting the first SLR on EL competencies, their impact, and development, this research identified key and recurring competencies and development, that presented dispersed literature. Future researchers can leverage these findings to construct a comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development, applicable across diverse economic landscapes, including both developed and developing economies (Bagheri and Harrison, 2020). The findings of the SLR also identify key research gaps and suggest future research directions, thus contributing to the theoretical development of entrepreneurial leadership (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009).

Furthermore, the study pioneers a team-based perspective on entrepreneurial leadership competencies, making a unique and innovative contribution to the field. Previous research has primarily focused on either a one-dimensional view of entrepreneurial leadership by focusing on leaders (Bagheri and Pihie, 2013; Clark, 2020) or a leader-follower perspective (Harrison, 2016). However, this is the first empirical research to examine the competencies of entrepreneurial leadership in a team context, providing a deeper understanding of the topic.

7.4.4 Practical contributions

This study provides valuable insights for policymaking aimed at fostering entrepreneurial leadership and cultivating the necessary competencies among emerging entrepreneurial leaders within UBI settings. The research findings serve as a basis for informing policies and best practices related to nurturing an entrepreneurial culture, identifying training needs, and fostering the development of entrepreneurial leadership skills specifically within the context of a developing economy.

The empirical findings of this study equip nascent entrepreneurial leaders with well-informed decision-making process, addressing the intricacies of team dynamics and the competencies essential for navigating the diverse challenges encountered in early-stage start-ups. Moreover, the results offer insights into effective approaches and strategies for acquiring entrepreneurial leadership skills within team environments, enabling leaders to critically evaluate learning strategies and implement effective tools to enhance their entrepreneurial capabilities.

Additionally, this study identified the significant contextual factors influencing entrepreneurial leadership outcomes within UBI settings. Consequently, the empirical findings serve as a guiding framework for incubation managers, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), and entrepreneurial leaders to comprehend the complexities of entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and development, facilitating the formulation of strategies that consider contextual nuances. Of particular importance, these empirical implications hold relevance for stakeholders such as the Higher Education Commission of Pakistan, the National Incubation Centre, Small and Medium Enterprise Development Authority, and Social Education Environment Development Pakistan. Furthermore, the findings offer potential for replication in other developing economies with similar socioeconomic landscapes, extending the applicability and impact of the study's insights.

7.5 Study limitations

7.5.1 Sample

This study concentrated on only 18 UBIs established at Pakistani public and private HEIs. The purpose of this study was to provide a rich insight into the challenges, competencies, and entrepreneurial leadership development of entrepreneurial leaders; therefore, the findings are highly contextual, may not be generalised to other sectors, and may not be representative of Pakistan's entire incubation community, i.e., technology incubators, agricultural incubators, and industry incubators. Even though the data were collected from all regions of the country, the conclusions are only applicable to UBIs. This necessitates the importance of further research into entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development in other incubation centres operating throughout the country using a quantitative method. Despite this limitation, this research provides valuable insights into the phenomenon of entrepreneurial leadership in the context of business incubators and lays the groundwork for future research in this field.

7.5.2 Context

This study's findings are limited to developing economy's context, specifically Pakistan. As a result, the findings of the study may not be applicable to other countries or regions with distinct economic, cultural, and political dynamics. As a result, caution must be exercised when interpreting and extrapolating the findings of this study to other contexts. Furthermore, the study's findings may not accurately reflect the experiences of entrepreneurial leaders in

developed economies with a different entrepreneurial ecosystem and leadership challenges. Future research exploring entrepreneurial leadership challenges and competencies in both developed and developing economies may produce deeper insights and expand the theoretical and empirical scope of entrepreneurial leadership literature.

7.5.3 Entrepreneurial leadership development model

This study provides fresh insights into entrepreneurial leadership practices and development within teams; however, it is important to note that the model developed is solely based on the responses of the study participants. Other methods and tools for developing entrepreneurial leadership, such as training programmes, mentorship, and coaching may have different effects on the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and should be investigated further in future research. In addition, incorporating other EL learning strategies, such as classroom learning approaches, i.e., flipped learning, scenario-based learning, and problem-based learning, into the proposed model may strengthen its scope and applicability in a wider context. Furthermore, the findings of this study are restricted to the context of Pakistan and may not be generalised to other countries or cultural contexts.

7.6 Direction for future research

7.6.1 Exploring other BICs

This study focuses solely on university-based business incubators and does not cover other types of incubators, such as those in the technology, industrial, or agricultural sectors. Future research should aim to broaden the scope of the study by exploring the competencies and

development of entrepreneurial leadership in these incubators. This could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in these industries and contribute to the development of better entrepreneurial leadership practices and methods. This would ultimately benefit new ventures and support their growth and success, particularly in developing economies.

7.6.2 Measurement tools

This research provides valuable insight into entrepreneurial leadership competencies in teams, particularly within university-based business incubators. It serves as a foundation for future studies to further develop a robust understanding of entrepreneurial leadership competencies in teams. Further research could build upon the proposed entrepreneurial leadership competency model presented in this study to validate and generalise its findings across various contexts and industries by employing quantitative research methods. Additionally, future studies could explore the impact of entrepreneurial leadership development interventions, such as training programmes and mentorship, the role of UBIs' administrations or leadership, and cultural factors on enhancing entrepreneurial leadership competencies within teams.

7.6.3 Gender perspective

This study has provided valuable insights into team-based entrepreneurial leadership competencies, but it is just a starting point. Further research is needed to explore the gender aspect of entrepreneurial leadership, which has received limited attention till now. A deeper understanding of gender differences in entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and entrepreneurial leadership development could be gained by conducting research on how male and female entrepreneurial leaders perceive these challenges and how they develop their

skills to overcome them. Such research could significantly advance our understanding of gender differences in entrepreneurial leadership and contribute to the development of more gender-inclusive policies and practices in both developed and developing economies.

7.6.4 Contextual barriers

Future studies could explore the impact of government policies, the entrepreneurial ecosystem, and national culture on the advancement of entrepreneurial leadership. This investigation would provide deeper insights into how these factors affect the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and entrepreneurial outcomes in both developed and developing countries. By comparing various contexts, valuable conclusions can be drawn about the effective promotion of entrepreneurial cultures and the enhancement of entrepreneurial leadership competencies. Moreover, future studies may benefit from exploring the impact of macro-factors on entrepreneurial leadership development, such as political conditions and economic situations in each country setting.

7.7 Summary

The research aimed to examine the dimensions of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and their development within teams in the context of university-based business incubators in Pakistan. A qualitative research method was adopted, utilising semi-structured interviews with 40 entrepreneurial leaders from 18 start-ups, and a systematic literature review was conducted to gain an in-depth understanding of the topic. The findings provided a comprehensive view of entrepreneurial leadership competencies and proposed a model for their development within teams. This research contributes to the current body of knowledge by offering a new

perspective on the complex phenomenon of entrepreneurial leadership practices within teams, shifting the focus of entrepreneurial leadership from an individualistic to a shared perspective. Additionally, the proposed model can be used to develop a framework for assessing entrepreneurial leadership competencies in a team setting, broadening the concept of entrepreneurial leadership by introducing a competency-based perspective.

References

- Abbas, M. K. (2014) The challenges of entrepreneurial leadership in Nigeria. Journal of Leadership and Management Studies (JOLMS). Vol.1 (1), pp.52–59.
- Abbas, S. and Tatfi, M. (2010) Entrepreneurial leadership: certainly a tool not a means to organizational success. Leadership. Vol.1 (2), pp.119.
- Acs, Z. (2008) How is entrepreneurship good for economic growth? In: Entrepreneurship, Growth and Public Policy. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Acs, Z. J. and Audretsch, D. B. (1988) Innovation in large and small firms: an empirical analysis. The American economic review. Vol. 78 (4), pp.678–690.
- Agbenyegah, A. T. (2013) Challenges facing rural entrepreneurship in selected areas in South Africa. North-West University, SA.
- Agbim, K. C. (2013) An Exploratory Study of the Entrepreneurial Leadership Capabilities of Entrepreneurs in Anambra State, Nigeria. Journal of Business Management. Vol.2 (9), pp.68–75.
- Agus, A. and Hassan, Z. (2010) The structural influence of entrepreneurial leadership, communication skills, determination and motivation on sales and customer satisfaction. International Journal of Business and Development Studies. Vol.2 (1), pp.109–130.
- Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2021) Challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in driving innovation at DIY laboratories. Technology Analysis & Strategic Management. Vol.33 (10), pp.1132–1146.
- Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2022) Entrepreneurial leadership development in teams: A conceptual model. The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation. Vol. 0 (2022), pp.1–13
- Ahmed, A. and Ramzan, M. (2013) A learning and improvement model in entrepreneurial leadership. IOSR Journal of Business and Management. Vol.11 (6), pp.50–60.
- Akbari, M., Bagheri, A., Imani, S. and Asadnezhad, M. (2021) Does entrepreneurial leadership encourage innovation work behavior? The mediating role of creative self-efficacy and support for innovation. European Journal of Innovation Management. Vol.24 (1), pp.1–22.
- Al-Khalifah, B. (2014) Entrepreneurial Leadership in Kuwaiti private firms. University of Stirling, UK.
- Almahdi, H. K. (2019) Promotion and participation of Saudi universities towards the development of entrepreneurial leadership—An empirical study in Saudi Arabian context. Journal of Entrepreneurship Education. Vol.22 (6), pp.1–14.

- Anderson, A. R. and Jack, S. L. (2008) Role typologies for enterprising education: the professional artisan? Journal of small business and enterprise development. Vol.15 (2), pp.259–273.
- Anderson, A. R. and Smith, R. (2007) The moral space in entrepreneurship: an exploration of ethical imperatives and the moral legitimacy of being enterprising. Entrepreneurship and Regional Development. Vol.19 (6), pp.479–497.
- Anesta, E., Caceda, A. and Michalka, S. (2004) Development of woodcarving small and medium-sized enterprises in Okahandja, Namibia. unpublished BSc thesis, Worcester Polytechnic Institute, Worcester, MA.
- Ansari, S., Bell, J., Iyer, B. and Schlesinger, P. (2014) Educating entrepreneurial leaders. Journal of Entrepreneurship Education. Vol.17(2), pp.31–45.
- Anyanwu, C., and Oad, S. (2016) Entrepreneurial leadership and organizational creativity in the collectivist context: The moderating role of emotional intelligence. International Journal of Management and Administrative Sciences. Vol.4 (2), pp.1-12.
- Antonakis, J., Schriesheim, C. A., Donovan, J. A., Gopalakrishna-Pillai, K., Pellegrini, E., & Rossomme, J. L. (2004). Methods for studying leadership. In J. Antonakis, A. T. Cianciolo, & R. J. Sternberg (Eds.), The nature of leadership (pp. 48 – 70). Greenwich, CT7 Sage.
- Aouni, Z. and Surlemont, B. (2009) Towards a model of the learning needs of the effective entrepreneur. International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business. Vol.8 (3), pp.431–446.
- Ariyani, D. and Zuhaery, M. (2021) Principal’s Innovation and Entrepreneurial Leadership to Establish a Positive Learning Environment. European Journal of Educational Research. Vol.10 (1), pp.63–74.
- Atiq, M. (2014) Sustainable corporate entrepreneurship: insights from Pakistan. University of Southampton, UK.
- Aziz, S. A. A. and Abiddin, N. Z. (2022) Leadership Style and Entrepreneurial Leadership among University Students: A Literature Review. International Journal of Learning and Development. Vol.12 (3), pp.1522–1522.
- Bagheri, A. and Akbari, M. (2018) The impact of entrepreneurial leadership on nurses’ innovation behavior. Journal of Nursing Scholarship. Vol.50 (1), pp.28–35.
- Bagheri, A. and Harrison, C. (2020) Entrepreneurial leadership measurement: a multi-dimensional construct. Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development. Vol.27 (4), pp.659–679.
- Bagheri, A. and Lope Pihie, Z. A. (2013) Role of university entrepreneurship programs in developing students’ entrepreneurial leadership competencies: perspectives from Malaysian undergraduate students. Journal of Education for Business. Vol.88 (1), pp.51–61.

- Bagheri, A., Lope Pihie, Z. A. and Krauss, S. E. (2013a) Entrepreneurial leadership competencies among Malaysian university student entrepreneurial leaders. Asia Pacific Journal of Education. Vol.33 (4), pp.493–508.
- Bagheri, A., Pihie, Z. A. L. and Krauss, S. E. (2013b) Entrepreneurial leadership self-efficacy: A Focus on Malaysian student entrepreneurial leaders. Archives Des Sciences. Vol.66 (1), pp.690–708.
- Bagheri, A. and Pihie, Z. A. L. (2009) An exploratory study of entrepreneurial leadership development of university students. European Journal of Social Sciences. Vol.11 (1), pp.177–190.
- Bagheri, A. Lope Pihie, Z.A. L. (2011a) On Becoming an Entrepreneurial Leader: A Focus on the Impacts of University Entrepreneurship Programs. American Journal of Applied Sciences. Vol.8 (9), pp.884–892.
- Bagheri, A. and Pihie, Z. A. L. (2011b) Entrepreneurial leadership: Towards a model for learning and development. Human Resource Development International. Vol.14 (4), pp.447–463.
- Bagheri, A., Pihie, Z. A. L. and Akmaliah, Z. (2010) Role of family in entrepreneurial leadership development of university students. World Applied Sciences Journal. Vol.11 (4), pp.434–442.
- Bagheri, A. and Pihie, Z. A. L. (2012) Entrepreneurial leadership competencies development among malaysian university students: The pervasive role of experience and social interaction. Pertanika Journal of Social Science and Humanities. Vol.20 (2), pp.539–562.
- Ballein, K. M. (1998) Entrepreneurial leadership characteristics of SNEs emerge as their role develops. Nursing administration quarterly. Vol.22 (2), pp.60–9.
- Baron, R. A. and Ensley, M. D. (2006) Opportunity recognition as the detection of meaningful patterns: Evidence from comparisons of novice and experienced entrepreneurs. Management science. Vol.52 (9), pp.1331–1344.
- Bass, B. M. (1990) From transactional to transformational leadership: Learning to share the vision. Organizational dynamics. Vol.18 (3), pp.19–31.
- Baxter, J. and Eyles, J. (1997) Evaluating qualitative research in social geography: establishing ‘rigour’ in interview analysis. Transactions of the Institute of British geographers. Vol.22 (4), pp.505–525.
- Bell, E., Bryman, A. and Harley, B. (2022) Business research methods. Oxford University Press.
- Blumberg, B., Cooper, D. and Schindler, P. (2014) EBOOK: Business Research Methods. McGraw Hill.
- Blake, R. and Mouton, J. (1964) The managerial grid: The key to leadership excellence. Houston: Gulf Publishing Company.

- Blake, R. R. and McCauley, A. A. (1991) Leadership Dilemmas-Grid Solutions. Houston, TX: Gulf Publishing Company.
- Blake, R. R. and Mouton, J. S. (1978) The new managerial grid: strategic new insights into a proven system for increasing organization productivity and individual effectiveness, plus a revealing examination of how your managerial style can affect your mental and physical health. Houston: Gulf Publishing Company.
- Blake, R. R. and Mouton, J. S. (1985) The managerial grid III, Houston, TX. Gulf publishing Company.
- Blanchard, K. H. (1985) A situational approach to managing people. Blanchard Training and Development. Escondido, CA.
- Blanchard, K. H., Zigarmi, D. and Zigarmi, P. (2013) Leadership and the One Minute Manager: Increasing Leadership Effectiveness through Situational Management II. New York: Harper Collins.
- Blanchard, K. and Hodges, P. (2003) The Servant Leader: Transforming Your Heart. Head, Hands & Habits, Nashville.
- Boettke, P. J. and Coyne, C. J. (2009) Context matters: Institutions and entrepreneurship. Foundations and Trends in Entrepreneurship. Vol.5 (3), pp.135–209.
- Boyatzis, R. E. (1991) The competent manager: A model for effective performance. John Wiley & Sons. New York Wiley.
- Blunt, P., and Jones, M. L. (1997) Exploring the limits of Western leadership theory in East Asia and Africa. Personnel Review. Vol. 26 (1), pp. 6–23.
- Bodolica, V. and Spraggon, M. (2021) Incubating innovation in university settings: building entrepreneurial mindsets in the future generation of innovative emerging market leaders. Journal of Education and Training. Vol.63 (4), pp.613–631.
- Boyatzis, R. E. (1998) Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development. Sage Publication.
- Brauckmann-Sajkiewicz, S. and Pashiardis, P. (2022) Entrepreneurial leadership in schools: linking creativity with accountability. International Journal of Leadership in Education. Vol.25 (5), pp.787–801.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. Qualitative research in psychology. Vol.3 (2), pp.77–101.
- Bryman, A. (2011) Research methods in the study of leadership. The SAGE handbook of leadership. Thousand Oaks, CA Sage Publication.
- Buller, P. F. and Finkle, T. A. (2013) The Hogan entrepreneurial leadership program: an innovative model of entrepreneurship education. Journal of Entrepreneurship Education. Vol.16, pp.113–131.

- Burrell, G. and Morgan, G. (2017) Sociological paradigms and organisational analysis: Elements of the sociology of corporate life. Routledge.
- Cai, W., Lysova, E. I., Khapova, S. N. and Bossink, B. A. (2019) Does entrepreneurial leadership foster creativity among employees and teams? The mediating role of creative efficacy beliefs. Journal of Business and Psychology. Vol.34 (2019), pp.203–217.
- Cameron, S. and Price, D. (2009) Business research methods: a practical approach. Kogan Page Publishers.
- Campos, J. D. S. (2021) Analysis of entrepreneurial leadership skills and sustainable employee productivity of MSMEs. Journal of Social Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice. Vol.1 (1), pp.12–27.
- Candolfi-Arballo, N., Hualde-Alfaro, A., Espinosa-Díaz, Y., Avitia-Carlos, P. and Rodríguez-Tapia, B. (2022) The Evaluation of Technological Competencies among Leaders of the Renewable Energy Industry: The Case of SMEs in Baja California, Mexico. Energies. Vol.15 (16), pp.2–20.
- Carey, J. C., Beitelspacher, L. S., Tosti-Kharas, J. and Swanson, E. (2021) A Resource-Efficient Modular Course Design for Co-Teaching Integrated Sustainability in Higher Education: Developing the Next Generation of Entrepreneurial Leaders. Entrepreneurship Education and Pedagogy. Vol.4 (2), pp.169–193.
- Carland, J. C. and Carland Jr, J. W. (2012) A model of shared entrepreneurial leadership. Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal. Vol.18 (2), pp.71-81.
- Carlyle, T. (1840) Lecture I. The Hero as Divinity. Odin. Paganism: Scandinavian Mythology. On Heroes, Hero-Worship, and the Heroic in History. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Carpenter, M. T. H. (2012) Cheerleader, Opportunity Seeker, and Master Strategist: ARL Directors as Entrepreneurial Leaders. College & Research Libraries. Vol.73 (1), pp.11–32.
- Castillo-Montoya, M. (2016) Preparing for interview research: The interview protocol refinement framework. The Qualitative Report. Vol.21 (5), pp.811–831.
- Chen, M.-H. (2007) Entrepreneurial leadership and new ventures: Creativity in entrepreneurial teams. Creativity and Innovation Management. Vol.16 (3), pp.239–249.
- Cheng, C. K. E. (2011) The role of self-regulated learning in enhancing learning performance. The International Journal of Research and Review. Vol.6 (1), pp.1–16.
- Choi, E. K. (2009) Entrepreneurial leadership in the Meiji cotton spinners' early conceptualisation of global competition. Business History. Vol.51 (6), pp.927–958.
- Churchill, R. Q., Agbodohu, W. and Arhenful, P. (2013) An Exploratory Study of Entrepreneurial Leadership Development of Polytechnic Students. Journal of Education and Practice. Vol.4 (24), pp.9–11.
- CIAWorldFactbook (2023) Pakistan: South Asia. (The World Factbook). [Online] Available: <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/countries/pakistan/>.

- Clark, C. and Harrison, C. (2017) Entrepreneurial leadership: Scotland, skills, and SMEs. In: British Academy of Management Conference 2017: Re-connecting management research with the disciplines: Shaping the research agenda for the social sciences.
- Clark, C. M. (2020) Entrepreneurial leadership: a study of Scottish small and medium-sized enterprises. University of the West of Scotland.
- Clark, C. M., Harrison, C., and Gibb, S. (2019) Developing a Conceptual Framework of Entrepreneurial Leadership: A Systematic Literature Review and Thematic Analysis. International Review of Entrepreneurship. Vol.17(3), pp. 347-384.
- Cogliser, C. C. and Brigham, K. H. (2004) The intersection of leadership and entrepreneurship: Mutual lessons to be learned. The Leadership Quarterly. Vol.15 (6), pp.771–799.
- Cohen, A. R. (2004) Building a company of leaders. Leader to Leader. Vol.2004 (34), pp.16–20.
- Connelly, M. S., Gilbert, J. A., Zaccaro, S. J., Threlfall, K. V., Marks, M. A. and Mumford, M. D. (2000) Exploring the relationship of leadership skills and knowledge to leader performance. The Leadership Quarterly. Vol.11 (1), pp.65–86.
- Cope, J. (2003) Entrepreneurial learning and critical reflection: Discontinuous events as triggers for 'higher-level' learning. Management learning. Vol.34 (4), pp.429–450.
- Cardon, M. S., Zietsma, C., Saporito, P., Matherne, B. P. and Davis, C. (2005) A tale of passion: New insights into entrepreneurship from a parenthood metaphor. Journal of business venturing. Vol.20 (1), pp.23–45.
- Covin, J. G. and Slevin, D. P. (1991) A conceptual model of entrepreneurship as firm behavior. Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice. Vol.16 (1), pp.7–26.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009) Research designs: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach. Sage Publication.
- Crotty, M. J. (1998) The foundations of social research: Meaning and perspective in the research process. The Foundations of Social Research. Sage Publication.
- Cunningham, J. B. and Lischeron, J. (1991) Defining entrepreneurship. Journal of small business management. Vol.29 (1), pp.45–61.
- Dansereau Jr, F., Graen, G. and Haga, W. J. (1975) A vertical dyad linkage approach to leadership within formal organizations: A longitudinal investigation of the role making process. Organizational Behaviour and Human Performance. Vol.13 (1), pp.46–78.
- Dardiri, A., Alfianto, I., Kuncoro, T., Suswanto, H. and Elmunsyah, H. (2018) Entrepreneurial leadership for excellent technical and vocational education institutions. World Transactions on Engineering and Technology Education. Vol.16 (4), p.441.
- Darling, J. R. and Beebe, S. A. (2007) Enhancing Entrepreneurial Leadership: A Focus on Key Communication Priorities. Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship. Vol.20 (2), pp.151–167.

- Davis, S. J., Haltiwanger, J. and Schuh, S. (1996) Small business and job creation: Dissecting the myth and reassessing the facts. Small Business Economics. Vol.8(4), pp.297–315.
- Day, D. V. (2000) Leadership development: A review in context. The Leadership Quarterly. Vol.11 (4), pp.581–613.
- Day, D. V. and Antonakis, J. (2012) Leadership: Past, present, and future. The nature of leadership. Sage Publication.
- DB (2020) Doing Business: Comparing Business Regulation in 190 Economies [Online]. World Bank. Organisation Report. Available: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/688761571934946384/pdf/Doing-Business-2020-Comparing-Business-Regulation-in-190-Economies.pdf> [Accessed 15 Apr 2023].
- Denyer, D. and Tranfield, D. (2009) Producing a systematic review. In: Buchanan, D.A.
- Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (2011) The Sage handbook of qualitative research. Sage Publication.
- Dess, G. G., Lumpkin, G. T. and Covin, J. G. (1997) Entrepreneurial strategy making and firm performance: Tests of contingency and configurational models. Strategic Management Journal. Vol.18 (9), pp.677–695.
- Devarajan, T. P., K. Ramachandran, and S. Ramnarayan. (2003) “Entrepreneurial leadership and thriving innovation activity.” In Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Global Business & Economic Development, Bangkok, Thailand.
- D’Intino, R. S., Boyles, T., Neck, C. P. and Hall, J. R. (2008) Visionary entrepreneurial leadership in the aircraft industry: The Boeing Company legacy. Journal of Management History. Vol.14 (1), pp.39–54.
- Dinh, J. E. and Lord, R. G. (2012) Implications of dispositional and process views of traits for individual difference research in leadership. The Leadership Quarterly. Vol.23 (4), pp.651–669.
- Easterby-Smith, M., Golden-Biddle, K. and Locke, K. (2008) Working with pluralism: Determining quality in qualitative research. Organizational Research Methods. Vol.11 (3), pp.419–429.
- Edmond, V. P., Brannon, D. L., Stewart, A. and Williams, J. (2017) Gender differences in entrepreneurial leadership skills training. Global Journal of Entrepreneurship. Vol.1 (2), pp.32–52.
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (2013) Top management teams and the performance of entrepreneurial firms. Small Business Economics. Vol.40 (4), pp.805–816.
- Ekpe, I., Mat, N. and Che Razak, R. (2011) Attributes, environment factors and women entrepreneurial activity: A literature review. Asian Social Science. Vol.7 (9), pp.124–130.

- El-Sabaa, S. (2001) The skills and career path of an effective project manager. International journal of project management. Vol.19 (1), pp.1–7.
- Ellingson, L. L. (2013) Analysis and representation across the continuum. Collecting and Interpreting Qualitative Materials. Sage Publication.
- Ensley, M. D., Pearce, C. L. and Hmieleski, K. M. (2006) The moderating effect of environmental dynamism on the relationship between entrepreneur leadership behavior and new venture performance. Journal of Business Venturing. Vol.21 (2), pp.243–263.
- Eraut, M. (1994) Developing professional knowledge and competence. Psychology Press.
- Eriksson, P. and Kovalainen, A. (2015) Qualitative methods in business research: A practical guide to social research. Sage Publication.
- Eshun, J. P. (2009) Business incubation as strategy. Business Strategy Series. Vol. 10 (3), pp. 156-166.
- ESP (2021) Pakistan Economic Survey [Online]. Finance Division, Government of Pakistan. Available:https://www.finance.gov.pk/survey/chapter_22/Economic%20Survey%202021-22.pdf [Accessed 15 Apr 2023].
- Etemad, H. (2013) The process of internationalization in emerging SMEs and emerging economies. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Evans, M. G. (1970) The effects of supervisory behavior on the path-goal relationship. Organizational Behaviour and Human Performance. Vol.5 (3), pp.277–298.
- Fernald, L. W., Solomon, G. T. and Tarabishy, A. (2005) A new paradigm: Entrepreneurial leadership. Southern business review. Vol.30 (2), pp.1–10.
- Fitzpatrick, R. (1994) Competence at Work: Models for Superior Performance. Personnel Psychology. Vol.47 (2), pp.448–460.
- Fiedler, F. E. (1978) The contingency model and the dynamics of the leadership process. In: Advances in experimental social psychology. New York Academic Press.
- Flamholtz, E. G. (2011) The leadership molecule hypothesis: implications for entrepreneurial organizations. International Review of Entrepreneurship. Vol.9 (3), pp.1–23.
- Fletcher, D. E. (2006) Entrepreneurial processes and the social construction of opportunity. Entrepreneurship & Regional Development. Vol.18 (5), pp.421–440.
- Fossey, E., Harvey, C., McDermott, F. and Davidson, L. (2002) Understanding and evaluating qualitative research. Australian & New Zealand journal of psychiatry. Vol.36 (6), pp.717–732.
- Frazier, B. J. and Niehm, L. S. (2006) Predicting the entrepreneurial intentions of non-business majors: A preliminary investigation. Presented at the Proceedings of the USASBE/SBI Conference, Tucson, AZ.

- Frederick, H. H., Kuratko, D. F. and O'Connor, A. (2015) Entrepreneurship: Theory/Process/Practice with Student Resource Access for 12 Months. Cengage AU.
- Freeman, D. and Siegfried Jr, R. L. (2015) Entrepreneurial leadership in the context of company start-up and growth. Journal of Leadership Studies. Vol.8 (4), pp.35–39.
- Gaglio, C. M. and Katz, J. A. (2001) The psychological basis of opportunity identification: Entrepreneurial alertness. Small Business Economics. Vol.16 (2), pp.95–111.
- Galloway, L., Kapasi, I. and Sang, K. (2015) Entrepreneurship, leadership, and the value of feminist approaches to understanding them. Journal of Small Business Management. Vol.53 (3), pp.683–692.
- GEM (2019) GEM 2019 / 2020 GLOBAL REPORT [Online]. Global Entrepreneurship Monitor. Organisation Report. Available: https://www.gemconsortium.org/report/gem-2019-2020-global-report?fbclid=IwAR0lv4N40jQL_FpZW-sy4QwmRg3-NYnIp3Be-4vRkPjUILSQ9WpqcRMWW4s [Accessed 15 Apr 2023].
- George, B. (2003) Authentic leadership: Rediscovering the secrets to creating lasting value. John Wiley & Sons. San Francisco Jossey-Bass.
- George, B. and Sims, P. (2007) The Warren Bennis series. True north: Discover your authentic leadership. San Francisco.
- Gibb, A., Haskins, G. and Robertson, I. (2013) Leading the entrepreneurial university: Meeting the entrepreneurial development needs of higher education institutions. In Universities in change. Springer.
- Gillen, D. J. and Carroll, S. J. (1985) Relationship of managerial ability to unit effectiveness in more organic versus more mechanistic departments. Journal of Management Studies. Vol.22 (6), pp.668–676.
- Giordano Martinez, K. R., Fernandez-Laviada, A. and Herrero Crespo, A. (2017) Influence of business incubators performance on entrepreneurial intentions and its antecedents during the pre-incubation stage. Entrepreneurship Research Journal. Vol.8(2), pp.3–35.
- Gladstein, D. L. (1984) Groups in context: A model of task group effectiveness. Administrative Science Quarterly. Vol. 29 (4), pp.499–517.
- Golafshani, N. (2003) Understanding reliability and validity in qualitative research. The Qualitative Report. Vol.8 (4), pp.597–607.
- Graen, G. B. (1976) Role-making processes within complex organizations. Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology, Scientific Research Publishing.
- Graen, G. and Cashman, J. F. (1975) A role-making model of leadership in formal organizations: A developmental approach. Leadership Frontiers. Vol.143 (165), pp.86–96.
- Gray, L. M., Wong-Wylie, G., Rempel, G. R. and Cook, K. (2020) Expanding qualitative research interviewing strategies: Zoom video communications. The qualitative report. Vol.25 (5), pp.1292–1301.

- Gray, J. H., Densten, I. L. and Sarros, J. C. (2003) Executive leadership in Australian small business: Beyond entrepreneurial vision. The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation. Vol.4 (1), pp.37–45.
- Greenberg, D., McKone-Sweet, K. and Wilson, H. J. (2013) Entrepreneurial leaders: Creating opportunity in an unknowable world. Leader to Leader. Vol.2013 (67), pp.56–62.
- Greer, L. L. and Van Kleef, G. A. (2010) Equality versus differentiation: The effects of power dispersion on group interaction. Journal of Applied Psychology. Vol.95 (6), pp. 1032–1044.
- Gronn, P. (2002) Distributed leadership as a unit of analysis. The Leadership Quarterly. Vol.13 (4), pp.423–451.
- Guba, E. G. and Lincoln, Y. S. (1994) Competing paradigms in qualitative research. Handbook of Qualitative Research, Sage Publication.
- Guerrero, M., Urbano, D., Cunningham, J. A. and Gajón, E. (2018) Determinants of Graduates' Start-Ups Creation across a Multi-Campus Entrepreneurial University: The Case of Monterrey Institute of Technology and Higher Education. Journal of Small Business Management. Vol.56 (1), pp.150–178.
- Guetzkow, J., Lamont, M., and Mallard, G. (2004) What is Originality in the Humanities and the Social Sciences? American Sociological Review. Vol.69 (2), pp.190-212.
- Gundry, L. K., Ofstein, L. F. and Monllor, J. (2016) Entrepreneurial team creativity: Driving innovation from ideation to implementation. Journal of Enterprising Culture. Vol.24 (1), pp.55–77.
- Guo, K. L. (2009) Core Competencies of the Entrepreneurial Leader in Health Care Organizations: The Health Care Manager. Vol.28 (1), pp.19–29.
- Gupta, V., MacMillan, I. C. and Surie, G. (2004) Entrepreneurial leadership: developing and measuring a cross-cultural construct. Journal of Business Venturing. Vol.19 (2), pp.241–260.
- Hackman, J. R. (1987) The design of work teams. In Handbook of Organizational Behavior, ed. JW Lorsch.
- Hackman, J. R. and Wageman, R. (2007) Asking the right questions about leadership: Discussion and conclusions, American Psychologist. Vol.62 (1), pp. 43-47.
- Hafeez, S., Ali, Q. and Nawaz, M. A. (2021) Business Incubators in Pakistan: State of the Art and Future Outlook. Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies. Vol.7 (4), pp.979–990.
- Halim, N. A. A. and Razak, N. A. (2014) Communication Strategies of Women Leaders in Entrepreneurship. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. Vol.118 (2014), pp.21–28.

- Hansson, F. and Mønsted, M. (2008) Research leadership as entrepreneurial organizing for research. Higher Education. Vol.55 (6), pp.651–670.
- Haq, S. (2011) Ethics and leadership skills in the public service. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences. Vol.15 (66), pp.2792–2796.
- Harrison, C. (2018) Leadership theory and research: A critical approach to new and existing paradigms. Switzerland, Palgrave MacMillan.
- Harrison, C. (2016) Entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy: a study in Nigeria. University of the West of Scotland.
- Harrison, C., Paul, S. and Burnard, K. (2016a) Entrepreneurial leadership: A systematic literature review. International Review of Entrepreneurship. Vol.14 (2), pp. 235–264.
- Harrison, C., Paul, S. and Burnard, K. (2016b) Entrepreneurial leadership in retail pharmacy: developing economy perspective. Journal of Workplace Learning. Vol.28 (3), pp.150–167.
- Harrison, C., Burnard, K. and Paul, S. (2018) Entrepreneurial leadership in a developing economy: a skill-based analysis. Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development. Vol.25 (3), pp.521–548.
- Harrison, C., Omeihe, I., Simba, A. and Omeihe, K. (2020) Leading the way: the entrepreneur or the leader? Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship. Vol. 35 (6) pp. 890–906.
- Hassan, N. A. (2020) University business incubators as a tool for accelerating entrepreneurship: theoretical perspective. Review of Economics and Political Science. [Ahead-of-print].
- Hayat, A., Latif, A., Humayon, A. A., Ahmed, M. and Azeem, M. (2019) The mediating role of entrepreneurial leadership in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance of ICTs SMEs. Journal of Multidisciplinary Approaches in Science. Vol.5 (1), pp.16–23.
- Haynes, K. T., Hitt, M. A. and Campbell, J. T. (2015) The dark side of leadership: Towards a mid-range theory of hubris and greed in entrepreneurial contexts. Journal of Management Studies. Vol.52 (4), pp.479–505.
- He, L., Standen, P. and Coetzer, A. (2017) The perceived personal characteristics of entrepreneurial leaders. Small Enterprise Research. Vol.24 (2), pp.97–119.
- HEC (2020) The Higher Education Commission Policy on Business Incubation Centres [Online]. Higher Education Commission Pakistan. Government Organisation. Available:https://www.hec.gov.pk/english/services/universities/EBIC/Documents/BI-Cs%20Policy%202021_Final.pdf [Accessed 20 Mar 2024].
- HEC (2023) Established-BICs [Online]. Higher Education Commission, Pakistan. Available: <https://www.hec.gov.pk/english/services/universities/EBIC/Pages/Established-BICs.aspx> [Accessed 15 Apr 2023].

- Heifetz, R. A. (1998) Leadership without easy answers. In: Leadership Without Easy Answers. Harvard University Press.
- Heifetz, R. A., Heifetz, R., Grashow, A. and Linsky, M. (2009) The practice of adaptive leadership: Tools and tactics for changing your organization and the world. Harvard Business Press.
- Hejazi, S. and Naeiji, M. (2012) Designing a scale for measuring entrepreneurial leadership in SMEs. In: Presented at the International Conference on Economics, Marketing and Management, IPEDR.
- Henry, C., Foss, L., Fayolle, A., Walker, E. and Duffy, S. (2015) Entrepreneurial leadership and gender: Exploring theory and practice in global contexts. Journal of Small Business Management. Vol.53 (3), pp.581–586.
- Hentschke, G. C. (2010) Developing entrepreneurial leaders. In: Developing Successful Leadership. Springer.
- Hentschke, G. C. and Caldwell, B. J. (2005) Entrepreneurial leadership. The essentials of school leadership. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Hersey, P. and Blanchard, K. H. (1969a) Life cycle theory of leadership. Training & Development Journal. Vol.5 (23), pp.26–34.
- Hersey, P. and Blanchard, K. H. (1969b) Management of organizational behaviour: Utilizing human resources. Academy of Management Briarcliff Manor, New York.
- Hewitt, L. M., and van Rensburg, L. J. J. (2020) The role of business incubators in creating sustainable small and medium enterprises. The Southern African Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management. Vol.12(1), pp. 1–9.
- Higgins, J. P., Thomas, J., Chandler, J., Cumpston, M., Li, T., Page, M. J. and Welch, V. A. (2019) Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions. John Wiley & Sons.
- House, R. J. (1971) A path goal theory of leader effectiveness. Administrative Science Quarterly. Vol. 16 (3), pp.321–339.
- House, R. J. and Dessler, G. (1974) The path-goal theory of leadership: Some post hoc and a priori tests. Contingency approaches to leadership. Carbondale: Southern Illinois University Press.
- House, R. J. and Mitchell, T. R. (1975) Path-goal theory of leadership. Washington University Seattle Dept of Psychology.
- Horan, J. (2007) Business driven action learning: A powerful tool for building world-class entrepreneurial business leaders. Organization Development Journal. Vol.25 (3), pp. 75–80.
- Horvatinovic, T., Mikic, M. and Dabić, M. (2023) Dissecting entrepreneurial team research: a bibliometric analysis. Review of Managerial Science. Vol.17 (2023), pp.1–39.

- Hunter, L. and Lean, J. (2014) Investigating the Role of Entrepreneurial Leadership and Social Capital in SME Competitiveness in the Food and Drink Industry. The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation. Vol.15 (3), pp.179–190.
- Hutabarat, Z. and Pandin, M. (2014) Absorptive capacity of business incubator for SME's rural community located in indonesia's village. Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences. Vol.115 (2014), pp.373–377.
- Ihua, U. B. (2009) SMEs key failure-factors: a comparison between the United Kingdom and Nigeria. Journal of social sciences. Vol.18 (3), pp.199–207.
- Iqbal, A., Nazir, T. and Ahmad, M. S. (2022) Entrepreneurial leadership and employee innovative behavior: an examination through multiple theoretical lenses. European Journal of Innovation Management. Vol.25 (1), pp.173–190.
- ILO (2021) Labour Force Survey 2021. (International labour Organisation). [Online] Available: <https://www.ilo.org/surveyLib/index.php/catalog/7929>.
- Jamil, F., Ismail, K., Siddique, M., Khan, M. M., Kazi, A. G. and Qureshi, M. I. (2016) Business incubators in Asian developing countries. International Review of Management and Marketing. Vol.6 (4), pp.291–295.
- IMF (2023) World Economic Outlook: Pakistan, 2023 [Online] Available: <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/PAK> [Accessed: 30/01/2023].
- Jawi, A. I. M. and Izhar, T. A. T. (2016) Entrepreneurial leadership capabilities and innovativeness in academic libraries: A research model. International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences. Vol.6 (1), pp.28–39.
- Johnson, P. and Duberley, J. (2000) Understanding management research: An introduction to epistemology. Sage Publication.
- Johns, G. (2006) The essential impact of context on organizational behaviour. Academy of Management Review. Vol.31 (2), pp.386–408.
- Jones, O. and Crompton, H. (2009) Enterprise logic and small firms: a model of authentic entrepreneurial leadership. Journal of Strategy and Management. Vol.2 (4), pp.329–351.
- Johnstone, B. A. (2007) Ethnographic methods in entrepreneurship research. Handbook of qualitative research methods in entrepreneurship. Tgn Learning Publication.
- Kansikas, J., Laakkonen, A., Sarpo, V., and Kontinen, T. (2012) Entrepreneurial leadership and familiness as resources for strategic entrepreneurship. International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research. Vol. 18(2), pp. 141-158.
- Kaplan, S. N. and Strömberg, P. E. (2004) Characteristics, contracts, and actions: Evidence from venture capitalist analyses. The Journal of Finance. Vol.59 (5), pp.2177–2210.

- Karanian, B. (2007) Entrepreneurial leadership and transformational change. In: 2007 Annual Conference & Exposition. Proceedings of the American Society for Engineering Education, Honolulu, HI.
- Karol, R. A. (2015) Leadership in the Context of Corporate Entrepreneurship. Journal of Leadership Studies. Vol.8 (4), pp.30–34.
- Kassai, Á. (2022) How successful entrepreneurs lead? Multi-method Analysis of Entrepreneurial Leadership. Budapesti Corvinus Egyetem.
- Katz, R. L. (1974) Skills of an effective administrator: Harvard Business School Press.
- Kempster, S. and Cope, J. (2010) Learning to lead in the entrepreneurial context. International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research. Vol.16 (1), pp.5–34.
- Kempster, S. (2009) Observing the invisible: Examining the role of observational learning in the development of leadership practice. Journal of Management Development. Vol.28 (5), pp.439–456.
- Kesidou, E. (2021) Enacting entrepreneurial leadership: a qualitative study of leadership behaviour in the context of Scottish growth-oriented businesses. Strathclyde University.
- Khalique, M., Bontis, N., Abdul Nassir bin Shaari, J. and Hassan Md. Isa, A. (2015) Intellectual capital in small and medium enterprises in Pakistan. Journal of Intellectual Capital. Vol.16 (1), pp.224–238.
- Khan, G., Naveed, R. T. and Jantan, A. H. B. (2018) Status of Wonder Women: Challenges for Young Future Women Entrepreneurs in Pakistan. International Journal of Experiential Learning & Case Studies. Vol.3 (1), pp.97–109.
- King, N., Horrocks, C. and Brooks, J. (2018) Interviews in qualitative research. Sage Publication.
- King, A.S. (1990) Evolution of leadership. Vikalpa. Vol. 15(2) pp. 43-54.
- Kirzner, I. M. (1997) Entrepreneurial discovery and the competitive market process: An Austrian approach. Journal of economic Literature. Vol.35 (1), pp.60–85.
- Koryak, O., Mole, K. F., Lockett, A., Hayton, J. C., Ucbasaran, D. and Hodgkinson, G. P. (2015) Entrepreneurial leadership, capabilities and firm growth. International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship. Vol.33 (1), pp.89–105.
- Kuratko, D. F. (2007) Entrepreneurial leadership in the 21st century: Guest editor's perspective. Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies. Vol.13 (4), pp.1–11.
- Kuratko, D. F. and Hornsby, J. S. (1999) Corporate entrepreneurial leadership for the 21st century. Journal of Leadership Studies. Vol.5 (2), pp.27–39.
- Kvale, S. (1994) Interviews: An introduction to qualitative research interviewing. Sage Publications.

- Kwapisz, A. (2019) Do government and legal barriers impede entrepreneurship in the US? An exploratory study of perceived vs. actual barriers. Journal of Business Venturing Insights. Vol.11 (2019), pp.2–14.
- Lajin, N. F. M. and Zainol, F. A. (2015) The effect of entrepreneurial leadership, Self-Efficacy and organizational performance: A conceptual paper. International Academic Research Journal of Social Science. Vol.1 (1), pp.16–24.
- Lans, T. and Mulder, M. (2009) Competence, empirical insights from a small-business perspective. In: Development of competencies in the world of work and education: conference proceedings, Ljubljana.
- Larson Jr, J. R. and Schaumann, L. J. (1993) Group goals, group coordination, and group member motivation. Human Performance. Vol.6 (1), pp.49–69.
- Le Deist, F. D. and Winterton, J. (2005) What is competence? Human Resource Development International. Vol.8 (1), pp.27–46.
- Lee, N. and Lings, I. (2008) Doing business research: a guide to theory and practice. Sage Publication.
- Leffel, A., Hallam, C. and Darling, J. (2016) Enhancement of entrepreneurial leadership: A case focusing on a model of successful conflict management skills. Administrative Issues Journal: Connecting Education, Practice, and Research. Vol.2 (2), pp.13–25.
- Leitch, C. M., McMullan, C. and Harrison, R. T. (2009a) Leadership development in SMEs: an action learning approach. Action Learning: Research and Practice. Vol.6 (3), pp.243–263.
- Leitch, C. M., McMullan, C. and Harrison, R. T. (2009b) Leadership development in SMEs: an action learning approach. Action Learning: Research and Practice. Vol.6 (3), pp.243–263.
- Leitch, C. M., McMullan, C. and Harrison, R. T. (2013) The Development of Entrepreneurial Leadership: The Role of Human, Social and Institutional Capital: Development of Entrepreneurial Leadership. British Journal of Management. Vol.24 (3), pp.347–366.
- Leitch, C. and Volery, T. (2017) Entrepreneurial leadership: Insights and directions: International Small Business Journal. Vol.35 (2), pp.147–156.
- Levine, J. M. and Moreland, R. L. (1990) Progress in small group research. Annual Review of Psychology. Vol.41 (1), pp.585–634.
- Li, C., Ahmed, N., Qalati, S. A., Khan, A. and Naz, S. (2020) Role of business incubators as a tool for entrepreneurship development: the mediating and moderating role of business start-up and government regulations. Sustainability. Vol.12 (5), p.1822.
- Lincoln, Y. S. and Guba, E. G. (1986) But is it rigorous? Trustworthiness and authenticity in naturalistic evaluation. New directions for program evaluation. Vol.1986 (30), pp.73–84.

- Liu, Y., Lee, J. M. and Lee, C. (2020) The challenges and opportunities of a global health crisis: the management and business implications of COVID-19 from an Asian perspective. Asian Business & Management. Vol.19 (2020), pp.277–297.
- Lippitt, G. L. (1987) Entrepreneurial Leadership: A Performing Art. The Journal of Creative Behavior. Vol.21 (3), pp.264–270.
- Lord, R. G. and Hall, R. J. (2005) Identity, deep structure and the development of leadership skill. The Leadership Quarterly. Vol.16 (4), pp.591–615.
- Lord, R. G., De Vader, C. L. and Alliger, G. M. (1986) A meta-analysis of the relation between personality traits and leadership perceptions: An application of validity generalization procedures. Journal of Applied Psychology. Vol.71 (3), pp.402–410.
- Lubis, R. L. (2017) Assessing entrepreneurial leadership and the law: Why are these important for graduate students in Indonesia. International Journal of Arts & Sciences. Vol.10 (2), pp.41–76.
- Luthans, F., Avolio, B. J., Cameron, K. S., Dutton, J. E. and Quinn, R. E. (2003) Authentic leadership development. Positive organizational scholarship. Berett-Koelher Publishers.
- Mansfield, B. (2004) Competence in transition. Journal of European industrial training. Vol.28 (24), pp.296–309.
- MacLaren, A. C. (2015) The stories of hoteliers, personal narratives in entrepreneurial leadership. Orchive.org.
- Mahmood, N., Jianfeng, C., Jamil, F., Karmat, J., Khan, M. and Cai, Y. (2015) Business Incubators: Boon or Boondoggle for SMEs and Economic Development of Pakistan. International Journal of u- and e-Service, Science and Technology. Vol.8 (4), pp.147–158.
- Mahmood, N., Jianfeng, C., Munir, H., Farhan Jami, Nusrat, A., Anum Nusrat and Jamil, F. (2016) The Role of University-Based Incubators in Developing Economies: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan. International Journal of u- and e- Service, Science and Technology. Vol.9 (11), pp.143–152.
- Mapunda, G. (2007) Entrepreneurial leadership and indigenous enterprise development. Journal of Asia Entrepreneurship and Sustainability. Vol.3 (3), pp.1–28.
- Mars, M. M. and Torres, R. M. (2018) Developing Collegiate Student Proclivities to Entrepreneurial Leadership. Journal of Leadership Education. Vol.17 (4), pp. 110–129.
- Mattare, M. (2008) Teaching entrepreneurship: The case for an entrepreneurial leadership course. In: United States Association for Small Business and Entrepreneurship. Conference Proceedings. Citeseer.
- Mavi, R. K., Gheibdoust, H., Khanfar, A. A. and Mavi, N. K. (2019) Ranking factors influencing strategic management of university business incubators with ANP. Management Decision. Vol.57 (12), pp.3492–3510.

- Mawoli, M. (2016) Transforming the Nigerian economy through entrepreneurial leadership: challenges and prospects. Journal of Entrepreneurship Research. Vol.7 (2016), pp.1–20.
- Mcadam, M. and Marlow, S. (2007) Building Futures or Stealing Secrets: Entrepreneurial Cooperation and Conflict within Business Incubators. International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship. Vol.25 (4), pp.361–382.
- McCall, M. W. and Lombardo, M. M. (1983) What makes a top executive. Psychology Today. Vol.17 (2), pp.26–31.
- McGrath, R.G., MacMillan, I.C., 2000. The Entrepreneurial Mindset. Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA.
- McEvily, S. K., Eisenhardt, K. M. and Prescott, J. E. (2004) The global acquisition, leverage, and protection of technological competencies. Strategic management journal. Vol.25 (8-9), pp.713–722.
- McMullen, J. S. and Shepherd, D. A. (2006) Entrepreneurial action and the role of uncertainty in the theory of the entrepreneur. Academy of Management review. Vol.31 (1), pp.132–152.
- Megheirkouni, M., Thirlwall, A. and Mejheirkouni, A. (2020) Entrepreneurial leadership in middle east sport businesses: The impact of gender differences in cultural values. Gender in Management: An International Journal. Vol.35 (2), pp.157–168.
- Mehmood, M. S., Jian, Z., Akram, U., Akram, Z. and Tanveer, Y. (2022) Entrepreneurial leadership and team creativity: the roles of team psychological safety and knowledge sharing. Personnel Review. Vol.51 (9), pp.2404–2425.
- Mehmood, M. S., Jian, Z., Akram, U. and Tariq, A. (2021) Entrepreneurial leadership: the key to develop creativity in organizations. Leadership & Organization Development Journal. Vol.42 (3), pp.434–452.
- Mehmood, M. S., Jian, Z. and Gilal, F. G. (2020) Entrepreneurial leadership and employee innovative behavior: intervening role of creative self-efficacy. Human Systems Management. Vol.39 (3), pp.367–379.
- Mezher, A. H. and Hamed, A. P. S. A. (2020) Diagnosing Entrepreneurial Leadership Factors Among A Sample of Managers of Companies of The Ministry of Water Resources. International Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. Vol.10 (3), pp.209–221.
- Miller, N. J. and Besser, T. L. (2003) Investigating small community influences on US entrepreneurs' goals, business strategies and success. The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation. Vol.4 (3), pp.149–161.
- de Mol, E., Khapova, S. N. and Elfring, T. (2015) Entrepreneurial team cognition: A review. International Journal of Management Reviews. Vol.17 (2), pp.232–255.

- Molina-Azorín, J. F., López-Gamero, M. D., Pereira-Moliner, J. and Pertusa-Ortega, E. M. (2012) Mixed methods studies in entrepreneurship research: Applications and contributions. Entrepreneurship & Regional Development. Vol.24 (5–6), pp.425–456.
- Morgeson, F. P., DeRue, D. S. and Karam, E. P. (2010) Leadership in teams: A functional approach to understanding leadership structures and processes. Journal of management. Vol.36 (1), pp.5–39.
- Mubaraki, H. M. A. and Busler, M. (2015) The importance of business incubation in developing countries: case study approach. International Journal of Foresight and Innovation Policy. Vol.10 (1), pp.17-28.
- Mumford, M. D., Zaccaro, S. J., Harding, F. D., Jacobs, T. O. and Fleishman, E. A. (2000) Leadership skills for a changing world: Solving complex social problems. The Leadership Quarterly. Vol.11 (1), pp.11–35.
- Mumtaz, S., Shafi, F. and Zafar, F. (2017) Role of technology business incubators to nurture entrepreneurship: a study on Pakistani universities. Journal of Account Marketing. Vol.6 (2), pp.226–230.
- Murphy, D. M., Hanchett, M., Olmsted, R. N., Farber, M. R., Lee, T. B., Haas, J. P. and Streed, S. A. (2012) Competency in infection prevention: a conceptual approach to guide current and future practice. American journal of infection control. Vol.40 (4), pp.296–303.
- Nasir, M. and Iqbal, R. (2019) Factors Affecting Growth of Women Entrepreneurs in Pakistan. Pakistan Administrative Review. Vol.3 (1), pp.35–50.
- Neergaard, H. and Ulhøi, J. P. (2007) Handbook of Qualitative Research Methods in Entrepreneurship. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Ngigi, S. (2018) Development of Entrepreneurial Leadership Competencies: The Case Of Ceos Of Mid-Sized Kenyan Companies. University of Nairobi.
- Nieman, G. and Nieuwenhuizen, C. (2009) Entrepreneurship: A South African perspective. Van Schaik Publishers.
- Nkechi, A., Emeh Ikechukwu, E. and Okechukwu, U. F. (2012) Entrepreneurship development and employment generation in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. Universal Journal of Education and General Studies. Vol.1 (4), pp.88–102.
- Northouse, P. G. (2019) Leadership: Theory and practice. Sage Publications.
- Oc, B. (2018) Contextual leadership: A systematic review of how contextual factors shape leadership and its outcomes. The Leadership Quarterly. Vol.29 (1), pp.218–235.
- Ogutu, V. O. and Kihonge, E. (2016) Impact of business incubators on economic growth and entrepreneurship development. International Journal of Science and Research. Vol.5 (5), pp.231–241.
- OEC (2021) Country profile Pakistan [Online]. Available: <https://oec.world/en/profile/country/pak> [Accessed 15 Apr 2023].

- Okudan, G. E. and Rzasa, S. E. (2006) A project-based approach to entrepreneurial leadership education. Technovation. Vol.26 (2), pp.195–210.
- Olawale, F. and Garwe, D. (2010) Obstacles to the growth of new SMEs in South Africa: A principal component analysis approach. African Journal of Business Management. Vol.4 (5), p.729.
- Olutade, M., Liefoghe, A. and Olakunle, A. (2015) Influence of entrepreneurial leadership skills on employees' motivation and job satisfaction: A leader member exchange (LMX) approach. International Journal of Academic Research In Business and Social Sciences. Vol.5 (9), pp.46–69.
- Omeihe, I., Harrison, C., Simba, A. and Omeihe, K. (2020) The role of the entrepreneurial leader: a study of Nigerian SMEs. International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business. Vol.49 (2), pp.1–48.
- Onugu, B. A. N. (2005) Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. St. Clements University, Nigeria.
- Ordu, U. B.-A. (2020) Entrepreneurial Leadership in Start-Up Businesses. Bulgarian Comparative Education Society.
- Osborn, R. N., Hunt, J. G. and Jauch, L. R. (2002) Toward a contextual theory of leadership. The leadership quarterly. Vol.13 (6), pp.797–837.
- Pal, R., Torstensson, H. and Mattila, H. (2014) Antecedents of organizational resilience in economic crises—an empirical study of Swedish textile and clothing SMEs. International Journal of Production Economics. Vol.147(2014), pp.410–428.
- Patterson, N., Mavin, S. and Turner, J. (2012) Envisioning female entrepreneur: leaders anew from a gender perspective. Gender in Management: An International Journal. Vol.27 (6), pp.395–416.
- Patton, M. Q. (2002) Qualitative research & evaluation methods. Sage Publication.
- Paudel, S. (2019) Entrepreneurial leadership and business performance: Effect of organizational innovation and environmental dynamism. South Asian Journal of Business Studies. Vol.8 (3), pp.348–369.
- Peters, L., Rice, M. and Sundararajan, M. (2004) The role of incubators in the entrepreneurial process. The Journal of Technology Transfer. Vol.29 (1), pp.83–91.
- Pihie, Z. A. L. and Bagheri, A. (2013) The impact of principals' entrepreneurial leadership behaviour on school organizational innovativeness. Life Science Journal. Vol.10 (2), pp.1033–1041.
- Pittaway, L. and Cope, J. (2007) Simulating entrepreneurial learning: Integrating experiential and collaborative approaches to learning. Management learning. Vol.38 (2), pp.211–233.

- Phillips, E., and Pugh, D. (1994) How to get a PhD, 2nd edn. Buckingham, Open University Press.
- Politis, D. (2005) The process of entrepreneurial learning: A conceptual framework. Entrepreneurship theory and practice. Vol.29 (4), pp.399–424.
- Prieto, L. C. (2010) Proactive personality and entrepreneurial leadership: exploring the moderating role of organizational identification and political skill. Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal. Vol.16 (2), pp.107–122.
- Putsom, W. and Suwannarat, P. (2019) The Effect of Entrepreneurial Leadership on Value Creation and Performance of Automotive Parts Manufacturers Businesses in Thailand. Mahasarakham University.
- Putsom, W., Suwannarat, P. and Songsrirote, N. (2019) Scale Development for Measuring Entrepreneurial Leadership Competencies. Human Behaviour, Development and Society. Vol.20 (3), pp.29–40.
- Qamar, U., Ansari, N., Tanveer, F. and Qamar, N. (2020) Social Entrepreneurship in Pakistan: Challenges and Prospects. Journal of Management and Research. Vol.7 (2), pp.1–41.
- Quaye, D. M. and Mensah, I. (2019) Entrepreneurial leadership and performance of female-owned small and medium-sized enterprises in Ghana. International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business. Vol.38 (1–2), pp.19–44.
- Qureshi, S. and Mian, S. (2021) Transfer of entrepreneurship education best practices from business schools to engineering and technology institutions: evidence from Pakistan. The Journal of Technology Transfer. Vol.46 (2), pp.366–392.
- Rahim, H. L., Zainal Abidin, Z., Mohtar, S. and Ramli, A. (2015) The effect of entrepreneurial leadership towards organizational performance. International Academic Research Journal of Business and Technology. Vol.1 (2), pp. 193–200.
- Ranjan, S. (2018) Entrepreneurial leadership: a review of measures, antecedents, outcomes and moderators. Asian Social Science. Vol.14 (12), pp.104–114.
- Ratten, V. and Usmanij, P. (2021) Entrepreneurship education: Time for a change in research direction? The International Journal of Management Education. Vol.19 (1), pp. 2–8.
- Ratwani, K. L., Zaccaro, S. J., Garven, S. and Geller, D. S. (2010) The role of developmental social networks in effective leader self-learning processes. In: Self-management and leadership development. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Reichertz, J. (2007) Abduction: The logic of discovery of grounded theory. The SAGE handbook of grounded theory. Sage Publication.
- Renko, M., El Tarabishy, A., Carsrud, A. L. and Brännback, M. (2012) Entrepreneurial leadership and the family business. In: Understanding Family Businesses. Springer.
- Renko, M., El Tarabishy, A., Carsrud, A. L. and Brännback, M. (2015) Understanding and measuring entrepreneurial leadership style. Journal of Small Business Management. Vol.53 (1), pp.54–74.

- Roomi, M. A. and Harrison, P. (2011) Entrepreneurial leadership: What is it and how should it be taught? International Review of Entrepreneurship. Vol.9 (3), pp. 1-49.
- Rusliati, E., Mulyaningtum, M., Wibowo, A. and Narmmaditya, B. S. (2020) Does Entrepreneurial Leadership Matter for Micro-Enterprise Development: Lesson from West Java in Indonesia. The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business. Vol.7 (8), pp.445–450.
- Saberi, M. and Hamdan, A. (2019) The moderating role of governmental support in the relationship between entrepreneurship and economic growth: A study on the GCC countries. Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies. Vol.11 (2), pp.200–216.
- Santos, S. C., Morris, M. H., Caetano, A., Costa, S. F. and Neumeyer, X. (2019) Team entrepreneurial competence: multilevel effects on individual cognitive strategies. International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research. Vol.25 (6), pp.1259–1282.
- Sathya, R. and Vithyapriya, B. (2016) Women entrepreneurship. Primax International Journal of Commerce and Management Research. Vol 6 (2) pp.53–58.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2012) Research Methods for Business Students. Pearson Education.
- Schofield, J. W. (1993) Increasing the generalizability of qualitative research. Open University Press; Sage Publications.
- Schjoedt, L. and Kraus, S. (2009) The heart of a new venture: The entrepreneurial team. Management Research News. Vol.32 (6), pp.509–512.
- Schumpeter, J. and Backhaus, U. (2003) The theory of economic development. Springer.
- Shahzad, K., Bajwa, S. U., Ali, Q. and Zia, S. (2012) Role of incubation in women entrepreneurship development in Pakistan. Asian Journal of Business Management. Vol.4 (2), pp.200–208.
- Shane, S. and Venkataraman, S. (2000) The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research. Academy of management review. Vol.25 (1), pp.217–226.
- Shaw, E. (1999) A guide to the qualitative research process: evidence from a small firm study. Qualitative Market Research. Vol. 2 (2), 59–70.
- Shuhong, Y. and Zia-ud-Din, M. (2017) Analyzing the Labour Issues in Pakistan: A Historical Background of Labour Laws and Labour Unions. Labour & Law Issues. Vol.3 (2), pp. 21–54.
- SMEDA (2021) National SME Policy 2021 [Online]. Small and Medium Enterprise Development Authority. Government Organisation. Available: SME Policy [2021] SMEDA <https://smeda.org> > smeda-publications > downl... [Accessed 15 Apr 2023].

- Siddiqui, S. (2007) An empirical study of traits determining entrepreneurial leadership-An educational perspective. Skyline Business Review. Vol.4 (1), pp.37–48.
- Siilasmaa, R. (2019) Entrepreneurial leadership: A new approach to strategy when you can't plan predictably. Leader to Leader. Vol.2019 (92), pp.32–36.
- Simba, A. and Thai, M. T. T. (2019) Advancing entrepreneurial leadership as a practice in MSME management and development. Journal of Small Business Management. Vol.57(2), pp.397–416.
- Sklaveniti, C. (2017) Processes of entrepreneurial leadership: Co-acting creativity and direction in the emergence of new SME ventures. International Small Business Journal. Vol.35 (2), pp.197–213.
- SMEDA (2021) National SME Policy 2021 [Online]. Small and Medium Enterprise Development Authority. Government Organisation. Available: SME Policy [2021] SMEDA <https://smeda.org> > smeda-publications > downl... [Accessed 15 Apr 2023].
- Smith, S., Kempster, S. and Barnes, S. (2017) Up the ANTe: Understanding entrepreneurial leadership learning through actor-network theory. Industry and Higher Education. Vol.31 (2), pp.132–139.
- Soomro, B. A., Shah, N. and Mangi, S. (2019) Factors affecting the entrepreneurial leadership in small-and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) of Pakistan: An empirical evidence. World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development. Vol.15 (1), pp.31–44.
- Spillane, J. P. (2005) Distributed leadership. In: The educational forum. Taylor & Francis.
- Stewart, G. L., Courtright, S. H. and Manz, C. C. (2011) Self-leadership: A multilevel review. Journal of management. Vol.37 (1), pp.185–222.
- Strubler, D. C. and Redekop, B. W. (2010) Entrepreneurial human resource leadership: A conversation with Dwight Carlson. Human Resource Management. Vol.49 (4), pp.793–804.
- Stogdill, R. M. (1948) Personal factors associated with leadership: A survey of the literature. The Journal of psychology. Vol.25 (1), pp.35–71.
- Stogdill, R. M. (1974) Handbook of leadership: A survey of Theory and Research. Free Press.
- Sundararajan, M., Sundararajan, B. and Henderson, S. (2012) Role of meditative foundation entrepreneurial leadership and new venture success. Journal of Spirituality, Leadership and Management. Vol.6 (1), pp.59–70.
- Surie, G. and Ashley, A. (2008) Integrating pragmatism and ethics in entrepreneurial leadership for sustainable value creation. Journal of Business Ethics. Vol.81 (1), pp.235–246.
- Swiercz, P. M. and Lydon, S. R. (2002) Entrepreneurial leadership in high-tech firms: a field study. Leadership & Organization Development Journal. Vol.23 (7), pp.380–389.

- Taherdoost, H. (2016) Sampling methods in research methodology; how to choose a sampling technique for research. How to choose a sampling technique for research. International Journal of Academic Research in Management. Vol. 5 (2), pp. 18-27.
- Tariq, J. (2016) Exploring entrepreneurial motivations and barriers: A study of female business owners in Pakistan. University of Hull, UK.
- Thietart, R.-A. (2001) Doing management research: a comprehensive guide. Sage Publication.
- Thompson, J. L. (1999) A strategic perspective of entrepreneurship. International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research. Vol 5 (6), pp. 279-296.
- Thomas, E. and Magilvy, J.K. (2011) Qualitative rigour or research validity in qualitative research. Journal for Specialists in Paediatric Nursing. Vol. 16 (2) pp. 151-155.
- Tian, Y. and Smith, W. K. (2014) Entrepreneurial leadership of social enterprises: Challenges and skills for embracing paradoxes. Journal of Leadership Studies. Vol.8 (3), pp.42–45.
- Todorovic, Z. W. and Suntornpithug, N. (2008) The multi-dimensional nature of university incubators: capability/resource emphasis phases. Journal of Enterprising Culture. Vol.16 (4), pp.385–410.
- Tracy, S. J. (2010) Qualitative quality: Eight “big tent” criteria for excellent qualitative research. Qualitative inquiry. Vol.16 (10), pp.837–851.
- Tranfield, D., Denyer, D. and Smart, P. (2003) Towards a methodology for developing evidence-informed management knowledge by means of systematic review. British Journal of Management. Vol.14 (3), pp.207–222.
- Tuckett, A. G. (2005) Applying thematic analysis theory to practice: A researcher’s experience. Contemporary nurse. Vol.19 (2), pp.75–87.
- Tunio, M. N., Chaudhry, I. S., Shaikh, S., Jariko, M. A. and Brahmi, M. (2021) Determinants of the Sustainable Entrepreneurial Engagement of Youth in Developing Country—An Empirical Evidence from Pakistan. Sustainability. Vol.13 (14), pp.7764.
- Van Assche, T. (2005) The Impact of Entrepreneurial Leadership on EU High Politics: A Case Study of Jacques Delors and the Creation of EMU. Leadership. Vol.1 (3), pp.279–298.
- UWS (2016) University Ethics Committee Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship.
- Van Maanen, J., Sørensen, J. B. and Mitchell, T. R. (2007) The interplay between theory and method. Academy of management review. Vol.32 (4), pp.1145–1154.
- Vanderstraeten, J. and Matthyssens, P. (2012) Service-based differentiation strategies for business incubators: Exploring external and internal alignment. Technovation. Vol.32 (12), pp.656–670.
- Vecchio, R. P. (2003) Entrepreneurship and leadership: common trends and common threads. Human resource management review. Vol.13 (2), pp.303–327.

- Wahab, A. and Tyasari, I. (2020) Entrepreneurial leadership for university leaders: A futuristic approach for Pakistani HEIs. Asia Pacific Management Review. Vol.25 (1), pp.54–63.
- Wang, C. L., Tee, D. D. and Ahmed, P. K. (2012) Entrepreneurial leadership and context in Chinese firms: a tale of two Chinese private enterprises. Asia Pacific Business Review. Vol.18 (4), pp.505–530.
- Wanyoko, A. M. (2013) Influence of business incubation services on growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya. International Journal of Social Sciences and Entrepreneurship. Vol.1 (7), pp.454–468.
- Wegner, D. M. (2002) *The Illusion of Conscious Will* MIT Press. Cambridge, MA.
- Weingart, L. R. (1992) Impact of group goals, task component complexity, effort, and planning on group performance. Journal of applied psychology. Vol.77 (5), pp. 33–54.
- Wibowo, A. and Saptono, A. (2018) Does entrepreneurial leadership impact on creativity and innovation of elementary teachers? Journal of Entrepreneurship Education. Vol.21 (2), pp.1–9.
- Wiggins, J. and Gibson, D. V. (2003) Overview of US incubators and the case of the Austin Technology Incubator. International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management. Vol.3 (1–2), pp.56–66.
- Williams, C. (2007) Research methods. Journal of Business & Economics Research. Vol.5 (3), pp.65–72.
- Woodruffe, C. (1993) What is meant by a competency? Leadership & Organization Development Journal. Vol.14 (1), pp.29–36.
- World Bank (2022) Pakistan Development Update [Online]. The World Bank Group. Available:<https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/410d0506bba8afc6fd9d9541148bfe4d-0310062022/original/PDU-April-2022-April18-ForWEB-Final.pdf>. [Accessed 18 Apr 2023].
- Yammarino, F. J. (2000) Leadership skills: Introduction and overview. The Leadership Quarterly. Vol 11(1), pp. 5–9.
- Yang Jun Hwan (2018) The Effect of Entrepreneurship Education on Entrepreneurial Leadership of University Students. Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Venturing and Entrepreneurship. Vol.13 (3), pp.59–69.
- Yi, G. (2018) Impact of internship quality on entrepreneurial intentions among graduating engineering students of research universities in China. International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal. Vol.14 (4), pp.1071–1087.
- Yin, R. K. (2003) Designing case studies. Qualitative research methods. Vol.5 (14), pp. 359–386.
- Yukl, G. (2010) Leadership in Organisation. 7th ed. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education Limited.

- Zahra, S. and Covin, J., (1995). Contextual influence on the corporate entrepreneurship – performance relationship: a longitudinal analysis. *Journal of Business Venturing*. Vol. 10(1), 43 – 58.
- Zaccaro, S. J. and Klimoski, R. J. (2002) The nature of organizational leadership: Understanding the performance imperatives confronting today's leaders. John Wiley & Sons.
- Zaleznik, A. (1990) The leadership gap. *Academy of Management Perspectives*. Vol.4 (1), pp.7–22.
- Zhao, H., Seibert, S. E. and Hills, G. E. (2005) The mediating role of self-efficacy in the development of entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of applied psychology*. Vol.90 (6), pp. 1265–1272.
- Zreen, A., Farrukh, M., Nazar, N. and Khalid, R. (2019) The role of internship and business incubation programs in forming entrepreneurial intentions: an empirical analysis from Pakistan. *Central European Management Journal*. Vol.27 (2), pp.97–113.

Appendices

Appendix 1a: Interview protocol

Interview Protocol for Nascent Entrepreneurial Leaders

Section 1

This section aims to explain the following aspects of research:

- A brief introduction and explanation of research are shared with study participants.
- The anonymity procedure is maintained.

Section 2

This section seeks the following information:

- Ask nascent entrepreneurial leaders about their backgrounds and their experiences of being part of business incubators.
- Ask about the challenges they confront in business incubators.
- Ask participants about their motivations for being part of business incubators.

Section 3

This section obtains the following information:

- At group level, general questions are asked about the competencies needed in business incubators. The participants are also asked about the experience of running their projects and launching new ventures at teams.
- Ask about the roles and tasks related to teams.
- Ask about their personal and functional competencies in a team context.
- Ask about other relevant competencies such as interpersonal, technological, conceptual, and entrepreneurial.
- The participants are asked about the challenges they face working as a team.
- Ask about the methods for entrepreneurial leadership development.

Section 4

This section includes

- Any other relevant information about the challenges, skills, roles, and tasks is obtained if it is not covered in the above sections.

Thank the interviewee for their time and contribution. Make sure they understand the importance of confidentiality and anonymity once more.

Appendix 1b: Interview questions

Topic of Research:

Entrepreneurial Leadership in Teams: Evidence from University-based Business Incubators (UBIs) of Pakistan

My name is **Fida Ahmed**, and I am a PhD candidate at the School of Business and Creative Industries, University of the West of Scotland. I am conducting my PhD research on “Entrepreneurial Leadership in Teams: Evidence from University-based Business Incubators (UBIs) of Pakistan.” I have purposefully identified you as a participant in this study because you are associated with a university-based business incubator and lead a start-up as a member of the team.

I assure you that your participation in this study is completely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any stage of the research. Your anonymity and confidentiality are strictly maintained throughout the course of research.

Interview Questions

1. **Entrepreneurial journey and motivation**
 - How did you start your entrepreneurial journey?
 - What was the motivation behind this journey?
2. **Entrepreneurial Leadership Challenges**
 - What kind of challenges do you face while leading your start-up at individual level in business incubator?
 - What kind of challenges do you face while leading your start-up at the team level in business incubator?
3. **Entrepreneurial leadership competencies**
 - What are the competencies required to cope with the challenges of leading entrepreneurial projects at individual level in business incubator?
 - What are the competencies required to cope with the challenges of leading start-up at the team level in business incubator?
 - Is there any difference in entrepreneurial leadership competencies between individual and team levels?
4. **Entrepreneurial Leadership Development**
 - How can entrepreneurial leaders develop these competencies at individual level in business incubator?
 - How can entrepreneurial leaders develop these competencies at the team level?
 - What are the factors affecting the development of entrepreneurial leadership competencies at individual and team level at UBIs?
5. **Is there anything you want to contribute about entrepreneurial leadership challenges, competencies, and competencies’ development?**

Thank you for your participation.

Appendix 2: Participant Information Sheet

Research Project Title

Entrepreneurial Leadership in Teams: Evidence from University-based Business Incubators (UBIs) of Pakistan

Invitation

You are invited to participate in this study. Before you decide to participate, it is important to know about the research project. In this regard, please read the following sections carefully to understand the study, its purpose, and its implications.

You can ask us anything about the research that is unclear or if you would like to know more information about the research.

Research Purpose

This research aims to explore the challenges and competencies of nascent entrepreneurial leaders at business incubators from a team perspective. The study identifies the challenges faced by entrepreneurial leaders and the competencies they need develop to overcome these challenges in a group setting by examining their lived experiences at business incubators in Pakistan.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to participate in this study because you are leading a start-up, and you are an active participant in university-based business incubator and have knowledge about the roles and responsibilities of entrepreneurial projects at business incubator. You have knowledge about the challenges that you face and the competencies essential for entrepreneurial leaders at business incubator.

Do I have to take part?

Your participation in this study would be entirely voluntary; it is up to you whether you participate or not. If you decide to participate, you can keep a copy of the information sheet and sign the participant consent form. You can withdraw from the data collection process at any time without mentioning the reasons.

What happens next? If you participate

Upon agreeing to participate in this study, you are expected to attend an interview that lasts approximately 45 minutes. You will be asked questions about the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders face and the competencies they need to overcome those challenges in leading start-up at business incubator.

Is there any risk in participating in this study?

This research will not cause any physical or emotional harm to participants. The participants are not forced to answer interview questions. The confidentiality and anonymity of participants' data will be ensured through research process.

What are the possible benefits of participating?

While this research project does not carry any immediate benefit for the participants, however, the findings and recommendations of this study may be used by universities, the higher education commission, and the government of Pakistan to assess the issues of incubation centres and outline plans for enhancing the competencies of entrepreneurial leaders and improving the performance of incubation centres.

What if something goes wrong?

If you face any issue during the research process or have any complaints about the research project, you can discuss it directly with the researcher. If you notice your complaint is not handled properly, you can contact the office of the registrar at the University of the West of Scotland for further action.

Will my participation in this project be kept confidential?

The anonymity and confidentiality of participants' data are strictly ensured throughout the research process. Anonymity is ensured by applying code names to participants and their institutions rather than using their actual names on the interview transcript.

This study ensures the confidentiality of participants' data by securing it in a coded external storage, and hard copies are kept safe in a locked cupboard.

Will the interview be recorded? How will the recorded media be used?

The interview will be recorded using digital recording. The recorded media will be saved on an encoded and protected external hard drive and locked in a cupboard. The recording will be used for ensuring the validity and accuracy of interview data.

How will the results of this study be used?

The results of this study may be reproduced for publication purposes. For any purposes other than this, the participant's permission is obtained. However, the anonymity of participants and its institutions will be ensured in published work.

Who is funding the research?

This research is self-funded.

Who has ethically reviewed this research?

This research is in line with the ethical guidelines of the University of the West of Scotland (2016). Therefore, the study will follow all ethical considerations as mentioned in the UWS ethics committee, such as non-maleficence and beneficence, confidentiality, justice, and anonymity.

Thank you for your participation.

Appendix 3: Participant Consent Form

Title of Research	Entrepreneurial Leadership in Teams: Evidence from University-based Business Incubators (UBIs) of Pakistan
Name of Researcher	Fida Ahmed
Director of Studies	Professor Christian Harrison
Address	Fida Ahmed School of Business and Creative Industries, University of the West of Scotland, Technology Ave, Blantyre, Glasgow G72 0LH
Contact No	Office: [REDACTED]
Brief Description of Research	This study collects data from nascent entrepreneurial leaders in business incubators of Pakistan by particularly focusing on the challenges and competencies form their lived experiences.
Details of Participants' interview time, procedures, confidentiality measures	<p>Interview Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The approximate duration of interview from each participant is 45 minutes. • Data would be collected by employing a semi-structured interview method. • All interviews are recorded digitally through digital recorder and transcribed verbatim. <p>Anonymity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The anonymity is ensured by applying codes to participants and their organisations rather than using the actual names. • The interview transcript will be sent to participants by email or post to ensure the accuracy of contents. <p>Confidentiality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This study ensures the confidentiality of participants' data by securing them in a coded external storage and hardcopies are kept safe in a locked cupboard. <p>Data analysis validity:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In order to ensure the validity of data analysis, hard copies of anonymised transcripts would be transferred to doctoral supervision team to review the accuracy. <p>Data Possession:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hard copies would be under the possession of researcher. <p>Usage of Data:</p> <p>The researcher may use and reproduce the data for research publication.</p>
Additional research information	The data will be collected during May 2021-July 2021

This study ensures the anonymity of participants' information such as the details of individual and organisation remains unidentifiable by researcher except excluded information.

The researcher may reproduce or publish the extracted data in different forms given the nature of study as discussed above. Except above mentioned reasons, the data will not be used for other purposes without participants' permission. The participation of participants in this study is entirely voluntary and the participants may withdraw at any stage of data collection.

Signing of this form indicate that you have clear understanding of research information, its purposes and scope and agree to participate in the study as per above information.

Name of Participant

Signature

Date

Name of Researcher

Signature

Date

Appendix 4: Invitation letter

Fida Ahmed

School of Business and Creative industries
University of the West of Scotland, Scotland

Manager University-Business Incubator

Dear Sir/Madam,

I hope this letter finds you well. I am writing to introduce myself as a PhD candidate at the University of the West of Scotland, where I am conducting research on Entrepreneurial Leadership in Teams: Evidence from University-based Business Incubators (UBIs) of Pakistan. As a lecturer in a public sector university, I am immensely interested in exploring the entrepreneurial process within business incubators and understanding the role of entrepreneurial leadership in these environments. After researching on the Higher Education Commission's website, I discovered your established incubation centre and believe that the knowledge and insight you can provide will be invaluable to my research.

I hope to gain a deeper understanding of the challenges that entrepreneurial leaders face, and the competencies they require to overcome them.

I would be grateful if you could introduce me to 2 to 5 of incubates who are running start-ups as a team. Please be assured that all ethical guidelines will be strictly followed, and all information collected will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Your identity will be kept anonymous, and I believe your participation will have a significant impact in my research.

Thank you for taking the time to read this letter, and I look forward to hearing back from you soon.

Yours sincerely,

Fida Ahmed

Appendix 5: Interview extracts: Challenges, Competencies, EL Development

Table 27 Interview extracts of entrepreneurial leadership challenges at UBIs	
Personal challenges	
Lack of qualification and experience	<i>“The first challenge I faced was about the irrelevant experience as I am bio scientist, and this is a tech-based start-up, so I did not have any exposure about how to write content or even write a blog. The first few months were challenging I had to write blogs so struggle with finding the keywords, SEO, and rank math.” (3B)</i>
Interpersonal issues	<i>“As a team there were challenges like communication gap, or I would like to call this a gender-based communication gap. We used to be with each other during university timings but after that every member left for where they were staying, as female and male members stayed in different hostels and females were not comfortable taking male members’ contact number so there were challenges to discuss various activities and tasks.” (17A)</i>
Entrepreneurial issues	<i>“When I applied in the business incubation centre, I didn’t know what it is basically, after getting in, I came to know what the incubation centre is and how it works.” (12A)</i>
Financial issues	<i>“Getting your business funded is one of the fundamental issues that all entrepreneurs face at individual level.” (17C)</i>
Operational issues	<i>“The first challenge we faced is time management. Now we must work more hours to develop networks and connections with other stakeholders. As we are only three members in team, and we must give a lot of time.” (14A)</i>
Business function challenges	
Accounting and Finance issues	<i>“Everyone can generate ideas, if we start, every idea is unique, and at the stage of implementation, the idea becomes useless or less viable. There are several reasons or lack of expertise behind this. Most of the entrepreneurs lack account management and financial skills to make accurate cost projections, and due to lack of business model flexibility, the initial idea gets changed at the time of implementation on the ground.” (11A)</i>
Marketing issues	<i>“Actually, there are some hurdles and problems because our main targeted customers are the farmer and we know that most of the farmers in our country are illiterate and it’s actually difficult for them to use an online web application on mobile phones or laptops, this is the kind of biggest challenge for us and in our start-up.” (2A)</i>
Human resource management issues	<i>“To be specific we need skilled workers, developers and computer system engineers as we are working on an online application and android application for farmers, so we need software engineers and developers.” (2A)</i>
Contextual challenges	
Lack of government support	<i>“Another issue is obtaining finances for the start-up. Only a few can get investment for their ventures, and those who are deprived, get demotivated. To avoid these issues, the government should support and promote young entrepreneurs. As practised in foreign countries, the government should provide subsidised loans to entrepreneurs to grow the entrepreneurial culture in the country.” (11B)</i>
Infrastructural constraints	<i>“Key factors that are affecting our entrepreneurial development are internet issues. If we are searching for some sort of jobs and contacting the clients, we mostly do these tasks on a remote basis, internet and electricity issues are the most shared challenges that are faced by entrepreneurs.” (1C)</i>
Societal challenges	<i>“There are some external issues in terms of pressure from family and friends. Most of the friends and family member chant negative comments about the project by saying it do not work, there is not market for such business ideas. These are some of the demotivating factors commonly observed with new start-ups.” (8A)</i>

Table 28 Interview extracts of entrepreneurial leadership competencies	
Self-Competencies	
Self-management skills	<i>"I worked more than 12 hours work daily basis, after coming from incubation centre I did some work in my home. Then after my family restriction, I limited myself from 9 to 5 jobs and I assured them during family time I will not do anything. One of the things I learned while doing entrepreneurship in this incubation centre is time management."</i> (9C)
Self-confidence skills	<i>"They should believe in their self-potential and believe in their skills.... Finally, they should be confident to face the men and other stake holders."</i> (16B)
Self-motivation skills	<i>"Everyone is voluntarily motivated, and we are determined to achieve the specific tasks on the day and then go home."</i> (11B)
Self-development skills	<i>"In order to perform these tasks, we have to develop our capacities and obtain the resources which can only be provided by business incubation centres."</i> (1C)
Organising competencies	
Business function skills	<p><i>Accounting and finance skills</i> <i>"We need to learn basics of business and entrepreneurship. Particularly, we must learn accounting and finance knowledge to move our business further."</i> (2C)</p> <p><i>Marketing skills</i> <i>"Other skills would be communication skills to attract as many customers as you can. If you have effective communication skills, then you can keep your customer intact with you for a long time and that customer will bring other customers to you. You can also be able to know the demand of the customer."</i> (18B)</p> <p><i>HR management skills</i> <i>"One must have human resource management skills or team management skill. They should know which team member is right fit for which tasks. If you have these two skills, you can sustain otherwise won't get the desired results."</i> (13A)</p>
Technical skills	<i>"If you are a graphic designer you have to know the guts of graphic designing and if you are working in account section, you need to have the knowledge of accountancy."</i> (1A)
Technological skills	<i>"We are in a technological era, so in this digital world, every entrepreneurial leader needs to learn basic IT skills to run their projects successfully."</i> (1A)
Interpersonal competencies	
Communication skills	<i>"The communication skills should be strong for individuals as we are entrepreneurs so we should be strong enough to communicate well to share what are our problems and how we can solve them."</i> (1C)
Networking and People Management skills	<p><i>People management skills</i> <i>"Managing team combined with best leadership skills bring out the most from employee."</i> (17A)</p> <p><i>Team building skills</i> <i>"The team leader should have conflict management skills. Since there is no formal structure in the start-up to handle everything through a proper mechanism, therefore, the issues should be</i></p>

	<i>resolved by team member themselves through proper communication and engagement.” (14B)</i>
Entrepreneurial competencies	
Opportunity identification and exploitation skills	<i>” We should observe our surroundings to find what our issues are. The issues are our opportunities we need to pursue them.” (14A)</i>
Innovation and creativity skills	<i>“In contrast, if you are working as team, you get motivation from your team member; they share ideas with each other because more minds bring out more perspectives and innovative ideas.” (11A)</i>
Risk management skills	<i>“I was mentally prepared that all disruptions are temporary and can be tackled if we are ready to face them. Because it is business you sometimes get profit and make a loss as well.” (13B)</i>
Conceptual Competencies	
Analytical skills	<i>“You must be a keen observer and attentive person. Practice is the key to analysis. To achieve the best of you doing a SWOT analysis is must. You should recognize your natural strengths and weaknesses, and work on weakness until they become strength.” (17A)</i>
Problem solving skills	<i>“I guess at some point there is difference between team and individual skills because if we face a big problem working in team it is more easily resolved and the time is saved by dividing the problem or tasks.” (1C)</i>
Business planning skills	<i>“We should be aware of systematic process of implementing something in the project; either it is related to finance, plan execution or assessment. The completion should not be focused we should consider each stage and emphasis on minimal viable product MVP.” (4A)</i>
Envisioning skills	<i>“The product is gradual process it takes time. We need to pick a team that prioritise the cause above monetary benefits” (8A)</i>

Classroom-based learning (CBL)	
Entrepreneurial leadership courses and diploma	<i>“I personally learned many things from my incubation manager, who helped me in refining my business idea and vision. They taught me how to patent my idea and legalise it.” (12A)</i>
Training, Workshop, Seminars	<i>“University can enhance the capacities of students by organising various sessions and learning activities through training and mentorship from experts. They can bring role model who had achieved entrepreneurial success to motivate and inspire the nascent entrepreneurial leaders.” 8B</i>
Project-based learning (PBL)	

Experiential Learning	<i>"I guess we can develop these skills by gaining experience by doing the things. I think we cannot develop the competencies by just reading the books or getting entrepreneurship courses. I think it will not work anymore. In entrepreneurial set up, doing things, or learning by doing matter most."</i> (1C)
Business plan competition	<i>"I remember there was a bio competition when I was in 5th semester. Our idea was the benefit of algae; we made a complete model of this and won the prize. From there, the incubation staffs have seen our idea and recommended for its materialisation. They took us on board to launch this business idea."</i> (9A)
Boot camps and Internship	<i>"The students should be given internship opportunities in multibillion project such as CPEC. This internship can boost up the skills of entrepreneurs."</i> (10A)
Social learning	
Observational learning	<i>"Here you can get a full-fledged business environment with all support. The environment broadens our minds and enhances our confidence skills. We can also enhance our innovativeness through looking at the competitors."</i> (6B)
Social Interaction	<i>"Because I know if I am stuck to some point on an individual level, some of my team members would help me in sorting it out. If the problem persists, I have a social circle and friends from similar backgrounds who can help me in sorting the problems."</i> (3A)
Self-Regulated Learning (SRL)	
Identifying self-learning needs	<i>"After coming here, we have seen people and learned about their success stories we got to know what can happen and how people are changing their lives through innovation. This as result, evokes our inner thirst for knowledge and learning, I understood what my strengths and weakness are and what areas need further improvement."</i> (9C)
Setting learning goals	<i>"During the start-up, the manger should give session and mange a policy team member follows this policy for example there are two team working in different works then each team have policy and rules and regulation which everyone should follow and make habit to develop this skill."</i> (5A)
Monitoring self-learning	<i>"Such as (member 'C') is the founder, but someone has to be a content writer. Everyone has to be mentally ready for the diverse nature of work. These are some sort of challenges. Initially, when you join, you are supposed to do certain tasks but at the end of the day, you will learn the skill of that task"</i> (2A)

Appendix 6: Coding process

Overarching Theme	→	Self-competencies
Interpretive codes	→	Self-Management skills
Descriptive codes	→	Self-awareness Balancing work and life Time management
Overarching Theme	→	Organising competencies
Interpretive codes	→	Business function skills
Descriptive codes	→	Accounting and Finance knowledge Marketing ability Team selection
Overarching Theme	→	Interpersonal competencies
Interpretive codes	→	communication skills
Descriptive codes	→	Verbal communication ability Written communication skills
Overarching Theme	→	Entrepreneurial competencies
Interpretive codes	→	Opportunity identification and exploitation skills
Descriptive codes	→	Pursuing new business opportunities Fulfilling existing market needs Sensing business opportunities
Overarching Theme	→	Conceptual competencies
Interpretive codes	→	Analytical skills
Descriptive codes	→	Analytical thinking Objective decision making Business assessment

Appendix 7: Thematic framework

Entrepreneurial Leadership Challenges

Personal Challenges

- Lack of Qualification and experience
- Interpersonal issues
- Entrepreneurial issues
- Financial issues
- Operational issues

Business Function Challenges

- Accounting and Finance issues
- Marketing issues
- Human resource management issues

Contextual Challenges

- Lack of government support
- Infrastructural Constraints
- Societal challenges
- BIC issues

Entrepreneurial Leadership Competencies

Self-Competencies

- Self-management skills
- Self-confidence skills
- Self-motivation skills
- Self-development skills

Organising Competencies

- Business function skills
- Technical skills
- Technological skills

Interpersonal Competencies

- Communication skills
- Networking and People Management skills

Entrepreneurial Competencies

- Innovation and Creativity
- Opportunity Identification and exploitation
- Risk Management Skills

Conceptual Competencies

- Analytical skills
- Problem solving skills
- Business planning skills
- Envisioning skills

Entrepreneurial Leadership Development

Classroom-Based Learning (CBL)

- Entrepreneurial leadership courses and diploma
- Training, Workshop, Seminars

Project-Based Learning (PBL)

- Experiential Learning

- Business plan competition
- Boot camps and Internship

Social Learning

- Observational learning
- Social Interaction

Self-regulated Learning (SRL)

- Identifying self-learning needs
- Setting learning goals
- Monitoring self-learning

Appendix 8: Interview reflection from field journal

On July 3, 2021, I conducted an interview with Entrepreneurial leader 2A at the University-Based Incubator (UBI) office. The purpose of the interview was to gain insights into the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs. The interview lasted 55 minutes and 18 seconds.

Entrepreneurial leader 2A was enthusiastic and willing to share his experiences as an emerging entrepreneurial leader. He shared his motivation for starting an entrepreneurial career and his journey in joining the business incubator. The respondent was open and receptive to discussing various aspects of the entrepreneurial journey, including challenges faced in UBIs, team support, and career prospects. He also shared his experience about the process of registering as an incubate within UBI and the associated challenges.

He offered suggestions for improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem in UBIs and emphasized the role of the government in providing resources and support to UBIs. He suggested that tailored training programmes and youth engagement in entrepreneurial activities could improve the effectiveness of business incubation centres.

In conclusion, the interview with Entrepreneurial leader 2A provided valuable insights into the challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in UBIs and offered suggestions for improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem in the country.

Appendix 9: List of publications

Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2021a) Entrepreneurial Leadership (EL): An Investigation of Entrepreneurial Competition on EL's Competencies Development. In: [Online]. Presented at the British Academy of Management, online. Available: <https://virtual.oxfordabstracts.com/#/event/1821/submission/164>.

Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2021b) Challenges and competencies of entrepreneurial leaders in driving innovation at DIY laboratories. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*. Vol.33 (10), pp.1132–1146.

Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2022a) Entrepreneurial leadership development in teams: A conceptual model. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*. Vol.0 (2022), pp.1–13.

Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2022b) Innovation Strategies of SMEs' Entrepreneurial Leaders: Evidence from Pakistan. In: [Online]. Manchester: British Academy of Management. Available: <https://www.bam.ac.uk/events-landing/conference.html>.

Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2023a) Leadership During a Crisis: A Focus on Leadership Development. In: Taylor Francis Group.

Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2023b) Exploring Entrepreneurial leadership: A multilevel Analysis. (Submitted in *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*)

Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2023c) Role of Business Incubation Centre in Developing Entrepreneurial Leadership competencies: A Team perspective.

Ahmed, F. and Harrison, C. (2023d) Entrepreneurial Leadership Competencies: A Systematic Literature Review. *International Review of Entrepreneurship*.